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ADVANCING INTEGRATION AND COLLABORATION
IN DIGITAL HUMANITIES

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GENERAL EDITORS

Wout Dillen, Margherita Fantoli, Julia Neugarten, Teresa Paccosi,
and Marieke van Erp

GUEST EDITORS

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DH Benelux Journal 7

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Editors’ Preface

Seven years after its creation, the DH Benelux Journal continues to gather contributions based on accepted papers from the DH Benelux conference. The conference is organized in turn by universities in the Netherlands, Belgium, and Luxembourg, but it welcomes a broad international community that joins each year. The current issue presents papers from the 2024 edition. Each accepted presentation at the conference can be submitted as a full paper to the journal, undergoing a completely new round of peer review by at least two reviewers. This year, 13 papers were accepted, covering a broad range of research topics and authored by scholars from multiple institutions. The 2024 edition—the 11th DH Benelux conference—was hosted by KU Leuven from June 4th to 7th in the charming setting of a 17th-century Franciscan College, the Irish College of Leuven, which today serves as an international residential centre for education, training, and networking. The conference theme, chosen by program chairs Thomas Smith, Estelle Bunout, Tom Gheldof, and Margherita Fantoli — "Breaking Silos, Connecting Data: Advancing Integration and Collaboration in Digital Humanities"—certainly contributed to the warm atmosphere of community building, and the sharing of best practices, data, and experiences that characterized these four sunny days. The articles in this issue contribute to this overarching theme from different perspectives, as the guest editors explain in their preface. We thank them for proposing such a stimulating program and for curating the publication process of the papers. We would also like to thank the local organizers who made the DH Benelux 2024 conference possible, ensuring a pleasant stay for all participants and providing space for all selected contributions, despite the steadily rising number of submissions. As guest editors, we hope you enjoy this volume and that you will join us at future editions of the DH Benelux conference.

November 28, 2025
Amsterdam, Borås, Nijmegen and
Leuven

Wout Dillen
Margherita Fantoli
Julia Neugarten
Teresa Paccosi
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Introduction: Breaking Silos, Connecting Data: Advancing Integration and Collaboration in Digital Humanities

Estelle Bunout¹, Tom Gheldof², and Thomas Smits³

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The 11th DH Benelux Conference, held at the Irish College in Leuven from 4 to 7 June 2024, gathered Digital Humanities scholars, developers, librarians, and cultural heritage professionals under the theme **Breaking Silos, Connecting Data: Advancing Integration and Collaboration in Digital Humanities**. This theme captured a prominent concern of our field today: the need to transcend disciplinary and institutional boundaries, while addressing the fragmentation of digital resources, infrastructures, and communities. The conference brought together a record number of contributions – 151 submissions, of which 111 were accepted - that examined how data, tools, and methods can be connected across space, time, and domain: from ancient prosopography to 20th-century propaganda archives, and from text analysis to computer vision. The theme was also particularly fitting for our venue, where the historical, archival and academic landscape of Leuven offered a natural setting for a meeting focused on linking data and scholars. The pre-conference program reflected the theme with workshops on collaborative tools such as Transkribus, the CLARIAH-VL tool suite, and sessions about making scholarly collections of letters accessible for a wide audience, experience and challenges with named entities, and opening up born-digital data for researchers. During the conference, the two keynote speakers also framed the conference’s theme by highlighting both the present reality and possible futures of the digital humanities. In her opening keynote *Medievalist in the Loop: Putting the Humanities back into the Digital Humanities*, Katarzyna Kapitan argued that, in an increasingly digital research landscape, virtually all humanities scholars already engage in digital scholarship to some extent. Rather than posing a threat to traditional methodologies, she emphasized that digital and conventional approaches function best in tandem: macro-scale analyses enabled by digital tools gain interpretive depth through traditional, close-reading perspectives, while established scholarly methods benefit from the new insights and efficiencies offered by computational techniques. The closing keynote by Manuel Burghardt (*The Future of Digital Humanities – Beyond Humanities?*) looked ahead and proposed a provocative vision for the field. He suggested that many branches of DH may gradually reintegrate into their respective humanities domains as digital methods become fully normalized, while Computational Humanities - with

its explicit modelling practices and formal, quantitative methods - may continue to develop as a distinct discipline. This forward-looking perspective underscored the characteristic openness of the field, as well as its willingness to question and redefine its own boundaries in response to evolving research practices. Across the three conference days, presentations, demos, and posters further explored how interoperability can foster more sustainable and inclusive digital scholarship. The papers published in this special issue represent a cross-section of that shared effort, demonstrating the diversity of approaches through which the DH Benelux community continues to advance the collaborative nature of our field.

Several contributions of this special issue turn their attention to the theme of data integration and network analysis, fields that lie at the core of research in digital history. These papers demonstrate how linking historical data can uncover new perspectives on social structures, migration, and intellectual networks. In their paper *Modelling Jewish Migration in Antiquity: connecting archaeological, inscriptional, and historical data from around the Mediterranean*, Stefan Dingemans, Tijmen C. Baarda, Berit Janssen, Arjan Mossel, and Leonard V. Rutgers reconstruct networks of Jewish communities across the Mediterranean from the 2nd century BCE to 600 CE. By integrating archaeological, epigraphic, papyrological, and literary datasets, the authors show how Jewish presence and movement can be visualised and quantified. Equally ambitious in scope, *STUDIUM.AI: datafying and connecting the 'webs of knowledge' around the premodern University of Leuven (1425–1797)* by Yann Ryan, Margherita Fantoli, Yanne Broux, and Violet Soen tackles the challenge of connecting several databases on the Old University of Leuven. Through standardization of person names, bibliographic records, and georeferenced locations, this project constructs a relational database infrastructure that dissolves the institutional silos of Leuven University. The authors demonstrate how linking these databases can provide a new perspective on early modern academic culture.

Other contributions examine the potential of automated text analysis, entity extraction, and AI-assisted annotation, showing how computational pipelines can structure vast and fragmented corpora. In *Accessing the Republic. Entity extraction from the resolutions of the Dutch States General*, Marijn Koolen, Esger Renkema, Nienke Groskamp, Frank Smit, Jirsi Reinders, Ronald Sluijter, Rik Hoekstra, and Joris Oddens describe how they developed a multi-layered pipeline that applies named-entity recognition to nearly one million early modern resolutions. Their approach enables the identification of individuals, committees, and dates in a body of texts that for centuries resisted systematic analysis, thus opening new avenues for the study of governance, deliberation, and political participation in the Dutch Republic. Maria Dermentzi, Mike Bryant, Fabio Rovigo, and Herminio García-González pursue a different yet complementary goal with their paper on *Multilingual Automated Subject Indexing: A Comparative Study of LLMs vs Alternative Approaches in the Context of the EHRI Project*, where they evaluate how large language models can assist archival indexing across languages. By comparing traditional lexical and statistical methods with fine-tuned and zero-shot LLM-based approaches, the authors highlight not only the accuracy of AI-driven classification but also its implications for cross-lingual discovery and the crucial role of human validation in curating Holocaust-related collections. Similarly, Mari Wigham, Rana Klein, Marjet Broelsma, and Roeland Ordelman (*Using AI to put together the wartime propaganda puzzle*) combine OCR, ASR, and NER technologies to link together radio broadcasts, their transcriptions, and contemporary newspaper materials on Dutch World War II propaganda. Despite challenges related to tran-

scription quality, their study demonstrates the integrative power of AI in restoring fragmented historical sources to analytical coherence. Florentina Armaselu's *Small-Scale Testing on Generative AI and Post-OCR Correction in Historical Datasets* offers a more experimental reflection, testing generative AI models for post-OCR correction on 18th-century French monographs. Her findings reveal how prompt engineering can balance historical fidelity with machine-readability, highlighting both the promise and risks, including the necessary ethical caution, when applying generative AI for text restoration.

Several papers discussed the infrastructural dimension of digital scholarship. In *Linking Person Observations FAIRly: PiCo in Practice*, Sytze H. J. Van Herck, Ivo Zandhuis, Richard Zijdemans, and Rick J. Mourits, present the Persons in Context (PiCo) ontology. They explain how a FAIR-compliant model can connect individual-level historical observations across datasets, creating provenance links that strengthen collaboration between archival and research institutions. Bert Aernouts, Mehmet Celik, and Joris Colla document the renewal of ODIS in *Breaking Down Barriers: The Transition of ODIS from a Relational to a Triple Store Database*. They not only detail their shift from a relational to a triple store architecture, but also explain how new SHACL-based workflows improve interoperability and enable richer forms of network visualisation and GIS integration. In a related exploration of audiovisual data (*Linking Het Amsterdams Stadsjournaal: A Case Study in Emerging Linked Open Data (LOD) Approaches to Audio-Visual Heritage*), Meg Weijers and Christian Olesen address the conceptual and technical complexities of connecting dispersed film materials across institutions through Wikibase/Wikidata and the CLARIAH Media Suite. Their study identifies the benefits of collaborative data modelling but also interrogates the interpretive tensions that accompany open linking in the heritage domain.

Equally significant are contributions that interrogate visualisation and bias in cultural heritage collections. *Herbaria Heritage: Visualising Colonial Bias in Natural History Collections* is the telling title of the paper in which Sakura Morales Furuta, Ana Reviejo Salamanca, Michaela Todd, Lise Stork, and Andreas Weber use interactive PowerBI dashboards to expose colonial extraction patterns in five million plant specimens. Their paper challenges the neutrality of data visualisation and re-situate natural history collections within their imperial context. Julie M. Birkholz, Benoît Crucifix, Erwin Dejasse, Sébastien Hermans, Krishna K. Thirukokaranam Chandrasekar, and Bas Vercruyssen show how computer vision (YOLOv8) can automatically detect and classify visual narratives in interwar Belgian periodicals (*Uncovering Interwar Comics: The Challenge of Labeling Graphics in Belgian Weekly Magazines*). Their paper provides a window into the visual and political culture of the 1930s and illustrates how visual data can be analyzed at scale. Katja Tereshko, Marijn Koolen, and Eva Viviani combine stylometric and reader-response methods in their paper *Reader response on the unconventional narrative tense in different genres*. They analyzed over 18,000 Dutch-language novels: this demonstrates how narrative experimentation with tense shapes readers' emotional and cognitive engagement. Julie Verlinden, Thorsten Mahieu, and Toon Goedemé's *Can stones be made (artificially) intelligent?* tackle similar methodological questions with an example from archaeology: the authors apply computer vision to detect recurring architectural motifs in Roman Asia Minor, combining pattern recognition with archaeological interpretation to reveal design logics invisible to the human eye.

Together, these 13 contributions exemplify the conference's overarching concern: how to overcome the disciplinary, technical, and institutional silos that continue to fragment Digital Humanities research. The authors address the challenges of working

with incomplete, fragmented, and heterogeneous datasets dispersed across institutions and formats. Their papers reveal how the analysis of data depends not only on technical interoperability but also on conceptual and ethical awareness.

Many contributions comply with FAIR and Open Research principles, showing how transparent and reusable infrastructure can underpin sustainable scholarship. Connecting data is a form of interpretation: it reshapes how researchers perceive relationships within and across collections, revealing patterns and biases that were previously hidden. Breaking silos, in this sense, is not only a technical challenge that can be tackled with a diversity of methods but also an interpretive one, which requires new conceptual frameworks.

At the end of this introduction, we would like to acknowledge and thank the local organising committee (Leah Budke, Demmy Verbeke, Rebecca Burke, Margherita Fantoli, Tom Gheldof and all the student volunteers) who made DHBenelux 2024 a temporary home for its participants. We also like to thank the local chairs and the reviewers, which made selecting the presentations and the papers for this volume an easy and enjoyable task.

Reader Response to the Unconventional Narrative Tense in Different Genres

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This article raises the issue of the conventionality of literary genres in terms of not only thematic distinction but also the use of basic narrative tense as a stylistic technique, and readers’ reactions to breaking these genre conventions. Using narrative tense as a marker for books that deviate from genre conventions and information about online reviews of these books, we found that readers tend to write more frequently reviews of those texts in which genre conventions are violated. It should be noted that narrative tense marks such deviations within the genre, but we have also found a correlation between the tense used and the themes covered in the book, compared to most books within the genre. For example, most nonfiction uses the present tense as the primary narrative tense, but books written in the genre using the past tense are more likely to address the theme of history. Although readers tend to react more strongly to deviations within a genre, their reactions are equally varied regardless of whether the author adheres to genre conventions or not.

1 Introduction

Man is a slave to habit. Many studies prove that people are more inclined to choose something familiar rather than something new. This applies to all areas of life, and sometimes has quite far-reaching consequences, as shows a well know example from social studies about the measurements used for the railways: the standard railroad gauge is 4 feet, 8 1/2 inches or 1,435 m, which is a weird measurement. To understand where it comes from, we have to know that the first rail lines were built by the same people who built the wagon tramways, which used the same gauge of the previously used horse drawn rail cars with such wheel spacing. This spacing was probably proved to be robust enough on the old long-distance roads in England. These on their turn were built by Romans there, whose carts and chariots were built so that two horses could draw them, and everyone had to stick to the wheel spacing the Romans used,

otherwise they would run the risk to break their wheels on the Roman ruts (Hilton, 2023).

Although this narrative represents only one version of reality—failing to capture all the nuances of what is happening and often referred to as the myth of the origin of the railway track width standard—it serves as a compelling illustration of the power and historical stability of norms and standards in shaping human activity and organization. Moreover, substantial evidence shows that people tend to repeat habitual actions unconsciously. Over a century ago, psychologist William James famously described humans as "bundles of habit" (James, 1890), and this observation remains relevant in the modern world. Crucially, the specific context in which habitual behavior occurs is a decisive factor in triggering and sustaining these actions, as it provides the cues that prompt repetition and reinforce routine patterns (Neal et al., 2012; Ouellette and Wood, 1998).

We propose that literary genre can function as a context in literature, shaping readers' expectations about both content and style, including the narrative tense. For instance, when we think of fantasy literature, we often have a general sense of its themes and narrative style, as is true for many other genres. In this article, we will explore to what extent different genres are conventional in terms of themes and style. To examine style, we will focus on the primary narrative tense, as this stylistic element is fundamental to any literary text. Additionally, in a previous study (Tereshko (2024)), we demonstrated that narratives written in the present tense within the literary fiction genre tend to elicit more reader engagement, as evidenced by a higher volume of online reviews.

In the present study, we focus not only on literature in the present tense, but on books written in a tense that is not conventional for a particular genre. For example, historical novels are most often written in the past tense, therefore such narrative in the present tense would be considered a deviation from what is conventional within the genre, and vice versa in the case of non-fiction, where such a deviation would be the choice of past tense narration. The aim of this study is to reveal how an average reader responds to literary texts in different genres which deviate from the genre conventions in terms of the choice of the main narrative tense.

1.1 Concept of normality and fiction

If we are so inclined to choose what is familiar, where are the opportunities for progress and creativity? It is conceivable that human existence is constituted by the tension between two opposing forces – the desire for development, which implies renewal, and inertia. Neither of these is bad in itself, but the consequence of inert behaviour is the notion of normality. However, this term is debated in the humanities.

Normality is a concept originating from the Latin word "norma," which means rate, scale, or figuratively, a rule. Norma (standard) is in a general sense a criterion for comparing and evaluating. Normality is defined as an agreement with the standard (Havigerová, 2012). These definitions are often debated by researchers in the field of social psychology, where the views on the operation of the concept of norm vary from a complete rejection of the concept (Gibbs, 1965) to the reduction of it to an empirical definition. In the latter case, a norm may be defined from an evaluative point of view - whether a person's actions are judged to coincide with a standard of behaviour – or from a reactivist point of view – whether actions are encouraged or caught up.

There is also a statistical approach to normality in science, in which case normality is defined as that which occurs frequently. While in social psychology this definition of norm has faded into the background, in linguistics or digital humanities it is now as

relevant as ever. For example, in the field of cognitive linguistics, the term 'conventional metaphor' has become firmly established, i.e. a metaphor that occurs in texts and speech so often that it may no longer even be recognised as a metaphor. Another example is the assimilation of the principles of conventionality/norm in children's language acquisition (Diesendruck, 2005).

While the notion of norm, due to its frequent use in various contexts, including unscientific contexts, has acquired a lot of connotations, the notion of conventionality is more neutral, so we will use it in this article. From the linguistic point of view, conventionality is an assumption or knowledge of interlocutors that for certain concepts there are forms of expression that are used in a certain linguistic community, these forms can be words, idioms, language constructions or their combination (Clark, 2010). These conventions are used even without participants being aware of them. Within a single language, conventions inherent in different types of discourse, for example, can stand out.

In the areas between social sciences and linguistics, there is also room for discussion of conventions. For example, literature, as an art form, is on the one hand subject to its own laws – conventional, but on the other hand, as any art form creative by definition. For more on views on the conventionality of literature and the understanding of literary text, see Olsen (2000).

Regardless of whether the pendulum swings in the direction of conventions or new forms, to some extent there are always rules in literature. In the same article, Olsen (2000) cites as an example "a *HIGHLY* conventionalised genre of literature, such as the sonnet" (author's italics). If the sonnet is a highly conventionalised genre, we can assume that there are also less conventionalised genres. Nevertheless, the very division into genres proves the existence of rules by which they are distinguished.

Distinguishing genres in literature is not always an easy task, and this task often has no unambiguous solution. For example, in Pratt (2016), she distinguishes linguistic expressions that occur in descriptive passages of fiction and non-fiction (historical) texts. Most often these expressions combine, undoubtedly repeating the formal structure, the meaning to be conveyed and the form of the utterance. But it is not the only way of distinguishing different genres; for example, we can use tense as a marker of genre, but even as a marker of fiction in general. In her study of the use of tense in the medieval French literature, Fleischman (1990) points out that the use of tense in narrative can be seen as abnormal compared to the use of tense in ordinary language. We suggest that tense can also be a marker of different genres.

Hyland (2002) moving towards the practical application of the concept of genre in education, defines it as follows: "Genres are rhetorical actions that we draw on to respond to received repeated situations; we recognise certain language/meaning choices as representing effective ways of getting things done in particular contexts" (p. 116). This definition again notes the relationship between the content of a text and its form. The genre thus can be understood very broadly, but he also notes that speaking about the literary genres we have to stick to literary genre theory, as also mentioned in Frow (2014), where the purpose of genres is mentioned, namely the use of discrimination and taxonomy to organise texts into recognisable classes. Genres have not only a practical meaning, they are also historically defined by social entities. In the same chapter about the literary genre theory, Frow (2014) cites the book 'Genre in Discourse' by Tzvetan Todorov, where he writes that genres are "only the classes of texts that have been historically perceived as such [...]. In a given society the recurrence of certain discursive properties is institutionalised, and individual texts are produced

and perceived in relation to the norm constituted by that codification. A genre, whether literary or not, is nothing other than the codification of discursive properties' (Todorov, 1990).

Given this, the genre creates a 'horizon of expectation' (Frow, 2014) for the readers within the society and historical period. That is why it is important to take the conventions of the genre in consideration while analysing reader response on literary works in different genres. In this article we will rely on the existing genre system used by publishers in the Netherlands (NUR-codes, discussed in details in section 3.1), which reflects the modern perspective of genres and is broadly used in the country.

Taking into account the fuzzy genre boundaries and the results of our previous research showing that readers tend to leave reviews of literary fiction in the present tense more often, this article will address the following questions:

1. Is it possible to distinguish more and less conventional genres and what could such a distinction be based on?
2. How do readers react to books that do not obey the canons of genre in terms of their choice of the main narrative tense?

2 Data and method

Thanks to the efforts of the National Library in The Hague and permission from many publishers, our project, Impact and Fiction at the Huygens Institute, got access to 18.885 books published in Dutch language, including translations into Dutch, for our analysis. The only selection criteria for this corpus were the language (Dutch) and the availability of the book in digital format, as it was not feasible to digitize print versions of the books. The collection includes all the books meeting these criteria, and contains books in a span from 1956 to 2022, the majority having been published between 1996 and 2018. To create a database with all these texts they were parsed by Trankit Van Nguyen et al. (2021), the meta-information about the books was added, such as ISBN, the year of publication and NUR-code(s) to detect the specific genres. After dropping the books for which we did not know the year of publication, 17736 ISBN's were left in the database. Based on the NUR-codes, these books are divided in 11 genres (see Table 1).

The same was done for the Reviews database, containing 634,614 reviews from different digital platforms such as Goodreads, Hebban.nl, Amazon, Bol.com and others. This database is based on the Online Dutch Book Reviews (ODBR) corpus (Boot, 2017), but includes also later additions. This corpus does not cover the whole corpus of books, but we have at least one review for a majority of the books. There are also books with uncredibly high number of reviews, for example "Fifty Shades of Grey" has 828 reviews, "The Kite Runner" and "A Thousand of Splendid Suns" - 817 and 612 reviews respectively, and "The Girl on the Train" - 630, however the books with more than 100 reviews make up less than 1 per cent of our database; 9% of the books got only one review; most of the books, which is 27%, have more than 1 but less than 10 reviews; another 15% have more than 10 and less than 50 reviews; and only 2% have more than 50 and less than 100 reviews.

For this article we applied statistical analysis, such as permutation test, regression analysis and other statistical tests to the text and reviews database. To the literary texts we have also applied a topic-modelling method, to test whether there is a correlation between the topics of the book and its genre. For our topic modeling of the novels,

Table 1: Number of books in each genre of our book collection.

Genre	Number of books
Literary fiction	5408
Non-fiction	4947
Other fiction	1931
Suspense	1626
Regional fiction	859
Literary thriller	800
Children fiction	518
Young adult	485
Romantic fiction	483
Fantasy fiction	352
Historical fiction	327

we used the Top2Vec model (Angelov, 2020), treating entire books as individual documents. Based on previous research (Sobchuk and Šeĵa, 2023; Uĵlanova and Gius, 2020; Van Zundert et al., 2022), we focused on content words – nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs – while removing any person names identified by the Trankit NER tagger, since we consider them as not relevant for topics and they can affect the modelling by grouping books or series of books around specific characters. However, we left the location names for the modelling, since they can be an important part of the setting, especially if the story takes part in real world. After filtering our corpus of books reduced from 1,92 billion to 826 million tokens. We then applied a frequency filter, removing terms that appeared in less than 1% or more than 50% of the documents. This left us with 190 million tokens, which is about 23% of all content words and just under 10% of the total tokens.

To test for the differences in the response to different genres we used the Dutch Reading Impact Model (DRIM), a rule-based model that works at the sentence level, using 275 rules to analyze impact in four categories: Affect, Aesthetic, Narrative, and Reflection. We excluded Reflection from our analysis due to unvalidated rules (Boot and Koolen, 2020). Aesthetic and Narrative are sub-categories of Affect, with relevant expressions requiring both an impact word or phrase and a book aspect term. In our analysis, we focus on Narrative and general Affect, identifying over 2 million impact expressions across reviews. To clarify distinctions, we treat generic Affect separately from Narrative and Aesthetic impacts, with 667,672 expressions identified for Aesthetic impact, 690,184 for Narrative, and 731,720 for generic Affect.

3 Conventions and genre

3.1 Genre and topic

If we accept as axiomatic the fact that the genres are defined in a certain historical period by social institutions and serving as a horizon of expectation for readers of this period are conventional, then it is necessary to define what their conventionality consists of. That is, it is necessary to determine on what principles the genre division takes place. Turning to classical sources, such as Aristotle’s Poetics, we can identify three principles of genre division: medium, theme and style. Aristotle writes of the

Figure 1: Use of themes in a selection of genres

kinds of poetry as ‘modus imitatio’ and says that they all differ from each other ‘either by a difference of kind in their means, or by differences in the objects, or in the manner of their imitations’ (McKeon et al., 2009). In the context of our study, medium is of the least value as a genre feature, since the literary work most often appears as a written (less often audio) text. Of greater interest are thematic and stylistic features, which can be the basis for distinguishing genres.

In this study we use the division into genres according to NUR (Nederlandstalige Uniforme Rubrieksindeling) – Dutch Uniform Subject Classification, which is based on an earlier version, NUGI (Nederlandse Uniforme Genre Indeling) – Dutch Uniform Genre Classification. Both systems use the subject division as a basis (van Rees, 2006).

To check if the genres are connected with the themes of the books, we have conducted the topic analysis on the whole text database. Afterwards, the computationally selected topics were manually tagged to merge them into more recognizable themes. Figure 1 shows how these themes are represented in a selection of genres.

To make these radar-plots the first 5 represented topics in each book were considered as relevant. The figures clearly show that there are thematic preferences within each genre. However, there are more robust genres such as for instance Fantasy fiction, Suspense or Historical fiction in comparison with looser genres in terms of topic preferences such as Literary fiction, Literary thriller or Children fiction. This observation suggests the conventionality of genre may be a question of degree.

3.2 Genre and tense

Having seen that genre division is related mainly to themes, we can ask what stylistic differences are associated with genre division. Considering the volume of the material under study and the specificity of computer-based methods of analysis, we focused on the use of tenses as a stylistic device. In the previous study (Tereshko (2024)), we managed to identify a pattern of reader reactions to literary works in the present tense. The conclusion of that study was that readers more often tend to write an online review to the books written mainly in present tense. However, now we have a much larger number of texts at our disposal, among which more genres are represented.

For this study, we determined the narrative tense of each book by utilizing grammatical parsing with Trankit. Following this, we developed a set of rules to assign a tense tag to each clause (see Table 2). In complex sentences, which may contain multiple clauses, these clauses can differ in tense, especially in Dutch. By calculating the proportions of the simple present, present perfect, simple past, and past perfect tenses, we identified the primary narrative tense for each book, regardless of genre. In Dutch, simple tenses are formed using only the main verb, while perfect tenses require an auxiliary verb combined with the perfect participle of the main verb.

Table 2: Examples of present and perfect tenses in Dutch

Tense	Example in Dutch	Translation of the example
Present Simple	Ik werk.	I work.
Past Simple	Ik werkte.	I worked.
Present Perfect	Ik heb gewerkt.	I have worked.
Past Perfect	Ik had gewerkt.	I had worked.

Figure 2: Distribution of books according to present ratio (left - simple present, right - simple and perfect present)

We have not looked for the future tense because, firstly, it is not used as the main narrative tense and, secondly, in Dutch the present tense can carry the meaning of the future tense. In the previous study, we included the present perfect in the grammatical present (based on grammatical parsing performed by Trankit), since we counted the main verb in the sentence. However, the present perfect refers to past events which are represented as given facts, which creates a break in the semantic and grammatical meaning and leads to confusion when determining the main narrative tense by counting only conjugated verbs. By counting clauses and assigning the tense to a clause rather than to the main verb in the sentence, we were able to measure the use of tenses more accurately. However, the use of perfect tenses in books seems to be insignificant for the main narrative tense, which is also logical, because this aspect cannot be used for the whole narrative and is represented in the text in small amounts. To avoid the debate over the use of the perfect, we assigned narrative tenses and divided the texts into categories – present, past, or mix - based on the proportions of the simple present and simple past tenses.

Figure 2 shows the distribution of books in our database based on the percentage of present tense usage (x-axis). In the graph we can see that many books contain few clauses in the present tense (the wave on the left), so these are mostly written in the past tense, but the right side of the graph also shows that quite a large number of books use the present tense in more than half of the clauses, which makes us believe that in this case present tense might be the main narrative tense. The left graph shows this distribution based on the simple tenses only, the proportion in this case is calculated as follows: the number of sentences in the simple past/present divided by the number of all sentences in the book, including sentences in the perfect. The right graph shows the same, but including the clauses in the perfect tenses, and the graph is slightly

Figure 3: Distribution of present ratios by genre (KDE-plot)

shifted to the right due to the larger number of counted sentences, but it does not change its shape, which means that, as mentioned above, sentences in the perfect do not significantly affect the narrative tense.

Given the notion of genre conventions, we might assume that the choice of narrative tense may be specific to each individual genre, which turns out to be true. Looking at Figure 3, we see that although most genres gravitate towards the past tense, while the present may be considered an exception to the rule, non-fiction clearly shows the opposite: these books are much more often written in the present tense than in the past tense. It is also interesting to note that authors in the genre of children's and teenage literature do not have strong preferences in the choice of narrative tense, and the same is true also for regional novels: books in these genres are almost equally found in both present and past tense. On the other hand, fantasy and detectives are genres where the choice of past tense is clearly preferred. Thus, we can speak of a greater or lesser conventionalisation of the genre in terms of the choice of the main narrative tense.

To illustrate this scale we assigned categories to each book in our database: if the percentage of present tense clauses in a book exceeds 60%, it is categorised as 'present', if the same is true for past tense sentences it is 'past', otherwise the book is defined as 'mix'. Then we grouped the database by genre to see how the books of each category are distributed within different genres. For this we counted the proportion of each category, considering the number of books within the genres (bar-plot on the right side of Figure 4). Then we looked at the difference between the proportions of categories,

Figure 4: Genres scaled by their robustness; the colour coding indicate the dominant category within the genre (left); Proportions of texts of each category within different genres (right)

namely, the difference between proportionally the most represented category and the less represented one. The bigger this difference, the more robust is the genre in terms of the choice of the main narrative tense. On the left side of Figure 4 we can for example see that in Fantasy fiction the past tense is highly preferred (coded blue), while for Regional fiction the difference is just a few percent (there are slightly more books in the present tense – coded red). Thus, Figure 4 shows on the one hand that each genre is more or less conventionalised and on the other hand highlights the most dominant tense used within particular genre.

If there is a tense which is used in most of the cases within a genre, there must also be the least represented tense, which is also occasionally used. The most used tense can thus be seen as an unmarked and the less used one – marked, as Fleischman (1990) explains:

In the unmarked context of ordinary (nonnarrative) language the PRESENT is generally regarded as the unmarked tense while the PAST is marked <...> in a narrative context the PRESENT – or any tense- aspect category other than the PAST – is marked with respect to one or more of a set of properties that together define the unmarked tense of narration, the PAST.

This passage supports our observations and is valid for most of the genres, except of non-fiction, other fiction, children literature and regional novel. In section 5 we'll spotlight the reactions of readers on the books which deviate from the conventions of the genre, such as a non-fiction book written in the past tense, or a literary thriller expressed in the present tense.

3.3 Topic and tense

As we have seen, literary genres are often distinguished by their narrative focus and seem to follow certain stylistic conventions, particularly in terms of narrative tense. This raises an interesting question: is there a connection between the topic of a text and its predominant tense?

To investigate that we can use the topic analysis described before but split the genres

Figure 5: Topics of books in marked and unmarked tense in different genres

into subgroups of books within the genre which are written in a marked tense and those where the unmarked (including the 'mix' category, except for other fiction) tense is used. In some genres the number of books in the unmarked tense would be very low; for instance, there are just a few historical books written in the present tense. To be sure that the number of books in the subgroup does not affect the results, we repeated the same procedure of plotting topics 1000 times with samples of 10 books from each subgroup – unmarked and marked. The results remained stable and comparable to the results that we got for the whole, which are represented in Figure 5 for selected genres.

On Figure 5 for each genre, the radar plot on the left shows the themes used in books written in an 'unmarked', convenient, tense for this genre, while on the right shows the themes of the books in 'marked' group, where the choice of tense deviates from the conventions of the genre. The numbers given indicate the number of books in each category respectively. For some genres the difference between the used themes is not so big, such as in the case of romance or suspense, these genres seem to be quite theme oriented. In non-fiction the choice of tense is also clearly seen on the radar plots: the non-fiction books written in the past tense (a marked tense for non-fiction) tend to be

Figure 6: Average number of reviews for books written in the marked and unmarked tense

more likely about historical events and geographical settings. Fantasy fiction written in the present tense (marked for fantasy) is more diverse in terms of themes used there. On the other side, young adult literature in present tense (marked for young adult books) seems to be more focused on feelings and behaviour in comparison with the young adult books written in the past tense, where for example the themes of supernatural, fantasy and science fiction play a great role.

Literary fiction in its turn appears very diverse in terms of the choice of narrative themes, so it is difficult to draw conclusions about the correlation between the choice of the main narrative time and the themes raised within this genre.

4 Reader response to deviations in tense use within the genre

In previous section we have seen that the genre, being defined mostly by theme, often has also a preferred tense. In this and the next section we test our hypothesis that the narrative tense is reflected in the online book reviews.

To do so, we have labelled the books written in a tense, which is the least represented within a genre as ‘marked’ and other books within each genre as ‘unmarked’. After that we have merged the data about the online book reviews and the data about the books. For all genres together the ‘marked’ category of books got 28316 reviews for 2832 books, and ‘unmarked’ category – 107476 reviews for 14904 books. Figure 6 shows the average number of reviews per category, and it is clear, that there are more reviews for books written in the marked tense.

The left side of Figure 6 shows the average number of reviews for the two categories for all genres, while on the right side we can see the average number of reviews for each genre. The significance of the difference in number of reviews for the two categories follows from applied permutation test with observed difference in average number of reviews between marked and unmarked categories 2.787 and p-value 0.0.

To ensure the robustness of our analysis, we identified and removed outliers from the dataset based on the interquartile range (IQR) method. Specifically, for each combination of genre and category, we calculated the IQR and defined outliers as

books with review counts outside the range of 1.5 times the IQR below the first quartile or above the third quartile. After excluding these outliers, we conducted a permutation test to evaluate the difference in the average number of reviews between the "marked" and "unmarked" categories. The results showed that the observed difference in average reviews decreased from 2.79 (with outliers) to 1.66 (without outliers), while the p-value remained 0.0 in both cases. This indicates that although the magnitude of the difference is affected by the presence of outliers, the difference remains statistically significant.

In general, the books from the 'marked' category gain more reviews, except the fantasy fiction books. It should be noted that the genre of fantasy is highly conventional in terms of the tense choice: we have just 7 books written mainly in the present tense from in total 352 for this genre. Since this creates a skewed representation of the genre in our database, and given the strong preference for past-tense narration in fantasy fiction, the fantasy fiction data should be re-examined using a more balanced sample of books in this genre.

This observation confirms the results of our previous study, as for the literary fiction genre the choice of present narrative tense is marked, which elicits a more active response from readers, same as is the case for books in other genres where marked narrative tense is chosen. We speculate that the reasons for this behaviour may lie in more general behavioural patterns that determine reactions to something different from the usual.

This statistically significant difference in the number of book reviews in the two categories - reflecting the conventional principles of the genre and deviations from them - is indicative in itself, but it would also be interesting to know whether this difference manifests itself only in the number of online reviews or whether they also differ from each other qualitatively.

4.1 Different or equally different: the content of the reviews

Although we observe a large variation in the length of texts in our review corpus, both in terms of word count and number of sentences - a review can consist of a single word or reach several thousand words - when filtered by genre and by marked and unmarked categories within genres, these differences turn out to be statistically insignificant. That is, online reviews of books, no matter what category they fall into, are equally diverse from a formal point of view.

Our interest in this study, however, centres on readers' reactions, including the content of those reactions. For now, we can nevertheless obtain data on the number of expressions and words reflecting reader affect. To do so, we use DRIM, a model that uses rules to identify and count words and expressions that signal reactions to the story (narrative affect), the style (aesthetic affect), or the book as a whole (general affect).

To identify whether there is a difference in readers' reactions to books in marked and unmarked categories across genres we applied DRIM to online book reviews separately for each type of affect. This gave us the opportunity to count the number of expressions reflecting a particular affect and compare the marked and unmarked categories in each genre using the permutation test. The results of the test showed no significant differences between the categories in any of the eleven genres, which means that either narrative, stylistic and general affect words and word combinations are represented equally in both groups. The number of these words differs per review, which depends among other on the length of a review, but not per category. This

makes us conclude on this stage of the research that even when readers respond to books which deviate from the tense conventions of the genre more often, the responses seem to be equally different in usage of impact terms.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

We have found that readers tend to respond more often to books that break out of genre tense conventions by writing a statistically significant higher number of online reviews. This may be due to psychological and/or biological prerequisites to respond to deviation from the accepted norm. However, the notion of norm in the literature, as already mentioned, is conditioned by the complex structure of social institutions at a particular historical time. In addition, by considering narrative tense in books as a marker of conventionality/deviation, we were able to find some patterns in readers' reactions, but this does not mean that these reactions are solely due to narrative tense. For example, the choice of narrative tense may, within some genres, be closely related to the themes of the book. It is also likely that there are other features besides narrative tense and content that influence the reader, for instance, the popularity of particular books in reading communities, or popularity of books connected with modern historical and political events, which we have not touched upon in this article, but which may be explored in the future.

The fact that we have not found any difference in the use of impact terms does not imply that reviewers respond identically to books across all categories and genres. This approach can be supplemented with an analysis of positive and negative words in the reviews, key terms, sentiment analysis, or other methods that provide deeper insights into the content of the reviews.

Not only lower-order features, but also factors such as the popularity of a book or topicality in a particular social and historical context can be considered as factors influencing readers. The present article thus represents only a small step in understanding the impact of fiction, much work remains to be done.

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Persons in Context: Potential and Pitfalls for the CLARIAH Infrastructure

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Historians and social scientists have been working with historical person data for decades, resulting in regional and national reconstructions of historical populations. However, current initiatives hardly allow for interlinking reconstruction projects, despite advances in computing power that allow population reconstructions of an ever-increasing size. With the Persons in Context (PiCo) vocabulary, the Center for Family History in the Netherlands (CBG) provides an opportunity to standardise historical person observations and interlink person observations from multiple sources into life courses in a FAIR way. As a result, PiCo could also facilitate modular person reconstruction software, allowing tools for cleaning, linking and evaluation to work in a single pipeline. The main aim of the paper is to describe the practical potential and predicaments of adopting PiCo in the current CLARIAH linked data pipeline for person reconstruction. In particular, we contribute (1) the incongruencies between the data model of PiCo and the CLARIAH record linkage tool, *burgerLinker*, and *C2RC*, the CLARIAH record linkage evaluation tool, (2) enhancing the interoperability of tools and data in a person reconstruction pipeline and (3) we present the concept of ‘provenance trails’, enabling a direct link between archival sources and research outcomes.

Keywords: [Data Models, FAIR, Person Observation, Person Reconstruction, PiCo-M, Provenance Trails, Research Infrastructure]

1 Introduction

The introduction of historical databases of person reconstructions 35 years ago initiated a new era for historical demography (Fauve-Chamoux et al., 2016). Archival sources containing personal demographic variables can be collected and organised in digital

resources to enhance our understanding of the past. The method of modeling the observations of personal characteristics is very important. Reconstructions of persons and family relations must follow standards to support combining or comparing datasets over time and space. Standards also ensure the quality and accountability of the data (Meroño Peñuela et al., 2020; Woltjer et al., 2024).

The importance of traceability is underlined by the long tradition in humanities research of making references to the sources on which the result is based. These references are traditionally organised in textual form as footnotes, end notes, or table captions. Such sources may include not only primary source material, but also secondary literature. There are important reasons to facilitate 'provenance trails' from archival source data to final research output. For one, references facilitate the reproducibility of the study and as a result increase its trustworthiness. References also reduce the time required to reproduce results, enhancing opportunities to evaluate research results. Finally, references explicate assumptions made in the data wrangling or research interpretation phase. This allows work to be revisited in the future, when more knowledge becomes available on assumptions made today.

Yet, in this day and age of Digital Humanities the field has hardly made progress in enhancing the degree of traceability. Reconstruction of historical persons requires data to flow from archival institutions to genealogists and researchers. Archival institutions scan, transcribe and disclose person observations from historical records. These observations are shared online for genealogists and researchers, who then create life course reconstructions based on these observations using manual methods or automated algorithms, of which the LINKS project has been the largest and most successful example in the Netherlands (Mandemakers et al., 2023). However, software made by different researchers and institutes is often not reusable, and the rationale behind reconstructions, also known as provenance, is often not retraceable. Moreover, in communicating the life course reconstructions, all links to underlying sources are aggregated into a handful of footnotes on which archival materials were used.

Having more detailed references to underlying sources, which we will call 'provenance trails', is feasible. Many of the larger research platforms stem from the 1990s and early 2000s, when FAIR was not yet an accepted philosophy, and especially memory or the use of the internet to link resources was limited. Yet, the same can be said for platforms such as *WieWasWie.nl* and *OpenArchieven.nl*, which both show how aggregator platforms can give credit to the original source in different ways, by directly pointing to that source online.

The fact that this state-of-the-art state is not yet embraced by research is in our view problematic for at least three reasons. The first is that the actual reproduction of research is still a very cumbersome process, requiring many manual, none traceable, actions. Second, as with research, archives are increasingly dependent on the explication of relevance to science and society, often expressed in usage indicators for funding. The occasional acknowledgment of archives in research papers is not retraceable for those archives and cannot be used to show their relevance to research. The third is a possibly waning relationship between GLAM institutions and academic research. FARO, the Flemish support institute for cultural heritage, has already called on Flemish heritage institutions to democratise their research function and emphasises the need to step away from measuring expertise based on academic and scientific merit releasing their exclusive authority as heritage institutions (Van Oost and Vander Stichele, 2024, p. 21).

In the Netherlands, there is a long-standing relationship between exchange of his-

torical person records via the archives, centralised by the Center for Family History (CBG), and person and family reconstruction via research embodied in the HSNDB at the International Institute of Social History (IISH). Research-made reconstitutions are returned to the CBG’s website as suggestions to help persons find their ancestors.¹ The CBG has recently, with the research and heritage community, released a Linked Data Vocabulary for the description of persons observations and person reconstructions in the heritage (archival) setting and the research setting. This vocabulary is called “Persons in Context” (PiCo) and will phase out an existing XML data model to support the ever-increasing exchange and use of historical person data, as meticulously described in Woltjer et al. (2024). The Netwerk Digitaal Erfgoed (NDE) urges Dutch GLAM institutions to provide their collections as linked data, archives are thus stimulated to use PiCo to describe person observations in their collection (Gaakeer et al. (2021); NDE and ministerie van OC&W (2024)). Linked Data “refers to a set of best practices for publishing structured data on the Web”.² Linked Data follows existing and widely adopted standards using vocabularies such as PiCo to model the data.

In this paper, we want to show how the PiCo vocabulary could be used to enhance the link between research and archival sources.³ We will do so within the Common Lab Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (CLARIAH) infrastructure framework, and discuss the implications of Persons in Context for the CLARIAH person reconstruction and evaluation tools, burgerLinker and C2RC.⁴ We also introduce the notion of ‘provenance trails’, a ‘bread crumb trail’ from research result to primary source as a means to capture the way that person reconstructions are built. By doing so, we underline the value of PiCo for (1) reusability of data and tooling, (2) enhancing the interoperability of tools and data in a person reconstruction pipeline and (3) the retraceability of research results to its archival resources. The importance of these concepts extends far beyond the presented pipeline and will be pivotal for sustainable Digital Heritage and Digital Humanities.

2 Generating Person Reconstructions

We first evaluate the software that generates person reconstructions from person observations in the indexed civil registry for the HSNDB project LINKS (Mandemakers et al., 2023). A Person Observation refers to a single instance of a person observed in a single source. LINKS aims to reconstruct all persons who were born, married, or died within the Netherlands within the 19th and 20th centuries by matching and harmonising person observations from civil registry records. A combination of several person observations that presumably refer to the same person is called a person reconstruction. The initiators of LINKS chose to base their person reconstructions on the civil registry, as historically willingness to register was high, checks on the registration practice stringent, and double storage meant that the source survived bombardments, fires, floods, and other mishaps (Vulsma, 1988).

Although the civil registry contains a rather complete recollection of all vital events within the borders of the Netherlands, it can be tricky to identify to which person each event belongs. The civil registry chronologically lists all births, marriages, and deaths that occurred in a municipality. Persons are only followed passively, and are

¹ See <https://WieWasWie.nl>

² ‘Linked Data’, W3CWiki (24 September 2023), <https://www.w3.org/wiki/LinkedData>.

³ We would like to thank Pieter Woltjer for his insightful feedback and comments.

⁴ See <https://www.clariah.nl>.

not observed outside of events, so while we get names of index persons and relatives, we cannot know whether and when a previous or next observation occurs (Alter et al., 2009; Gill, 1997; Van den Berg et al., 2021). As a result, any person reconstruction based on person observations in civil records is always to some extent open to interpretation, as we cannot ascertain that all events associated with a person have been added to a reconstruction. Hence provenance data and a transparent pipeline are key.

Figure 1: Civil Registries schema for burgerLinker (Raad et al., 2020) (CC0)

Data models help to create reusable software and introduce standards on data provenance. However, the current pipeline (Van Herck and Mourits, 2023) was developed before the creation of PiCo. The Civil Registries schema in figure 1 was purpose-built resulting from ad hoc needs for matching person observations with the custom-made tool burgerLinker.⁵ burgerLinker was designed to solve computational problems in comparing millions of name combinations. burgerLinker generates person reconstructions regardless of minor differences in name spelling using the Levenshtein distance to measure similarity between names on two different records (Raad et al., 2020). In order to retrieve unique matches, multiple names on civil certificates are matched, for example ego, father, and mother. The matching strategy in figure 2 demonstrates how person names can be compared for seven types of links, six of which are included in burgerLinker.⁶

Because person observations are converted and checked before person reconstructions can be generated, this schema increases the overhead. In addition, burgerLinker cannot be generalised. Any variation in other sources or similar sources from other countries will likely cause errors. Moreover, comparing output with other matching algorithms is cumbersome, as each package describes provenance slightly differently in their metadata.

If we were to adopt the PiCo standard, dates will be standardised to YMD ISO 8601, names are edited according to the rules of the Person Name Vocabulary (PNV) and Schema.org, certificate types are listed in PiCo terminology, relations are listed in Schema.org, and roles according to PiCo terminology (Woltjer et al., 2024). However,

⁵ Joe Raad, 'CLARIAH/burgerLinker', Java (2021; repr., CLARIAH, 30 November 2023), <https://github.com/CLARIAH/burgerLinker>

⁶ Within D-M is currently not included.

Figure 2: burgerLinker matching strategy (Van Herck and Mourits, 2023). Image reproduced with permission from the copyright owner.

other parties involved in historical person reconstruction have generally used their own schemas and developed their own algorithms to match historical person records, which has hampered the interoperability and reusability of software (Mourits et al., 2023).

The PiCo vocabulary will supersede the Civil Registries vocabulary specifically created for burgerLinker. When creating burgerLinker, no existing ontology fully covered what we needed, therefore we created the Civil Registries vocabulary. The Civil Registries vocabulary was kept simple, because creating a proper schema would be another project entirely. burgerLinker’s architecture was designed to incorporate an ontology with as little effort as possible. The adoption of the ‘new’ PiCo vocabulary, will therefore come with minimal adaption cost as the community has anticipated the arrival of a more fully fletched ontology to describe person observations.

We note three conceptual differences between PiCo and the Civil Registries vocabulary that are important to implement anew in burgerLinker. First, unlike the Civil Registries vocabulary, PiCo discerns the date of the registration of the event and the actual event. While a marriage is usually registered on the same day, there can be a time difference in registration of death and birth. This seemingly small distinction in time is of crucial importance when registrations of baptisms are used to estimate birth dates and in research focusing on infant mortality. Second, PiCo’s elaborate modelling of family relationships and roles supersedes the Civil Registries schema. Third, while the Civil Registries vocabulary was designed with vital event registers in mind, PiCo was designed to be compatible with a wide variety of historical documents, making PiCo more versatile and interoperable.

To illustrate some of the more detailed differences between the PiCo and Civil Registries vocabularies, we created Figure 3, showing the properties relating an event to a person; picot:newborn refers to the role of a newborn on a birth certificate, while picom:deceased has become a property of a person observation, schema:spouse refers to both bride and groom, and schema:parent replaces mother and father. The Civil Registries schema implies gender within the language used to describe the role, whereas

Figure 3: burgerLinker matching strategy remodeled according to PiCo

information on a person's gender in PiCo is explicated via the property schema:gender.

To illustrate the difference in handling names between the Civil Registries Schema and PiCo, figure 4 provides an example of a marriage certificate.⁷ While the Civil Registries schema uses the Schema ontology for names, the PiCo model extends Schema with the Person Name Vocabulary (PNV) to include peculiarities of Dutch names.⁸ Similarly PiCo allows for other regional and language specific additions to accommodate the expression of names. burgerLinker already dropped the prefix of Dutch surnames for matching, as prefixes are generally seen as separate from the surnames in the source material and can introduce spelling variations in the full sdo:familyName. This split between prefixes and surnames becomes easier when PiCo is implemented. Specifically, burgerLinker can use PiCo's distinction between pnv:surnamePrefix and pnv:baseSurname for family names. These are all minor tweaks to burgerLinker, but would make the program much easier and less labour-intensive to use.

Provenance is central to the PiCo data model, whereas the Civil Registries schema only indirectly links to the source through a civ:registrationID. We created figure 5 to illustrate the PiCo model and to show the link between person observations and archive components in PiCo.⁹ This figure illustrates the relation between a node representing the PersonObservation on the left (in blue), with all its potential properties. Moreover, PersonObservation is linked to an ArchiveComponent (in yellow) on the right side of the figure with a property from the PROV-O ontology, specifically designed to capture provenance. This relation is called the 'hadPrimarySource' property. One of the properties describing the ArchiveComponent is the URL that points to the web

⁷ CBG, 'PiCo/examples/various-sources/huwelijksakte.ttl', 14 December 2024 <https://github.com/CBG-Centrum-voor-familiegeschiedenis/PiCo/blob/a01283ffc1469285c2dcb280e32842b616187791/examples/various-sources/huwelijksakte.ttl#L77-L88>; CBG, 'PiCo', 20 september 2024, <https://github.com/CBG-Centrum-voor-familiegeschiedenis/PiCo/blob/main/PiCo%20Specificatie.md>.

⁸ Schema.org, 9 January 2024, <https://schema.org/>. Lodewijk Petram, Elvin Dechesne, and Gijsbert Kruithof, 'Person Name Vocabulary', Person Name Vocabulary, 1 July 2019, <https://www.lodewijkpetram.nl/vocab/pnv/doc/>.

⁹ Visual created in Grafo (<https://grafo>).

to relate the established PersonReconstruction to the PersonObservations. Because of all these links, a PersonReconstruction can be traced back to its original source, constituting a provenance trail containing all the steps from the research result to the sources it was based upon. In this way we are describing the knowledge production process, which enables research replication in the future. (Stapel and Zandhuis, 2024)

3 Identifying Person Reconstructions

The second challenge is generating a unique identifier for every person. When civil registries were introduced in the late nineteenth century, governments did not assign identifiers. The civil registry never followed persons over time and 'only' reports on the births, marriage, and deaths that occurred that year within a municipality. However, when the civil registry for a province or the entire country is combined, the person observations can be used to reconstruct life courses and families. In order to keep track of these person reconstructions, we suggest to create a unique identifier for each person reconstruction linking to all observations of that individual.¹⁰ Such a identifier helps to keep track of provenance on changes in sets of observations that 'reconstruct' a person's life course, including edits or dissolution of such a reconstruction.

Generating person identifiers on a national scale over two centuries is no small feat, especially across borders and sources. It requires a balancing act between a stringent protocol stable between different versions of the data and a system tailored to continuous changes. To compare person reconstructions between versions, identifiers cannot be generated randomly. This also means that the name of a person reconstruction cannot rely on the combination of matched certificates, as this would not allow reconstructions to be checked for merging and splitting. PiCo enables us to model person reconstructions with a unique identifier and provenance to the underlying observations.

However, tracking all mutations would generate an unfathomable change log. We suggest using an authority list because some historical person records are more useful than others to determine which unique persons lived in the past. A person reconstruction would receive an identifier based on the highest authority certificate. For the civil registry a logical authority list would be first birth, then death, and finally marriage certificates. This system allows for person identifiers that can be traced whilst allowing for changes between versions. For example, if a person reconstruction contains two sisters named Anna and Anna Maria, it should be split in two separate person reconstructions. One reconstruction with the identifier of the birth certificate of Anna to identify the first person reconstruction and another with an identifier from the remaining certificate with the highest authority to identify Anna Maria. An authority list can also be a set of thoroughly checked person reconstructions. In that case, an alternative to the previous logical historical identifier would be to assign serial identifiers. When mistakes in links are discovered the serial identifier would need to be changed and could possibly result in multiple identifiers for person reconstructions with updated life courses.

Historical person identifiers can be maintained at any level, but ideally at the national level. In the Netherlands, the Center for Family History (CBG) is aiming to become the central network partner that identifies historical persons and assigns them historical person identifiers. In Belgium a logical approach to identifiers would be to transpose the current logic of national person identification numbers (*rijksregisternummers*) to the

¹⁰ Al Idrissou, 'C2RC', Python, 26 December 2023, <https://github.com/CLARIAH/C2RC>

past, whereby the date of birth (YY.MM.DD) is followed by a serial number of three digits according to the order of registration of a person with even numbers for female persons and uneven numbers for male persons. The final two digits are calculated by dividing the birth date and serial number by 97 as a checksum. Persons born in or after the year 2000 are assigned an additional digit (2) at the start of their national person identification number. With each century the order of registration begins again, which causes problem for collections of historical person data that span multiple centuries. Therefore, the identifier should be expanded to YYYY.MM.DD-XXX.XX.¹¹

4 Evaluating and Validating Person Reconstructions (C2RC)

Thirdly, we investigate the role of PiCo in the evaluation and validation of the - possibly automatically generated - reconstructions. The Civil Registry Reconstitutions Cleaner (C2RC), developed in the context of CLARIAH similar to burgerLinker, was designed to systematically evaluate record linkage, such as output from burgerLinker. Reconstructing life courses from person observations is a challenge. Information on records is often incomplete or slightly inaccurate. Moreover, explicitly stating why some matches are considered sound, while others are not, supports reproducibility. Therefore C2RC provides an adaptable set of hard rules and soft rules. Hard rules are matches deemed impossible, such as a reconstructed life course containing multiple birth records. Soft rules are more domain-specific and for example specify a person's oldest feasible age or the maximum number of children a person might have. In addition to evaluation, C2RC allows users to improve upon incongruencies in the linkage based on the hard and soft rules. In line with the concept of provenance trails, C2RC monitors edits based on these violations. To track these improvements C2RC uses the VOID+ vocabulary (Idrissou et al., 2022) as shown in Figure 6.¹²

The VoID+ vocabulary documents *the Creation, Manipulation and Evaluation of Links for Reuse and Reproducibility* and indicates which sources and entities are covered by the dataset, the algorithms and criteria used to generate the data, whether links are validated or not, and if for instance person observations are clustered (Idrissou et al., 2022, p. i). The VoID+ vocabulary reuses the existing vocabularies VoID and PROV-O to create provenance trails (Idrissou et al., 2022, p. ii). Figure 6 illustrates the example from the previous section of a person reconstruction that contains the two siblings Anna and Anna Maria. The initial person reconstruction is now identified as the original cluster that is split into two subclusters. For each of these new subclusters VoID+ tracks what cluster this new person reconstruction was derived from and which person observations it is composed of.

VoID+ allows us to keep track of how data is generated, which validations were applied and how person reconstructions can be split or merged. However, this does not resolve issues in identifying person reconstructions between different matching efforts, as validations and changes to the dataset are lost with each iteration. Furthermore, we could end up with an unfathomable change log that makes the dataset harder to work with despite increasing the chances of proper reproducibility. While PiCo does not implement VoID+ as a way to establish provenance trails, it enables including the PROV vocabulary to model the prov:Activity and thus keep track of the research

¹¹ See https://www.ibz.rrn.fgov.be/fileadmin/user_upload/nl/rr/toegang/bestand-rr.pdf

¹² 'VoIDPlus', 1 August 2022.
<https://github.com/VoIDPlus-owl/EKAW2022/blob/main/voidPlus.owl>.

```

@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> .
@prefix voidPlus: <http://lenticularlens.org/voidPlus/> .
@prefix resource: <https://iisg.amsterdam/id/civ/resource/> .
@prefix dio: <https://w3id.org/dio#> .
@prefix civ: <https://iisg.amsterdam/id/civ/> .
@prefix ind: <https://iisg.amsterdam/links/person/> .

resource:Zeeland-Manual-Validation-H3b094c2f2c6e192
{{{}}} {

    ### 2023-07-11 14:49:13.218922
    ind:i-26785
    a
        voidPlus:ResourceCluster,
        voidPlus:SplitCluster;
        ind:i-1_Hf897efcefc13cf5 ;
        ind:i-2_H988ebffe3f7467e .

        voidPlus:hasValidatedSubCluster
        voidPlus:hasValidatedSubCluster

    ind:i-1_Hf897efcefc13cf5
    a
        voidPlus:ResourceCluster,
        voidPlus:SplitCluster;
        ind:i-26785 ;
        ind:p-411799, ind:p-2867421 .

        voidPlus:derivedFrom
        voidPlus:isComposedOf

    ind:i-2_H988ebffe3f7467e
    a
        voidPlus:ResourceCluster,
        voidPlus:SplitCluster;
        ind:i-26785 ;
        ind:p-2526610 .

        voidPlus:derivedFrom
        voidPlus:isComposedOf

```

Figure 6: C2RC export of the manual validation of a person reconstruction. Screenshot from a user session in C2RC.

process of generating a Person Reconstruction as we have illustrated in figure 7.

Figure 7: PiCo Person Reconstruction.

As PiCo is expressed using RDF, an alternative and better approach would be to use the standardised Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL) for validation purposes. A shape graph consists of triples describing what patterns can be expected, for example, that a birth year should be expressed as a date in YYYY.MM.DD and the date must fall within a certain time range. This shape graph is compared to a data graph to show incongruencies, similar to the 'hard' and 'soft' rules in C2RC. SHACL will provide an important contribution as it can be used to see whether data was put in the right data format, and reused in similar tools across the ecosystem. We have included an example of a translation from C2RC's rule to SHACL in Figure 8. Ideally, there

should be different SHACL shapes for ‘hard’ rules and ‘soft’ rules, standardising current evaluation purposes. Internationally providing these SHACL rules holds huge potential as most evaluation is now done within countries on country-specific linkage methods.

Figure 8: SHACL example for PiCo. Image reproduced with permission from the copyright owner.

When the indexed civil registry data is remodelled into PiCo, the Civil Registry Reconstitutions Cleaner (C2RC) needs an extensive update. C2RC relies on the graph structure to evaluate person reconstructions against a set of rules, changes to the graph structure would require changes to C2RC. In addition to the benefits of SHACL for record linkage evaluation, SHACL would also make C2RC interoperable with other software components.

5 Conclusion

This paper describes potential benefits of applying a standardised data model to an existing pipeline. First we discussed how PiCo (Woltjer et al., 2024) can impact and expand burgerLinker, the software that generates person reconstructions. The second challenge is identifying person reconstructions by generating a unique and persistent identifier. Finally, we explained how a remodel of the indexed civil registry enables a standardised SHACL implementation of the Civil Registry Reconstitutions Cleaner (C2RC), a tool to evaluate and validate person reconstructions. We conclude that PiCo makes each component of the pipeline reusable by improving the interoperability of datasets and algorithms for historic archival sources containing person observations.

The model is only the beginning of expanding across time, space, and source types. PiCo as a shared data standard allows us to further integrate tools into an ecosystem. Anyone can select only part of the ecosystem for their project as long as they adhere to the standard. The tools that are already developed based on the standard can be further integrated into other pipelines. An additional advantage in saving both input and output, is that by using provenance trails, provenance is saved independent from

tooling (Stapel and Zandhuis, 2024).

The updated pipeline allows us to publish the most extensive version of the linked civil registry to date. Implementing major changes for both burgerLinker and C2RC depends on future project funding. Ideally, we make all tools schema agnostic, or at least implement the PiCo model and translate C2RC's evaluation rules to SHACL. Schema agnostic tools can be used for slightly different sources, or for different schemas adapted to similar sources in other countries. The LINKS pipeline could serve as a proof of concept and practical implementation to create person reconstructions for the civil registry. In the future we want to use a more diverse set of sources. By incorporating PiCo, Openarchieven.nl shows how archival data can be provided openly and research ready, building an important bridge between heritage and research. New projects could take the development a step further to link and analyse large amounts of data such as historical sources, texts, and images.¹³

For the Netherlands, the population registers ('bevolkingsregisters') and personal cards ('persoonskaarten') first come to mind, but more elaborate sources like notarial deeds could be included. Current projects about causes of death (Janssens, 2021; Janssens and Devos, 2022), and inheritance (de Vicq and Peeters, 2020) and income taxes¹⁴ can make use of PiCo to enable linkage and result in analyses of a larger combination of variables. People migrate and relate to people in other countries, so data does not stop at the Dutch border. PiCo has chosen international standards such as PROV-O to facilitate linking persons across countries.¹⁵ In the Dutch colonial context, a reconstruction of life courses for Suriname and the Caribbean (HDSC) has been undertaken (Raaijmakers, 2024; Van Galen et al., 2023). We are not aware of person reconstructions in Belgian or Luxembourgish projects.

While indexed civil registries for Belgium have only been made available online from 2017 onwards, 30 years of transcription precede the current LINKS dataset(s).¹⁶ Unlike wiewaswie.nl, genealogie.arch.be separates digitised certificates from persons in the database. Both countries have asked volunteers to transcribe and index the civil registry. Scanned Belgian sources containing person observations are available via Family Search, while person observations have sporadically been transcribed manually by volunteers resulting in substantial differences in availability by region and research project.¹⁷ Furthermore, person observations can be searched via the National Archive website and are not available as a complete dataset for researchers.¹⁸ One Belgian database similar to LINKS worth mentioning is the Antwerp COR-Database built by the Leuven Research Group Family and Population Studies (FAPOS) containing "longitudinal and intergenerational data at the individual level".¹⁹

AI can ease the workload for data entry from scanned sources with Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) or Optical Character Recognition (OCR), and Named Entity

¹³ Thijs van der Veen, 'SSHOC-NL infrastructuur ontvangt 15,2 miljoen', *Huygens Instituut (blog)*, 20 February 2023, <https://www.huygens.knaw.nl/sshoc-nl-infrastructuur-ontvangt-152-miljoen/>.

¹⁴ 'HIP-NL: A Historical Income Panel for the Netherlands', PDI-SSH, 2021. <https://pdi-ssh.nl/nl/2021/11/gehonoreerde-projecten-2021-call/>.

¹⁵ 'The PROV Namespace', The PROV Namespace, 19 May 2013, <https://www.w3.org/ns/prov>.

¹⁶ Mourits, Rick J., Kees Mandemakers, Fons Laan, and Richard L. Zijdeman. 'Cleaned Civil Registry, Netherlands'. IISH Data Collection, 12 July 2023. <https://datasets.iisg.amsterdam/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=hdl:10622/0N0SRV>.

¹⁷ An overview of finished and ongoing projects is available here: <https://search.arch.be/en/zoeken-naar-personen/projecten>

¹⁸ See <https://genealogie.arch.be/>.

¹⁹ See <https://ehps-net.eu/databases/antwerp-cor-database>.

Recognition (NER) to extract person names and model them in line with the PiCo ontology. In turn, the PiCo data model eases the workload by ensuring that burgerLinker can be reused in the Belgian context, while also ensuring that new techniques to create person reconstructions developed in Belgium can be reused in the Netherlands.

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Multilingual Automated Subject Indexing: a Comparative Study of LLMs vs Alternative Approaches in the Context of the EHRI Project

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The European Holocaust Research Infrastructure (EHRI) facilitates transnational Holocaust research by making information about dispersed archival sources accessible through the EHRI Portal. An important aspect of effectively integrating this information is the indexing of collection metadata from institutions worldwide based on a common domain-specific controlled vocabulary (EHRI Terms). However, challenges persist in harmonising the use of subject headings across institutions. Hence, this paper explores approaches for Automated Subject Indexing (ASI), including statistical, lexical, and fusion approaches, as well as the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) for zero-shot classification. We describe how we use archival descriptions ingested into the EHRI Portal as training data for Machine Learning (ML) algorithms, including for fine-tuning an LLM. We evaluate LLM- and non-LLM-based tools quantitatively and qualitatively, with our focus being to explore if and to what extent LLMs can play a role in developing reliable ASI tools. We conclude that although some tools under evaluation score quite highly, they are at present best suited for use as part of semi-ASI workflows with human oversight. However, this study charts a promising course towards developing tools that are reliable enough to facilitate subject indexing processes and enhance metadata according to the FAIR Data Principles.

Keywords: Automated Subject Indexing, Natural Language Processing (NLP), Multilabel Text Classification, Holocaust, Controlled Vocabularies, Archives

1 Introduction

Since its launch in 2010, one of the principal goals of the European Holocaust Research Infrastructure (EHRI) has been to catalyse transnational Holocaust research by making information about dispersed archival materials more interconnected, coherent, and accessible. For researchers into the Holocaust, the landscape of archival sources is a highly complex one, for reasons including the deliberate destruction of evidence, dispersal of materials, and the migration of survivors (Blanke et al., 2014). This has resulted in material being fragmented, duplicated, and separately described by a multitude of institutions with different mandates, cataloguing practices, and approaches to curation. The EHRI Portal is an attempt to integrate archival metadata from these dispersed sources into a single framework, creating a virtual observatory within which fragmented collections can be connected and contextualised (Blanke et al., 2017).¹

Aggregating and integrating archival descriptions from hundreds of institutions around the world poses considerable institutional, social, and technical challenges. As previously observed (Erez et al., 2020; García-González and Bryant, 2023; Rodriguez et al., 2016), in the context of Holocaust-related archives, different institutions take a wide range of approaches to describing their materials, even putting aside those differences imposed by factors such as their specific collection management systems and institutional environments. The use of index terms — controlled vocabularies of subject headings, people, organisations, and places — is a cornerstone technique in enhancing the discovery and retrieval of archival material. Yet across the hundreds of institutions holding Holocaust-related material, or specialising in the field, there is negligible commonality in the application of index terms or the use of common controlled vocabularies. In most cases where index terms *are* used, an in-house vocabulary is the typical approach. While a small minority of institutions do use general-purpose subject heading thesauri such as the Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH)², that does not necessarily mean that they interpret and apply the index terms to their material in consistent or interoperable ways (Erez et al., 2020).

This lack of a common vocabulary for Holocaust-related material was one of the problems EHRI set out to address in its first phase (2010-2014) with the creation of the *EHRI Terms* vocabulary, a hierarchically organised, multilingual set of subject headings. While the starting point for EHRI Terms was a controlled vocabulary in use at Yad Vashem (Erez et al., 2020),³ it has since undergone considerable expansion and restructuring in both the terms and available languages, and at the time of writing consists of 913 terms translated in 12 languages.⁴ The vocabulary is used by EHRI's own subject-matter experts when creating new descriptions for as-yet uncatalogued material, and as an integration and interlinking point when ingesting into the EHRI Portal material described by EHRI's many partner institutions. It is also available in the Resource Description Framework (RDF) in Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) format, along with two other controlled vocabularies focusing on World War II *ghettos* and *camps*.⁵

While EHRI has built a robust data integration infrastructure, improving the discoverability and interconnectedness of multilingual collection metadata, sourced from

¹ <https://portal.ehri-project.eu/>.

² <https://www.loc.gov/aba/publications/FreeLCSH/LCSH44-Main-intro.pdf>

³ <https://www.yadvashem.org/>

⁴ English, Hebrew, Italian, Dutch, Russian, Ukrainian, Czech, Hungarian, French, Polish, Serbo-Croatian, and German. As of 24 January 2025.

⁵ <https://portal.ehri-project.eu/vocabularies/>

multiple institutions, remains key objective for the project. The harmonisation of subject headings, using the EHRI Terms vocabulary as an integration point, is one particular area where there is room for improvement, not only because much of the aggregated metadata does not currently align with it but because many archival collections lack index terms entirely. At present, 25% of collection-level descriptions have no index terms at all.⁶ Of those that *do* have index terms, only 30% have subject terms aligned with the EHRI Terms vocabulary.⁷

Past work has described how vocabularies in use by a selection of partner institutions were systematically co-referenced to EHRI Terms (Erez et al., 2020). This paper, however, investigates whether archival descriptions in the EHRI Portal could be made more discoverable and interlinked *at scale* through Automated Subject Indexing (ASI), i.e., the use of machine-based methods, such as computational linguistics and statistics, to perform the subject indexing steps typically performed by human indexers (Golub, 2021). The findings of this investigation are applicable beyond EHRI and its partners, as they could help other institutions address similar challenges in their specific contexts.⁸ Experimenting with ASI is also part of a larger effort to integrate automated metadata generation techniques into EHRI’s workflows. Other techniques we have been exploring include multilingual Named Entity Recognition (Dermentzi and Scheithauer, 2024) and Automatic Speech Recognition (Wynne, 2023). Such efforts fit into the broader context of cultural heritage institutions viewing their collections as data that can be used to experiment with and develop innovative digital tools as described in Candela et al. (2023) and Candela et al. (2024).

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: in Section 2 we provide an overview of ASI and the related work in this area; in Section 3 we describe in more detail the EHRI Terms vocabulary and a corpus of documents derived from metadata in the EHRI Portal; in Section 4 we present our experiments, the different tools under evaluation, the quantitative and qualitative methodology and the metrics used; in Section 5 we present the results obtained from our evaluation, followed in Section 6 by a discussion of various issues identified in this work. Finally, in Section 7 we draw the future lines of work based on the obtained results and in Section 8 we present our conclusions.

2 Automated Subject Indexing

Approaches to ASI vary based on the purpose of the application and the field from which it originates (Golub, 2021). The two prevailing approaches are the statistical/associative and lexical techniques respectively (Suominen and Koskenniemi, 2022; Toepfer and Seifert, 2020).⁹ The statistical associative approach involves Multi-label Text Classification (MTC) methods, where a supervised Machine Learning (ML) model is trained on the already indexed texts of a collection. The model learns weights that are used to predict the correct set of terms given the text of a document. Lexical approaches, on the other hand, employ string-matching to match terms in the controlled vocabulary with words in the text of the record’s description using similarity measures (Golub, 2021). Recent research has also suggested fusion approaches that

⁶ Accessed 29th Jan 2024: <https://portal.ehri-project.eu/api/datasets/E136TY2zwL>

⁷ Accessed 29th Jan 2024: <https://portal.ehri-project.eu/api/datasets/CtaJXtPuZA>

⁸ This is especially the case given EHRI’s use of archival standards, e.g., General International Standard Archival Description (ISAD(G)), and the fact that the tools used by the authors are open-source, meaning that others can reuse and adapt them for their use cases.

⁹ Lexical approaches are also known as string-matching or rule-based approaches (Golub, 2021).

combine statistical and lexical methods using ensemble techniques (Suominen and Koskenniemi, 2022; Toepfer and Seifert, 2020).

More recently, the emergence of Large Language Models (LLMs) has enabled a novel approach: transfer learning using zero-shot or few-shot classification (Chow et al., 2024). A general-purpose pre-trained LLM can be used to predict suitable labels from a list of candidate terms (derived from a controlled vocabulary) without needing fine-tuning on domain-specific data (Zhang et al., 2023, p. 3). Presently, the zero-shot classification approach (where the model is made to return predictions without having been provided with any examples of its task) is commonly used as a data augmentation method to overcome class imbalance or the lack of training examples (Møller et al., 2023; Van Nooten and Daelemans, 2023). Zhang et al. (2023) and Chow et al. (2024) have experimented with subject indexing using few-shot learning (meaning the instructions provided to the model included a few examples of the task along with the list of the candidate subject terms).

While EHRI has not so far deployed ASI, it has used lexical techniques in its Entity Matching Tool (EMT) for co-referencing index terms from third-party vocabularies to EHRI’s terms (or to GeoNames in the case of place names).¹⁰ If the third-party vocabulary used to index an archival description uses terms that are morphologically very similar to the EHRI Terms, and in a language included within the EHRI Terms vocabulary, this method can return accurate results. This tool, however, was intended for assisting keyword-to-keyword alignment or aligning a set of discrete textual references, and not for generating keywords from the running text of an archival description. It does not consider the semantics of specific terms, and cannot assist with terms in languages other than those included in the target vocabulary.

3 Dataset

This section characterises our dataset — derived from archival descriptions within the EHRI Portal — and the EHRI Terms vocabulary that comprises our label set. As an aggregator of archival metadata, EHRI integrates descriptions of Holocaust-related archival material from a wide range of collection holders around the world. These range from small local archives and museums with very limited digital capabilities, to large and comparatively well-resourced institutions dedicated to memorialising the Holocaust. Among the latter include prodigious aggregators of physical archival material, such as Yad Vashem and the United States Holocaust Memorial Museum (USHMM)¹¹, who have amassed extensive collections of material sourced from other institutions and described using their own in-house standards and styles. A more in-depth explanation on how data integration takes place within EHRI’s current phase can be consulted in (Vanden Daelen et al., 2024).

As noted in the introduction, diversity and complex provenance are notable characteristics of the archival landscape relating to the Holocaust. One result of this is that some important collections do not yet have any metadata available in digital form. Since 2010 EHRI has sought to mitigate this by providing its own English-language descriptions of such collections in the EHRI Portal. Thus, the Portal contains not just metadata sourced from third parties, but original descriptions authored by subject matter experts following EHRI’s ISAD(G)-based descriptive standard and indexed against EHRI’s vocabularies, including EHRI Terms.

¹⁰ <https://emt.ehri-project.eu/>

¹¹ <https://www.ushmm.org/>

EHRI Terms¹² is structured as a Directional Acyclic Graph (DAG) with 15 top-level terms (“top concepts” in SKOS parlance¹³). The hierarchical structure has a maximum depth of 10 from broadest to narrowest, but the median depth is shallower at just 3 terms. The vocabulary is, additionally, not strictly hierarchical; many terms have multiple “broader” concepts, for example, the term “Healthcare” has three broader terms (“State Functions”, “Aid, Welfare, Rescue”, and “Daily Life”). Overall, 291 of 913 subjects fit within more than one higher-level category.

To construct a training and test set from structured metadata in the EHRI Portal we were restricted to the subset of archival descriptions which had already been assigned subject headings, either manually (by EHRI’s cataloguers) or via the co-referencing process described in Erez et al. (2020). This resulted in 48,854 individual archival units at all levels of description (from collection to item level). We then transformed each description into a single text by concatenating the fields considered most likely to capture the topical content of the material, as opposed to administrative details. The fields selected were ISAD(G) elements 3.1.2. Title; 3.2.2. Administrative / Biographical History; 3.2.3. Archival History; and 3.3.1. Scope and Content. We acknowledge that there is inevitably some imprecision in the selection of these fields, in terms of relevancy.

This dataset contained archival descriptions in 17 different languages. Polish and Finnish were represented in the dataset by only one example each. To retain these two descriptions in the dataset before splitting it into training and test sets would mean that descriptions in Polish and Finnish could only ever be present either in the training or in the test set. To avoid training on only one example of these two languages, or testing on them without having seen any in the same language during training, we decided to remove these descriptions from our dataset, leaving us with 48,852 entries. After de-duplicating our dataset to remove descriptions of the same archival units in different languages, we were left with 36,801 archival units.

In common with many multi-label classification tasks, particularly those featuring a large number of labels, class imbalance was a significant feature of our dataset. After some exploratory data analysis, we noticed that the most populous term, “Photographs”, was represented by 4,819 positive examples, while some of the least popular terms, like “Jewish religious leaders and functionaries”, were represented by only one example. Given the hierarchical nature of the label set, it is unsurprising that certain broader terms, especially terms pertaining to the genre of the material, such as “Photographs” or “Letters” were more frequently used than highly specific ones (e.g., “Activists in justice against criminals”). In fact, 215 terms had fewer than five positive examples in the dataset. To ensure better label distribution across training and test datasets, we removed terms with fewer than five examples. As a result, some descriptions matched to only one subject term lost their positive label and were also removed. The final dataset included 36,759 archival descriptions. Of the 913 subject terms in the EHRI vocabulary, only 554 met our threshold of at least five examples per term.

As in related work (Skenderi et al., 2021), to obtain a training and a test dataset we used the iterative multi-label stratification method proposed by Sechidis et al. (2011) as implemented in the Python package `iterative-stratification` (Bradberry, 2021). We opted for this method of stratification to increase the chances that all labels (as well as all languages) – no matter how rare in the dataset – would still have positive

¹² https://portal.ehri-project.eu/vocabularies/ehri_terms

¹³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/#L2446>

examples in both the training and test set. This was crucial to ensure that the evaluation of our model on the test set would be as complete as possible, covering the entire label space. It would also reduce the probability that certain multi-label classification metrics would be impossible to calculate due to the lack of positive examples as explained in Sechidis et al. (2011).

Specifically, we performed an initial multi-label stratified shuffle split of the dataset to obtain one split, where the test set size would include 30 per cent of the dataset (11,027 archival descriptions) and the train set would include the remaining 70 per cent of the dataset, i.e. 25,732 archival descriptions. The test split obtained through this process was further stratified/split once more in the same manner to obtain a third, considerably smaller, test set for evaluation purposes, which included 167 archival descriptions out of the 11,027 descriptions obtained through the first split. Since we wanted to perform both quantitative and qualitative evaluations to compare the different models used in our experiments, it was essential to have a manageable yet representative final test set that would be feasible for human evaluators to process in only a few working hours. Moreover, since we wanted to experiment with at least one LLM for zero-shot classification, obtaining predictions for a very large number of archival descriptions using 554 candidate labels would have been very costly and time-consuming to run on locally available hardware. While the larger test set obtained through the second splitting process (comprising 10,860 archival descriptions) was used to estimate model performance while training and fine-tuning new models, the smaller test set (167 archival descriptions), henceforth called the “evaluation” set to avoid confusion, was reserved for the final quantitative and qualitative evaluation and comparison of all the models in our experiment and was not used during training or fine-tuning. However, due to the very small size of the evaluation set and despite following the iterative stratification method for obtaining it, only the 134 most frequent labels had positive examples within it, while the remaining 420 did not. Similarly, although the test set used during training included examples in all 15 languages present in the training set, the evaluation set included examples only in the nine most frequent languages of our dataset,¹⁴ represented proportionally based on their distribution within our dataset. While performing these splits, a random state seed was used to make our experiment reproducible.

The dataset has been made openly available following best practices on publishing cultural heritage datasets (Alkemade et al., 2023; Candela et al., 2023).¹⁵

4 Experiments

This section describes how we selected the tools we put to the test: a transformer-based zero-shot classifier, a transformer-based model for fine-tuning, and other classical and non-LLM approaches. Key considerations in selecting the transformer-based models were support for multilingual text in languages relevant to EHRI’s material, being open source and easily accessible, having well-documented training data, and giving us the ability to quantitatively evaluate their performance using our in-house compute infrastructure.

¹⁴ English, Hebrew, Dutch, Czech, German, Multiple (used for descriptions containing text in more languages than one), French, Russian, Italian.

¹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14697253>

4.1 Zero-shot Classification Approach

The first approach, zero-shot classification, is the labelling of input data without the use of any prior context, e.g. labelled examples. In the context of LLMs it relies on the model having sufficient training data to have encountered related examples in its pre-training phase and to be able to make suitable inferences when given new data to classify. The purpose of this approach was to help us answer the question of whether using an LLM out of the box for classification purposes could be sufficiently reliable to be used as part of an automated or semi-ASI process or, alternatively, whether it could be used to augment our labelled dataset in order to reduce our class imbalance problem.

While at the time of writing the most advanced generally available LLM is OpenAI's GPT4 (OpenAI, 2023), we decided to omit this from the comparison at this stage due to the fact that it is not open source and due to the lack of transparency surrounding its development and training data. For practical reasons, we were also unable to include some newer LLMs capable of being self-hosted, such as TII's Falcon¹⁶ and Meta's Llama2¹⁷, both of which have exceedingly demanding inference requirements.

The model we selected for the zero-shot approach was mDeBERTa-v3-base-mnli-xnli (Laurer et al., 2023) available through Hugging Face (HF) which uses mDeBERTa v3 (He et al., 2023) as base model. mDeBERTa v3 is a multilingual model pre-trained on the CC100 multilingual dataset covering 100 languages (including all of the languages in our dataset) (He et al., 2023). mDeBERTa-v3-base-mnli-xnli is a fine-tuned version of mDeBERTa v3 for Natural Language Inference (NLI), trained using the XNLI (Conneau et al., 2018) and MNLI (Williams et al., 2018) datasets. These datasets include texts in 15 languages, but some of the languages that are present in our EHRI MTC dataset were not included in the datasets used to fine-tune mDeBERTa v3. However, since multilingual models for NLI are known for their cross-lingual transfer learning capabilities (Conneau et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2023), the fine-tuned model can still classify texts in the rest of the languages covered in the dataset that was used to train the base model despite not having seen any examples of them during fine-tuning.

4.2 Fine-tuning Approach

The second approach was to fine-tune a pre-trained LLM on EHRI's data, thus giving us some insight into whether the already-indexed archival descriptions can be harnessed to train models capable of performing effective classification of the remaining material. Although there is no shortage of pre-trained multilingual Transformer models to fine-tune, we decided to select BERT-base, Multilingual Cased (Devlin et al., 2019). In addition to being multilingual and open-source, we picked this model over more state-of-the-art (SOTA) alternatives for other important reasons. First, compared to more recent models it is much lighter and does not require significant resources to fine-tune. Second, it was trained on Wikipedia data rather than a CommonCrawl dataset, eliminating the chance of the model having already seen data in our training or test set (derived from either the EHRI Portal itself or EHRI-affiliated institutions). Third, as the original transformer implementation, it has gained a lot of popularity and is still widely used for tasks like text classification. It is also often used as a baseline with which to compare more recent models, helping us determine whether spending

¹⁶ <https://huggingface.co/tiiuae/falcon-180B>

¹⁷ <https://ai.meta.com/llama/>

more resources to fine-tune SOTA models would be something worth pursuing.

As suggested by the authors in the instructions accompanying the GitHub repository of the BERT family of models (Devlin et al., 2023),¹⁸ the “cased” version of the model is suggested for use in multilingual settings, especially with non-Latin alphabets, since it does less normalisation of the input. According to the authors, the data that was used to train the model comprised the entire Wikipedia dump for each of the top 100 languages with the largest Wikipedia instances.¹⁹ This list of languages includes all of those present in our train, test and evaluation sets. The transformers library (Wolf et al., 2020) developed by HF, as well as tutorials developed by the HF community (Rogge, 2021), provided an accessible way to proceed with fine-tuning Transformer models for multi-label classification. Underneath the hood, fine-tuning the pre-trained base BERT model on our EHRI dataset for MTC adds an extra linear layer on top of BERT’s final layer, which is trained to output scores that indicate how likely it is for each label to be the correct label for each text in the input.

To fine-tune BERT, we used a batch size of 32 and trained for 25 epochs, selecting the model with the best micro-averaged F1 score. We set the learning rate to $2e-5$. To avoid overfitting on the training set, we set the hidden dropout probability hyperparameter to 0.2 when instantiating the model and the weight decay hyperparameter to 0.01 when specifying the training arguments. The best micro-averaged F1 score on the large test set (≈ 0.56) was achieved by the model obtained in the final epoch.²⁰

4.3 Other Approaches

As a framework for quantitative evaluation we chose to employ Annif (Suominen, 2019; Suominen and Koskenniemi, 2022; Suominen et al., 2022, 2023), a tool for multilingual subject indexing already used by a number of cultural heritage institutions. Annif has been designed to enable the use of different multi-label classification backends tailored for specific types of material. It includes implementations of classical indexing algorithms like TF-IDF, as well as state-of-the-art approaches such as fastText (Joulin et al., 2017), and Parabel (Prabhu et al., 2018). Annif is written in Python and can be extended with additional backends by implementing specific subclasses. These new backends can then leverage Annif’s evaluation tools for generating metrics such as precision, recall, and F1 score (per-document, as well as using macro or micro averaging) along with ranked metrics such as non-discounted cumulative gain (NDCG).

In addition to the LLM-based approaches detailed in Section 4.1 and 4.2, we also evaluated a selection of Annif backends in order to provide a performance comparison.²¹ These included:

TF-IDF A baseline method capable of fast, resource-efficient labelling.

MLLM Maui-like Lexical Matching, inspired by Medelyan (2009).

fastText A fastText classifier.

¹⁸ <https://github.com/google-research/bert/blob/master/multilingual.md>

¹⁹ See <https://github.com/google-research/bert/blob/master/multilingual.md#data-source-and-sampling>

²⁰ EHRI’s fine-tuned BERT-based model is available on Hugging Face (<https://huggingface.co/mdermentzi/finetuned-bert-base-multilingual-cased-ehri-terms>) and Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14680007>)

²¹ More details about these backends can be found in the Annif wiki page: <https://github.com/NatLibFi/Annif/wiki>

Omikuji A Parabel implementation as an example of a state-of-the-art non-LLM method.

NN Ensemble A neural-network-based method of dynamically combining the outputs of several other discrete classification tools, in this case TF-IDF, MLLM, fastText, and Omikuji.

While it is capable of being configured for use in a multilingual setting, Annif does not currently have explicit support for heterogeneous corpora, e.g. those containing documents in a variety of languages. Since testing on our predominantly English evaluation dataset showed minimal impact on performance, however, we did not seek to address this limitation at this stage, noting that it could be worthwhile to explore as future work.

We created custom Annif backends for our fine-tuned BERT model and our zero-shot model of choice run via the HF transformers library, allowing us to deploy them and evaluate their performance in a consistent manner alongside Annif’s native backends. For the purpose of this experiment we only implemented the inference/suggestion functionality, however as future work the fine-tuning process could also be reimplemented to fit within Annif’s backend framework, including training and hyper-parameter optimisation.²²

4.4 Evaluation Metrics

We decided to evaluate the results of our experiments both quantitatively and qualitatively. Properly evaluating subject terms and consequently subject indexing tools is a very challenging task for a plethora of reasons (Golub et al., 2016). First and foremost, assigning and evaluating subject terms is a very subjective process and a term that may be considered pertinent by some may not be perceived as such by others. In fact, several inter-indexer consistency studies have proven that consistency levels between different indexers are typically very low (Tonta, 1991; Vaughan and Rafferty, 2011). Moreover, depending on the target audience of an institution, narrower and more specific subject terms may be preferred over broader ones, while other institutions may prioritise indexing records with as many terms as potentially useful rather than only a few specific ones (Golub et al., 2016). Ultimately, people browsing a catalogue to search for information on a specific topic will perceive a subject term to be correctly assigned only if it leads them to records relevant to their specific needs. Ideally, the evaluation of ASI tools should be based on how successful they are at helping users find answers to their questions. However, performing this kind of evaluation is extremely difficult and due to the subjective nature of the task may still lead to inconclusive results.

Usually, already indexed records are used as gold standard datasets based on which different tools can be evaluated quantitatively (Ahmed et al., 2023; Golub, 2021; Golub et al., 2016; Suominen et al., 2022). However, since subject indexing is a subjective task that is influenced by many factors (level of indexer’s expertise, institutional priorities, length of the vocabulary, etc.) (Golub, 2021; Golub et al., 2016), it is very hard to develop a truly comprehensive gold standard dataset on any real-life collection indexed with a sizeable enough controlled vocabulary. While we acknowledge this limitation, for the purposes of the quantitative evaluation herein we assume that the terms

²² A branch containing modified Annif code is available on Github (https://github.com/EHRI/Annif/tree/ehri_masi) and Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14697325>).

assigned to EHRI-ingested records through the methods described in the previous sections are complete and correct (Golub et al., 2016). As explained by Suominen et al. (2022), treating parts of already indexed collections as gold standard collections allows for quick and easy experimentation and evaluation of different algorithms. However, the authors agree with Suominen et al. (2022) that this method is best seen as a “ballpark estimate of quality” and other methods of evaluation should also be considered.

Similar to previous work (Ahmed et al., 2023; Asula et al., 2021; Chou and Chu, 2022; Gárdos et al., 2023; Skenderi et al., 2021; Toepfer and Seifert, 2020), to quantitatively evaluate the different multi-label classification methods we computed precision, recall and F1 scores. We computed these scores in three different ways: micro-averaged (taking into account total true positives, false negatives and false positives), weighted macro-averaged (computing the metrics per label weighted by each label’s number of true instances to account for class imbalance) and averaged per document. All of these scores range from zero to one, with one being the best possible score.

We have used as our primary metric the F1 score as provided by the Annif framework (Suominen et al., 2022) which considers the top five suggestions returned by the algorithm, averaged across all text samples. Since labels display some degree of imbalance due to the hierarchical nature of the vocabulary and preponderance of broader terms, other metrics display a degree of divergence from this figure and have also been given in Table 1. The F1 micro average, which considers true positive, false positive, and false negative values summed across all text samples, gives proportionally higher weight to performance on common labels. The F1 weighted macro score, on the other hand, averages individual scores across all labels and gives a better indication of performance on rare labels. Since labels are unordered we have not included NDCG or other ranked measures.

Since only 134 of the 554 subject terms we are considering in this experiment had positive examples in the evaluation set, our evaluation of these models only covers around 24 per cent of the labels that the models were trained (or—in the case of zero-shot classification—asked) to predict. We acknowledge that this is an important limitation but at this stage of our research, this evaluation is regarded more like a first soundness check before proceeding with a more thorough evaluation. Nevertheless, thanks to the stratification method that we followed, the evaluation set still contained sufficient labels with positive examples which helped us understand the overall strengths and weaknesses of the different models under evaluation.

5 Results

5.1 Quantitative evaluation

The results of the quantitative evaluation, in terms of F1 document average, weighted subject average (weighted macro average), and micro average are shown in Table 1 and Figure 1. Considering the F1 document average and F1 subject average scores, Annif’s Neural Network ensemble classifier gave us the best results with 0.5884 and 0.5568 respectively. However, the fine-tuned BERT model achieved the highest micro average F1 score with 0.5916, and beat all other non-ensemble methods across all metrics, including Omikujji/Parabel, the best-performing non-ensemble classifier. This might be explained by the fact that during training the fine-tuned BERT model was optimised for better micro-averaged F1 scores.

The quantitative evaluation scores achieved by our zero-shot LLM model, mDeBERTA v3, were generally poor compared with other methods, with a document average F1 of just 0.1099, narrowly ahead of MLLM but behind other classification methods.

Figure 1: F1 scores for 7 classifiers under test

	F1 (doc avg)	F1 (weighted subj avg)	F1 (micro avg)
TF-IDF	0.2373	0.3640	0.2533
MLLM	0.0849	0.1762	0.1284
fastText	0.3606	0.4331	0.3768
Omikuji/Parabel	0.3771	0.4776	0.3975
NN Ensemble	0.5884	0.5568	0.5256
mDeBERTa	0.1099	0.2055	0.1126
BERT-EHRI	0.5556	0.4844	0.5916

Table 1: F1 document average, weighted subject average, and micro average scores for different models. The results in bold represent the best metrics per type of measure. The two horizontal grey lines delimit the three categories of tools under evaluation, namely the first group is composed of the Annif originally supported multi-label classification backends, the second group comprises the zero-shot LLM and the final group contains the fine-tuned LLM.

5.2 Qualitative Evaluation

Given the complexities of evaluating subject indexing tools as described in Section 4.4, we decided to complement our quantitative evaluation with a small-scale human evaluation. Complementing quantitative with qualitative evaluation is typical in similar studies (Chou and Chu, 2022; Suominen et al., 2022). Due to resource restrictions, we decided to limit the human evaluation to the best-performing Annif model and the two LLM-based models, since the focus of this study is on comparing LLMs against older methods that are less computationally intensive. The human evaluation was conducted by three of the authors of this paper who specialise in Digital Humanities and are familiar with EHRI’s vocabularies and metadata under their capacity as research software developers or digital archivists working for EHRI.

We performed a subjective qualitative evaluation of four distinct label sets:

- the original labels assigned by EHRI staff or co-referenced with data from EHRI partner institutions,
- the NN Ensemble classifier, which performed best out of the Annif backends in our quantitative evaluation,
- the BERT-based model fine-tuned as described above,
- the mDeBERTa-based zero-shot model.

The evaluation was performed using a programmatically-generated spreadsheet (see Figure 2 for illustrative purposes) that displayed input texts alongside columns containing labels assigned by each tool, anonymised as Tool 1, 2, 3 and 4 and randomly ordered.²³ Beside each individual label were checkboxes to denote whether it was a favourable or unfavourable label in the opinion of the adjudicator, with the default state (both boxes unchecked) indicating that there was insufficient evidence on the basis of the input text to make a judgement. The undecided (neutral) state was particularly relevant in cases where the labels were assigned on the basis of external knowledge, e.g. direct knowledge of the underlying archival sources, rather than being an alternative view of descriptive text, a very common case in our dataset and an inherent limitation of deriving keywords from metadata that may be incomplete or otherwise brief. When performing the evaluation, the three judges were asked to rate the subject terms based on the following question: “If you used the subject term under consideration as an access point (either as a search term or by clicking on it to browse linked archival units), would you expect to see the archival unit that contains the corresponding input text in the list of results returned by the EHRI Portal?”. For texts in languages that were not amongst the ones spoken by the evaluators, Google Translate was used.

²³ A Python script for generating this spreadsheet on Google Sheets can be found in the Annif repository containing our custom backends, named `annif-to-spreadsheet.py`.

Texts		Tool 1			Tool 2			Tool 3			Tool 4		
#	ID	Text	Labels	Good	Poor	Labels	Good	Poor	Labels	Good	Poor	Translate?	Translation
1	us-005678-ins12730	Oral History Interview with Edith Klein and Lilian Glass 1 - Videocasette (Betacam SP) Safe Haven Inc. The interview with Edith Klein and Lilian Glass was conducted on August 6, 1994, by Safe Haven, Inc. as part of a project documenting the testimonies of refugees from the Fort Ontario Emergency Refugee Shelter in Oswego, N.Y., The United States Holocaust Memorial Museum received a copy of the interview in August 1996.	Displaced persons Memorial sites Refugees Holocaust memory Jewish Displaced persons	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Jewish Refugees	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Jewish Refugees	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	us-005678-ins20221	Colonel Alexander Zabin, MD collection oversize box folders oversize folder 1 12	Military service Military operations Medical personnel Newsreels Military leaders	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Photographs Newspapers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Photographs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	ca-002302-hermann_us mmlung_of_4116_2	PT 4116 / 2 Přednášek přednášek - prof. Dr. H. Strauss I. Summary of the lectures of Prof. Dr. Hermann Strauss	Academic faculty Pastors Official documentation Jewish intellectuals Intellectuals	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Culture Healthcare	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Culture	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	be-002157-ad_00390	vwv Het Ondergedoken Kind, Brussels Collection L'Enfant caché asbl, Bruxelles The Hidden Child association, Brussels 15 meters, 161 numbers, 88 boxes The archive of vzw Het Ondergedoken Kind - L'Enfant caché asbl consists of (1) institutional files and series on the creation of the association, on the administrative committee, on the yearly	Wartime period Hidden children Jewish organizations Pre-war period Archives	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Children Socialism Judaism	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hidden children Commemorati on Jewish organizations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 2: Spreadsheet for performing a subjective qualitative evaluation of three MTC tools along with the anonymised gold standard labels.

Scoring the subjective evaluation was done by summing each of the good, neutral, and poor labels assigned by three separate judges to the labels produced by each of the four methods, with one method including the ground truth data. The inclusion of the ground truth data, the original labels assigned either by EHRI specialists or co-references from the index terms assigned by EHRI partner institutions, was intended to serve as a control.

The result of the manual evaluation is shown in Table 2 and demonstrates the subjectivity of the multi-label classification task. Unsurprisingly, in terms of percentages, the gold standard label set achieved the highest scores of labels deemed favourable and the smallest scores of unfavourable labels. The tool with the second-highest favourable scores as percentages was the fine-tuned multilingual BERT model (favourable judgements ranging from 45 to 53 per cent), with the NN Ensemble classifier performing similarly (favourable judgements ranging from 43 to 48 per cent).

A key outcome, however, is that the predictions made by the zero-shot mDeBERTa classifier were judged qualitatively to be substantially better than suggested by our quantitative evaluation. In terms of absolute numbers, human judges awarded it the highest number of favourable labels. In a case where the institutional priority would be to have an exhaustive index, this tool could lead to better recall, potentially increasing the number of helpful index terms assigned to our descriptions. However, it was also the model that returned the largest number of suggestions in general, out of which many were deemed unfavourable (though mostly by one reviewer). That said, most importantly, “neutral” scores ranged between 37-55 per cent across all ASI tools, which means that for many of the labels included in these label sets, we simply did not have enough text to determine whether they were good or poor suggestions.

6 Discussion

The EHRI Portal includes metadata describing both physical and digital materials that may or may not have been made publicly accessible online. In our experiment we used all metadata as described in Section 3 without distinguishing between the medium of the archival material or our ability to access it ourselves. This was a fundamental limitation of the qualitative evaluation. Practising archivists will often choose index terms on the basis of their specialised knowledge of the source material to which they

J	GS Labels			NN Ensemble			BERT-FT			mDeBERTa		
	F	N	U	F	N	U	F	N	U	F	N	U
J1	221	69	4	267	252	37	233	179	28	340	312	183
	75%	23%	1%	48%	45%	7%	53%	41%	6%	41%	37%	22%
J2	210	83	1	239	288	29	197	213	30	342	444	49
	71%	28%	0%	43%	52%	5%	45%	48%	7%	41%	53%	6%
J3	191	99	4	238	303	15	217	209	14	344	460	31
	65%	34%	1%	43%	55%	3%	49%	48%	3%	41%	55%	4%

Table 2: Results of the manual evaluation showing total favourable (F), neutral (N), and unfavourable (U) assessments of gold standard labels and ASI tools. For each judge (J), the first row shows absolute numbers and the second row shows percentages rounded to the nearest integer. Due to rounding, percentages may not sum to exactly 100%.

have direct access, with textual description serving a disjoint purpose. This might have influenced the results of both the qualitative and quantitative evaluation.

When it comes to the qualitative evaluation, without access to the source material the input text was frequently not sufficient to help us conclude on whether the subject terms predicted by the different tools under evaluation were appropriate or not. This might explain why the neutral assessment is in many cases the prevailing one for many suggested labels. Considering quantitative evaluation, the fact that the texts in our dataset often contained little clue as to what the correct classification may be could also account for the relatively low performance of all the classifiers we have tested. An offsetting factor is the prevalence of broader terms in the dataset that is the result of co-referencing partner institutions' in-house vocabularies with EHRI Terms; if labels assigned in the gold standard dataset had been generally narrower (more specific) then performance in the quantitative evaluation would likely have been lower still.

For example, in many cases the concatenated text used in the first column of the evaluation spreadsheet would only include information similar to the following input text:

“Oral history interview with Olga Horak
1 sound cassette,
Australian Institute for Holocaust and Genocide Studies
The Australian Institute of Holocaust Studies conducted the interview with Olga Horak on March 12, 1990 for the Twelfth Hour Project. The United States Holocaust Memorial Museum received a copy of the interview in April 2006 from the State Library of New South Wales where the collection is housed.”²⁴

Among the subject terms predicted for the description above by one of our tools under evaluation were the following: Forced labour, Death marches, Escape, Hiding places, Camp inmates. Without having listened to the oral interview this text is concerned with, we lack adequate context to rate the terms listed above based on this text alone. However, finding the metadata associated with this Oral History on the website of the source institution²⁵, the United States Holocaust Memorial Museum (USHMM), one may find a more insightful description that is not part of the metadata ingested by the EHRI Portal for this description and see that some of the predicted

²⁴ The text is derived from the following description: <https://portal.ehri-project.eu/units/us-005578-irn523956-irn43072>

²⁵ <https://collections.ushmm.org/search/catalog/irn43072>

labels (Death Marches, Hiding Places, Camp Inmates) were actually included in the original set of terms as indexed by the USHMM cataloguers themselves; while additionally the term “Escape” could also have been considered favourably.

Indeed, there were many examples where — despite the lack of sufficient salient information in the input text — some tools were suggesting terms that would have been considered favourably by human cataloguers if they had access to more context or the source material. Inspecting the reasons why this may be happening was outside the scope of this experiment. However, there are at least three potential explanations. First, this was a typical occurrence when it came to texts deriving from USHMM metadata concerning oral histories where the descriptions that EHRI had ingested contained almost no salient information about the contents of the interview (another example is the description with ID `us-005578-irn558093`²⁶). After inspecting some of these examples, we realised that the interviewees mentioned in their titles are people who have given multiple interviews throughout their lives. This means that it is possible that the metadata of other interviews they have given were present in the dataset, despite our deduplication process. Consequently, the models may have correlated the topics that certain persons tend to talk about in their interviews across multiple distinct archival descriptions. Another reason could be that some of the models might have learned to associate certain series of interviews with certain topics. For example, the description associated with the item with ID `us-005578-irn508794`²⁷ includes text that reads “(...) The United States Holocaust Memorial Museum, Oral History Branch, in cooperation with Watchtower Bible and Tract Society, Inc. (...)”. In the USHMM catalogue, items that include this text in their metadata tend to carry the label “Jehovah’s Witnesses” that was correctly predicted by at least one of our tools. A third reason which is relevant specifically to the predictions made by the zero-shot tool is that the base model was trained on a CommonCrawl dataset which might have already “seen” some of the descriptions in our dataset. It is also entirely possible that a combination of these explanations might be valid at the same time.

In the subjective qualitative evaluation, all three judges gave the zero-shot LLM model high scores for the number of labels considered favourable. This is justified by the fact that its predictions were usually much more specific and informative compared to the predictions returned by the other tools, which tended to be broader and more generic. A couple of examples that attest to this assessment are the label sets predicted for text with ID `us-005578-irn515693`²⁸, where mDeBERTa returned “Identification papers”, “Displaced persons”, and “Allied Forces” among the top five predictions, which can all be deemed favourable and extend the golden standard “Children” and “Photographs” labels. Another such example is the description with ID `us-005578-irn36408`²⁹, which included only one label in the gold standard dataset, “Photographs”, while mDeBERTa additionally returned “Prewar period”, “Jewish population”, and “Jewish culture” among the top 5 predictions. However, given the fact that this model was not trained using EHRI’s dataset but was instead used out-of-the-box, the creativity of this model was not surprising to the authors because as previously explained, the majority of the true subject terms in our dataset consisted of mainly broader terms and genre terms which may be perceived as having low information value.

²⁶ <https://portal.ehri-project.eu/units/us-005578-irn533934-irn558093>

²⁷ <https://portal.ehri-project.eu/units/us-005578-irn39098-irn508794>

²⁸ <https://portal.ehri-project.eu/units/us-005578-irn515693>

²⁹ <https://portal.ehri-project.eu/units/us-005578-irn36408>

However, there were also a number of cases where a lack of context about the overall task — labelling Holocaust-related archival descriptions — resulted in incorrect or inappropriate labels predicted by the zero-shot model as a result of text describing the history of the collection or chain of custody. As an example, the text with ID `us-005578-irn508794` reading “[USHMM], Oral History Branch, in cooperation with Watchtower Bible and Tract Society, Inc. produced the interview with...” was labelled with the term “Collaborators”, a word which has obvious semantic connection with the metadata due to the existence of the phrase “in cooperation” within the text but could be inappropriate to the content of the material (as it is for this case). A more benign example of potential mislabelling is the suggestion of terms such as “Memorial sites” or “Holocaust Memory” being suggested from text containing United States Holocaust Memorial Museum as the donor institution. A common thread to these cases is that the text used as input for the classifier is imprecise and not properly descriptive of the contents of the material (as opposed to its provenance), but as future work we will investigate whether more tailored prompting can improve the precision of the zero-shot classifier here. Another example where the zero-shot model predicted inappropriate terms was the case of the text with ID `nl-002896-nl_asdniod_imagecollection-212545`³⁰, which concerned a family that has been recognised as righteous amongst the nations³¹ and yet, amongst the predicted terms, one will find the inappropriate term “Jewish collaborators”.

Another remark that needs to be made with regard to (mainly) the zero-shot model but also to a lesser extent the fine-tuned BERT model is that our decision to conduct this experiment without taking the hierarchical nature of our vocabulary into account (but rather assuming a flat hierarchy) led these two models to sometimes predict hierarchically relevant and overlapping terms. For example, in ID `us-005578-irn49797`³², amongst the top five labels predicted by the zero-shot model are “Photographs”, “Photographers” and “Photography” as separate predictions. In `us-005578-irn1002858`³³, amongst the top five labels one will find “Political activities”, “Politics”, “Political organisations” and “Political movements”. Future work should account for the different levels in our vocabulary’s hierarchy and seek to avoid such redundant classification.

Overall, despite these limitations, we found that in many cases the tools were not only predicting the true labels found in the gold standard dataset (either partially or completely) but they were suggesting additional labels that were highly relevant and informative. Although a fully automated solution is not yet feasible for our use-case, therefore, the tools discussed here all show considerable promise as part of a semi-automated indexing system, with a subject matter expert able to verify labels. Such a system, complementing EHRI’s existing co-referencing tools such as the EMT described in Section 2, could enrich our dataset with sufficient labels to, in turn, train better classification models.

7 Future Work

LLMs are a fast-developing technology and, as noted above, the models covered in this paper for fine-tuned and zero-shot MTC respectively are far from the state-of-the-art.

³⁰ https://portal.ehri-project.eu/units/nl-002896-nl_asdniod_imagecollection-212545

³¹ https://www.yadvashem.org/odot_pdf/Microsoft%20Word%20-%206069.pdf

³² <https://portal.ehri-project.eu/units/us-005578-irn49797>

³³ <https://portal.ehri-project.eu/units/us-005578-irn1002858>

As new “open source” models become available, with well-documented training data sets and inference characteristics that can be reasonably well understood, we look forward to seeing how they compare in terms of the qualitative evaluation discussed in Section 5.2. We are also keen to understand how different prompting techniques can better align the labels produced by LLMs for given texts with cataloguers’ expectations, by incorporating more domain-specific information into the LLM’s context window. For archival descriptions which are structured hierarchically, more “archival context” is typically available from parent and/or sibling descriptions, as well as information about the holding institution, and this can be incorporated to give a classifier more data with which to work.

We are also keen to expand this experiment to incorporate more of the expertise of professional archivists in developing our dataset and understanding the characteristics of (semi-)automated subject indexing tools, not limited solely to LLMs. Integrating a semi-automated labelling pipeline into EHRI’s cataloguing environment will allow us to gain more experience in the practical application of multilingual ASI with the EHRI Terms vocabulary, expanding our overall dataset and improving its overall balance with regard to less represented languages and narrower, more specific index terms.

8 Conclusion

This paper has presented an experiment where two different approaches to the use of LLMs for text classification, zero-shot and fine-tuning, were compared with alternative non-LLM-based MTC tools, using Annif as a framework, metadata from the EHRI Portal as a dataset, and the EHRI Terms vocabulary as a label set.

As described in Section 3, our dataset, drawn from metadata in the EHRI Portal, is not ideally suited for training text classifiers, with a degree of class imbalance favouring broader, more generic terms, and a lack of examples featuring narrower, more specific terms. Because of this, we have reduced the size of the label set used in this experiment from 913 to 554 labels to ensure sufficient representation. We have also had to carefully stratify the dataset in order to produce training and test sets, along with a small 167-example evaluation set, that each contains sufficient numbers of labelled examples and is balanced in terms of languages used. A small evaluation set was necessary to make both manual (human) and computationally intensive processing more feasible.

Using Annif as a framework, we created backends for our zero-shot and fine-tuned models so that they could be run in the same manner as Annif’s own classification backends, and evaluated using the same metrics. Due to class imbalance, different F1 metrics produce slightly different results across the various classifiers, although the difference is not large. With fine-tuning, our BERT-based model performed in a manner very comparable to the best-performing Annif backends, exceeding the performance on our data of the best non-ensemble classifier (Omikuji/Parabel) and closely matching the NN Ensemble. Given that this is a fairly lightweight 109M parameter LLM and trainable on relatively modest resources, this is a promising result. According to the quantitative evaluation, the zero-shot mDeBERTa classifier was one of the worst-performing ASI backends.

Along with this quantitative evaluation, we also undertook a blind qualitative evaluation on our small evaluation set, with output from the best-performing out-of-the-box Annif backend (NN Ensemble), our two LLM-based classifiers, and the original labelled data as a control. The results of the qualitative evaluation suggest that the potential of the zero-shot model is not fully captured by the quantitative

evaluation. Quite consistently it output labels that were considered good by all three human judges, along with a relatively large quantity of labels considered poor by one judge. As an assistive tool, therefore, it could be considered more useful than the trained models, which — consistent with the label distribution in the dataset they were trained on — tend towards broader, less specific terms. Potentially offsetting this, however, are the computational requirements of the zero-shot model, which was several orders of magnitude slower than alternative methods on the same hardware.

As highlighted in Section 6, based on our experiments the ASI tools described in this paper can realistically be considered only as part of a semi-ASI workflow. The fine-tuned multilingual BERT model can return good label sets, but the NN Ensemble model shows very similar performance while being considerably less resource-intensive to run. Given its tendency to result in more specific terms, zero-shot classification using LLMs could be potentially useful as part of data augmentation efforts to improve the representation of more specific labels, resulting in a richer and more balanced dataset that could, in turn, contribute to training more accurate domain-specific models.

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Can Stones be Made (Artificially) Intelligent? A Pilot Study for AI-based Repeated Pattern Detection of Architectural Decoration in Roman Asia Minor

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The disciplines of History, Archaeology and Computer Vision have each stimulated the development and use of diverse digital tools within their own domain. But what if we dare to ask a research question positioned right at the crossroad of these fields, necessitating the computer-based analysis of people’s past via both inscriptions and monuments? In this paper we return to the dawn of our era (1st century BCE - 3rd CE) in the historical region of Asia Minor (roughly modern-day Turkey) to put this to the test. Our starting point? The many legacy photographs of so called *Bauornamented* buildings. With the help of pattern recognition techniques, we attempted to design a (proof-of-concept) AI-algorithm capable of detecting and segmenting the various complex designs in pictures of such embellished building blocks. In doing so, we focused on mitigating the bottlenecks of the traditional time-consuming *manual* comparative approaches, allowing to unlock this data’s true historical potential¹.

Keywords: Computer Vision, Repeated Pattern Detection, AI, Architectural Decoration, Roman Asia Minor

1 Introduction

Our starting point is a simple, yet significant observation about the Roman empire: archaeologists and ancient historians encounter a remarkable degree of similarity in the material culture and architecture of its many studied provincial cities (Van Oyen and Pitts, 2017). Focusing on buildings, we observe that, despite differences of detail,

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constructions look remarkably similar, also in Asia Minor. What processes explain this similarity in an empire where the central government was bureaucratically minimalist (Garnsey and Saller, 2015, 1987) and local communities enjoyed a lot of autonomy (Zuiderhoek, 2009)? Furthermore, the socio-cultural effects of imperial politics and policies were never top-down, nor straightforward, and could take many forms (Mattingly, 2011). A pivotal dataset, omnipresent but so far overlooked in any attempt to unravel this commonality², forms our dataset of choice: that of architectural decoration. Also known as *Bauornamentik*, the canon of geometrical and vegetal designs found on a building has no structural function, yet is present on nearly every monument with some grandeur in the empire. And, it is prone to fashions, changing over time and space, yet displaying the above-mentioned similarities (Ginouvès and Martin, 1985; Vandeput, 1997). Especially in Asia Minor, many monuments are also linked to surviving inscriptions. These provide information on who commissions or pays for these buildings; who sets trends or copies them; who plays which role in the game of social status. These texts, in other words, connect the buildings and their decorations to the people behind the stones: the elite protagonists who built their lives in these ornamented cities. In brief, we investigate if the similarities identified in the ornaments match with other (un)known forms of connectivity (institutional, cultural, social, religious) between the same cities and their elites, known from written sources³.

The opportunity for computer vision techniques here pertains to the quantity and granularity of detail that needs to be captured. At this stage, our data compendium contains just under 2,000 images of decorated blocks from ca. 300 monuments on 40 archaeological sites. Since every building block typically exhibits multiple different designs, mapping and comparing these manually is practically impossible, both in terms of time consumption and because the sheer number of research components exceeds the human capacity of analysis and comparison. Hence, AI-based automatic pattern recognition (step 1) and comparison (step 2) techniques are indispensable, placing architectural decoration studies on an exciting and innovative new footing. Indeed our proposed workflow consists of a two-step approach: 1) isolate the separate repetitive decorative patterns as identified in literature from the legacy photographs,⁴ yielding a digital library of pattern snippets per different canonized design class, 2) sub-cluster the latter per ornament class to unveil, measure and quantify the mentioned (dis)similarity via an *embedding learning* or *metric learning* approach. This consists of

² Different scholars have attempted to answer this question, e.g. based on the concepts of globalization (Pitts and Versluys, 2015) or on social and cultural revolutions (Wallace-Hadrill, 2008). To date, however, the main merit of the field of architectural decoration studies (typically part of the broader domain of *Bauforschung*) lies in its contribution to establishing chronological frameworks for archaeological buildings, sites and regions e.g. Gliwitsky (2010). As a result, this archaeological dataset's potential to answer broader socio-historical questions has so far remained underexplored.

³ Roman Imperial Asia Minor provides an ideal and relevant laboratory to perform such stylistic, architectural, urban and historical exercise, considering the comparatively high degree of urbanization and monumentalization of the vast peninsula (Willet, 2020), the number of extensively excavated ancient cities in the region (Gates, 2011), their well-studied architectural (Yegül and Favro, 2019) (esp. ch.10) and exceptionally rich epigraphical record. Moreover, there is the simultaneous academic recognition of both ancient historians and archaeologists of the significance of these topics (Koller et al., 2021; Lohner-Urban and Quatember, 2020; Marek, 2016)

⁴ For a comprehensive overview of the nomenclature of the main decorative designs, see eg. Vandeput (1997) in English, Cavalier (2005) in French, Rumscheid (1994) in German. This Ph.D. project also works on the disambiguation of the existing nomenclature as apt terminology in English is for some patterns still problematic. This will be presented in the database which will be made publicly available.

converting a photo/snippet into a descriptor vector (*the embedding*) that describes the image content. Distances between those vectors are then trained to correspond to the visual (dis)similarity which can vary per region and/or time window. This allows to compare a set of snippets of the same family/class of patterns (e.g. Ionic kyma decoration) and divide them into subsets of (more) homogeneous groups (e.g. egg-and-dart, egg-and-tongue, intermediate forms) according to the needed granularity (De Feyter et al., 2023).

In this paper, we focus on the first step of our workflow, the application of artificial intelligence (AI) for the automated recognition of the architectural decoration canon in Roman Asia Minor. Our core task is thus automating the identification and classification of repetitive decorative patterns found in Roman architecture, thereby enabling a more efficient exploration and deeper understanding of cultural transmission and stylistic evolution across the Roman Empire.

2 Proposed AI pipeline

In short, we have developed an AI-driven system that can recognize, segment, and classify these architectural patterns from photographic data. In this paper, we explore state-of-the-art computer vision techniques that would render this task totally automatic, without any of the manual labor traditionally involved in analyzing these motifs. Indeed, the very fact that these patterns consist of a unit that consistently repeats multiple times on the image makes a clue to detect and isolate each pattern without supervision.

A limited but representative dataset of 50 images of already published Roman blocks from across Asia Minor was compiled, serving as the basis for training, testing and refining our algorithm. Since this dataset purely served the purpose of establishing our novel pipeline, we did not impose any further chronological or spatial selection of the Roman building blocks depicted. Preprocessing techniques were applied to improve the accuracy. First, Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) was used (Reza, 2004), where histogram equalization is applied to small parts of the image ('tiles') and combined via bilinear interpolation. This improved the contrast between shadow and sunlight without disrupting major contrasts. In addition, gamma correction further refined the contrast. For the actual repeating pattern detection, we explored and compared two types of algorithms, leading to the new fusion of them presented in this paper: semantic pattern discovery to segment each pattern from the image and convolutional neural networks (CNNs) activation analysis for detecting the recurring pattern units. In the text below, we will first tackle each separately, to then demonstrate what our novel synthesis provides as assets and improvements.

2.1 Repeating pattern segmentation

After having scanned the existing repeating pattern detection algorithms to identify the most apt one for the task here at hand (Das and Mandal, 2018; Mahmudnejad et al., 2023; Qu et al., 2020; Sakai et al., 2024), a first algorithm that showed potential was "Unsupervised Semantic Discovery through visual patterns detection" by Pelosin et al. (2021). It is the most optimized state-of-the-art open source algorithm that can detect multiple patterns by deploying the Canny algorithm, DAISY and SLIC techniques. The algorithm works independently of a fixed geometric scheme and proved more performant than GRASP (Liu and Liu, 2013). This makes it possible to detect a wider

Figure 1: Repeating pattern segmentation results by using Pelosin et al. (2021) on a typical image from our dataset, here from the ancient city of Attaleia (figure after Kaymak (2009) figs.142-147 & 270, adaptations by the authors).

range of diverse patterns, even if they vary in scale, orientation or (partial) visibility.

As can be seen on Figure 1, after having finetuned the hyperparameters through a limited labeled ground truth set (13 images), the algorithm was able to successfully segment few patterns, but some inconsistencies remained, e.g. two separate patterns were segmented as one (the pink coloured segment on Figure 1, 4th coloured band from below combines a bead-and-reel string with Ionic kyma decoration into a single segment), some motifs remained undetected (see Figure 1, the wide floral scroll band located in the middle of the image, probably due to the lack of strict identical repetitions in the displayed part), while other plain sections of the building block were identified as repeated motif (see Figure 1, the orange coloured segment). Interestingly, the inscription on the building block was also detected (in violet). To be clear, the goal of our approach here is not to be able to individually detect every of the composing units/letters for an inscription (as will be presented in the second step in subsection 2.2 for all other patterns). This would be redundant work as all inscriptions on legacy blocks have already been identified, translated and made accessible via corpora and collections such as *Inscriptionen griechischer Städte aus Kleinasien* (IGSK), *Monumenta Asiae Minoris Antiqua* (MAMA), *Tituli Asiae Minoris* (TAM), Regional Epigraphic Catalogues of Asia Minor (RECAM) and the PHI Greek Inscriptions Database (<https://inscriptions.packhum.org/>). What we do want to achieve is (as happened here) that when present on a block, the inscription is segmented so that archaeologists/historians are notified of its presence (even when badly visible/weathered) and can incorporate the translation and content into their analysis.

Figure 2: Results of Lettry et al. (2017). Left: on an image of a building block with multiple repeating patterns (figure by the authors). Right: on a wavyly cut-out part (figure after Başaran and Ergürer (2018) fig.15a, adaptations by the authors).

2.2 Repeating unit detection

The second algorithm "Repeated Pattern Detection Using CNN Activations" (Lettry et al., 2017) was initially not considered because it is unable to detect multiple patterns at the same time. Due to the need to outline the various units for classification, however, this was also tested. The hypothesis we made was that the most prominent pattern would be detected. After that, the other patterns would be covered. As shows Figure 2, however, this algorithm was not consistent in outlining the repetitive unit. It pinned the horizontal distribution to the second pattern starting from below. However, the vertical distribution did not consistently grip on the same part of the unit of that pattern. Therefore, we sought to give each pattern separately as input to frame the individual units.

2.3 Combined approach

Since both algorithms individually did not meet our goals, we propose to combine them into a novel pipeline, providing a more robust system capable of handling most complexities of ancient decorative motifs. We deployed the technique of Pelosin et al. (2021) to segment and extract the patterns present in the image first. Next, for each of the cut-out pattern segments, we used the method of Lettry et al. (2017) to frame the individual repetitive units. This combined approach is illustrated in Figure 3. The first algorithm was performed with one of the best hyperparameter combinations, derived from the CSV file, where each separate strip of detected patterns was stored as separate segments. We then used these segments as input in the second algorithm to frame the individual figures.

It was important that the image used did not contain other repetitive elements that would derive the algorithm from the main pattern. This problem arose when the segmentation was not straightforward and wavy or jagged lines were present at the edges, in which the algorithm found regularity (see Figure 2, right). Therefore, we adjusted segmentation to take the maximum x and y coordinates of the segment and cut out a rectangle. Lastly, the algorithm sometimes drew unneeded horizontal lines because it recognized multiple patterns on a vertical plane while there was only one. Therefore, we adjusted the code so that it only drew vertical lines and a frame around the full horizontal pattern (see Figure 3, the right green arrow).

Figure 3: Our combined pipeline demonstrated on a block from the ancient city of Sagalassos. Each of the detected pattern segments is cut-out from the image and individually analysed to find the repeating unit, before composing again together (figure after Poblome et al. (2022) p.39, adaptations by the authors).

3 Results

Put all together, our newly fused algorithm consists of the following pipeline: after image cleaning, we extract all pattern segments from an image by applying a modified version of the initial semantic discovery algorithm with optimized parameters. Subsequently, the bounding boxes for each segment are determined via the CNN filter activations. Using the stored coordinates, the segment is then provided with a frame in a random color in the right place in the image. Within this frame, the vertical separations between the figures are drawn based on the bounding boxes. If no coordinates are stored, they are determined via template matching. The bounding boxes are also stored for future use. This process is repeated for each segment, after which the entire figure becomes visible. We tested this process on both the labeled training data and new test images from the dataset.⁵ As our research is rooted in and feeds a visual-comparative inquiry, not a statistical one, we opt to present an evaluation of our detection based on the comparison of the frequency of the unit separations with the repetition frequency of the pattern (see Figures 4 to 7).

First, our algorithm was successfully able to find and segment all horizontal patterns, except for one. In Figure 4, 11 horizontal pattern segments are visible but the so-called anthemion frieze (3rd from above) remained undetected. Interestingly, the algorithm did find the same anthemion pattern in Figure 7 where it also occurred (top moulding, yellow bounding boxes). Looking at the nature of the motif in Figure 4, the lack of more than one full repeating unit, the damage and the fact that this pattern class typically displays in-class variation (both mentioned segments in Figures 4 and 7 are classified in literature as anthemion friezes but the way in which the individual flowers are sculpted and combined into a repeating sequence can vary greatly) might explain this difference in detection. In one case, the algorithm also identified two discrete patterns as one horizontal segment, *in casu* a bead-and-reel string surmounted by Ionic kyma decoration (egg-and-tongue) (see pink bounding boxes in Figure 6). In Figure 4, however, the same positioning of these two designs was also present (even twice), but here both were correctly split up into two separate horizontal segments (see light green and brown bounding boxes for the first and second design counted from the top as well as the red and olive coloured units for the third and fourth motif starting from the bottom of the image).

Second, turning to the detection of the individual repeating units, three observations are to be noted. In few occasions, we encountered the issue of oversegmentation (see

⁵ Our code is openly available on <https://github.com/duster3000/pattern-detection-roman-architecture>.

green and blue bounding boxes in Figure 6) and undersegmentation of the repetitive unit (see the bead-and-reel string at the bottom of Figure 4 with the purple bounding boxes). In addition, we observed that the algorithm did not always consistently follow one and the same fixed start and endpoint for all attestations of patterns of one class. For example, the delineation of an individual bounding box for the egg-and-dart motif at times cuts right through the onset of an egg design (see Figure 5, green bounding boxes) while in Figure 6 for example, the individual repetitive unit detected by the algorithm for the same motif starts at a different point in the sequence (the pink bounding boxes fully enclose the egg). Lastly, the delineation of the bounding boxes once intersected with important semantic information in a motif, for example when cutting right through the core and central vein of an acanthus leaf (see Figure 5, yellow bounding boxes). These last two remarks touch upon the core of the second step of our workflow and analysis described above, the sub-clustering per ornament class to unveil, measure and quantify the mentioned (dis)similarity via an *embedding learning* or *metric learning approach*. Comparing two non-identically delineated repeating units of the same pattern would cause a false bias. The same holds for comparing two half acanthus leaves instead of the full leaf.

Figure 4: Resulting pattern detections on a decorated block from the ancient city of Myra (figure by the authors).

4 Discussion

With this novel synthesis method, we demonstrated that the system effectively detects and segments common horizontal patterns, such as the bead-and-reel or egg-and-dart motifs. Remarkably, this process runs totally autonomously, without any human intervention. However, we also encountered some limitations in terms of the consistency and definition of the unique repeating unit. Further research could therefore refine the model to accommodate more complex patterns (eg. sloping or oblique ones) and handle incomplete or degraded architectural elements.

At the same time, we realized that the unique start and end point of such a repeating unit is actually not defined. As there are multiple possibilities per pattern, setting the unit of analysis is not unambiguous but the golden rule is simply: consistency. Based on the lessons we have learned from developing this pipeline as well as looking into our future historical analysis' component, we actually doubt it is necessary to each

Figure 5: Resulting pattern detections on a decorated block from the ancient city of Aizanoi (figure after Jes et al. (2010) fig.66, adaptations by the authors).

time find the repeating unit. Rather, it is the full sequence and its interconnections that hold most semantic information. Therefore, in the future we will also invest in and orient us more towards *semantic segmentation* rather than *object detection* (eg. YOLO) to automatically retrieve all decorative patterns.

5 Conclusion

Based on its rich attestation in Roman Imperial Asia Minor, we are assembling and studying the region's *Bauornamentik* corpus from a multidisciplinary and methodologically innovative perspective. In doing so, we aim to for the first time connect this hitherto overlooked archaeological dataset to the broader socio-historical study of Roman urban culture to generate important new insights into the development of provincial Roman urbanism. However, as manually comparing all legacy photographs is unfeasible, we presented in this paper a proof-of-concept AI-algorithm that could serve as a first methodological step to detect the different repeating motifs. To do so, we fused two existing algorithms into a novel pipeline, capable of detecting the repetitive unit of each horizontal pattern segment.

As we have presented here, the basis for classification has been reached, but there is still room for improvement in the following areas: ensuring a consistent start and end point for all motifs, addressing both over-segmentation and under-segmentation as well as combining patterns or splitting patterns appropriately. In the coming time, we thus aim to extend our approach to handle non-horizontal patterns, expand the labeled dataset, and foremost, to improve the detection of certain patterns that are currently not always being recognized (e.g. the scroll pattern in Figure 1). Based on the insights from this research, we will likewise shift our focus more towards *semantic segmentation* instead of object detection to automatically capture all decorative patterns.

As demonstrated in this paper, the integration of AI with traditional historical methods opens up new possibilities for large-scale cultural analysis and cross-site comparisons, providing novel insights into the socio-historical diffusion of people, artistic styles and the networks of Roman artisans. Our next challenge encompasses the

Figure 6: Resulting pattern detections on a decorated block from the ancient city of Attaleia (figure by the authors).

Figure 7: Resulting pattern detections on a decorated block from the ancient city of Letoon (figure by the authors).

development of step 2, a technique to measure fine-grained similarities and differences between the patterns detected, in order to be able to pinpoint and compare subtle stylistic details across archaeological sites. Only by using high-performance embeddings (e.g. SimCLR(Chen et al., 2020)) we will unveil subtle differences between patterns within a class, offering the crucial yet previously invisible clues for our novel historical analysis. In this way, we argue, ornamental patterns of (dis)similarity within and between ancient cities can be discerned on an unprecedented scale, as well as the structure of the communities and social networks responsible for these buildings, whose actions might explain the sameness in the decoration.

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Breaking Down Barriers: The Transition of ODIS from a Relational to a Triple Store Database

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In this paper, we discuss the ongoing transformation of the ODIS database – a key digital infrastructure for historical research on civil society in Flanders and Brussels – from a relational to a triple store architecture. Originally developed in the early 2000s and overhauled between 2009 and 2013, ODIS is now undergoing a comprehensive renewal to align with linked data principles and the FAIR data guidelines. The transition involves the implementation of a Virtuoso triple store, a redesigned RDF-based data model, and a new user interface. Central to this effort is the development of SOLIS (Smart Ontology Layer for Interoperable Systems), a tool that bridges domain expertise and technical implementation by generating SHACL-based APIs from spreadsheet-defined ontologies. The paper discusses the rationale behind adopting a triple store, the challenges of semantic modelling, multilingual data handling, and the integration of external authorities such as OpenStreetMap. It also highlights the benefits of semantic richness, interoperability, and enhanced data visualisation through network and geographical tools. This case study offers insights and best practices for digital humanities projects seeking to modernise their data infrastructures and foster interdisciplinary, data-driven research.

Keywords: civil society, contextual disclosure of heritage, digital humanities, heritage and research database, linked open data

1 Introduction

As research trends in the humanities change over the years, tools evolve to follow and sometimes even shape these new approaches. ODIS, a contextual relational database on the history of civil society that is used by a growing number of research and heritage organisations in Flanders and Brussels, was developed between 2000 and 2003. From 2009 to 2013, the database underwent a major overhaul to better meet the needs of its users. With the broader adoption of linked data in cultural heritage and humanities research, and with researchers demanding more advanced tools for data visualisation

and analysis, the database is currently undergoing another renewal process, propelled by an infrastructure grant from the Research Foundation Flanders (FWO). At the core of the ‘ODIS renewal project 2022–2027’ is the development of a new triple store database and a new user interface. This stems from a desire to create new ways to query, analyse, and visualise the ODIS datasets, as well as to develop an interoperability and discovery layer.

This paper focuses on the backend transition from a relational to a triple store database, discussing the decisions, methods, and workflows implemented to enable the desired functionalities for the new user interface. We first provide some background information on ODIS, its history, and the current architecture of the database. We then discuss the approaches to data(re)modelling, as well as the tools used and created. Our aim is to offer an account of our efforts and journey through this transition. We seek to share our experiences with the digital humanities community, advocate for a linked data approach, and present some best practices.¹

2 ODIS: Past and Present

ODIS is a research-driven relational and contextual database on the history of civil society (ODIS, n.d.b). It was developed between 2000 and 2003, thanks to a grant from the Research Foundation Flanders (FWO – Max Wildiers Fund) (Heyrman and Weber, 2007). Four major cultural archives in Flanders, all seeking a system to store, interconnect, and disclose contextual metadata related to their heritage collections, formed the basis of the project: ADVN - archive for national movements, Amsab-Institute of Social History (Amsab-ISG), KADOC-KU Leuven, and Liberas (the former Liberal Archives). Other heritage and research organisations and projects in Flanders and Brussels soon joined the partnership, making ODIS one of the most widely used historical research instruments in Flanders.² As ODIS does not receive structural funding, its management and maintenance are covered by the annual operational usage fees paid by the partners.

In 2006, the management of the database was entrusted to a non-profit association under Belgian law.³ The universities of Antwerp (UA), Brussels (VUB), Ghent (UGent), and Leuven (KU Leuven) are represented in its General Assembly. KADOC, the interfaculty Documentation and Research Centre on Religion, Culture and Society at KU Leuven, is responsible for the day-to-day management of ODIS, while LIBIS-KU Leuven is the main technical service provider. From 2009 to 2014, a research infrastructure grant from the Hercules Foundation of the Flemish authorities enabled the development of a new database (De Maeyer, 2015). The data structure of ODIS was expanded with new modules for the description of buildings, families, and events. Bilingualism (Dutch–English) became a key feature of the database, significantly increasing its usability, though also adding complexity to the data model. A mix of language-dependent and language-independent fields makes up the descriptions,

¹ We would like to thank Peter Heyrman (KADOC-KU Leuven), Stephan Pauls (LIBIS-KU Leuven), Rachele Ricceri (LIBIS-KU Leuven), Winand Van Meerbeek (KADOC-KU Leuven), and Roxanne Wyns (LIBIS-KU Leuven) for their valuable input.

² A complete overview of the ODIS partners, with links to their websites, is available on the ODIS website (ODIS, n.d.a).

³ The bylaws of the non-profit organisation (vzw) ‘Onderzoekssteunpunt en Databank Intermediaire Structuren in Vlaanderen (19de-20ste eeuw)’ were published in the Belgian Official Gazette (*Belgisch Staatsblad*), 13 November 2006, 884.703.544. Their most recent update was published on 8 January 2024 (noa, 2024).

resulting in shared data between the two language versions of a record, but also discrepancies. Translation projects aimed at closing this information gap have already yielded significant progress, though the issue remains on the agenda.

Stimulating cross-fertilisation between heritage and research has always been a major goal of ODIS. By offering researchers and heritage experts a shared platform, the database aims to foster interdisciplinary research into the history and heritage of civil society. First and foremost, it provides its partners with a stable, reliable, and user-friendly environment to centralise and store contextual information on civil society and its documentary heritage. This enables them to safeguard, supplement, update, and correlate their dispersed datasets and repertoires, keeping them accessible in the long term and ensuring the reproducibility of research. Secondly, the system is used to validate data and publish them on the World Wide Web, via the ODIS public catalogue (OPAC) and specific OPACs on the websites of partners and projects. Finally, ODIS enables its partners to analyse their datasets by means of advanced search tools (Angelaki et al., 2019; Colla and Heyrman, 2019; Heyrman, 2025).

The broad scope of the ODIS partnership is reflected in the comprehensive content of the database. Many thematic fields are addressed at the international, national, regional, and local levels: politics, social movements and organisations, culture, art and architecture, religion, national movements, education, care provisions, migration, and more. In May 2021, the ODIS datasets on religion, culture, and society, managed by KADOC, were recognised as a core research facility of KU Leuven (KADOC-KU Leuven, 2024; KU Leuven, 2024). As of early 2024, ODIS contained 308,144 records on organisations, persons, families, buildings, events, archives, and publications (mainly periodicals). Nearly 48% of them are available for consultation under a Creative Commons licence (BY-NC-SA 4.0), facilitating their reuse in other initiatives and projects. In 2023, the ODIS OPAC was visited 91,642 times by 51,517 unique visitors, resulting in 604,982 page views. Visitors use the database in several ways: 1) as an encyclopaedia; 2) as a heuristic instrument; 3) as an authority database; and 4) as a digital humanities research tool.⁴

The current ODIS data model consists of eight interlinked modules (see Figure 1). The structure of the modules is based on international standards wherever possible: ISAAR(CPF) for organisations, persons, and families; the DOCOMOMO Guidelines for buildings; ISAD(G) for archives; ISBD for publications; and ISDIAH for repositories (Docomomo International, n.d.; International Council on Archives, 2024a,b,c; International Federation of Library Associations, 2011). All modules share a parallel structure. Each includes 'authority entries' for identification data (e.g. names, titles, dates and places of birth and death). Furthermore, data inputters can use both free text fields and repeatable fields/field groups. In the latter category, systematic data input is carried out based on validated thesauri and lists of choices. Finally, ODIS features relational field groups. These ensure the interconnection between the ODIS modules and enable the creation of clear and unambiguous links between records. By interconnecting records, the ODIS data model makes it possible, for example, to map networks and discover unexpected connections. With some research effort, the contextual information clusters in the database provide a multifaceted view of civil society in Flanders/Belgium, its key players and documentary heritage. Since only some authority entries are mandatory, authors and partners can determine the scope and depth of their datasets in alignment with future research objectives. They also

⁴ More information on the content and use of ODIS can be found in the ODIS annual reports, available on the ODIS website (in Dutch) (ODIS, n.d.a).

Figure 1: Entity-relationship diagram of the ODIS database.

independently determine whether they would like to publish their series in the OPAC.

Striving for versatility and cooperation, ODIS seeks to address and even anticipate the technical needs of its diverse partners and users. These users are a balanced mix of academic researchers, heritage experts, individuals involved in local historical research, genealogists, journalists, and other information seekers.

As several features of the database have become somewhat outdated and no longer provide the expected functionalities, nearly ten years after the so-called ‘ODIS Hercules Project 2009–2014’, another comprehensive renewal of ODIS became necessary. Supported by a research infrastructure grant from FWO and benefiting from a technical collaboration with LIBIS-KU Leuven, the database has embarked on a transformative journey since 2022.⁵ The ‘ODIS renewal project 2022–2027’ aims to update the mission and goals of ODIS, foster data input and data quality management, strengthen participation, and implement a revamped communication strategy. However, its core ambition is the technical renewal of the database.

Although the project resources did not allow for extensive user research, ODIS had a good understanding of the technical needs of its backend and frontend users through a user survey conducted in 2020, and through several technical workshops at the annual ODIS community day. A key element is the development of new ways to query, analyse, and visualise the ODIS datasets, such as network and geographical visualisation. This will enable ODIS to provide its users with more hands-on research tools. Secondly, we aim to develop an interoperability and discovery layer, offering more and better connections with other catalogues, research instruments, platforms, and linked open data resources. This serves as the cornerstone of a sustainable open access policy, based on the so-called FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) (GO FAIR initiative, 2022). Endpoints (JSON:API and SPARQL endpoint) will enable end users – both ODIS partners and external users – to retrieve data from ODIS for reuse in other databases or within research tools. Rights and responsibilities of the data creators and users will be defined in a data management and sharing plan, which is currently being developed. The endpoints will also facilitate the semantic enrichment of the ODIS content through interconnections with complementary datasets.

To achieve these project goals, the development of a new database and user interface is underway. For the database, it was decided to switch from a relational Oracle database to a triple store database developed in Virtuoso. In the following sections of this contribution, we will discuss the challenges involved in the backend renewal of

⁵ Research Foundation Flanders, I011122N. The supervisors of the renewal project are Prof. Dr. Kim Christiaens (KADOC-KU Leuven), Dr. Peter Heyrman (KADOC-KU Leuven), and Jo Rademakers (LIBIS-KU Leuven).

Figure 2: Left: the current ODIS search interface. Right: the new ODIS search interface.

ODIS in more detail.

3 A Database in Transition: ODIS Yet to Come

In the current phase of the project, a new frontend has been envisioned to maintain a strong connection with users' evolving needs. To implement this renewed vision within the existing infrastructure, a new backend had to be designed and developed. To better understand the choices made for the backend, allow us to outline a vision of *ODIS Yet to Come*.

The website will undergo a facelift, featuring a new logo, new brand colours, updated graphics, and more (see Figure 2). Users will be able to query the OPAC more easily through updated simple search functionalities, a more user-friendly advanced search, the ability to filter the result set using facets, and the option to represent the result list either in a table or in a more detailed manner. All of this should help accommodate researchers of all levels. Navigation will be more intuitive within the website and between the various records, allowing for seamless movement back and forth within the OPAC.

We also aim to enable a 're-presentation' of the rich data already stored within ODIS by offering new ways to explore them both visually and analytically. Not only will the records have a new layout, but there will also be an integrated geographical tool to plot results on a map, helping to contextualise the data spatially. To conclude our vision of *ODIS Yet to Come*, we must mention one final visualisation tool: the network graph. Inspired by, for instance, the *Gemeinsame Normdatei* (GND), managed by the German National Library, we will integrate a network representation within our records (GND-Explorer., n.d.). Users will be able to open the network from a record and further explore the multitude of relationships interconnecting records, hopefully discovering network clusters at a higher level. In short, the current OPAC will be updated to meet the latest standards in search functionalities, along with some

useful extras.

Tackling the renewal of the entire infrastructure is no easy task, and neither is describing the process. To meet all the needs of the envisaged frontend, the entire backend architecture must be stable and versatile enough to support it. This can be broken down into a few components: a new database environment, a new data model to structure that environment, and a new API layer to facilitate the exchange of data between the database and the OPAC, as well as between the database and external authorities.

The first task we faced was selecting a new database platform that would meet our needs. Our decision was partially influenced by the type of data model we intended to use. The cultural heritage sector has increasingly shifted towards a linked data approach, exemplified by the International Council on Archives (ICA) launching its new description standard, Records in Contexts (RiC),⁶ and the Flemish authorities with their Open Standards for Linking Organisations (OSLO) (International Council on Archives, 2024d; Vlaanderen, n.d.).⁷ Given that our frontend applications strongly suggest a linked data framework, this direction appeared to be the most logical choice. Separate from the frontend requirements, the opportunities for the research data in ODIS to be disseminated more widely and at the same time being enriched by external authorities are too important to be overlooked. ODIS data were already interlinked by the many relationships between the different modules, such as between organisations and persons. These links, however, were not always as easy to perceive on a larger scale. This is where an RDF (Resource Description Framework) approach could allow the data to shine.

Although RDF models can be stored in relational databases – typically yielding high-quality results (Hernández et al., 2016) – we decided to embrace the triple store approach.⁸ While many are familiar with the concept of relational databases, it is helpful to briefly describe what a triple store entails. A triple store is a database optimised for storing and querying RDF data. Conceptually, it functions as a key-value store, where the key is split into a subject (identifier) and predicate (property name). Unlike relational databases, triple stores lack predefined table structures or constraints, instead relying on standards like RDF and SHACL for data organisation and validation.

While triple stores offer unparalleled flexibility, their layered approach can make them difficult to adopt. Developers often perceive linked data technologies as overly complex, with limited immediate value. This situation underscores the importance of having an API that takes care of validation and database communication.

Several challenges are connected to the adoption of a triple store database, often cited by developers as reasons to refrain from embracing this novel approach. Firstly, it is well known that linked data has a steep learning curve, involving effort and time investment that are often unavailable within the constraints of a specific project. Secondly, some inherent challenges of adopting a triple store system include higher complexity when integrating with other platforms, such as frontends. Specific queries

⁶ The International Council on Archives (ICA) launched its first drafts of a conceptual model and ontology for Records in Contexts in 2016 and most recently published version 1.0 in 2023.

⁷ The Flemish authorities have been rolling out linked open data standards across several fields and have been in the process of working on a standard for cultural heritage since 2020. Their aim is to help facilitate data exchange within the heritage sector in Flanders, for example, between archives and museums, but also to connect with international players.

⁸ Ravat et al. (2020) have shown that for querying vast datasets, relational databases still have the upper hand. However, we believe that a triple store approach is appropriate for our case since, despite being large in comparison to other historical research infrastructures, our dataset (308,144 records as of 1 January 2024) is still relatively small compared to those in most performance tests.

must be constructed to make relevant information human-readable. In terms of maintenance, we still observe more complex debugging, as well as performance issues for larger triple stores. Moreover, as ecosystems are not yet as expanded as RDBMSs, triple stores come with a tooling complexity that can be perceived as too high at first.

Yet, we believe that the path to linked data can and should be pursued using triple stores, and that these challenges are outweighed by numerous long-term advantages. Firstly, data models are more flexible and adaptable to the needs of evolving projects, accommodating the needs of different users. A new record structure or graph can thus be easily created using construct queries. Additionally, a significant added value of a triple store approach includes semantic richness and interoperability. These two reasons support our choices. Semantic richness is guaranteed by the possibility of referring to different schemas (e.g. `schema.org`), and to maintain consistent values. Agent entities are more easily integrable into the data model. Interoperability is a major asset of the new data model built using triple stores, as it is achieved both by smoothly exporting information to other triple stores and by acquiring data from external systems. The apparent tooling complexity can be overcome by implementing an appropriate API layer to facilitate data exchange. Finally, the relative performance issues that can be experienced when running large triple stores are mitigated by using Elasticsearch.

We were not the first humanities database infrastructure in Flanders to transition from a relational to a triple store database. Archiefbank, the database of Archiefpunt, made a similar transition between 2020 and 2022 (Archiefpunt, n.d.; FARO Vlaams steunpunt voor cultureel erfgoed vzw., 2020).⁹ Like our colleagues at Archiefpunt, we opted for a Virtuoso Triple Store. Virtuoso is open-source software that provides all the functional necessities for our project: it is a well-maintained product, offers high-performance SPARQL querying for efficient handling of complex queries and optimised RDF graph traversal, supports federated SPARQL queries enabling remote RDF data source queries, is scalable for large datasets through distributed deployment, and includes reasoning and inference support. Additionally, it facilitates data integration across multiple formats, such as XML, CSV, and other databases, while ensuring ACID-compliant transactions.¹⁰ From a financial perspective, it also offers excellent support at a relatively low cost. It is important, however, not to become dependent on one database platform. The way we have built our data model and surrounding infrastructure (as discussed in the next section) ensures that we can easily migrate between platforms if and when we choose to do so. The only requirement for the platforms is that they have an HTTP SPARQL endpoint.

4 Working out Solutions, Challenges Along the Way

The successful implementation of data-driven applications in the digital humanities hinges on the seamless integration of domain expertise with technological proficiency. While scholars possess invaluable knowledge of historical sources, cultural contexts, and research methodologies, they often lack the technical expertise to translate their

⁹ Archiefpunt vzw is a cultural heritage organisation that aims to raise awareness of private archives in Flanders and Brussels. Its Archiefbank database makes thousands of archival descriptions available to the public. In their 'DATA project', spanning 2020 to 2022, the infrastructure (backend and frontend) underwent a total facelift to better serve its stakeholders.

¹⁰ ACID (Atomicity, Consistency, Isolation, and Durability) is a set of rules expected from database platforms.

data models into accessible and interoperable APIs. Conversely, developers may possess the necessary programming skills but lack the nuanced understanding of the domain-specific requirements and constraints that underpin effective data modelling. This inherent disconnection between domain experts and developers presents a significant bottleneck in the development lifecycle, leading to:

1. **Increased development time:** The manual translation of data models into APIs is a time-consuming and error-prone process, requiring constant communication and iterative refinement between domain experts and developers.
2. **Reduced agility:** The rigid separation of roles hinders rapid prototyping and experimentation, both of which are crucial aspects of research and development in the digital humanities.
3. **Limited interoperability:** Inconsistent and poorly documented APIs impede data sharing and integration across different projects and research teams, hampering collaborative research efforts.

This suggests that tools designed to reduce the time taken to transition from a model to an API are highly welcome. The team working on the ODIS transition consists of various profiles, each with its own skill set. On the KADOC side, most members have limited technical skills, but they possess extensive domain knowledge of the existing data model, the data, and the functionality of the database and its interface. LIBIS, the technical partner in the project, has all the technical proficiency but lacks knowledge of the intricacies of ODIS and its data. At first glance, they complement each other beautifully, but this also brings its own set of challenges.

In short, we required a workflow that would allow us to:

1. describe a new RDF-based model,
2. enable people with domain knowledge to work on it independently while ensuring that the deliverables are suitable for the developers,
3. ideally generate the blueprint for an API.

4.0.1 Spreadsheets as Description Tool

Describing a model is a way to express what you know about a business domain. It can be used for documentation, data validation, or in our case, the creation of APIs. Although many methods are available for describing models, the easiest approach – requiring no prior knowledge of a specific methodology – is to use one or more **spreadsheets**. This allows for description of the model in a structured yet user-friendly manner and easy segmentation between namespaces, entities, properties, and links. A system of spreadsheets was set up using Google Sheets, where we began to outline the necessary entities and overall structure of the new model. The spreadsheets act as a bridge between the functional and technical sides of the project, enabling team members with more functional knowledge of the database to interact with and help shape the model in an accessible way. In doing so, attention must always be paid to the bilingual nature of the data in ODIS. Initially, ten workbooks were created: one for each module (namespace), a ‘general’ workbook for modelling entities shared between the various namespaces, and another one to model all code tables. The first tabs in every workbook, as shown in Figure 3, begin with an underscore and are specific to the system:

	A	B	C	D	E	F
4	baseDataTypes	Description	AllDatatypes	AllDatatypes	ProjectEntities	ProjectEntities
5	rdf.JSON		geo:wktLiteral	xsd:string	odis:Agent	odis:Agent
6	rdf.langString	Multi language string	odis:Agent		odis:Archief	
7	xsd:anyURI	A valid URI	odis:Archief		odis:Archiefcode	
8	xsd:boolean	boolean	odis:Archiefcode		odis:Archiefvormer	
9	xsd.date	date	odis:Archiefvormer		odis:Auteur	
10	xsd.dateTime	date + time	odis:Auteur		odis:Beroep	
11	xsd.double	converted to float. double is 64bit, float 32bit	odis:Beroep		odis:BeroepTitel	
12	xsd.duration	iso8601 duration	odis:BeroepTitel		odis:Beschermsstatus	
13	xsd.float	a float	odis:Beschermsstatus		odis:Beschrijvingsniveau	
14	xsd.gYear	an integer	odis:Beschrijvingsniveau		odis:Bevoegdheid	
15	xsd.integer		odis:Bevoegdheid		odis:Bewaarplaats	
16	xsd.string		odis:Bewaarplaats		odis:BewaarplaatsCode	
17	xsd.time		odis:BewaarplaatsCode		odis:BouwhistorischFeitSystematisch	
18	time:DateTimeInterval		odis:BouwhistorischFeitSystematisch		odis:Bouwstructuur	
19	schema:temporalCoverage		odis:Bouwstructuur		odis:Bron	
20	geo:wktLiteral		odis:Bron		odis:BronParalleld	
21	v.Geometry		odis:BronParalleld		odis:ChronologischeBouwgeschiedenis	
22			odis:ChronologischeBouwgeschiedenis		odis:Codetabel	
23			odis:Codetabel		odis:Contact	
24			odis:Contact		odis:Context	
25			odis:Context		odis:Copyright	
26			odis:Copyright		odis:DateringSystematisch	
27			odis:DateringSystematisch		odis:Diploma	
28			odis:Diploma		odis:Entiteit	
29			odis:Entiteit		odis:Ereteken	
30			odis:Ereteken		odis:Erkenning	
31			odis:Erkenning		odis:ExterneCatalogus	
32			odis:ExterneCatalogus		odis:Familie	
33			odis:Familie		odis:FamilieFunctie	
34			odis:FamilieFunctie		odis:FamilieWoonplaats	
35			odis:FamilieWoonplaats		odis:Formaat	
36			odis:Formaat		odis:Functie	

Figure 3: Example of the `_DATATYPES` tab.

- **`_README`**: A brief explanation of the spreadsheet structure.
- **`_DATATYPES`**: A comprehensive list of data types across namespaces.
- **`_PREFIXES`**: Taxonomies and external references.
- **`_METADATA`**: Metadata such as the model's title and version.
- **`_REFERENCES`**: Links to additional spreadsheets within the model.

4.0.2 Namespace-Specific Sheets

The main difference between the global and namespace workbooks is the `_ENTITIES` sheet. Each namespace has a dedicated `_ENTITIES` worksheet, which describes entities, their plural forms, and relationships (e.g. inheritance (`subClassOf`) or external equivalence (`sameAs`)). For each entity, additional worksheets define its properties, including data types, constraints, and links to other entities. Every entity defined in the `_ENTITIES` sheet can have a separate tab that describes all the properties associated with that entity. When an entity has a `subClassOf` relationship, it will inherit all of the properties of its parent entity, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Let's have a look at a couple of entities in Figure 5. `Entiteit` does not have a `subClassOf` relationship, as it is the basis for all entities within the model. In Figure 6, we can see that it has three properties: `id`, `parallel_id`, and `_audit`. When we look at the entity `Codetabel`, we see it is a `subClassOf` of `Entiteit`, meaning it inherits all of its properties. The properties of `Codetabel`¹¹ thus include `id`, `parallel_id`, `_audit`, `waarde`, and `context`, with the latter two defined in the `Codetabel` tab.

¹¹ `Codetabel` is a separate entity that describes all code tables used throughout the database.

	A	B	C	D	E
1	Name	NamePlural	Description	subClassOf	sameAs
2	Agent	Agenten		odis:Entiteit	rico:Agent
3	Auteur	Auteurs		odis:Entiteit	
4	BeroepTitel	BeroepTitels		odis:Codetabel	
5	Beschrijvingsniveau	Beschrijvingsniveaus		odis:Codetabel	
6	Bevoegdheid	Bevoegdheden		odis:Codetabel	
7	BewaarplaatsCode	BewaarplaatsCodes		odis:Codetabel	
8	BouwhistorischFeitSystematisch	BouwhistorischFeitSystematisch		odis:Codetabel	
9	Bron	Bronnen		odis:Codetabel	
10	BronParalleld	BronParallelds		odis:Codetabel	
11	Codetabel	Codetabellen	Basis Klasse voor code tabellen	odis:Entiteit	
12	Context	Contexten		odis:Codetabel	
13	Copyright	Copyright		odis:Codetabel	
14	DateringSystematisch	DateringenSystematisch		odis:Entiteit	
15	Entiteit	Entiteiten	Basis klasse voor alle entiteiten		schema:Thing
16	ExterneCatalogus	ExterneCatalogi		odis:Entiteit	
17	Functie	Functies		odis:Codetabel	
18	GeografischeTrefwoord	GeografischeTrefwoorden		odis:Codetabel	
19	Geslacht	Geslachten		odis:Codetabel	
20	Illustratie	Illustraties		odis:Entiteit	
21	Landcode	Landcodes		odis:Codetabel	
22	Naam	Namen		odis:Entiteit	
23	Naamsoort	Naamsoorten		odis:Codetabel	
24	Onderwijsinstelling	Onderwijsinstellingen		odis:Organisatie	
25	Onderwijsniveau	Onderwijsniveaus		odis:Codetabel	
26	OnlineBijlage	OnlineBijlagen		odis:Entiteit	
27	Orgaan	Organen		odis:Codetabel	
28	Paralleld	Parallelelds		odis:Entiteit	
29	Periodiciteit	Periodiciteiten		odis:Codetabel	
30	PersoonEretekens	PersoonEretekens		odis:Codetabel	
31	PersoonTitel	PersoonTitels		odis:Codetabel	
32	Publicatiesoort	Publicatiesoorten		odis:Codetabel	
33	Relatie	Relaties		odis:Codetabel	

+ ≡ _README ▾ _PREFIXES ▾ _DATATYPES ▾ _METADATA ▾ **_ENTITIES** ▾ Agent ▾ Autei

Figure 4: Example of the `_ENTITIES` tab.

Name	NamePlural	Description	subClassOf	sameAs
Agent	Agenten		odis:Entiteit	rico:Agent
Auteur	Auteurs		odis:Entiteit	
BeroepTitel	BeroepTitels		odis:Codetabel	
Beschrijvingsniveau	Beschrijvingsniveaus		odis:Codetabel	
Bevoegdheid	Bevoegdheden		odis:Codetabel	
BewaarplaatsCode	BewaarplaatsCodes		odis:Codetabel	
BouwhistorischFeitSystematisch	BouwhistorischFeitSystematisch		odis:Codetabel	
Bron	Bronnen		odis:Codetabel	
BronParalleld	BronParallelds		odis:Codetabel	
Codetabel	Codetabellen	Basis Klasse voor code tabellen	odis:Entiteit	
Context	Contexten		odis:Codetabel	
Copyright	Copyright		odis:Codetabel	
DateringSystematisch	DateringenSystematisch		odis:Entiteit	
Entiteit	Entiteiten	Basis klasse voor alle entiteiten		schema:Thing
ExterneCatalogus	ExterneCatalogi		odis:Entiteit	

Figure 5: Example of class inheritance.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
Name	Description	MIN	MAX	sameAs	datatype	Parent							
id	UUID	1	1	schema:Identifier	xsd:string	-							
parallel_id	Anderse ids die naar hetzelfde object verwijzen	0	1	odis:Parallelid	odis:Parallelid	-							
_audit	link naar audit	0	1	xsd:anyURI	xsd:anyURI	-							
_type	entity type, usefull when querying parent entities	1	1	xsd:anyURI	xsd:anyURI	-							

Figure 6: Example of class *Entiteit* worksheet.

The `sameAs` column references a context outside this model. For *Entiteit*, this indicates that it shares the same context as `schema:Thing`. That approach ensures the interoperability of our model with external standards and systems. By defining parent and child entities, we dismantle the barriers that previously separated the eight modules in ODIS. In the old model, humans could identify similarities in field groups and assume their equivalence; however, this logic was not apparent to machines. By employing shared entities, we define and embed these similarities in aspects such as dates and names, as well as in our conceptualisation of these ‘base entities’ as agents.

4.1 SOLIS

The sheets provide a foundation, yet the transition from a conceptual data model to functional APIs is a resource-intensive process. Our research focuses on leveraging the expressive power of **SHACL** (Shapes Constraint Language), a W3C standard for defining and validating RDF data, to bridge the gap between data models and APIs (W3C, 2017). SHACL provides a declarative and human-readable syntax for expressing constraints and expectations on RDF data, making it an ideal candidate for capturing domain-specific knowledge and translating it into machine-processable specifications.

Building on the spreadsheets’ foundation, we developed **SOLIS** (Smart Ontology Layer for Interoperable Systems). This engine can take the information in the sheets to generate ERDs and, more importantly, SHACL files. These files contain the logic and rules necessary to validate data ready for import into the triple store. SOLIS is also a novel library that automates the generation of RESTful APIs directly from SHACL-based data models. By leveraging the flexibility and scalability of **triple stores**, SOLIS enables developers to:

- **Rapidly prototype and iterate:** The automated API generation process significantly accelerates the development cycle, enabling researchers to quickly test and refine their data models and explore different API endpoints.

Code tables are controlled lists of values that aren’t subject to constant change but provide a stable way of preserving controlled data and links. Since we are using an open API, we need to limit certain entities to read-only, and these are grouped under `Codetabel`.

Figure 7: SOLIS pipeline diagram.

- **Focus on user experience:** By abstracting away the complexities of API development and RDF interpretation, SOLIS empowers developers to concentrate on building intuitive and user-friendly interfaces that cater to the specific needs of humanities scholars and researchers.
- **Enhance data interoperability:** The use of standardised formats and protocols ensures that APIs generated by SOLIS are easily discoverable, accessible, and compatible with a wide range of tools and platforms, fostering data sharing and collaboration within the digital humanities community.

SOLIS represents a significant step towards streamlining the development of data-driven applications in the digital humanities. By empowering domain experts to actively participate in the API development process, and by providing developers with a powerful and efficient toolkit, SOLIS has the potential to unlock new avenues for research and innovation in this exciting field. It explicitly addresses the challenges of the current situation by highlighting the inefficiencies caused by the disconnection between domain experts and developers, and it emphasises the significance and potential of SHACL for capturing domain knowledge and generating API specifications.

By leveraging SHACL, SOLIS transforms these constraints into functional API endpoints, bridging the gap between data modelling and application development. Based on the files, SOLIS generates two things: documentation about the model, and a JSON:API layer that will enable interoperability between the database, the new frontend, and third-party users (Aernouts and Celik, 2025; Celik, 2025; JSON:API, n.d.). This is crucial to our architecture, as it enforces the logic and rules for data validation entering the triple store, while also providing sense and structure to the data coming out of the database. The triple store serves as a backend storage: all logic is stored and enforced through the API, allowing for easy iterative work. Whenever any changes have to be made to the model during the modelling and remodelling process, a simple regeneration of the SHACL will resolve the issue efficiently.

4.2 Modelling Challenges

In reshaping the data model, there were two main goals: 1) it must facilitate an easy transition from the old model to the new; and 2) it must be compliant with RiC. The first requirement was driven by a desire to avoid alienating users familiar with the existing model, as well as by the need to transition as efficiently as possible. As

mentioned earlier, the old model was based on several ICA description standards that were subsequently incorporated into RiC, making compliance easily achievable. Some logical changes were made in the new ODIS model, such as incorporating Agent entities and using generic entities to serve similar functions; for instance, the `odis:Naam` entity is utilised for both names and titles of publications or archives. These abstractions were necessary to rationalise the model. Obsolete fields – fields that were rarely used or often misused – were discarded where possible. This approach helps to maintain the quality of data input by limiting certain fields and better guiding users in their data input efforts.

The bilingual nature of the data presented another challenge. The method used to store language variants in the relational database is difficult to replicate. Records consisted of language-dependent and language-independent text fields, a specific solution for the 2009–2013 renewal that does not translate well to the new approach. By assigning the datatype `rdf:langString` to these properties in the new model, we were able to address the language issue. In the future, the database can potentially be expanded to accommodate more language variants, moving from bilingualism to multilingualism.

One of the requirements for the new frontend is an integrated geographical visualisation of the data. This necessitates, among other things, GIS data to enable plotting on a map. The current database already contains an extensive geographical thesaurus, built on a dataset from TomTom for Europe, which has been manually enriched with data for locations outside the European continent. While this provided a foundation for the geo tool, it was a self-contained thesaurus with no links to other authorities. This prompted the desire to use external authorities for our geographical thesaurus. The authority had to meet several requirements:

1. there should be metadata to reconstruct the hierarchy of place names,
2. it should grant free access to global data,
3. it should allow for multiple authority references such as Wikidata IDs,
4. given that ODIS works with historical subjects, historical place names should be available as aliases.

We found that OpenStreetMap met most of our needs and provided not only data but also a widespread community (OpenStreetMap, n.d.). It also offers us the opportunity to contribute to the community by documenting places used in ODIS that are not yet present in OpenStreetMap. At the time of writing, we have successfully mapped the old geodata to the OpenStreetMap model and are researching ways to incorporate their data, either by ingesting and regularly updating it or through a ‘live call’.

One of the factors that ignited interest in linked data for this project was network visualisation. In the academic year 2023-2024, Yiyao Jin, an MSc student in Digital Humanities at KU Leuven (supervised by Prof. Dr. Katrien Verbert), worked on this topic for ODIS. She produced a first draft of what a network visualisation of our data could look like in her master’s thesis (Jin, 2024). Her research was already very promising; using Gephi to represent a select dataset yielded some exciting results. Her findings will serve as a starting point for developing the visualisation tool in the frontend.

ODIS is a dynamic database, and part of the transition project involves migrating the legacy data to the new environment. To transfer the data from the old database

to the new one, the existing structure had to be converted to the new triples format. Mappings were made to facilitate an easy transition, which served as a useful test to identify any omissions or logic errors in the new model. Once the conversion scripts were completed, the newly converted data were ingested in the triple store via a JSON:API. This functioned as a preliminary test to ensure that the necessary constraints and logic were being enforced. The process resulted in several iterations of the model, as well as updates to the SHACL and API. This highlighted the advantages of this approach, allowing for easy adjustments to the model in the spreadsheet and seamlessly triggering subsequent changes to the SHACL and API.

5 Concluding Remarks

In this paper, we shared insights from the ongoing technical renewal project for the contextual database ODIS. The journey to the new ODIS environment is an adventurous one; we are currently halfway through and on track to complete the project on time. We have established a new triple store database in Virtuoso, reworked the data model, and set up a user-friendly workflow for easy modelling and API generation with SOLIS. Furthermore, we have successfully converted the data and rigorously tested the setup. The shift to a triple store approach enables us to break down barriers not only between ODIS and other data repositories but also between the separate modules within the database. Additionally, it has enabled us to align the ODIS data model with Records in Contexts. Alongside redesigning the database structure, the public interface of ODIS will undergo a revamp.

The technical renewal programme aims to strengthen the flexibility and multifunctional use of ODIS, fostering its broad applicability in individual and collaborative scientific research, all within a multidisciplinary and international-comparative perspective. The system will help ODIS users compose and query consistent data packages. It will also enable them to visualise and analyse ODIS datasets in novel ways, supporting, for example, a more in-depth understanding of associational life, the prosopographical analysis of civil society organisations, the visualisation of biographical and associational itineraries, the spatial and territorial impressions of civil society, and more. In addition to opening new perspectives for data-driven research in the social sciences and humanities, we are confident that the investment programme will also encourage more research units to join the ODIS partnership and incorporate their own data series, further strengthening the thematic scope and research potential of the database.

We hope that our journey will inspire similar projects and demonstrate that it is possible to navigate the challenging middle ground between business and technical teams. We also hope to have offered convincing reasons for developers to take the leap into the RDF domain and overcome the obstacles. Our approaches can serve as a foundation for others to further develop their own workflows and streamline their transition processes.

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Linking Het Amsterdams Stadsjournaal: A Case Study in Emerging Linked Open Data (LOD) Approaches to Audio-Visual Heritage

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Taking the case of *Het Amsterdams Stadsjournaal* (*ASJ*) as a starting point, this article aims to advance emerging Linked Open Data (LOD) approaches to AV heritage. The archiving of *ASJ* materials, a political film collective that produced politically engaged documentaries between 1974 and 1984, raises several challenges and questions concerning archival access to AV heritage and standardisation because the materials preserved are located at three different institutions with diverging missions and user groups: respectively Eye Filmmuseum (Eye), the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (NISV), and the Stadsarchief Amsterdam (SAA). Addressing this circumstance, the article evaluates the potential of Linked Open Data as a way to connect and enhance data on *ASJ* to make the preserved materials more widely accessible. This entails critically discussing the current access given to *ASJ* films in the CLARIAH Media Suite in light of the infrastructure’s Wikidata features, focusing on how these functionalities may accommodate the user requirements identified at the institutions preserving *ASJ* materials. By emphasizing the specific challenges of AV archives, the article also seeks to broaden the scope of current digital humanities discussions concerning LOD as these have hitherto had a tendency to leave out collections preserved by AV heritage institutions.

Keywords: audiovisual archiving, linked open data, documentary cinema, Wikidata

1 Introduction

Focusing on the example of *Het Amsterdams Stadsjournaal*, this article aims to advance discussions around emerging Linked Open Data (LOD) approaches to AV heritage.¹

¹ The research for this article was initiated in the context of Meg Weijers’ MA thesis, and further developed in the context of the CLARIAH Media Suite Learn initiative.

Het Amsterdams Stadsjournaal, henceforth *ASJ*, was a political film collective that produced critical documentary productions about the misconducts and malpractices in capitalist society between 1974 and 1984 (Heijs, 1984). The archiving of the *ASJ* materials, and their associated datasets, raises several challenges and questions concerning archival access to AV heritage and standardisation because the materials are located at three different institutions with diverging missions, user groups and definitions of film works: Eye Filmmuseum (Eye), the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (NISV), and Stadsarchief Amsterdam (SAA). Addressing this challenge, and elaborating on the reflection developed in the context of the DH Benelux 2024 Conference theme “Breaking Silos, Connecting Data”, this article discusses the research done on evaluating the potential of Linked Open Data as a way to connect and enhance data on *ASJ* to make it more widely accessible. Moreover, this article discusses and critically evaluates the access currently given to a part of *ASJ*’s films in the CLARIAH Media Suite and the environment’s recently developed LOD and Wikidata features, focusing on how these functionalities may accommodate the user requirements identified at the institutions. By pointing out specific challenges we deal with within AV archives, we aim to shed new light on discussions concerning LOD and digital humanities.

1.1 The Shared Custodianship of *ASJ*

One of the challenges raised by the ways in which *ASJ* materials are currently accessible is the shared custodianship over the collection. Currently, the films are preserved and documented by three different institutions, each operating with a distinct perspective and definition of the films, namely as respectively art (Eye), historical artefact (NISV), and as part of a specific urban history (SAA). Due to this shared custodianship, the records have been provided with different information and metadata that lacks standardisation, a topic we shall return to later in the article in more detail. This is problematic: the archives use different databases and have ingested them for different reasons. As a result, some films have been provided with elaborate metadata whereas other films are only provided with a minimal amount, as you can see in Figures 1 and 2, screenshots taken from Eye’s database CE, and Figure 3, a screenshot taken from the NISV’s database DAAN.

Because of an extensive research project by curators and volunteers of Eye on the *ASJ* collection, CE has an elaborate description of the film in its database, including keywords and metadata on the physical aspects of the material such as sound, color, and image ratio. In contrast, the metadata on the same film in DAAN lacks some metadata such as a description of the film but does have technical metadata and keyframes.

It should be noted that this incoherence is not a unique phenomenon within audiovisual heritage practices. Even within an archive, metadata can differ greatly between films from the same collection. At Eye for instance, metadata is continuously added when films are taken out of the vaults for research or viewings. However, a lack of metadata makes it harder to depart from the collection of an archive when doing research because it means you need a considerable amount of tacit knowledge to understand the information in a database.²

Authority Heading	
Identificatie	
ID:	FLM3085
Authority heading:	Amsterdams stadsjournaal 8 (NL, ASJ Collectief (corporatie), 1976)
Kopieën in eigen beheer:	14
Urls:	http://eye-d.ka.filmmuseum.nl/Home/Select/kopieId/KOP1291883 Open kopie-item http://eye-d.ka.filmmuseum.nl/Home/Select/kopieId/KOP1291884 Open kopie-item
Typering	
Categorie:	fictie/non-fictie
Korte beschrijving:	Documentaire/reportage uit een 36-delige reeks politiek georiënteerde films uit socialistische hoek over misstanden in de kapitalistische maatschappij.
Titels	
Originele titel:	Amsterdams stadsjournaal 8
Originele titel:	Surinamers in Nederland
Originele titel:	De terugkeer van het zwarte goud
Serietitel:	Amsterdams Stadsjournaal (serietitel)
Regie	
Regie:	ASJ Collectief (corporatie)

Figure 1: Screenshot of record of Amsterdams Stadsjournaal 8 in CE

Inhoudelijke ontsluiting	
Inhoudsbeschrijving NL:	Over de emigratie van Surinamers naar Nederland en hun inburgering (met de cursus 'Zó is Nederland'), neokolonialisme (export hout, bauxiet en fruit; met het geluid van een kassa als terugkerend element), de positie van Surinamers in Nederland en remigratie. De film eindigt met een landbouwcollectief (Vereniging Alladoti) dat naar Suriname gaat. De gestelde vragen aan de directeur van Bureau Rijksgenoten verschijnen als tekst in beeld. Film bevat ook een Surinaams lied. [gemaakt i.s.m. Centrum Anton de Kom]
Onderwerp (trefwoord):	etnische minderheden
Onderwerp (trefwoord):	migratie
Onderwerp (trefwoord):	integratie
Onderwerp (trefwoord):	koloniën
Onderwerp (trefwoord):	kolonialisme
Onderwerp (geografisch):	Nederland
Onderwerp (geografisch):	Suriname
Onderwerp (geografisch):	Amsterdam (Noord-Holland)
Onderwerp (geografisch):	Schiedam (Noord-Holland)
Onderwerp (datering):	1976
Fysieke kenmerken (eerste release)	
Geluid (eerste release):	geluid
Kleur (eerste release):	zwart-wit
Image ratio:	1.33:1 volbeeld

Figure 2: Screenshot of record of Amsterdams Stadsjournaal 8 in CE

² By tacit knowledge, we mean the knowledge possessed by individuals working at institutions that is not made explicit to others, for example user groups and coworkers. For a better understanding of the role of tacit knowledge within audiovisual archives, see *Share That Knowledge!: A Road Map for Sharing Knowledge across Generations of Audiovisual Archivists* (van Dalen and Šičarov, 2023).

METADATA				
Serie titel	AMSTERDAMS STADSDJOURNAAL			
Programma titel	Amsterdams stadsjournaal nr. 8: Surinamers in Nederland			
Licensor	Broadcast organisation NIET VAN TOEPASSING			
Asset Rights: License	License check			
Publication	Distribution channel overig-video	Publication type niet van toepassing	Broadcaster NIET VAN TOEPASSING	Broadcast organisation NIET VAN TOEPASSING
Material type	video			
Annotation	Dossiernr RVD: 07-7093			

Figure 3: Screenshot of record of Amsterdams Stadsjournaal 8 in DAAN

This need for adequate and coherent metadata is even more crucial for a collection like *ASJ*, dispersed over multiple archives. To be able to approach them as a collection, you need to be able to link the individual films to each other. In short, the shared custodianship requires a certain coherence in metadata without changing the databases of the three archives. Here, metadata should enhance the collection's access to a broad public. Moreover, the information needs to reflect these three perspectives on the nature of film and the different user groups of the institutes.

As interest in unlocking the materials grew, an alternative way had to be found to enable access to them as a whole, while being preserved at three different institutions. The research presented in this article first approaches this challenge conceptually and practically, while experimenting with potential solutions, focusing on the following main question:

- What are the potential affordances of metadata and Linked Open Data (LOD) in overcoming the challenge of shared custodianship and cataloguing contextual information in the archiving of the *Amsterdams Stadsjournaal*?

The overarching aim of this research is to contribute to two academic discussions in the AV heritage field, namely:

1. the archiving of films that are produced outside the mainstream film circuit from the perspective of archival access,
2. the emergence of Linked Open Data in the AV heritage field.

As these are relatively unknown topics in the AV heritage field, this research can be seen as an experiment with this technology, how it interacts with metadata in catalogues dealing with filmographic metadata, and to examine its potential and pitfalls within film archival practices, thus advancing discussions around LOD in connection to film and AV heritage, which still tend to be underrepresented.

In this research, we particularly focus on the two LOD-technologies Wikibase and Wikidata. By taking this focus, the article furthers research around film heritage and LOD, while also building on current efforts by considering non-theatrical films, a type of film that has not yet been a main focal point for LOD in film and AV archives. Moreover, Wikibase and Wikidata are already being used by one of the custodian archives (NISV) and incorporated in the annotation functions of the CLARIAH Media Suite. Hence, Wikibase and Wikidata were logical platforms to build this research on.

2 Theoretical Framework

Before diving deeper into the case of *ASJ*, we want to sketch the theoretical context and reference frame our endeavor is situated in. With the help of some examples, we

discuss archival access and linked open data in light of AV heritage to understand the link between the two and challenges that are particular to our field.

In the past decades, archival access has been considered an increasingly important archival paradigm in the (AV) heritage sector. From the 1980s onwards, with computerization and digitization, archival access has increasingly become a concern for AV archives. In "Access – the reformulation of an archival paradigm", Angelika Menne-Haritz (Menne-Haritz, 2001) defines access as a professional strategy that is user-oriented. In contrast to the precedent, custodial paradigm, in which records are considered as evidence of which archivists are impartial (but not really impartial) custodians (Cook, 2013), the access paradigm is "neutral towards the content but passionate concerning openness and availability of information potentials" (Menne-Haritz, 2001, p. 63). Within this paradigm, the role of the archivist is to enable the user to find their way through the archive and evaluate the relevance of the found records themselves. In other words, archival access is about providing tools rather than giving meaning to the records. Therefore, Menne-Haritz argues that archival descriptions and presentations should be user-driven, as each researcher has their own specific research question and is the only one to determine what is relevant for answering that question.

For Prelinger (2009), one of the more prominent voices within this debate, archival access helps AV archivists validate our work and ensure against institutional irrelevance. As he states about the current state of archives concerning access: "Unlike public libraries, which have long-established traditions of access, we lack a strategy that might help move us toward greater openness" (p. 168). This lack of strategy is related to a certain hesitation by many film archivists to open up their archives because of risks concerning copyright, piracy, and loss of control. In "Archives and Access in the 21st Century", (Prelinger, 2007) explains how, traditionally, archivists have privileged preservation over access for several reasons that are more or less tied to "copyright maximalism" (p. 115). However, he argues that access is more than a binary choice between publicly usable, fully available records or only private, in-house viewings. Between these options, there is a great range of possible uses that circumvent the risks of copyright infringement. An example of this is the solutions of the CLARIAH Media Suite for works of which film archives only partially have the rights, such as the Peter Rubin Collection of the Eye Filmmuseum. Peter Rubin was an American filmmaker and VJ active in the Amsterdam club scene and German techno collectives *Mayday* and *Love Parade* (Tzialli, 2017). His VJ works contain footage of television items filmed on VHS alternating the original work. Whereas Eye is allowed to put Rubin's work in the Media Suite, the segments with television items are at risk of copyright infringement. These parts can be blocked in the Media Suite, but users are still able to see where they were being used in the work in question. This allows users to see the 'copyright safe' segments in the right context.

In terms of archival access, the example above shows the particular challenges in AV heritage such as copyright. The emergence of digitization and digital tools have further complicated these challenges as they have changed users' perception of access. For many users, archival access means searching by theme or topic and accessing materials on a streaming platform, creating high expectations which often cannot be met because of insufficient finding aids (Heftberger, 2022). Cataloging is key here, as Adelheid Heftberger writes in "Access is Not a One-Way Street: The Relation Between Access to Collections and Cataloguing" (Heftberger, 2022). In this article, she explains how cataloging practices "define the kind of knowledge and concepts we make accessible

for our institutions” (p. 47). Hence, archival access and good quality cataloging are intertwined. In terms of the *ASJ* collection, LOD can potentially help in this regard to enhance cataloging practices.

The *ASJ* films are also present in the CLARIAH Media Suite. As a central access point to digitized AV collections and tools for analyzing them - among which metadata inspection and manual annotation tools - the Media Suite results from previous mass-digitization efforts and the emergence of digital humanities projects in the Netherlands (van Noord et al., 2021). Among others, this entails NISV’s Dutch public broadcasting collections, oral history collections from DANS, parliamentary debates, and a small number of collections from Eye. In this context, around 25 films from the *ASJ* have metadata descriptions in the Media Suite, of which around 15 films can be viewed directly in the Media Suite’s environment. In this context, the films are associated with metadata that have been created following descriptive practices at NISV. In a few instances, in particular for person categories, item descriptions have been enriched with wikidata identifiers that were used for cleaning names in NISV’s metadata by way of disambiguation, allowing users of the Media Suite to search in three different categories, namely person appearing in a broadcast program, person as subject of discussion, or person involved in a broadcast in a production crew role. For instance, the item *Amsterdams Stadsjournaal nr. 34: Hoeveel ging u naar school?* (1983), is one of very few items to have data in one of these categories, linking filmmakers Floor Kooij, Goert Giltay and Barbara den Uyl to these films. Clicking on the names in the items metadata description allows users to go either to the Wikidata identifier’s page of the person in question, or to carry out an additional search in NISV’s collection based on the name to explore other potentially relevant items featuring them. In this respect, the digitized *ASJ* items have to a limited extent already been enriched using Wikidata. Yet, these enrichments result from a generic approach that is taken for all items in the Media Suite, and do not reflect a tailor-made solution that take into consideration the specific challenges of the collection. However, it is possible for users of the Media Suite to add additional data of a higher level of granularity using the environment’s annotation functionality, to the potential benefit of developing a LOD approach further. The annotation functionality enables users to annotate items on item level or on segment level, based on personal segmentations and coding schemes, and researchers using this functionality create significant amounts of additional research data. Yet, the data resulting from this functionality are not currently automatically shared and streamlined with a LOD approach – among others because of data privacy – but it is an ambition to devise workflows in the future that may allow for such data to feed into an LOD approach. In the next section, we reflect on these challenges in relation to LOD in more detail.

2.1 *LOD as a potential solution*

Why take a look at LOD as one of the potential solutions for the challenge of shared custodianship of *ASJ*? In recent years, LOD-based technologies have sparked increased interest among film and AV archives looking for ways to make collections accessible online and to enrich metadata within existing systems. For example, workshops have been organised to discuss the usage and tasks of LOD in film archives, where this is still a very novel approach (FIAF, 2019). However, despite this growing interest, the promise of standardisation and interoperability between different systems has not been fulfilled, just as film archival data presents challenges that are mostly only sparsely covered in existing literature on LOD. As Seth van Hoogland and Ruben

Verborgh argue: “[a]gain and again, projects have demonstrated that even if people and institutions are using the same tools and standards, they implement them in different ways to accommodate the specific nature of their collection” (van Hoogland and Verborgh, 2014, p. 14). In other words, linked data is an interesting technology but still needs good-quality, standardised metadata to be used efficiently in film and AV archives.

In the community of film archives, explorations of possible solutions for metadata exchange between institutions go back to at least the 1970s, and were initially centered around MARC formats (machine-readable cataloging), yet without fulfilling promises of shared systems, standards and databases across national borders (Smither, 1987).³. For decades the process of developing shared standards for moving image metadata in the context of film archives was slow to catch on, but this has gained momentum in the 2010s. For instance, the launch of resources such as filmstandards.org or the Cinematographic Works Standard EN 15907 in 2011 may be considered significant steps forward in this regard.

In recent years film heritage institutions have begun taking a serious interest in LOD and Wikidata, particularly in the context of the organizational framework of FIAF (International Federation of Film Archives), as offering an approach that may fulfill needs for exchanging data that have long been difficult to realize.

Like explained in the introduction, Wikibase and Wikidata were examined in this article’s research. As a basis for this examination, we take a cue from Heftberger and Duchesne’s article “Cataloguing Practices in the Age of Linked Open Data” (Heftberger and Duchesne, 2020) which argues that “[b]y linking similar properties back to Wikidata we can have the best of both worlds, allowing for a higher level of specification on our platform, while also allowing the ability to push and pull data between other knowledge bases where desirable”. One example of why a personal Wikibase is desirable is the difficulty of adding different film titles as released in the distributing countries. Because Wikidata has the option to directly translate text, this causes some problems for film titles in a language different than the one of the country of release, but the same language as the original production country. In their article, Duchesne and Heftberger illustrate this problem with the film *The Hangover* (2009). In Wikidata, this title would be literally translated to “La gueule de bois” instead of the title in which the film was released in France, *Very Bad Trip*. As Duchesne and Heftberger argue: “This would be controversial, as it would be the primary metadata field against the film on French Wikidata, yet it is a title under which the film was never released. Essentially this is a conflict between following the strict logic of a machine - readable environment, while also allowing for human-readability”. This example shows a conflict between Wikidata’s machine-readability and human-readability, and the specificity of filmographic information thus complicates the mapping of information on Wikidata.

Based on this starting point, we consider a personal Wikibase (theoretically) desirable because of conflicts between Wikidata’s machine-readability and human-readability, and the specificity of filmographic information that complicates the mapping of information on Wikidata, while arguing that the shared custodianship of the ASJ materials suggests that the usage of Wikidata and Wikibase by AV-archives

³ For early discussions of moving image metadata standardization we refer to Roger Smither’s work. A more extensive account of metadata standards in the context of film archives can also be found in the work of one of this article’s authors, Christian Gosvig Olesen, *Visualizing Film History: Film Archives and Digital Scholarship*, published with Indiana University Press in 2025 (Olesen, 2025).

need to be revisited and tailored to the specifics of this collection. To identify what kind of information about the *ASJ* collection goes into the Wikidata and the personal Wikibases, it is necessary to analyze the potential use of this technology first.

3 Methodology

The methodology of this research was divided into three consecutive parts. The first part covered an inventory of the paper documents available about three *ASJ* films: *Werkloosheid* (1975, no. 4), *Surinamers in Nederland: De Terugkeer van het Zwarte Goud* (1976, no. 8), and *Gebroken Tijd* (1982, no. 30). These titles were chosen because together, they reflect different production phases of *ASJ* and a range of topics that are still pressing matters in today's society. For instance, *Surinamers in Nederland* touch on topics such as neocolonialism, and *Gebroken Tijd* is about the position of Turkish migrants in the Netherlands.

3.1 Contextualizing the individual films

The contextualization of the individual films included watching the three films and searching articles about these films on Delpher. These articles helped to acquire more insight into the context in which these films were made. Many people in the films of *ASJ* refer to developments and events that are not known to current viewers. These articles helped to understand what the people in the films referred to. For example, some articles helped to link the film *Surinamers in Nederland* to specific events and social developments, such as public discussions about remigration of Surinamese people (1976, *De Volkskrant*). These kinds of articles therefore contextualized the films in their time. Other articles were reviews of the films, showing how the films were received by the public. For the feasibility of this research, a maximum of 10 articles were written down and provided with a short description of the kind of information they contained.

Alongside the articles on Delpher, documents stored at Eye, NISV, and SAA were examined. For each film, the number of documents and the type of information these documents provided varied significantly, ranging from newspaper clippings to grant applications. Since the paper documents are not yet registered in the database, a full day was devoted at each institution to inventorying the available documents. Again, each document was recorded, categorized, and accompanied by a brief description in the spreadsheet. However, it soon became evident that this would be too time-consuming for the scope of this research, as many documents contained merely scribbles and notes, often difficult to read and identify the film they referred to. Therefore, only the documents containing information about the production process, distribution, and screening/reception of the films were documented. This information helped verify certain things, such as the target audience and the collective's perspective on the individual film. These were then either copied or photographed for further reading and analysis at a later stage. The insights gained from this thorough reading formed the foundation of the user requirement study.

3.2 User requirement study

The user requirement study, consisting of interviews with employees of the three institutions, assessed which insights gained from the archival research were vital to cataloging the records of *ASJ* as respectively a form of art, historical artefact, and

urban history. The term ‘user requirement’ was used as explained by Kathy Baxter and Catherine Courage, who define it as “the features/attributes your product should have or how it should perform from the user’s perspective” (Baxter and Courage, 2005, p. 3). In this research, the features refer to the kind of information and the product of archival descriptions or other kinds of metadata. This method was chosen because it helped to take inventory of a broad scope of users and programming ambitions based on the answers of those who would eventually work on the collaborative project of Eye, SAA, and NISV. As this has not been done before, the study should be seen as a first, qualitative test based on the findings from the first part. There was a specific focus on the *reasoning* behind the preferences for certain kinds of information. Where to place them instead was not intended to already determine which information needs to be cataloged and where and how this should be done.

3.2.1 Set up user requirement study

Three interviews were conducted for this research: one employee of each institution was interviewed who had knowledge about the users and records usage of their archives and about the possibilities their databases provide in terms of metadata and linked data.

Part 1: cataloging the records: The first part of the analysis of the paper documents was rewritten to discuss the findings of the selected films with the interviewees. These rewritten parts were structured in the same way, containing the following elements:

- Summary, including aesthetic features
- The film’s aims and target groups
- Production process
- Reception and reflection on the film, which included reviews from newspapers, comments during discussions afterwards, and the reflection of the makers themselves, if applicable
- Background information, including an elaboration on societal debates and topics

Standardizing the findings helped to determine what was considered relevant/useful in general, and whether there were certain circumstances in which these considerations varied. For the user requirement study, the interviewees were asked to read the descriptions, explain their general impression of the description and then cross out everything that they considered as not relevant to be added as descriptive metadata and provided with an explanation.⁴

Part 2: potential users and uses: The second part of the user requirement study consisted of three questions, if these had not already been answered in the first part:

1. What are the potential uses of the records by the NISV, Eye, and Amsterdams Stadsarchief?
2. Who are the potential users of the records?

⁴ Not relevant is defined as not useful for understanding the film or too elaborate for the database.

3. Which kinds of metadata are usually provided by the different databases and what are the differences between them?

The answers and insights derived from the user requirement study were used to analyse the affordances of Wikidata and Wikibase to determine if these were potential ways of linking the records with each other and other records in the three archives.

Finally, focusing on our ongoing research, we compared the results of the thesis research project to a selection of *ASJ*-films currently made available in the CLARIAH Media Suite infrastructure in relation to the infrastructure's LOD and Wikidata features, taking into account how they may (or may not) accommodate for the identified user requirements.

4 Analysis

Despite the many differences in production, distribution, and reception of the three films, the paper documents provided insight into certain aesthetic choices, the co-producing organizations, productional changes made during the process, and showed how the films were perceived by members of *ASJ* and the public. Some documents also covered research done by *ASJ* that contributed to the arguments made in their films. These documents provide clarity on what the film does not explicitly cover but what is nonetheless part of the meaning behind the film. This is especially true for societal developments depicted in these films. The newspaper articles from Delpher provide different arguments and the reviews and discussion notes show what the audiences added to the film. This was most prominent in the paper documents of *Surinamers in Nederland*. The discussion afterwards contained certain topics not explained in the film, such as discrimination that Surinamese people encountered. As the discussion was a very important part of the screening of the film, information like this helps to contextualize what cannot be extracted from the film's content. Hence, the paper documents provide layers inherent to the meaning of the film.

The user requirement study shows that there are metadata specific to *ASJ* as a film collective and metadata specific to *ASJ* as a form of art, a historical artefact, and part of urban history. For instance, the target groups, aims, societal developments and co-producing organizations were generally considered relevant to be added as metadata. However, the answers also offer different perspectives on film, shaping the relevancy of the contextualizing metadata for the interviewees. For instance, the interviewee from Eye had a clear focus on the visual structure of the individual films as well, which was in line with their perspective on film as a form of art. For SAA, on the other hand, one of the most important kinds of metadata was the locations shot in Amsterdam, as 80% of the queries covered locations. This shows the different aims and target groups of SAA as a city archive with the duty to provide service to the citizens of Amsterdam.

Although much of the information discussed in the findings was considered relevant, the findings suggest a need for providing this information on a meta-level. This means that elaboration on certain events, developments, or concepts should be noted down. However, in terms of access, this could be problematic for users who don't know what these references mean. For example, some users might not know about certain historical events, so this kind of metadata might not help them to contextualize these films. Hence, the interviews suggest the need for an external place in which this kind of information can be explained further.

Next to relevant metadata, this study also covered potential users and uses of the *ASJ*

collection. In terms of users, they can be divided into three groups, according to the way they will likely use the films and the metadata: film- and television makers, users with an education or research background, and citizens of Amsterdam and/or the target groups of the films. Film and television makers are expected to use only fragments of the films to integrate them into their work. For this group, the context of these films is of less importance, as it is about what they literally see to (re)use these images in their own context. On the other hand, users with an education or research background will likely use the films to study them in a broader context and illuminate current affairs from a historical point of view. However, as one of the interviewees pointed out, researchers are also more inclined to distrust the contextualizing metadata as this would be considered a secondary source. The last group, the citizens of Amsterdam and/or the target groups of the films, are likely to use the films to get a better understanding of their community's history. Whereas contextual metadata might be a convenient addition for researchers and filmmakers, it could be essential for this specific user group. For instance, individual users might not have certain research skills or tacit knowledge, and this could help them along with their search question and interest.

4.1 Wikidata

A first observation that emerges during the analysis is the practical way in which Wikidata can provide contextual information while remaining readable at the same time. This is relevant to the notion of describing contextual information on a meta-level. For instance, the mention of PvdA leader and Prime Minister Den Uyl was considered relevant for the film *Werkeloosheid* to understand the political environment at the time, but not of additional value for the database. This means that the metadata should only highlight the main points, functioning as a first lead for the user in case they want to know more about it. In this case, '*Werkeloosheid*' would become an item and 'Prime Minister Den Uyl' a value of a certain statement. However, the value 'Prime Minister Den Uyl' is an item at the same time, namely "Joop den Uyl" (Q318320) (Wikidata, c). Hence, Wikidata enables the archives to add contextualizing metadata by means of other items. This way, the item *Werkeloosheid* does not get flooded by an extensive amount of information while providing the tools to navigate further if desired. This means that contextual information considered too elaborate to catalog can still be linked in the Wikidata.

As Wikidata supports other Wiki-projects, items and values can also be linked to their corresponding Wikipedia page, which contains much more information. For instance, the statement 'themes' in the item *Surinamers in Nederland* would get the values 'neocolonialism' and 'decolonization'. These values can then be linked to a Wikipedia page about these concepts. Although it is debatable whether a Wikipedia page is trustworthy, we argue that this is still a helpful beginning for users, especially for those without tacit knowledge. For instance, it can help them to gather a general impression and provide other sources for further research. Ultimately, it does offer the tools to navigate through the information. Another consideration is the items and values without a Wikipedia page. As the co-producing organizations, such as the Anton de Kom Centrum for *Surinamers in Nederland*, were considered relevant metadata by the interviewees, these would become statements in items. However, a Wikipedia page about the Anton de Kom Centrum does not yet exist. In the case there are many items and values like these, this could become too time-consuming. The three archives must therefore make practical decisions about which items and values

need a Wikipedia page and which do not.

Another way in which Wikidata helps users navigate through the information is the multilingualism of the technology. As explained on their introductory page, Wikidata is multilingual which means that “Data entered in any language is immediately available in all other languages” (Wikidata, b). This enables users for whom Dutch is not their native language to access the metadata as well. More specific to the films of *ASJ*, this affordance can also be used to open up the archive to certain user groups such as the target groups of the films. For instance, *Gebroken Tijd* and *Surinamers in Nederland* targeted Turkish and Surinamese immigrants. This affordance helps to make the collection accessible for those more fluent in Turkish and Sranantongo (or other languages spoken in Suriname) than Dutch.

Despite the helpful affordances described above, some affordances of Wikidata need more critical examination. One of the affordances is the free and openly collaborative nature of the database, which opens up some questions concerning ethics and the challenge of shared custodianship. As mentioned on Wikidata itself, their data is “published under the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication 1.0, allowing the reuse of the data in many different scenarios” (Wikidata, b). This needs careful consideration of the information put on the Wikidata as reusing data could also mean recontextualization and loss of control. Therefore, the archives need to determine whether there is any data too sensitive to publish under creative commons. Next to ethical issues like these, one may also argue that co-editors outside the archives are not desirable in the case of *ASJ*. Because it is a collaborative data repository, solely using Wikidata means that all the contextual information could be edited by users outside the three archives. This could mean that the data will become unevenly described, further complicating the need for coherency between the films and thus the challenge of the shared custodianship. Therefore, the archives need to determine which data would fit in Wikidata and which data should only be created and edited by three archives in the Wikibase.

4.2 Wikibase

The section above shows that Wikidata has several affordances that can help with contextualizing and linking the films. However, as previously argued, it might not be desirable to contextualize and link the films by solely using Wikidata as the archives might want to retain some control over the information stored on this platform. Here, Wikibase could be used to create an individual platform to adapt it to the unique characteristics of the *ASJ* collection, circumventing the limitations of Wikidata while using the technology at the same time. This does not only help to archive the collection coherently, as argued in the previous section, but it also enables the archives to create collection-specific statements. For instance, *Surinamers in Nederland* as an item in the Wikibase would be followed by statements about the film. Some statements would be very generic, such as the length and spoken language. However, as the target groups, aims, and cooperating organizations were also considered relevant to be added as metadata, these statements could potentially be quite confusing if target groups were used as properties in a different context in other Wikidata items. Therefore, metadata that is very specific to *ASJ* needs to get a property in an individual platform to be as unambiguous as possible. In this sense, it shows similarities to the conclusions of Duchesne’s and Heftbergers article on cataloguing practices.

Another limitation in Wikidata that can be circumvented by creating an individual platform, is the descriptions of the items. As can be seen in Figure 4 below, items are

Figure 4: Screenshot of item *Spirited Away* and its discription

minimally described.

Wikidata itself has limited item descriptions, as they explain on their help page: “For those who are familiar with Wikipedia, it may be tempting to initially think of items as like the Wikidata version of Wikipedia articles. While items and articles are both pages for storing information about different concepts or topics of human knowledge, it’s important to keep in mind that Wikidata is not just a database of Wikipedia content” (Wikidata, a). In other words, the item’s description is just to distinguish the item from items with the same name. However, for the items referring to the films of *ASJ*, it would be helpful to state the film’s content more elaborately. Other contextual information, such as the societal debates and perspectives, can be put as statements. Here, Wikibase can be used to adapt the platform to the specific needs of the *ASJ* collection. In this respect, it would make sense to set up a dedicated Wikibase insofar as it offers more autonomy. Yet, on the other hand, it should also be highlighted that while such a solution may appear more accommodating when it comes to contextualizing the collections and defining ontologies, it also comes with significant technical overheads that the institutions involved may not be able to dedicate to a subcollection.

5 Conclusion

The user requirement study showed which contextual information was relevant specifically for understanding *ASJ* as a film collective and for understanding *ASJ* as a form of art, a historical artefact, and part of urban history. Moreover, the findings suggested a need for providing this information on a meta-level, noting down only distinctive events, developments, or concepts without further elaboration. However, this could be problematic for users who do not have the required knowledge or research skills. To solve this problem, the interviewees suggested an external place for this kind of information, helping this specific target group further without overloading the databases.

The findings from the affordances analysis implied that metadata and LOD-based technologies such as Wikidata and Wikibase can be used to capture contextual information of the individual *ASJ* films to adequately catalog the collection to such an extent that all users can understand it regardless of their background. Hence, their potential is to open up the collection for a broad group of users. Concerning the challenges of the *ASJ* collection, metadata should be used to capture the information relevant to all three institutes whereas Wikidata and Wikibase can be used to store more specific information and to link the individual films to each other, helping users

understand the collection as a whole. Additionally, it can offer users starting points for further research by providing links to other web pages containing contextual information. Therefore, LOD has two potential roles: to connect the films and to offer users specific tools to investigate topics, concepts, and persons further if wanted. The latter is currently facilitated in the CLARIAH Media Suite. Here, the results show the biggest potential of using LOD in audiovisual archives in light of current practices: as a way to contextualise political films without having to change an entire database.

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Herbaria Heritage: Visualizing Colonial Bias in Natural History Collections

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As a result of the colonial entanglements of many natural history collections, much of the world’s biodiversity heritage is housed in Europe. Increasingly, natural history institutions have begun to address their colonial past. However, in this regard, computational methods for analyzing large collections tend to consist of static visualizations of collection provenance. Moreover, in regions where cutting-edge visualization technologies are only scarcely available - often these are the same areas from which most European plant collections originate - there is a lack of simple, accessible solutions that can generate meaningful results. Thus, we argue that accessible, simple, yet interactive visualizations of collection provenance allow users to understand colonial bias in natural history collections better. Our solution allows users to focus on content gaps and highlights historical patterns and trends in collection data. Using a dataset containing metadata of five million entries from the Naturalis Biodiversity Center botanical collection as a use case, we created an interactive visualization with Microsoft Power BI. The visualization showcases the origins and movements of botanical specimens from former Dutch colonies to the Netherlands on an interactive map and timeline. This addresses not only a gap in historical research on the colonial legacy of Dutch botanical collections but also a gap in digital humanities research regarding simple and easy-to-use computational techniques for distant reading of natural heritage data. The particular use case demonstrates only a fraction of the research possibilities that this tool enables. Our interactive visualization increases the accessibility of the available scientific data, and contributes to a better understanding of the relationship between cultural history and natural history, highlighting

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the greater importance of easy-to-use, interactive and accessible visualizations of biodiversity collection histories. Ultimately, our project suggests a way forward for natural history museums not only in the Netherlands to reinterpret the colonial past of their collections.

Keywords: visualization, colonial bias, natural history collections, digitization

1 Introduction

While Natural History museums and herbaria in the Global North house much of the world's biodiversity heritage, they have tended to disassociate themselves from the cultural histories inherent to their collections (Borren and Drieënhuizen, 2022; Das and Lowe, 2018; Drew et al., 2017; Kaiser et al., 2023). This lack of recognition of the histories behind collections becomes even clearer when situated alongside other museum disciplines that have been grappling with this problem for years (Haarnack, 2021). However, acknowledging the inherent colonial entanglements of natural history collections is the first step in writing more nuanced histories of these collections. This entails a greater analytical focus on the histories of acquisition and appropriation in the field (Dubald and Madruga, 2022; Hünninger, 2021) and on the subsequent movement of objects to Europe. Such a focus ensures the political context of collections is not hidden under the guise of biodiversity science and rationality, as is often the case today (Driver et al., 2021; Nadim et al., 2024). Additionally, this type of recognition becomes vital for understanding the implications of such colonial entanglements for global biodiversity and conservation efforts (Johnson et al., 2023; Park et al., 2023).

The work done to uncover these hidden histories has tended to concern researchers working primarily with textual or object-focused approaches, lacking computational methods and visualizations (e.g. Alcantara-Rodriguez et al. (2022); Drieënhuizen and Sysling (2021); Jacobs and Koch (2021); Müller (2023); Wingerden (2020)). Some studies by Mohammed et al. (2022) and Park et al. (2023) utilized heat maps, world maps, etc. to illustrate botanical specimen movements across the globe and categorize trends. However, these existing visualizations, such as herbaria snapshots, lack interactivity, leaving a rich trove of information untapped. This lack of interactivity means users cannot currently engage with the different temporalities that natural historical collections and their digitized counterparts entail (Hopman, 2024). Moreover, in localities where advanced and cutting-edge visualization technologies are limited – often the same regions where many European plant collections originate – there is a shortage of simple, accessible tools capable of generating meaningful results (Buschke et al., 2023). Our tool is therefore not intended to be cutting-edge from a technological point of view. On the contrary, we seek to provide a simple, accessible and user-friendly solution that can be used as widely as possible.

Given the increasing digitization of natural history collections and the availability of large datasets related to these collections (Beltrame et al., 2024; Hedrick et al., 2020; Pickering, 2024; Stork et al., 2019, 2021), there is great potential to exploit the data in *simple, meaningful* and importantly, *interactive* ways. Thus, we propose *interactive visualizations* as a computational technique for distant reading of natural heritage data. Focusing on the provenance of botanical specimens – specifically those stored in Naturalis Biodiversity Center (Leiden, The Netherlands) – we create an interactive and multi-layered visualization to trace historical movements of species from Indonesia

and Papua New Guinea¹ using Microsoft Power BI (see Figure 2). Our dashboard and accompanying use case are insightful for the processing, design and visualizations of other collection data. Since Microsoft BI is already used in the domain to visualize digitization progress and the composition of collections, we foresee a fast uptake of our solution (Breugelmans and Trekels, 2023; DiSSCo, 2023).

We are of course aware that there is a deep disciplinary and institutional divide between the natural sciences and cultural, colonial and historical studies. While natural science oriented researchers consider digitized natural history collections merely as abstract and decontextualized datapoints, historians read them as entangled cultural objects with a long history of collection, appropriation, circulation and datafication. While some have suggested that hiring more diverse staff at natural history museums is the way forward to achieve a more holistic understanding of such collections (Das and Lowe, 2018), we think that an intensified training of historians in critical and reflective digital humanities, for instance with a focus on interactive visualization techniques, should play an important role to fill this epistemological and methodological gap (Díez Díaz et al., 2025). A smart use of interactive and easy to use visualization tools such as Power BI can help to reconnect datasets to their cultural and historical roots. Taken together, we hope that our paper serves as inspiration for (biodiversity) scientists, historians, data providers and a general public - not only in the Western world - to actively continue and engage in conversations about new ways of access and visualization of collection datasets in the field of natural history.

To outline our research, we first describe the dataset (Section 2), before detailing our use case and the historical, practical relevance of the case. Secondly, we compare existing computational methods to further highlight the gap we aim to address in the related work (Section 3). With this background, we describe our method (Section 4), before discussing the obtained results from a qualitative perspective (Section 5). In the final section (Section 6), we reflect upon our methodology, suggesting follow-up work. Ultimately, this article aims to bridge the gap between the historical and digital, exploring how data visualization can be used as a tool to uncover the histories hidden behind scientific collections.

2 Dataset

Our paper employs the “Naturalis Biodiversity Center (NL) - Botany” dataset, obtained through the GBIF website (Creuwels, 2015)². GBIF, or the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), is an international network and data portal that aggregates data from natural historical institutions all over the world (Feng et al., 2022). The physical plant specimens that this dataset represents are stored in the depots of Museum Naturalis in Leiden. This freely available tabular dataset comprises more than five million entries registering botanical specimens found in the Naturalis natural history collection. It has 51 columns with metadata about collected specimens, from which we use: country of origin (referred to as *country* in the dataset), *recordedBy*, *continent*, *family* and *typeStatus*. These five categories have been implemented as filters

¹ We are aware of the complex colonial history of Papua New Guinea. In-depth historical research would be necessary to find out which - and even more important when - specific botanical specimens were registered under the locality of Papua New Guinea.

² The dataset can be downloaded through the following link: <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/15f819bd-6612-4447-854b-14d12ee1022d>, however, its download is not necessary in order to run the Power BI file.

Figure 1: General Interface, including two pie charts, map, and timeline.

within the interactive interface, as well as through a world map to plot specimen occurrences.

Looking more closely at the data from Figure 1, the Netherlands accounts for 650,464 (22.21%) of Naturalis' specimens, followed by Indonesia at 568,517 (19.42%) and Papua New Guinea at 152,914 (5.22%). Taking the *Orchidaceae* family as an example (see Figure 3), the visualization reveals that Indonesia leads with 19,695 occurrences (37.38%), followed by 'Unknown', with 13,519 specimens (25.66%), and finally Papua New Guinea with 8,437 occurrences (16.01%). Significant spikes in registered specimens occurred in 1909 (907 from 51 countries), 1936 (1,328 from 34 countries), and 1986 (1,791 from 47 countries). Orchids are interesting, since in the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, orchids from colonial areas were an important economic luxury good and played an important role in scientific debates within the botanical sciences. Not only for individual botanists, but also for scientific institutions such as herbaria or natural history museums, it was important to acquire and publish about new specimens collected in colonized areas (Endersby, 2016, pp.105-128). Next to orchid hunters, colonial botanical gardens such as the one in Buitenzorg (now Bogor, Indonesia) or gardens in British India played key role in establishing global networks of plant exchange (Baber, 2016; Drayton, 2000; Goss, 2011; Weber and Wille, 2018).

3 Related Work

3.1 Colonial Roots of Natural History Collections

Although a contentious issue, an important body of literature exists exploring various topics which relate to the broader issue of addressing the colonial roots of natural history collections (Coote et al., 2017; Curry et al., 2018). There is consensus surrounding the finding that it is not uncommon for natural history museums to present their collections in a way that blurs "its entanglement with the human world" (Drieënhuizen and Sysling, 2021, p.305). For instance, scholars have found that Eurocentric perspectives

Figure 2: Indonesia and Papua New Guinea Interface, including a pie chart, filters, a donut chart and a timeline.

Figure 3: General Interface with the Orchidaceae family selected, shifting the visualizations to be filtered by this family.

in natural history museums have neglected indigenous contributions, perpetuating troubled social histories and emphasizing the need for decolonization (Andel, 2017; Ashby and Machin, 2021; Leonard, 2024). Mohammed et al. (2022), for example, reveal how colonialism erased indigenous knowledge in the Caribbean archipelago, creating biases in biodiversity collections. Similarly, the ‘coloniality of power’ concept coined by Quijano (2007), as discussed by Kaiser et al. (2023), highlights ongoing epistemic forms of extraction and racism during post-colonial rule, influencing scientific practices and collection growth. From those working within the natural sciences field, attempts to address such colonial roots have recently received more urgency, with organisations such as NatSCA (Natural Sciences Collections Association) hosting conferences to tackle this issue.³

Interestingly, however, (Park et al., 2023, p. 1060) note that the focus has largely been on “human- and animal-related collections” with comparatively less attention paid to botanical collections, possibly due to “lower visibility; few herbaria offer public displays, and plant awareness is generally lacking”. Moreover, there are only a few works which investigate the parallels between specimen acquisition and historical events from a longer term historical perspective. For example, researchers such as Goss (2011, 2018, 2023); van de Loosdrecht et al. (2024); Weber and Wille (2018); Wille (2019) uncover a connection between botanical research and the Dutch colonial project in Indonesia from a historical perspective. Nevertheless, work that uncovers the colonial entanglements of natural history collections of former colonizing countries – especially botanical collections – through the lens of large datasets remains limited and thus presents a gap to which our work aims to contribute.

3.2 Visualizing Colonial Bias in Botanical Datasets

Computational approaches addressing the colonial roots of natural history collections are limited, particularly concerning visualization tools. Looking more broadly at visualization techniques, several options exist, albeit more tailored toward cultural heritage – rather than natural history – and largely limited in interactivity. These include Information Visualization (InfoVis), which involves visualization methods such as graphs, charts and maps (Windhager et al., 2018). In a broader exploration of herbarium collections and their colonial legacies, (Mohammed et al., 2022, pp.147-148) employed visualizations to trace specimens from Trinidad and Tobago and the Bahamas. Their use of a heat map displaying institutions and collection sizes, along with a stacked bar chart illustrating accessioning patterns within the University of the West Indies Zoology Museum, effectively highlighted the historical role of islands as natural laboratories and the lasting impact of colonial influences on scientific practices. Related to this, Park et al. (2023) conducted a global investigation, examining herbarium disparities and presenting their findings through various visualizations. For instance, a world map visualized plant specimen movements, while relationship charts depicted intercontinental flows before and after colonialism. Their use of histograms in combination with maps provided a comprehensive illustration of the percentage of internationally collected herbarium specimens and categorizing trends across institutions and continents. These are both examples of how visualization was leveraged as a tool to increase the accessibility of natural history data, uncovering the colonial bias of collections in the process.

However, as noted by (Boakes et al., 2010, p. 1), “For these and related purposes,

³ See for more details: <https://www.natsca.org/event/2605>, accessed 19 October 2024.

biodiversity information must include more than a simple snapshot of the current status and distribution of species.” The static nature of these techniques, including the R package *bdvis*,⁴ is self-evident (Barve and Otegui, 2016; Medeiros e Sá et al., 2022). Multi-Touch interfaces, on the other hand, offer greater interactivity by enabling the intuitive exploration of collections, such as browsing museum image collections on multi-touch tables (Windhager et al., 2018, p.12). However, these are largely focused on exploring collection items rather than the distant reading of data. Moreover, 3D visualizations offer 3D depictions of artifacts or sites, but again, this visualization method is limited in applicability to our specific research dilemma (Windhager et al., 2018, p.15). A similar limitation exists for augmented reality and virtual reality. A technique more relevant for our purposes – specifically, contextualizing collections – is narrative visualization, which guides users through collections using storylines, timelines or spatial encodings. Again, however, interactivity within the visualization is a key element that is often missing. The same can be said for network visualizations and faceted browsing. Thus, more relevant for our purposes are ‘generous interfaces’, which allow users to interact serendipitously; and interactive timelines which in our case, are particularly important to understand the colonial contexts behind collections (Windhager et al., 2018, pp.1-15). Although interactive visualizations of museum collections do exist, there is a clear gap in the field of natural history collections specifically. This is despite archival and digitized collection databases being more openly available. It has been acknowledged by scholars that “the world’s museums contain information that is irreplaceable, especially a unique historical perspective, yet their information is often hard to access, even in the case of some well-funded, national museums” (Boakes et al., 2010, p.7). Thus, there remains a gap when it comes to making natural history museum data more accessible, especially for low-resource settings. Building on the above-mentioned visualization techniques offers a promising solution.

Ultimately, our paper argues that *multilayered, interactive* visualizations which allow users to explore and understand the history and provenance of scientific collections using any openly available data are lacking. This is especially problematic in settings where computational power and resources are limited. Research on the design of interactive health-related data dashboards in low resource contexts can serve as an inspiration here, for instance Akpan et al. (2022); Mgusha et al. (2021), which both utilize Power BI. The unavailability of interactive dashboards in the context of large natural history-related datasets restrains the range of research questions that can be asked: important stories that lie beneath the surface of the data are unlikely to be revealed, and the serendipitous discovery that often prompts further investigation is prematurely stunted.

4 Approach

For our visualization we used Power BI Desktop, which allows interactive maps, timelines and filters based on database column headers. There are different reasons why this specific tool was put to use. First of all, Power BI is an established tool for visualizations of collection data in the field of natural heritage collections (see Collection Digitization Dashboard, <https://www.dissco.eu/services/#cdd>). Moreover, it is an established way to create interactive data visualizations in other scientific disciplines, e.g. health science Akpan et al. (2022); Mgusha et al. (2021). Second, we were

⁴ <https://github.com/vijaybarve/bdvis>

looking for a tool that is freely available, enables replicability, and is easy to use. The tool allows for an interactive, user-friendly experience without requiring advanced programming knowledge. This makes replicability accessible, not only to historians and scientists but also to museum professionals, policy makers, and the general public. Thirdly, we were looking for a solution that does not require extensive computational resources and energy. Since the tool maintains its interactive performance even when handling large datasets, we opted for Power BI. We created dashboards on a laptop PC with a Ryzen 5 5500U processor and an AMD Radeon Graphics GPU. Since the selected Dutch botanical dataset from Naturalis is extremely large (with about more than five million data entries), we decided to create two views on the data: a general interface (see Figure 1) for an overview of the database, and a focused one (see Figure 2). For the focused one, we chose a focus on Indonesia and Papua New Guinea due to their colonial history, allowing researchers to get an overview of *when* Dutch researchers registered specimens native to these two countries, to understand *how* the collection's colonial bias has evolved over time and space.

4.1 Preprocessing

The “Naturalis Biodiversity Center (NL) - Botany” dataset was processed by: collapsing date ranges from *eventDate* into single dates (some were single-day timestamps, and some spanned one year), and removing the empty, null and “?” values, which was done through filters within the software. To replace the dataset with another, the same processing steps need to be repeated.

4.2 Solution Approach and Design

After loading the data into Power BI Desktop, the next step was to decide how to best represent it visually, in order to achieve our overarching aim of understanding the colonial bias of this collection. Given the geographical focus of our project, the most appropriate starting point was a map; specifically, one which visualizes the number of specimens in the Naturalis collection that originate from a particular country. Size and color were used to differentiate (e.g. the larger the circle, the more specimens that originate from that country). The interface also shows two pie charts, one with the percentage of traceable families, and another with the percentage of specimens per country. Importantly, there is a timeline plotting the number of specimens collected over time (see bottom of Figures 1 and 2). All visualizations are interactive, increasing the user-friendly nature of the tool. Given that previous computer science knowledge is not a prerequisite to interact with such a tool, the accessibility of the data improves substantially. Moreover, despite the size of the dataset, Power BI Desktop only needed a fraction of the available computational resources to compute the above-described interactive dashboards.

In terms of the design, the interface is aimed at both historians and scientists as well as the general public with a particular interest in this kind of data. Therefore, we prioritized readability and simplicity but also ensured that a more detailed investigation can be conducted where necessary through the use of the aforementioned filters, which increases the interactivity possibilities of the visualizations (top middle on Figures 1 and 2) and more importantly, the research questions that might be answered. Some of the filters, such as *TypeStatus*, might not be familiar to all users of the dashboard. Selecting this filter lets the user classify specimens by their type. An example of type is holotype. A holotype is a physical plant specimen (e.g. a dried plant) that was used for

the formal description of a species (for more details, see Sluys, 2021). The *recordedBy* filter lets the user filter by the botanist who obtained and recorded the specimen for the Naturalis collection. This directly contributes to questions about the colonial links of collections, as many collectors and botanists (e.g. Carl Ludwig Blume, Pieter Willem Korthals, Jaheri, Kees van Steenis) were closely affiliated with the botanical garden in Bogor, Indonesia and 's Rijksmuseum van Natuurlijke Historie (National Museum of Natural History), as the institutional predecessor of the Naturalis museum in Leiden was called (Goss, 2023; Jacobs and Shea, 2022; Manse, 2013; Miracle, 2021; Sysling et al., 2024; Weber, 2018; Wingerden, 2025). The capability of creating multiple interfaces with the same database illustrates the future possibility to broaden the scope of the relatively small-scale project as it is described in this paper.

5 Qualitative Evaluation

The following section evaluates the functionality of the interface, highlighting its ability to display and filter data accurately while facilitating accessibility without requiring the original dataset. The file is easily shareable, and a receiver does not need the dataset (unless they aim to make changes to the underlying data) in order to access the visualization. The interface is responsive, fast and accurately displays the selected data when run on the aforementioned device. This is key for improving the overall accessibility of such large datasets. Furthermore, the chosen filters (such as the *Orchidaceae* family filter on the second interface) function perfectly and can be modified at any time. Through the malleability of the visualizations, many historical or scientific questions relating to the colonial bias of natural history collections can be addressed. Nonetheless, it would be necessary to obtain a larger dataset with more than only botanical specimens to fully uncover the colonial bias of natural history museums. Given the fast-growing number of datasets of Dutch and other natural historical collections, we see ample opportunity for future research in this field (García-Roselló et al., 2023).

When evaluating the interface from a qualitative point of view, we can conclude that it showcases historical trade and collection patterns of various plant species, notably in Indonesia and Papua New Guinea, while linking specimen collection trends to significant colonial and scientific events, demonstrating the potential for deeper exploration of colonial biases in natural history collections. Looking at the map on the first interface as well as the pie chart, there is a significant clustering of specimens obtained from South-East Asia, most notably Indonesia. It comprises 19,42% of the total dataset, when not accounting for occurrences which are 'Unknown', or 'Null'. More importantly, according to the dataset, 70,23% of all holotype specimens in the Naturalis plant collection (=14.580) stem from Indonesia, Papua New Guinea and Suriname. The unknown cases also remain relevant: (i) they provide museums with a starting point for improving their datasets by highlighting data gaps, and (ii) could be a signal: such specimens could have come from former Dutch colonies, or perhaps locations that museums prefer not to publicize. The unknown cases in our dataset remain, therefore, relevant as they provide museums with a starting point for improving their datasets by addressing data gaps that biodiversity researchers have not considered before. While biodiversity researchers usually focus on specimens and inconsistent metadata (e.g. Boakes et al. (2010); Franz and Sterner (2018); Hughes et al. (2024); Maldonado et al. (2015)), our approach offers a tailored solution to contextualize these gaps within historical and colonial frameworks.

There are several mechanisms to expand approaches for addressing the aforementioned data gaps in collection-related biodiversity research. This involves improving metadata consistency, enhancing specimen traceability, and integrating standardized data-sharing practices (Franz and Sterner, 2018; Hughes et al., 2024; Maldonado et al., 2015). However, beyond these technical solutions, there is a need to contextualize such gaps within historical and colonial frameworks to understand their broader implications. By engaging with biodiversity researchers and data providers, future research in the field of data visualization could work toward refining datasets in ways that not only enhance their scientific utility but also uncover hidden biases in data collection and representation (Islam et al., 2022; Weber and Turnhout, 2024). Incorporating colonial histories into data improvement strategies may help museums and researchers acknowledge the socio-political forces that shaped natural history collections. Addressing these gaps through interdisciplinary collaboration with a specific focus on visualization allows for a more holistic understanding of both the scientific and historical significance of these collections (Viola, 2023).

As mentioned, the dates on which each specimen was collected were visualized in a simple interactive timeline. Peaks and declines in registered specimens can easily be detected this way, thus allowing for parallel historical research. The peaks in 1918 and 1920 might be associated with the onset of the idea of 'pure science', which was used to portray the Dutch colonial project as "running a moral and decent colony, generating scientific knowledge untainted by conquest or occupation ideology" (Goss, 2009, p.191). Another peak occurred in 1970 - 1979, which can be explained by the rapid advancements in botany, particularly in orchid biology. Other peaks, though smaller, are distinguishable, such as in 1936 and slightly in 2004. These provide impetus for future research. Drops in the timeline also correlate to specific historical events. In the 1800s, only 1 or 2 specimens were recorded until the 1890s, possibly due to the lack of documentation or interest in the Orchidaceae family of plants. The fall in 1914 - 1915 can be attributed to World War I (Hiepkko, 1987). With World War II alongside the invasion of the Dutch East Indies by the Japanese, rates of occurrences from Indonesia drastically decreased, from 237 specimens recorded in 1939, to 1 recorded in 1945 (Boomgaard, 2008). Other lows can be attributed to other events, such as anti-western and anti-imperial ideologies in the Indonesian government during the 1960-1970s (Boomgaard, 2008).

Moreover, the general interface also allows us to zoom in on specific plant families (Figure 4). Among the species shown in the percentage of traceable families, commercial and traded specimens can be identified. The numbers explained below offer historians and other researchers concrete points of departure for their contextualization of the growth of specimens belonging to specific plant families. Approaching the evolution of the collection's colonial bias through the lens of economically valuable plant families is another area in which our dashboard yields new visual insights. *Rubiaceae*, for instance, most commonly known as coffee, take up the largest percentage of traceable plant families collected in Indonesia and Papua New Guinea. In the early 1880s, the Dutch East Indies was one of the major producers of coffee in the world (Fernando, 2003). Since most of the coffee was exported to the Netherlands, detailed knowledge about coffee plants was essential for colonial administrators and botanists in Europe and insular Southeast Asia (Schoor, 2012).

Orchids also represent an important section, comprising 12,65% of traded species in our dataset. Furthermore, other plants seen in the interface such as *Moraceae* (most commonly known as figs), *Lauraceae* (laurel), *Leguminosae* (legumes and peas), *Myr-*

Figure 4: Percentage of traceable families from all the countries (top) and from Indonesia and Papua New Guinea (bottom).

taceae (clove) and *Meliaceae* (cotton fruits, commonly consumed in South East Asian regions) were collected during colonial times. According to our data, the Naturalis collection entails ca. 20.000 *Moraceae* specimens from Indonesia with a collection peak in 1961. Legumes, peas and other edible plants were also accumulated, particularly between the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, matching the timeline showcased on the interface (Wasino et al., 2017, pp. 265-267). Observing the bottom of Figure 4, *Meliaceae*, most commonly known as neem, was widely traded and forms an important part of the museum's botanical collection. Its consumption took many forms, particularly for "pressed seed oil, mainly used as insecticide, but also for cosmetic, medicinal and agricultural uses" (Sujarwo et al., 2016, p.186). Data with respect to other species, such as *Labiatae* (mint), and *Compositae* (daisies) also show interesting spikes which would require further contextualization. Taken together, the in-depth examination of data related to specific plant families illustrate how the collection's composition was also shaped by economic motives geared towards extracting agricultural resources from areas which fell under Dutch colonial rule.

6 Discussion and Conclusion

This project thus contributes to filling a gap in historical research regarding the colonial legacy of Dutch botanical collections, highlighting the intertwined nature of scientific endeavors and history. Furthermore, it addresses a gap in visualization-oriented digital humanities research by providing a concrete example of how easy-to-use computational techniques can help in understanding the cultural histories of scientific collections in an interactive way, and can thereby help decolonization of natural history collections. Specifically, we have demonstrated how simple and interactive visualizations can help researchers to develop a better understanding of a collection's colonial bias and how this bias has evolved historically (Nelson and Ellis, 2019). Our paper presents an opportunity for natural history museums to make their data more accessible through a user-friendly and visual tool that is easy to deploy and does not consume much computational resources.

Other Dutch museums such as the Wereldmuseum have addressed colonial Dutch history by decolonizing their collections and exhibits.⁵ Their work has shown how addressing colonial history can lead to making collections and exhibitions more inclusive and reflective of diverse cultural histories. Enabling museum visitors and users of scientific collection-related datasets to study colonial provenance acknowledges the colonial biases of natural history collections. Tools such as Power BI play a crucial role in reconnecting datasets to their cultural and historical roots by enabling dynamic visualizations that reveal patterns, biases, and historical trajectories otherwise hidden in raw data. By integrating spatial, temporal, and categorical filters, these tools allow scientists to trace the provenance of specimens, historians to contextualize collection practices within colonial frameworks, and a broader multidisciplinary audience to engage with data through an intuitive interface. The ability to filter by collector, location, time period, *inter alia*, highlights how scientific knowledge production was shaped by historical power dynamics, making the tool particularly useful, i.e. for museum professionals and researchers investigating provenance. At the same time, its accessibility, which does not require specialized coding skills, expands its reach to the general public, fostering greater engagement with the ethical dimensions of natural history collections. By bridging these disciplinary and public divides, Power BI

⁵ See also here: [../why-exhibition-about-our-colonial-inheritance](#), accessed 10 October 2024.

serves as a vital instrument for uncovering, analyzing, and sharing the layered histories embedded within scientific datasets. Thus, our interactive tool links the Netherlands' colonial past with Naturalis' scientific plant collection through multi-layered visualizations. Additionally, it helps researchers to uncover important stories of how the collections have been brought together, contributing to a more nuanced interpretation of their collections' evolution over a longer period. The initial colonial context behind botanical acquisitions set the trajectory for future Dutch botanical endeavors in the various countries, even after they gained independence.

Our dashboards - and our focus on the two former Dutch colonies - allows users to employ a historical lens to reveal dynamic relationships between natural history collection patterns and broader socio-political contexts. Since the interactive visualizations allow natural history collections to be studied in terms of their movement (via the map tool) over time (via the timeline) and allow for detailed analysis (via the metadata filters), it can be used to investigate a range of questions related to the cultural histories of scientific collections. The flexibility it allows the user, its ability to make data more accessible, its potential use in flagging missing data and the clear ability to reveal information that would otherwise be hidden shows that this interactive visualization can best contribute to understanding the cultural histories of scientific collections in a way that static visualizations otherwise would not. As depicted, the visualization tool enhances the collections' accessibility through visual reading, with the potential to reveal insights otherwise hidden and uncover data-related concerns. The tool thus aids biologists and those interested in tracing the provenance, geographical spread of natural objects in collections and the ethics of obtaining these specimens in the context of colonial power asymmetries.

However, certain limitations remain. Firstly, this study focuses solely on the botany subsection of Naturalis, leaving the broader applicability of our approach to the entire natural history collection untested, particularly in terms of merging multiple datasets and assessing Power BI's scalability. Due to the scope of this research, we were unable to evaluate the generalization of our experiment by incorporating additional large datasets, an avenue we intend to explore in future work. Expanding this approach to include datasets from different institutions would provide a more thorough assessment of Power BI's ability to handle larger and more diverse data sources. While the platform is well-suited for structured data visualization, its performance may be challenged by increased data volume and variability, potentially necessitating extensive preprocessing or alternative tools for optimal scalability. Future research should examine how integrating datasets from various natural history museums, each with distinct formats and metadata standards, influences the visualization process while ensuring that insights into colonial biases remain clear and accessible. Secondly, since the Naturalis botany dataset originates from the GBIF platform, adjustments may be required to accommodate datasets from other institutions, as formatting conventions are unlikely to align seamlessly. Lastly, leveraging Power BI for such visualizations may demand significant data preprocessing, which could present a barrier for users with limited data management skills.

Nonetheless, this visualization tool provides a starting point for tracing the histories of any museum collection, provided they have the data. The *recordedBy* metadata, for instance - through which explorations and records made by botanists can be tracked and mapped - is an interesting starting point to understand the specific acquisition histories of certain specimens. For example, Carl Ludwig Blume - whose records show that 95,77% of the specimens he recorded belong to Indonesia (see Figure 5)

Figure 5: General Interface with the Recorded By filter set to Blume CL, showing that the majority of specimens he recorded came from Indonesia.

- is a relevant finding, indicating the Dutch botanical connection to their colonies. Blume was the founder of 's Rijksherbarium (National Herbarium), an institutional predecessor of what is now museum Naturalis. The sheer amount of orchids taken from Indonesia by a single researcher is also an interesting finding in itself, opening a Pandora's box of other insightful questions. Thus, the scope of such a tool can undoubtedly be extended to address other questions of contemporary relevance. While in the nineteenth century, orchids were primarily seen as scientific study objects and luxury products from the East and West Indies, they are now a globally traded horticultural commodity whose presence in almost every European household has severe environmental consequences (Soode et al., 2015).

7 Data Access

The Power BI file used for this paper can be downloaded through Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13958314>.

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Small-Scale Testing on Generative AI and Post-OCR Correction in Historical Datasets

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1. Introduction

Recent developments in large language models (LLMs) and generative AI (GenAI) chatbots such as Chat-GPT, Google Bard (now Gemini), and YouChat (Brown et al., 2020; Chaka, 2023; Manyika and Hsiao, 2023) have fostered new types of interaction that can lower the barrier in human-machine communication through conversation in natural languages. We assume that such chatbots may be able to act as conversational assistants in tasks that otherwise require more complex processing to improve the results produced by simpler or earlier, less accurate techniques. This article proposes a set of small-scale tests with GenAI chatbots on post-OCR correction in historical datasets. It illustrates, through examples of responses obtained from GenAI agents integrated into post-OCR correction and assessment tasks, what types of challenges should be addressed in this context when working with historical datasets.

Previous studies have shown that OCR errors in input data can have a non-negligible impact on downstream language processing, such as sentence segmentation, named entity recognition (NER), topic modelling, word embedding, sentiment analysis and information retrieval (Nguyen et al., 2022; Strien et al., 2020). Therefore, various methods have been envisaged to tackle this problem, including post-OCR detection and correction of errors. Recent surveys classified these methods into manual and (semi-)automatic, isolated-word and context-dependent types, and emphasised the trend in the development of neural network- and context-based approaches (Nguyen et al., 2022). Other enquires focused on the use of machine learning techniques to automatically estimate text quality and select candidates for OCR rerun within cultural institutions that deal with lower quality historical data (Schneider and Maurer, 2022). On the other hand, studies on post-OCR error detection and correction investigated the use of large language models in this type of tasks. For example, pre-trained language models from the GPT-2 family were tested on datasets of English books and texts from post-OCR competitions by combining multiple OCR versions of an object and choosing the best-scored option, with the goal of reducing the number of errors (Gupta et al., 2021). Tests with other models, such as Llama 2, and a corpus of 19th century British newspapers containing aligned excerpts of machine and manual transcriptions, were also performed to assess the ability of prompt-based approaches to detect and correct OCR errors (Thomas et al., 2024). The performance of generative LLMs in post-OCR

correction tasks was also examined by conducting experiments with GenAI agents such as ChatGPT-4, ChatGPT-4o, Claude 2.1, and Gemini 1.0 Pro and comparing their outputs when exposed to historical datasets in different languages and various types of prompt (Bang, 2024).

While these studies were generally based on the investigation of larger text collections, our set of tests explored the potential of using GenAI agents in post-OCR correction from a small-scale perspective. This involved the analysis of a use case and particular examples, with the aim of identifying potential categories of challenges and drawing a generic pipeline that may serve as a preliminary testbed for larger-scale applications. We assumed that early identification of challenges and prompt calibration scenarios from small-scale tests can eventually guide further developments. This type of enquiry was part of a larger project that used word embedding results (neighbour lists) and citations extracted from a selection of historical French monographs (1690-1918).¹ These extracts were integrated into a multilingual diachronic collection of interconnected terms expressed in RDF-XML, following a linguistic linked open data (LLOD) model (Armaselu et al., 2024).² In this context, the need for OCR correction of neighbour lists and citations has been identified. The article presents the applied methodology and its results in Section 2. Section 3 is dedicated to a discussion of the findings followed by a conclusion and remarks on future work in Section 4.

2. Methodology and results

The examples presented below were produced using three chatbots, ChatGPT-4, Google Bard, and YouChat, which were selected based on availability via subscription and free accounts and on reports considering them among the top AI chatbots (Davis, 2023). The conversations were intended to identify potential problems in the lists of neighbours of the word *révolution* extracted from the French monograph dataset by time slice, such as OCR errors (Table 1). The three chatbots were also asked to provide confidence levels for their corrections (in percentage).³

More complex prompts included several exchanges with the GenAI agent (ChatGPT-4) when asking for OCR error identification in citations extracted from the corpus corresponding to a given sense of the word *révolution* (Figure 1). Information about the origin of the excerpts, that is, French historical texts and their publication year or period, was also included in the prompts. Figure 1 (right) shows the OCR-ed text that was sent to ChatGPT-4 for correction.

Following this preliminary testing phase, a small-scale assessment of ChatGPT-4 was also performed using test and gold standard excerpts from the ICDAR 2017 competition on post-OCR text correction (Chiron et al., 2017; Rigaud et al., 2019) that included English and French monographs and periodicals from 1654 to 1934. The fragment contained 50 sentences from a text by Montesquieu, *Arsace et Isménie*, published in 1783, chosen to be close to the publication date of the text shown in Figure 1. Both the test fragment and the gold standard were extracted from the ICDAR2017 dataset of French monographs.⁴

¹ The MONOGRAPH TEXT PACK from the BnL Open Data Collection. <https://data.bn1.lu/data/historical-newspapers/> (accessed 10 February 2025).

² The LLODIA model is available at: <https://github.com/nexuslinguarum/LLODIA>.

³ The chatbot confidence levels were considered as indicative, especially in cases when the agent changed its response in its interaction with the user. More research is needed to evaluate this type of chatbot self-assessment.

⁴ <https://sites.google.com/view/icdar2017-postcorrectionocr/dataset> (accessed 10

Table 1: Identifying OCR errors. Prompt: Please try to identify the words that may be due to OCR errors in the following list: *vandalisme, insurrection, insurgé, confédération, lirnbourg, évolution, vindépendance, holstein, usurper, exéquatour*.

Chatbot	Interaction date	Answer excerpts	Chatbot confidence
ChatGPT-4	15.12.2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • confédération - Possible Correction: "confédération" (confederation) • lirnbourg - Possible Correction: "Limbourg" (Limburg) • évolution - Possible Correction: "révolution" (revolution) • vindépendance - Possible Correction: "indépendance" (independence) 	85% 80% 95% 90%
Bard	18.12.2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • confédération - confédération • lirnbourg - Luxembourg • évolution - évolution • vindépendance - indépendance 	100% 95% 90% 80%
YouChat	16.12.2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "lirnbourg" to "Limbourg" • "évolution" to "révolution" • "vindépendance" to "indépendance" 	60% 80% 90%

ChatGPT-4 was asked to correct the first 50 sentences of the test fragment that was supposed to contain OCR errors. Then, it was asked to compare the initial and corrected texts with the corresponding gold standard (GS), to calculate the character error rate (CER), word error rate (WER) (Abadie et al., 2022), and the corresponding accuracy values.⁵

Figure 1: Extract (Rosset, 1789, p. 13): a) image; b) OCR-ed text (French).

Table 2 shows two iterations of this process, since it was observed that ChatGPT-4 had a tendency to correct historical word forms in French, and additional prompting was necessary to prevent this type of change.⁶ For comparison, the CER and WER

February 2025). The first 50 sentences were extracted from the full dataset, fr_monograph sub-folder, file 8.txt. Some preparations were necessary, for example to remove the symbol '@' from the excerpts, which was used in the competition for alignment at the character level. The sentences were also manually separated, one per line, and numbered from 1 to 50 to facilitate the interpretation of the results.

⁵ This was done by subtraction of the error rates from 100.

⁶ ChatGPT-4 was selected for this type of task since it allowed downloading the files corresponding to the various versions to be compared. Due to instability in results and reported errors by the GenAI agent, the calculation of the CER and WER values was repeated several times (on 31.01.2024, 07.02.2024,

Table 2: ChatGPT-4 CER, WER (with jiwer references and P, R, Fm) and examples (ICDAR 2017 excerpts).

Test excerpts, ICDAR and ChatGPT-4 corrected versions after iteration 1 and 2	Interaction date	CER, P, R, Fm	WER, P, R, Fm	Chatbot confidence	Differences in the analysed text / GS
OCR_toInput_Arsace_et_Isménie_1783 (ICDAR test fragment to be denoised, 983 tokens)	03.05.2024	1.22% 1.38% (<i>jiwer</i>) P = 0.98 R = 0.99 Fm = 0.99	6.68% 7.55% (<i>jiwer</i>) P = 0.92 R = 0.94 Fm = 0.93	95%	“.on” / “son” “pres-que” / “presque” “Ambassadeurs,” / “Ambassadeurs,”
ChatGPT-4_Corr1_Arsace_et_Isménie_1783 (ICDAR test fragment after correction 1 by ChatGPT-4, 980 tokens)	03.05.2024	5.44% 5.15% (<i>jiwer</i>) P = 0.95 R = 0.97 Fm = 0.96	18.22% 18.01% (<i>jiwer</i>) P = 0.83 R = 0.84 Fm = 0.83	95%	“règne” / “regne” “d’Artamène,” / d’Artamene,” “laissant” / “laissa” “désirait” / “desiroit”
ChatGPT-4_Corr2_Arsace_et_Isménie_1783 (ICDAR test fragment after correction 2 by ChatGPT-4, 977 tokens)	03.05.2024	3.23% 3.00% (<i>jiwer</i>) P = 0.97 R = 0.99 Fm = 0.98	12.63% 12.31% (<i>jiwer</i>) P = 0.88 R = 0.89 Fm = 0.88	95%	“règne” / “regne” “d’Artamène,” / “d’Artamene,” “et” / “1” “âme” / “ame”

values (in italics) were computed independently by a program that we have written for this purpose and that used the Python library *jiwer*.⁷

For each of the three analysed texts, we used the sentence alignments and number of hits or correct items (H), substitutions (S), deletions (D) and insertions (I) provided as output by the *jiwer*-based program. With these values, we computed more general evaluation metrics, precision (P), recall (R), and F-measure (Fm), corresponding to the two types of error calculated at the character and word level. The formulae for calculating P, R and Fm were inspired by general approach descriptions (Abadie et al., 2022; Karpinski et al., 2018; Morris et al., 2004) and adapted to our task and data as detailed below,⁸

$$P = H / (H + S + I) \quad (1)$$

$$R = H / (H + S + D) \quad (2)$$

$$Fm = 2PR / (P + R) \quad (3)$$

where P is the number of hits divided by the total items in the hypothesis (text to

02.05.2024 and 03.05.2024). The last results, which seemed more stable and closer to the *jiwer*-calculated values, were included in the table.

⁷ <https://jitsi.github.io/jiwer/> (accessed 10 February 2025).

⁸ The values presented in Table 2 were computed in Excel using the information collected manually from the output files of the Python program, and formulae 1-3.

be assessed), R is the number of hits divided by the total items in the reference (GS), and F_m is the harmonic mean of P and R .

3. Discussion

A qualitative analysis of the chatbot's responses for the first task (Table 1) indicates that the three AI agents were quite successful in identifying possible errors. The word similarly identified by all the chatbots was "vindépendance", while slight differences in agreement can be observed for the other words. ChatGPT-4 agreed with Bard on "confération" and with YouChat on "lirnbourg", while Bard and YouChat agreed on "éévolution". Additional prompting was needed to remind Bard that corrected words should be provided in French (A: Table 4), since the proposed corrections were initially expressed in English. This behaviour was not observed for the other two agents that provided the answers directly in French (YouChat) or in French with English translations (ChatGPT-4).

When the prompt included more details about specific types of error, such as the use of elongated 's' in older texts, often confused by the OCR software with the letter 'f', the chatbots were able to propose plausible corrections. For example, YouChat after first proposing 'fantastic' as a correction of 'fuppofant', re-examined it in favour of the form "supposant" (confidence 70%) (A: Table 5) and re-assessed the level assigned to the initial choice "fantastic" (confidence 40%). ChatGPT-4 identified the correct form "supposant" (confidence 95%) and explained that in this case the long 's' was probably misinterpreted as 'f' in the OCR process.⁹

More complex prompts included several exchanges when asking for error identification in citations extracted from the corpus corresponding to a given sense of the word révolution (Figure 1). Although errors such as "platune" instead of "platine", "jufque pardeffus" instead of "jusque pardessus", or "fert" instead of "sert" were easily identified (confidence 90%), the form "chaufée" was more difficult to analyse and required additional prompting. After asking ChatGPT-4 to reconsider the form to take into account the elongated 's' issue, the context "roue de chauffée" and the possibility that it may refer to clock making in the 18th century, the chatbot proposed the correction "roue de chaussée", with "'chaussée' potentially referring to a part or a process in the clock's mechanism" (confidence 75%) (A: Table 6). Other difficulties consisted in preventing corrections of possible historical word usages, which were not due to OCR errors, such as "moyene", "engrenne", "afrotement" and their transformation into modern forms (A: Table 7). It can be noted that in response to prompts related to the historical use of certain words, the agent proposed plausible corrections, accompanied by explanations of the most likely modern forms, their English translations, and potential contextualisation from a historical point of view.

The same issue related to historical forms was observed when comparing the corrected ChatGPT-4 version with the ICDAR 2017 gold standard (Table 2). The lowest error and highest values of P , R , and F_m correspond to the ICDAR test fragment. For the two iterations using ChatGPT-4, the error rate decreased and the P , R , F_m increased for correction 2 as compared with correction 1 after the use of specific prompts indicating that historical forms should be preserved.¹⁰ Regarding ICDAR 2017 results, (Chiron et al., 2017) reported that the best performing method of the competition in

⁹ Google Bard was not tested for this particular form.

¹⁰ Example of such prompt: *Please try to correct only the clear OCR errors, such as misrecognised characters and incorrect word splits, while retaining the historical French forms, such as "reposito", "faudroit".*

terms of F-measure (Fm 0.55, P 0.51, R 0.59) for historical French monographs was WFST-PostOCR based on weighted finite-state edit transducers and bigram language models derived from the Google Books Ngram Corpus. The values shown in Table 2 for these measures and the texts we analysed are much higher. However, it should be considered that the sample used in the French monograph competition counted 32274 tokens with an average character error rate of 5%, higher than the text size and initial error rate from our small-scale test. These evaluation measures were calculated for task 1 (error detection), in which the competition participants were asked to provide only the position and length of the alleged erroneous tokens in the raw OCR-ed text, which differs from our full correction task.¹¹ Therefore, these values are not directly comparable with our figures, but may be used as indicative reference points. It should also be noted that some inaccuracies in the GS itself were reported by ICDAR participants, according to the article cited. Such inaccuracies can be observed as well in Table 2 (column 6) that shows some diacritics missing from the GS version while they are properly rendered in the ChatGPT-4 corrections.

An additional test was performed to compare the texts corrected by ChatGPT-4 with a more modern version (1876) (MD) of the fragment from *Arsace et Isménie*.¹² The calculated CER and WER values using jiwer for the GPT-corrected texts using this text as a reference¹³ were higher compared to the values based on the gold standard in Table 2. Thus, MD-based rates compared to GS-based rates computed via jiwer showed an increase of 0.37% in CER and 2.35% in WER for correction 1, and respectively 2.41% in CER and 10.56% in WER for correction 2. This was surprising since given the agent's tendency to modernize the word forms, a closer resemblance with the MD version and lower error rates based on the comparison with it were expected. Some mismatches between the GenAI corrections and the reference versions were due to the use of different types of punctuation marks (e.g., straight vs. curly apostrophes, colon, semicolon and comma used differently) and capitalisation (e.g., Reine vs. reine). A closer look at the differences also showed that the ChatGPT-4 corrections not only targeted presumed OCR errors, but sometimes involved changing the order of words or rephrasing.¹⁴ These findings align with recent studies reporting that GenAI agents, such as ChatGPT-4, ChatGPT-4o, Claude 2.1, and Gemini 1.0 Pro, show a certain tendency towards oversimplification or modernisation when applied to post-OCR correction of historical texts, which may impact the degree of accuracy and fidelity of the corrections as compared with the original content (Bang, 2024, pp. 40, 46).

Table 3 summarises the categories of differences observed between the versions

¹¹ ICDAR 2017 also included task 2 (correction of OCR errors) in which the participants were asked to provide a ranked list of replacement candidates for each error detected during task 1. The official metric for this second task consisted of the improvement rates with respect to the weighted sum of the Levenshtein distances between the correction candidates and the corresponding token in the GS, considered in fully- and semi-automated scenarios (Chiron et al., 2017).

¹² https://fr.wikisource.org/wiki/Arsace_et_Ism%C3%A9nie (accessed 10 February 2025).

¹³ MD reference, ChatGPT-4 correction 1 (5.52% CER and 20.36% WER); correction 2 (5.41% CER and 22.87% WER).

¹⁴ For instance, "Il écrivait à la Reine les lettres les plus tendres du monde" (corr. 1) vs. "Il écrivait à la Reine les lettres du monde les plus tendres" (GS, corr. 2) vs. "Il écrivait à la reine les lettres du monde les plus tendres" (MD); "Elle descendit de son char et entra dans le temple" (corr. 1) vs. "Elle descendit de son char, entra dans le temple" (GS, corr. 2) vs. "Elle descendit de son char, et entra dans le temple" (MD); "il cherchait l'étranger et le trouva plongé dans une affreuse tristesse" (corr. 1) vs. "il cherchoit l'étranger, il le trouva dans une affreuse tristesse" (GS) vs. "il cherchoit l'étranger, et le trouva dans une affreuse tristesse" (corr. 2) vs. "il cherchait l'étranger, et il le trouva dans une affreuse tristesse" (MD).

Table 3: Diff examples classified by ChatGPT-4o and its confidence levels (07.10.2024).

Diff category	Examples (GS / ChatGPT-4_Corr1)	Chatbot confidence
Punctuation	*Soyez mon ami*, lui dit-il, *puisque vous êtes malheureux.* / "Soyez mon ami", lui dit-il, "puisque vous êtes malheureux."	95%
Orthography	Cette entrée fut singuliere. / Cette entrée fut singulière.	85%
Paraphrasing	Ce Prince mourut accablé d'ennuis, laissa** son trône à sa fille Isménie. / Ce Prince mourut accablé d'ennuis, laissant son trône à sa fille Isménie.	85%
Modernisation, orthography, syntax/structure	Il menoit avec lui tout ce qui étoit propre à un appareil de nôces **des danseurs, des joueurs d'instruments, des farceurs, des cuisiniers, des eunuques, des femmes il menoit avec lui une formidable armée. / Il menait avec lui tout ce qui était propre à un appareil de noces : des danseurs, des joueurs d'instruments, des farceurs, des cuisiniers, des eunuques, des femmes, ** *e***t***** une formidable armée.	90%

corrected by ChatGPT-4 and the two references (GS and MD).¹⁵ To compile the table, we used the output files of the Python program for CER and WER computing, which contained character-level alignments for pairs of aligned sentences between the compared versions, and difference markers (for substitution, insertion, deletion).

We prompted ChatGPT-4o, with the diff files attached to the prompts, to assist in classifying the sentence pairs according to six categories of differences. As illustrated in the table, the analysed sentences can belong to single or multiple categories. The diff categories were defined as follows: *spacing* (differences in missing or extra-spaces between characters or words), *punctuation* (use of different punctuation marks), *orthography* (differences at the character level, such as diacritics or minor spelling variations in a word form), *modernisation* (replacement of older word forms by modern equivalents), *paraphrasing* (use of different words or phrases intended to convey a similar meaning), *syntax/structure* (changes in sentence structure through word insertion, deletion or reordering). This type of analysis can draw paths for further enquiry regarding the use of GenAI technology in two different types of tasks, post-OCR correction and modernisation of historical texts. While some changes can be imagined as potential ingredients of a modernisation pipeline, others should be prevented by explicit specifications included in the prompts to preserve the original forms as much as possible.

Based on these observations, we argue that GenAI-based workflows for post-OCR correction should include preliminary small-scale testing and prompt calibration to enable early identification of accuracy issues and their potential solutions. Figure 2

¹⁵ The experiment involved several iterations with ChatGPT-4o for the refinement of the categories and classification of sentence pairs according to these categories. Four files were attached to the prompts to be analysed. They contained aligned sentences at the character level for the ChatGPT-4_Corr1 and ChatGPT-4_Corr2 as compared with the GS and MD versions. Some simplifications were applied to the categories proposed by ChatGPT-4o to avoid category overlapping. The character "*" was used by the Python program for alignment, in case of differences between sentences.

Figure 2: Generic pipeline for small-scale testing of GenAI post-OCR correction.

illustrates a generic pipeline that considers both the preservation and modernisation branches, taking into account the various types of OCR errors due to misinterpretation of letters, specific or older fonts, print quality, etc., and the categories of differences between the original and corrected text resulting from the particularities of the generative AI technology.

One of the typical emergent abilities of large language models, which are not present in smaller pre-trained models, is in-context learning. Compared to fine-tuning that implies adaptation of a model to a specific task by training it on a tailored dataset and updating its weights, or to retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) that combines information retrieval and domain-relevant knowledge bases, in-context learning involves the use of zero-, one- or few-shot learning including in the prompts task descriptions with or without examples, and no update of the model parameters (Brown et al., 2020; Li, 2023; Zhao et al., 2024). While various fine-tuning and RAG techniques are available (Parthasarathy et al., 2024), in-context learning may represent an approach that is potentially interesting to explore for tasks such as LLM-based post-OCR correction. Recent multilingual benchmarks have shown both promise and challenges in applying LLMs in zero- and few-shot settings to post-OCR correction of historical datasets (Boros et al., 2024; Kanerva et al., 2025), some of them similar to observations presented in this paper (e.g., tendency of the models to overcorrect and paraphrase). The decision on which of these categories of adaptation techniques to choose also depends on the complexity of the project and the budget allocated to it. Although the utility of large-scale benchmarking is undeniable, small-scale testing, including data preparation, processing, and evaluation, and iterative prompt tuning, can prove its usefulness as a faster and cheaper way of identifying categories of problems from the outset, suggesting directions for adaptation, further investigation, or assessment aligned with existing standards, that may inform the design of subsequent larger-scale phases or applications.

4. Conclusion and Future Work

The article proposes a small-scale investigation on the use of GenAI agents in post-OCR correction workflows for historical datasets. Although preliminary results show a certain potential for this type of technology in solving tasks in this category, more tests are necessary to assess the capacity to respond to specially conceived prompts for historical text processing. In particular, it was shown that the agents have a tendency to replace historical forms with more modern ones, to reformulate whole phrases,

or to change word order and punctuation. Specific instructions should be devised to prevent these forms of modification. However, building modernised layers for documents with old spelling may be considered a possibly interesting application in tasks such as the transformation of older texts to be read by modern users or computer programs.

Another potential challenge resides in a certain degree of instability observed in computing character and word error rates (CER, WER). This indicates that comparing the GenAI values with independently computed results using programming languages such as Python or R should be envisaged. The study was limited to interactions with three agents that involved the use of online platforms, while the integration of this type of technology into larger-scale pipelines would require more code-oriented or batch processing solutions that need to be further examined. Future work can include additional testing with other GenAI agents, open-source large language models in a programming environment, datasets in other languages, and further enquiry about the application of these technologies in post-OCR correction for historical and digital humanities research. Although limited in scope, it may be argued that small-scale testing of the kind presented in this paper can serve as a pilot phase in the pipeline, that allows for early identification of problems, synthesis of observations, assessment, and articulation of hypotheses for further testing or potential solutions, which can inform the design of subsequent larger-scale phases in the workflow or applications.

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A. Appendix

Table 4: Prompt and response excerpts, reminding the language (Google Bard, 18.12.2023).

User	GenAI agent (Bard)
Please try to identify the words that may be due to OCR errors in the following list and assign a confidence level in percentage to each proposed correction. The words are in French and the corrections should also be in French. ...	Sure, here are the words in the list that may be due to OCR errors, along with proposed corrections and confidence levels: ... confération confédération 100% ...

Table 5: Prompt and response excerpts, "supposant" (YouChat, 16.12.2023).

User	GenAI agent (YouChat)
Would your decision be different if you consider that usually elongated 's' in older texts is producing OCR errors, such as considering 'f' instead of 's'?	Considering the possibility of an OCR error substituting "f" for elongated "s" is indeed a relevant factor to consider. Given this information, the potential correct form for the word "fuppofant" might indeed be "supposant" if we consider the substitution of "s" with "f" due to OCR errors in older texts. Taking this into account, the corrected potential form for "fuppofant" could be "supposant" instead of "fantastic." ...

Table 6: Prompt and response excerpts, "roue de chaussée" (ChatGPT-4, 15.12.2023).

User	GenAI agent (ChatGPT-4)
Can you please reanalyze the word "chauffée" given the context "roue de chauffée" and the fact that the text refers to clock making in the 18th century?	In the context of clockmaking during the 18th century, the term "chauffée" in "roue de chauffée" could be a historical or technical term related to the mechanism of a clock. Considering the OCR misinterpretation of long 's' as 'f', and given the clockmaking context, the term could be "roue de chaussée", with "chaussée" potentially referring to a part or a process in the clock's mechanism. However, without specific knowledge of 18th-century clockmaking terminology, it's difficult to ascertain the exact term. "Roue de chauffée" could refer to a heated part or a wheel that is treated in a particular way, but this seems less likely in the context of mechanical clockwork where terms like "chaussée" do not clearly fit. Considering this, a more likely correction would be "roue de chaussée" if "chaussée" is a term used in the context of clock mechanics at the time. However, if "chauffée" is not due to an OCR error and is actually a correct transcription of the original text, it might require specialized historical knowledge to interpret accurately. Based on common French usage and the potential for an OCR error, "roue de chaussée" could be a plausible correction with a medium to high confidence level, but without specific expertise in historical clockmaking terminology, I cannot provide a definitive correction.

Table 7: Prompt and response excerpts, "afrotement", "engrenne" (ChatGPT-4, 15.12.2023)

User	GenAI agent (ChatGPT-4)
<p>Do you have any information about the word "afrotement", in the text "tige entre afrotement dur", and its possible usage in French in the 18th century? Same question for "engrenne", in "ce pignon engrenne". It is possible that these are historical usages that should be kept in the transcription of the text. The goal is to correct just the errors that may be due to OCR misinterpretation.</p>	<p>In the 18th century, French language and spelling were less standardized than they are today, and many words could have various spellings or be spelled according to phonetics. With this in mind:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Afrotement: The correct modern French word is "frottement," which means "friction." It is plausible that "afrotement" is a historical spelling or a typographical error in the original text. If "afrotement" is not an OCR misinterpretation, it could be an archaic spelling of "frottement" that was used at the time. This would be especially true in the context of clock mechanisms where friction is an important concept. • Engrenne: The modern French word "engrène" comes from the verb "engrener," which means "to mesh" or "to engage," as gears do in a clock. "Engrenne" could be an old conjugation or spelling of the verb. If "engrenne" is correctly transcribed, it may not be an OCR error but rather a historical usage that should be preserved in the text. ...

Uncovering Interwar Comics: The Challenge of Labeling Graphics in Belgian Weekly Magazines

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Comics in Belgian weekly magazines remain understudied due to their fragmentary presence and the challenges of retrieval within large periodical collections. While comics are crucial artifacts of visual culture, their marginal status in general-interest magazines and their multimodal nature hinder both their discoverability and scholarly analysis. This article addresses the need for systematic identification of comics in mass-digitized archives by developing a semi-automatic detection workflow grounded in computer vision and object detection techniques. Drawing on a representative corpus of six general-interest illustrated magazines published in Belgium between 1934 and 1940, the study applies a distant viewing approach using YOLO models to detect and label comics alongside related visual categories such as cartoons, photographs, and advertisements. The methodology combines expert-driven annotation, collaborative labeling with weighted majority voting, and model evaluation to fine-tune visual classification. Our results highlight the conceptual and technical complexities of defining comics computationally, the importance of contextual metadata, and the benefits of hierarchical and iterative model training. The proposed workflow not only enhances access to hidden visual materials in historical magazines but also contributes to broader discussions on the remediation of cultural heritage collections and the role of computational methods in comics studies.

Keywords: Historical Comics, Object Detection, Computer Vision, Periodical Studies, Distant Viewing, Visual Culture

1 Introduction

Comics are important objects of study for understanding visual culture. The emergence of broad-audience illustrated magazines in the late 19th century arguably transformed visual culture and thus the vehicle for disseminating comics. However, only recently have magazines and periodical media been a focus of comic studies, favoring more permanently available and visible formats to piece together comic histories (Brinker et al., 2022; Letourneux and Verilhac, 2025)¹. Comics make up only a small portion of the varied and heterogeneous contents of such mass-market magazines, complicating their retrieval.

The core issues for understanding the place and function of comics within periodicals, even with increasingly available digital collections, remain those of identification, accessibility, and archival visibility. The new opportunities and challenges raised by mass-digitization programs for cultural and media histories are well-known namely: if online repositories have radically altered the means of accessing and exploring archival sources, they nevertheless echo (in a different tone) the same issues of selection and erasure that bear on analogue archives (Bunout et al., 2023). The increased availability of digitized collections, as Patrick Leary famously argued in a 2005 piece on the impact of online archives on periodicals research, also produces and maintains an “offline penumbra [...] that increasingly remote and unvisited shadowland into which even quite important texts fall if they cannot yet be explored, or perhaps even identified, by any electronic means” (Leary, 2005). As Pierre-Carl Langlais suggests, “the main stake today is to develop ways of making visible what has been hidden or excluded from the historical indexing systems” (Langlais, 2021)². With the amount of archival data exponentially increasing, the issue of the digital divide has gradually shifted from the ‘what’ to the ‘how’: how to facilitate and enhance accessibility and findability within such massive corpora? How to navigate online collections beyond textual characteristics (e.g. keyword search)?

Against this background, identifying comics in magazines brings up important issues: not only because comics make up an often overlooked and neglected corpus, but also because their identification and indexing within digitized collections is particularly complex due to their multimodal and intermedial features. Manually browsing these analogue magazines would be too time-consuming and would reduce the research to a small corpus better suited for close-reading. Working with the digitized corpus, a text-based keyword search also falls short: many comics feature no text captions or titles, and text in comics is more often than not handwritten, making Optical Character Recognition (OCR) of little use for that specific purpose. In this context, it becomes essential to turn to image-based computational models as a means to identify comics in these magazines.

This research reflects on an attempt and proposes a method for semi-automatic detection of comics with the support of computer vision workflows. Specifically we investigate this method on a corpus of digitized facsimile images of mass-market illustrated weekly magazines published in Belgium during the interwar period, as part of the ARTPRESSE project at Royal Library of Belgium (KBR) (Lemmers et al., 2023). The ARTPRESSE project centered on the representation of fine arts in general-audience

¹ The focus in comics histories has moreover mostly lied on comics magazines and periodicals that feature a significant portion of comics material (children’s magazines, but also comics magazines for adults, for instance); rather than on the publication of comics within general-audience and multi-subject magazines.

² All translations are ours, unless otherwise indicated.

magazines, and it has made an extensive corpus of general-interest magazines digitally available. The place and function of comics in general-audience weeklies is an important blind spot in histories of comics in Belgium, and which remain extremely patchy in their account of the interwar period (Paques, 2011). The interwar indeed marks a fluctuating period where various models of comics and graphic narratives coexist across different formats (such as broadsheet newspapers, children’s magazines, woodcut novels), with the 1930s as a crucial decade for the “breakthrough” of comics in the press (Lefèvre, 2009). This rich corpus offers many more possible avenues of inquiry in terms of historical research and further allows for new computational approaches to grasp with its volume. The underlying research for this article thus participates in a further remediation of these digitized magazines following in the approach to “collections as data” (Padilla et al., 2023) and ultimately, in the stage of the project, aims to produce a dataset based on a single genre within these periodicals.³ This article thus is a mid-stage reflection on the preliminary results and the identification of a workflow to identify comics within a selected corpus of mass-market magazines. This is explained in detail from the corpus, the proposed computer vision workflow used to detect, label and extract comics from the ARTPRESSE corpus, and thereby considers the conceptual and technical challenges for image classification raised by graphic material in such magazines.

2 Theoretical Framework

2.1 Computational Approaches: From Text to Object detection

Traditionally, computer vision methods for historical sources have largely focused on the extraction of text (Bhatt et al., 2021; Paaß and Konya, 2011) using both Optical Character Recognition (OCR) for printed sources and Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) for handwritten sources. These advancements made it possible for maps, letters, books, and more to be transcribed at continuously larger scales (Nockels et al., 2024). OCR was quickly embedded within most display interfaces and access platforms for cultural heritage materials, making text-based search and data mining the most common operations. In the last decade, the introduction of deep-learning algorithms has nevertheless allowed for the development of new approaches that more fully account for images and illustrations in large digitized archives. Melvin Wevers and Thomas Smits, among others, have argued for a “visual digital turn”, suggesting that convolutional neural networks (CNNs) “open up a new world of intuitive and serendipitous exploration of the visual side of digital archives.” (Wevers and Smits, 2020)

Computational approaches to comics reflect those trends in digital humanities. OCR technology has contributed to direct efforts towards transcribing text balloons (Baskaran and Devi, 2023; Guo et al., 2006). Some recent and notable research includes Soykan, Yuret and Sezgin who showed that training newer OCR models, combined with segmentation techniques and pre/post-processing methods, significantly improves the accuracy of text detection within text balloons (Soykan et al., 2022). Hiroe and Hotta used OCR to find exclamation points in text balloons with the idea of enabling the detection of scene changes and providing a rough under-

³ The present project thus follows in the footsteps and draws inspiration from previous research aiming to automatically retrieve information such as literary feuillets from KBR’s newspaper collections (Ali et al., 2024)

standing of comics content, as exclamation marks often indicate intense moments in the story (Hiroe and Hotta, 2017). Such approaches, however, lead to neglect both the multimodal and intermedial features of comics, as a medium combining text and image and in which the visual properties of text are also key aspects (Miodrag, 2013). Computational approaches in comics are importantly faced with medium- or field-specific hurdles. Even though contemporary comics are increasingly available as “big data” in their current digital economy (Manouach, 2024), there are few readily available research-based datasets for comics: their constitution often follows quite specific aims and targets but they do form a helpful benchmark (Laubrock and Dunst, 2020)

The concept of “Distant Viewing” was introduced by Arnold and Tilton as a theoretical framework for analyzing large visual corpora: “Distant viewing responds to the need for a theory of how computer vision algorithms serve as a means of analysis to study visual materials, and can account for the ways that these algorithms mediate the interpretation of digital images” (Arnold and Tilton, 2023). The framework integrates theories from visual semiotics, photography, and computer vision to establish a code system that translates visual elements into a format suitable for large-scale analysis. Distant viewing relies on algorithms to automatically detect and categorize objects, colors, shapes, and other visual features in images. These extracted elements are then aggregated and analyzed to identify patterns, trends, and relationships that might not be apparent through close examination of individual images (Arnold and Tilton, 2023). The theory and method has been applied to a range of visual media from historical photographs to television sitcoms - and even newspaper comic strips as in their analysis of the 50-year long run of *Peanuts* daily comic strips (Arnold et al., 2023).

Comics further require taking into account multiple factors when developing tools for computational analysis depending on research aims (Laubrock and Dunst, 2020). Those can cover a wide span between empirical cognitive approaches to comics reading (often relying on eye-tracking technology; see for instance (Baroni and Aydemir, 2022; Dunst et al., 2018)) and data-led histories of comics in particular cultural contexts; impinged on the construction of well-curated datasets to track changes across a particular period or to map a transmedial network (see for instance (Dunst, 2023; Hibbett, 2024)).

The introduction of deep learning algorithms, rapidly advancing since 2013, has opened up for new possibilities in computer vision that could ultimately prove to be a game-changer for computational approaches to visual materials and can be particularly useful for detecting and classifying comics material within digitized archives. The first of these advancements was made with the emergence of two-stage object detection. In essence, two-stage object detectors first propose regions in an image where an object may be located. In the second stage, these regions are further refined and classified, determining the precise location and category of the object. Some years later, another advancement was made when the first *YOLO* (*You Only Look Once*) algorithm was introduced (Redmon et al., 2015), which performed the two individual stages at the same time. These algorithms directly predict bounding boxes and class probabilities (Zou et al., 2019). One-stage detectors offer great advantages in terms of speed, enabling real-time object detection and simpler training processes. However, they are slightly less accurate than two-stage detectors, particularly in cases involving small objects or more dense contexts⁴.

⁴ Workarounds have been made for these particular issues: see for example SAHI (Slicing Aided Hyper Inference), which slices an image in smaller images, makes them more manageable for object

In comics studies, various object detection methods have been effectively applied for different purposes. Iyyer et al. demonstrated the utility of *Faster R-CNN* (a two-stage object detector) in training models to identify text boxes and balloons within comic panels (Iyyer et al., 2016). Additionally, Nguyen, Rigaud and Burie employed both *Fast R-CNN* and the third version of the YOLO family of models to improve character detection and scene understanding in comics (Nguyen et al., 2018). Their findings indicated that *YOLOv3* slightly outperformed the *Fast R-CNN model* in this context.

In our specific application, the limitations with single-stage object detectors are less relevant, as comics typically occupy large portions of a magazine page and are not obscured. Therefore, for this research, we opted for a YOLO model. Since 2017, the YOLO family of models has seen rapid advancements and at the beginning of this research the selection was made for the (then) best performing model: *YOLOv8*. However, since then three new versions *YOLOv9*, *YOLOv10* and *YOLOv11* have been released outperforming various other models (Jocher and Qiu, 2024).

2.2 Selected Data: Six General-Interest Illustrated Magazines in Belgium, 1934-1940

The complete ARTPRESSE corpus consists of more than 500.000 images of digitized facsimile pages from general-audience weekly illustrated magazines. These magazines come in various formats, rely on different printing techniques (letterpress, offset, rotogravure), and contain a wide variety of graphic material: photographic reportages, film stills, cartoons, comics, illustrated fiction, painting reproductions, and more. Many of these magazines rely on new rotogravure facilities, which allowed for the high-quality printing of photographs and visual material, leading to an increased presence of illustrations and images organized in often creative layouts. These new approaches to illustration, design and layout reflected wider European trends in magazine culture of the Interwar, with film periodicals pushing other magazine genres to upscale their visual offering (Rössler, 2023) and with the integration of avant-garde and modernist approaches within ‘middlebrow’ weekly magazines (Truxa, 2023). While maintaining a continuity with 19th traditions of graphic humor and caricature, comics are a part and parcel of this increased and diversified visual offering in mass-market magazines.

In order to work with a more manageable amount of data, we composed a selection of six key periodicals published in both Dutch and French between 1934 and 1940: *Hebdo*, *A-Z/Bonjour*, *Le Soir illustré*, *Ons Volk*, *ABC* and *Zondagsvriend* (see Fig. 1). These titles are not only major large-circulation magazines in the Belgian publishing landscape of the interwar, they are often related to daily newspapers and reflect in various degrees the ideological strands of a then heavily ‘pillarized’ society: *ABC* and *A-Z/Bonjour* are connected to socialist publishing ventures, *Ons Volk* and *Zondagsvriend* closer to the catholic spectrum, *Hebdo* is close to the liberal press but, like *Le Soir illustré*, claims journalistic neutrality (Baetens et al., 2023). The specific period, focused on the mid-1930s, is so delineated because of its importance as a turning point in comic history: in 1934, Paul Winkler’s *Opera Mundi* launched *Le Journal de Mickey in France*, which marked a breakthrough after his repeated attempts at importing and licensing American comics in the European press (Crépin, 2001; Sausverd, 2023). The hypothesis behind this specific periodization is that the intensified circulation of American comics in children’s periodicals might have impacted the distribution of comics in general-audience magazines. From these parameters, the selected data totals 112.220 pages

detectors and then stitches them back together.

Figure 1: Covers from the various magazines in the corpus. From left to right, top to bottom: *Hebdo*, no. 237, 6 November 1936; *Zondagsvriend*, vol. 6, no. 52, 24 December 1935; *Ons Volk*, vol. 24, no. 1, 2 January 1938; *A-Z*, no. 14, 20 June 1937; *Le Soir illustré*, vol. 11, no. 538; *ABC*, vol. 1, no. 18, 29 May 1932. Source: KBR, Belgica Periodicals.

featuring various forms of text, images and illustrations. This sample serves as a basis to develop a workflow, which we aim to expand at a later stage and apply to the entire ARTPRESSE corpus of digitized general-audience magazines.

3 Methodology

Implementing a distant viewing approach, we aim to identify comics within a digitized corpus, using a number of YOLO object detection models to group pixels and assign them to designated classes. In this paper, we discuss the process, challenges, and results of labeling of graphic material in the ARTPRESSE corpus. The goal is to fine-tune a model to recognize the visual features that characterize comics in periodicals. To achieve this, we establish a robust classification system, defining the labels (i.e. categories or classes) that the model will use.

3.1 Annotation

Annotation is a key process in distant viewing, which draws on theories of visual culture and recognizes not only images themselves but also vision (including computer vision) as socially and culturally mediated (Arnold and Tilton, 2023). Determining these categories and labels in our case demands a particular awareness of this cultural mediation, which requires us to reflexively ‘construct’ comics as a category only with hindsight and mostly for heuristic purposes.

Comics studies has indeed moved beyond efforts to outline a formalist or essentialist

Figure 2: From left to right: Anonymous, “Une bonne journée,” A-Z, vol. 2, no. 22, 2 August 1933, p. 25; Stephen Slesinger (uncredited), “Le Roi de la Police Montée,” *Le Soir illustré*, vol. 10, no. 512, 11 December 1937, p. 31; Marten Toonder (uncredited), “Fik et Fok,” A-Z, vol. 4, no. 12, 19 June 1935, p. 4. Source: KBR, Belgica Periodicals.

definition of comics, and rather embraced the view that ‘comics’ offers a convenient broad term encompassing a great variety of forms, traditions, practices shaped by social, cultural and historical contexts. Such a view rejects the idea of comics as a stable universal and rather embraces the idea that comics are constantly changing, always only provisionally stabilized in forms and formats shaped by a repeated negotiation between different social groups and actors, competing media forms, technological changes and processes of institutionalization.⁵

Our corpus strongly reflects this fluid definition shaped by negotiation of various factors, as different models of comics are found coexisting even within weekly magazines. This has to do with the fact that ‘comics’ in Belgium in the Interwar do not exist as such (under the qualifier *bande dessinée* or *stripverhaal*), do not have a strongly recognizable and institutionalized “medium identity” (Marion, 2016) but rather consist of multiple entangled publishing formats and traditions (Lefèvre, 2009; Paques, 2011). In weekly magazines of the mid-1930s, the use and placement of text is indicative of different coexisting models: one might find reproductions of internationally-circulating syndicated comics (using a clear grid layout and speech bubbles), captioned graphic narratives drawn in the ‘older’ style of Epinal popular prints (with text in caption and often decorative layouts), as well as more hybrid cases mingling the two (see Fig. 2). We further find other common models, such as the short gag comic strip consisting of four or three panels in a row, and more occasionally ad hoc graphic compositions that borrow formal features associated with comics.

When constructing comics as a heuristic category for this project, we wanted to keep an open definition to embrace those varied forms of comics and comics-like graphic productions in weekly magazines. This broad definitional scope and fluidity complicate the task of creating formal rules for categorization. For the purposes of computational classification, these boundaries must be defined to enable the model to make definitive decisions. Thus, while we recognize the inherent variability in the definition

⁵ This media-historical approach to comics is largely shared in comics studies, but can follow somewhat different emphases depending on the theories that undergird these approaches (see for instance (Baetens et al., 2023; Marion, 2016; Smolderen, 2014; Sánchez-Mesa and Baetens, 2023; Wilde, 2017)). This means that certain key features of ‘comics’ can be regarded in terms of ‘dominant’ and ‘marginal’ uses, themselves varying in time and space.

Figure 3: Some examples of drawings detected in the ARTPRESSE corpus.

of comics, we had to construct a specific set of criteria to operationalize the concept for our classification task and hence further recognize the need and use of building “flexible working definitions” in the context of cultural heritage institutions (Aggleton, 2019).

This involves two critical steps: identifying regions of interest (ROI) and extracting these regions from relevant pages. These initial steps are essential because, at this stage, we lack precise knowledge regarding the location or quantity of any graphic material within the corpus. While our research’s focus is specifically on comics, our methodology has the result of including much more than just comics.

3.2 Identifying and extracting ROI’s

For detecting regions of interest (ROI’s) in the source material, YOLO was fine-tuned on labeled data from ten randomly selected magazines using *Visual Geometry Group’s Image Annotator* (Dutta and Zisserman, 2019). At this stage, all relevant graphic material - including photographs, illustrations, comics, and cartoons - was classified as ‘relevant_information’ without further categorization. We deliberately chose to include as many regions as possible in this first set of “relevant” data. This was done since our initial testing revealed that including as much variation as possible in graphic material resulted in the inclusion of rarer types of comics, which we ultimately want to find. The data annotated using the VGG Image Annotator was exported in JSON format and converted into the data structure required for YOLO.

3.3 Labeling and Extracting comics

The second component of our methodology labeled the data extracted in the previous step into specific types of graphic material. As discussed in the theoretical framework, defining the boundaries of different graphic representations can be quite challenging. We developed five distinct categories based on preliminary observations and expectations, as well as discussions with art historians, comics scholars and computer-scientists.

1. **Comic:** Visibly hand-drawn, comics consist of multiple images in relationship with each other. Images are segmented into panels organized in a layout, often in a sequence, whether as a single strip or as a grid (see examples in Fig. 2). Comics generally contain text within or under the panels (except for silent or

wordless comics).⁶

2. **Cartoon:** Though closely related to comics, cartoons were classified separately. Cartoons are single, standalone drawn images depicting a specific scene, usually underlined by a single textual caption providing the humorous *pointe*.
3. **Photograph:** Predominantly black-and-white images, photographs are the most common graphic elements in the ARTPRESSE corpus. This category was included to prevent the model from mistakenly identifying photographs as comics or cartoons.
4. **Drawing:** This category covers all other types of drawings that do not fall under the comic or cartoon categories, such as technical drawings, fashion illustrations, and crossword puzzles (see Fig. 3).
5. **Advertisement:** Advertisements also combine text and image and frequently feature illustrations, whether as drawings or photographs. A complex case is that many ads in weekly magazines of the time rely on comics-like features, such as a grid layout or by using speech bubbles (see Fig. 4)

Figure 4: Advertising for Lux soap, *Bonjour!*, vol. 8, no. 47, 12 May 1940, p. 32. Source: KBR, BelgicaPeriodicals.

The main goal was to outline clear labels in order to facilitate the labeling and detection of comics, rather than to strive for an accurate classification of the wildly heterogeneous contents of weekly magazines. These concepts should thus rather be understood as heuristic tools for the process of annotation, as a means to facilitate the computational detection of comics material. Accordingly, the ‘comics’ category was the central focal point, while other categories were more loosely defined but contributed to mark important differences relevant to fine-tune computer vision to detect comics, such as the distinction between drawings and photographs.

The case of ads using comics-like elements required a further disambiguation: it is indeed common to find advertisements that borrow and reference comics features, such

⁶ This definition aimed at a clear description, avoiding jargon, but relied on key comics theories that put the focus on the “iconic solidarity” between various images (Groensteen, 2009)

as a grid layout and speech bubbles. In this soap commercial using the new culture of film stardom to sell skin care products (see Fig. 4), for instance, the ad relies on the juxtaposition of various images and scenes, featuring dialogues in speech bubbles. In such cases, annotators were requested to prioritize the category ‘comics’ above the category ‘advertisement’, since we wanted to make sure that such examples were also included in comics detections as they present an important source for revising comics histories that have routinely neglected such hybrid productions.

The labeling task was conducted on a smaller subset of the overall corpus. Specifically, we selected 105 magazine issues from the total 2,756 available. From each magazine title, 15 issues were randomly chosen to create a diverse and representative sample of graphic material. Following the methodology for the ROI model, multiple models were created to detect comics, cartoons, photographs, drawings, and advertisements.

A significant challenge arose in how to process and extract the visual data, particularly with respect to comics. Initially, our focus was on extracting individual comic panels. However, it became clear that object detection models did not account for the potential sequential relationship between panels, often extracting them in a random order. This randomness would not only have required extensive manual reordering, but also made it difficult for annotators to distinguish between comics and cartoons.

To address this, we revised our fine-tuning approach to treat entire comic strips, or *bandes*, as single objects, rather than focusing on individual panels. This adjustment not only clarified the visual distinction between cartoons and comics but also aligned more intuitively with how comics are typically structured. Despite this change, the approach still had limitations. Contextual elements, often located outside the comic panels, were frequently omitted. For instance, as illustrated in Fig. 5, while the comic strips were successfully detected, the hand-lettered title banner and accompanying illustrations were excluded. The highly variable proportions taken up by comics in weekly magazines (from three-panel comic strips taking only a small segment of the page to full pages occupying the main surface) thus proved a challenge for defining ROIs.

To solve the issue of missing context the final data output was modified to include the entire page, along with metadata indicating the number of comics and other possible items present on the page. It is indeed crucial to view comics within their publication context and placement on the page. In a second stage of this project, additional metadata has further been produced, gathered and encoded through Tropy, an open-source image annotation tool, to compile a data-rich collection of comics from the detected corpus.

4 Labeling Process

Our labeling methodology was a collaborative effort involving comic scholars, historians, and computer scientists. A small crowdsourcing initiative, including a literature scholar, further enriched the process.

4.1 Crowdsourcing

Crowdsourcing is an effective approach for supervised learning. We employed repeated labeling to achieve consensus among annotators through truth inference, specifically using a probabilistic majority voting method (Sheng and Zhang, 2019). This

FIK et FOK

comic 0.93

Malgré la pluie l'une nous allons examiner l'autre à notre Dieu.

Qu'est-ce qui s'est passé?

Ces gaffards sont partis. Je vais inspecter cette statue.

Il est bon que j'ai laissé dehors la statue. Elle est brisée.

Les deux sacs d'or ont disparu. Qui peut avoir fait cela? Se demandent les deux bandits avec effroi.

Il se mit à crier Brom-brit-bi Notre bon Dieu a ri! Fok, entièrement tranquille S'en va tout inspecter.

Je vais longer ce mur. Malgré que le chemin soit très dur. Mais si je veux connaître la vérité Il ne s'agit plus de reculer.

comic 0.96

Pourquoi la statue terriblement endormie d'habitude? Elle ne dort-elle que un bras mystérieux.

Il se peut que dans cette eau vive une belle saucisse qui mange tous les autres et un tabac.

Mon Dieu! Grâce! Un polype!

Tout à coup il entend un clapotement. Une chose tremble sur ses fondements.

Tout à coup une idée lui vient. Si je comprends l'affaire très bien, Une cave est creusée tout autour. Si j'en faisais la tour?

Devant ses yeux apparaît brusquement L'auteur de ce grand clapotement: Une pieuvre, un polype affreux Lui lance des regards hargneux!

comic 0.90

AU SECOURS! AU SECOURS! AU SECOURS!

Fok reste bien longtemps...

Oh! stupé, notre Fok se met à trembler. Le monstre vient de l'empoigner Et menace sa jeune vie. Tant qu'il peut notre ami crie!

Dehors ses deux amis l'attendent Plongés dans de profondes pensées Et pour tromper l'attente...

Un cri rauque vient les tirer de leur songe Nigro que le remords d'être resté rouge Se retourne brusquement et voit...

AVIS TRÈS IMPORTANT

A-Z HEBDOMADAIRE ILLUSTRÉ

BON No. 13

ASSURANCE-ACCIDENTS GRATUITE

Il nous revient que des lecteurs s'imaginent qu'une fois en possession de la police d'assurance A-Z, leur remise par leur marchand, ils sont automatiquement assurés et ne doivent plus s'occuper de rien. C'est une erreur! Nous avons expliqué à plusieurs reprises les conditions auxquelles un lecteur est assuré. Celui qui reçoit une police d'assurance - et tous nos lecteurs peuvent la recevoir, il suffit qu'ils la demandent à leur marchand, ou s'ils sont abonnés par la poste, aux éditeurs d'A-Z - doit remplir dûment, les trois parties dont elle se compose: la police proprement dite et les deux talons. La police est à conserver par le lecteur, les deux talons sont à renvoyer aux éditeurs de la revue. Le lecteur n'est assuré, en réalité, que du moment où les deux talons sont reçus au bureau des éditeurs. Que ceux qui ont remis les deux talons au marchand de journaux se renseignent aux fins de savoir si celui-ci les a bien envoyés aux éditeurs. Il y va de leur intérêt!

Editeurs d'A-Z: pour le Pays-Noir: 24 rue du Collège - Charleroi; pour le pays de Liège: 53 rue de la Régence - Liège; pour toutes les autres régions du Belgique: 35 rue des Sables à Bruxelles

Figure 5: An example of the prediction for comics using a conventional layout structure.

approach determined the most frequent label for each instance, enhancing dataset reliability.

Our annotator team included a comic expert and five non-experts. Labeling occurred over several months, with annotators working at different times. To ensure consistency, we conducted an introductory session led by comic scholars and provided a detailed labeling guide with clear examples.

A custom Python tool streamlined the process, allowing annotators to label instances efficiently by inputting a number between 1 and 7. It displayed images, recorded labels, and managed file generation (see Fig. 6).

To handle uncertainties, we introduced two additional labels: ‘trash’ (erroneous detections) and ‘other/unsure’ (ambiguous cases). As annotators’ understanding evolved (Kulesza et al., 2014), these instances were later reviewed by experts to improve dataset accuracy, following the approach of (Wiebe et al., 1999).

Figure 6: The labeling tool as used by annotators.

4.2 The consensus dataset

As previously mentioned, the consensus dataset was created through truth inference with majority voting. However, majority voting poses challenges, particularly when ties among labels occur. To address this, we implemented “weighted majority voting”, which takes into account the annotator’s varying levels of confidence and expertise. By weighting votes based on annotator’s confidence, this method provides more accurate labels in cases lacking consensus (Dogan and Birant, 2019)). Our implementation was based on the work of Georgescu and Zhu, which focuses on calculating worker confidence to enhance the precision of the voting process (Georgescu and Zhu, 2014).

For each label, we calculated an annotator confidence score, assigning a value between 0 and 1 to reflect an annotator’s confidence with a specific label. For example, annotator A might receive a confidence score of 0.7 for identifying comics, while annotator B could receive a score of 0.9 for the same label. These confidence scores are then incorporated into the majority voting process, weighting each annotator’s input according to their confidence level per label.

These per label scores were determined using a mutually agreed-upon labeling benchmark based on a subset of magazines from our labeling corpus. To streamline this process, we converted our multi-label setup into a single-label binary system,

(i.e. one-hot encoding). Each annotator’s label was compared to the benchmark on a label-by-label basis, assessing whether their labeling aligned with the benchmark. This binary comparison allowed us to accurately calculate the confidence scores for each label, ensuring that they precisely reflected the annotators’ performance relative to the agreed-upon benchmark.

The advantage of this approach is twofold. First, it ensures that an annotator’s accuracy in one label category does not affect their accuracy in another, allowing for a more precise evaluation of their performance across different labels. Second, it allows the system to weigh the contributions of expert annotators - who are most familiar with the content - more heavily. Since expert annotators are likely to align more closely with the benchmark, their labels carry more weight during majority voting than those of less experienced annotators.

5 Results and evaluation

5.1 Evaluating the annotators

Figure 7: Distribution of all labels per annotator.

The evaluation served two purposes: comparing the performance of five annotators with different backgrounds and assessing the suitability of label categories. It also revealed the influence of the labeling guide and in-person discussions on accuracy and consistency. Notably, not all annotators attended the introductory session, nor did they all speak Dutch and French.

Among the five annotators, only Annotator Four was familiar with both the source material and comics’ structure. While all had access to the labeling guide, Annotator One missed the in-person session. Annotator Five joined later but received the same introduction with an expert and another annotator.

Initial label distributions (see Fig. 7) suggest strong agreement on defined concepts. Inter-annotator agreement, measured by Cohen’s Kappa Score, ranged from 0.68

(substantial agreement) to 0.88 (near-perfect agreement).

A key outlier was Annotator One, who mislabeled many cartoons as comics. This highlights the value of in-person discussions, which clarified challenging distinctions, such as cartoons often appearing together in magazines, mimicking comics' structure. Fig. 8 illustrates this confusion: six visually similar cartoons by J. Pruvost appear cohesive but are individual gags with unique captions. The improved accuracy among other annotators suggests these discussions were instrumental in refining understanding.

Figure 8: Jacques Pruvost, “L’humour de J. Pruvost,” *Hebdo*, vol. 8, no. 320, 21 January 1938, p. 2. Source: KBR, BelgicaPeriodicals.

To further evaluate the annotators, we created a benchmark similar to the one used during the confidence score calculation. These scores closely align with the confidence scores each annotator received for the consensus dataset. A verified opinion of an expert was used and verified to conduct this comparison.

The benchmark does not seem perfect, since there are some perfect matches when the distribution in Table 1 clearly shows differences. We assume this means that the selection made for the benchmark is either too small or that coincidentally the graphics were easy to classify. However, these results further validate our earlier findings of the discrepancy between annotator one and the other annotators since in general they score worse.

Additionally, while our distribution showed close results for the amount of the advertisement class, the accuracy of the labeling is significantly more spread out. The substantial variation in labeling accuracy between advertisements and comics suggests that the stylistic similarities between comics and comic-style advertisements necessitate a more advanced semantic or spatial understanding. After all, as is often typical in

newspapers and magazines, advertisement space is often frequently positioned in a fixed recurring location of the periodical.

Table 1: Accuracy of labelers compared to verified expert labeling.

	Comics	Cartoons	Photographs	Drawings	Advertisement
Annotator 1	0.92	0.91	0.71	0.91	0.66
Annotator 2	1	0.92	0.88	0.97	0.96
Annotator 3	1	0.84	0.79	0.98	0.84
Annotator 4	1	1	0.82	0.98	0.71
Annotator 5	1	0.98	0.88	0.92	0.81

Language barriers further complicated the task, as only Annotator Two was fluent in both Dutch and French. Since our model does not incorporate semantic meaning in object detection, it relied entirely on the annotators’ interpretations. Notably, annotators who attended the in-person meeting demonstrated a clearer understanding of class definitions and their variations, underscoring the session’s positive impact on annotation accuracy.

5.2 Evaluating the labels

As discussed, the accuracy of the labels varied depending on the annotator’s understanding and experience. When comparing the number of labels included in the learning process of YOLO, it becomes evident that visually and semantically more complex labels, such as advertisements, pose greater challenges. This can be seen in see Fig. 9, which was fine-tuned on the same dataset but only Model B included the advertisements. This confirms our assumption that to distinguish between complex categories semantic understanding is required, which our current model lacks.

It is important to recognize human annotators’ ability to successfully identify all instances does not necessarily imply that the computer model will achieve the same level of accuracy. The capabilities that human annotators have, such as semantic understanding or access to the context of the full page, is not directly transferable to our model, which relies solely on visual features without the context or interpretative skills that humans possess.

The second two models were fine-tuned on datasets labeled by individual annotators. Model A achieved a higher mean average precision (mAP), precision and recall - all key metrics in evaluating object detection models (see Fig.10)⁷. These metrics are included within the YOLO framework and calculated while training. This is intriguing given that the dataset for Model B was annotated by a more experienced comic annotator. However, the higher scores of Model A does not necessarily imply better real-world performance. Upon closer examination, Model B is more accurate in successfully classifying the actual comics. We hypothesize that Model B was fine-tuned on a broader range of exceptions, instances that do not strictly conform to the conventional stylistic characteristics of comics. The exposure to diverse and atypical instances may have decreased the mAP of Model B, but increased its real-world ability to correctly classify unseen data by improving its ability to handle such variability effectively. Additionally,

⁷ Mean Average Precision (mAP) measures the average precision across all classes while considering both precision and recall. A higher mAP generally indicates better model performance in detecting and classifying objects.

Figure 9: The performance of model A (3 classes) versus model B (5 classes)

Figure 10: The performance of model A versus model B (experienced annotator).

contextual factors such as language play a significant role in the performance of both models.

For both models, recall is lower than expected. One notable area of difficulty for both models is the comics class, which is frequently confused with cartoons, particularly in less conventional comics formats. For example, while the model detects traditional comics styles with high confidence (90% to 100%), it struggles with more complex instances - here coincidentally also an advertisement in comic form. While our current approach only allowed for one label to be assigned to a particular instance, our model was able to classify one graphic as both comic and advertisement. However, these classifications consequently have a lower confidence.

Another key observation was the advantage of incorporating multiple classes rather than training the model on a single class. When the model was trained exclusively on the comics class, a significantly lower mAP was observed compared to when cartoons and photographs were included. Notably, the occurrence of false positives on photographs was particularly substantial.

5.3 Evaluating the corpus

A quantitative examination of our sample of the ARTPRESSE corpus revealed a distribution of labels that largely met expectations. This distribution provides a basis for making informed assumptions about the corpus as a whole. To achieve the most accurate representation, we used the aggregated labeled dataset, which comprised 6,800 valid labels. Photographs constituted approximately 60% of the data, followed by various illustrations (13%) and cartoons (12%). Comics were significantly under-represented, comprising less than 5% of the corpus.

A closer examination of individual magazines provides an even clearer picture of how our classes are distributed (see Fig. 11). The amount of graphic material present in each magazine title typically ranges between 63 and 73 items, with only a few outliers - one magazine averaging around 40 items per issue and another around 86. This variation in the number of graphic items can largely be attributed to the differing lengths of the magazine issues. Lengthier magazine titles naturally contain more graphic material, leading to this observed range in distribution across different magazines.

This trend, however, does not directly correlate with the presence of comics or cartoons within a magazine, nor is there a consistent relationship between the number of comics and cartoons featured in any given magazine. For instance, *Ons Volk*, a magazine with a higher page count than most others in our corpus, rarely includes comics and only sporadically features cartoons. Similarly *Zondagsvriend* seldom contains either cartoons or comics. These observations suggest that the relationship between magazine length and the integration of comics or cartoons is not straightforward, and rather has to do with editorial choices. That both titles are aligned on Catholic media groups might partly account for such editorial choices, but one should be cautious as such assumptions run the risk of jumping to conclusions by privileging a single explanatory factor. Rather, this makes clear that a more fine-grained approach to the corpus of identified comics in weekly magazines requires additional metadata to support a quantitative approach and make these numbers more meaningful to the cultural and media history of Belgian comics. It also demands a closer qualitative analysis of the corpus of detected comics, which needs to unfold with a good grasp on the editorial context of these broad-audience magazines.

Figure 11: Predictions with confidence ratio made on different pages from *Hebdo*.

6 Conclusion and Future steps

The semi-automatic detection of comics (and other visual genres) using computer vision models is a promising avenue for cultural heritage institutions and research in cultural history, by providing another mode of exploration and access beyond full-text search. This is especially useful for comics productions that do not perform very well when it comes to OCR. The aim of this paper was to reflect on the workflow implemented to detect comics within a large corpus of mass-market periodicals in which comics were precisely hard to otherwise identify because relatively scarce in the corpus and present in a wide variety of forms and layouts. This variety of forms and layouts raise interesting questions for the application of computer vision as a means of detection and classification. We have developed a workflow that considers and frames comics as ‘objects’ rather than ‘layouts’ (thus mostly defined by their spatial coordinates). In doing so, this approach follows a different course from the recourse to document layout analysis that has been particularly relevant for the segmenting of articles, genres, texts and images in digitized newspaper collections (Ali et al., 2024; Bunout et al., 2023; Gutehrle and Atanassova, 2022). A possible alternative method would have involved a two-step approach based first on layout recognition and then proceeding with object detection. Such an approach - common in computation approaches to digitized newspapers - would be particularly beneficial to recurring serial comics, which are usually segmented in clear and recognizable ways and tend to occupy the same spatial coordinates across different issues. Notwithstanding some important similarities between newspapers and magazines (both as periodicals), popular illustrated magazines of the Interwar period arguably present a marked heterogeneity in terms of contents, layout, and text-and-image combination that might complicate any straightforward application of identification and classification models used for daily newspapers to weekly illustrated magazines.

The question of layout is nevertheless a crucial one: comics indeed raise productive questions for computer vision and the automatic detection of images precisely because they consist of multiple images arranged in a multiframe. As many projects of distant viewing start with the automatic extraction of individual images, comics always involve relationships between multiple images at various levels: both in terms of the relative internal coherence and in terms of their ‘paratextual’ anchorage on the page. This is also where the (partly retrospective) distinction between comics and cartoons becomes operative and complex to automatize. Noticing the complex case of images functioning as ‘tableaux’ in the 19th illustrated press, Paul Fyfe and Qian Ge already highlighted the “interpretive violence” that accompanies the act of “‘chunking’ the visual experience of illustrated periodicals into discrete objects,” reminding us with Johanna Drucker of the historical situatedness of visual epistemologies that is also relevant and applicable to computer vision (Fyfe and Ge, 2018). This ‘chunking’ is also at play in this current research, which has sought a way of identifying comics based on the relations of multiple images, while extracting them from their immediate context.

The closer analysis of the corpus of comics detections that this workflow has yielded will be fleshed out in next steps: the automatic classification indeed allows for a serendipitous approach to comics in periodicals that accounts for the variety and heterogeneity of comics forms in such magazines, broadening our understanding of early comics history in the Interwar period. It is precisely this variety that has required fine-tuning a flexible and open definition of comics, necessary to generate labels differentiating various types of visual contents. Our classification of images into

different categories (photographs, comics, cartoons, drawings, advertisements) relies on an annotation for fine-tuning the algorithm in order to better recognize ‘comics’ specifically, rather than aiming for an accurate classification of the various types of visual contents that can be found in those magazines. By modeling comics as ‘objects’, we have aimed at developing a model that can recognize a broader ambit of comics or comics-like materials.

This is further reflected in the labeling process and evaluation of annotations. Our study particularly highlights the value of integrating annotator confidence scores into the labeling process, which significantly improves the reliability of the dataset by prioritizing input from expert annotators. The distribution evaluation of annotators also revealed that in-person discussions, in addition to a detailed labeling guide, improve accuracy, particularly in distinguishing complex categories like comics and cartoons.

Our future work will focus on a more layered, multi-stage approach to comics detection. Initially, models should focus on separating photographs from illustrations, which would require more data. Once this distinction is made, the second phase can be fine-tuned on differentiating between comics and cartoons. This hierarchical approach would allow for more precise classification by addressing stylistic overlaps in stages. Additionally, incorporating a model with semantic capabilities, for example the quickly advancing multimodal large language models, could enhance detection by identifying advertisements disguised as comics within the dataset.

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Documenting Jewish Mobility in Antiquity: Connecting Archaeological, Inscriptural, and Historical Data from around the Mediterranean

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We present Modelling Jewish Migration in Antiquity, a project in which we have created an interactive platform that brings together evidence of Jewish presence in Antiquity as a searchable database and an interactive map, in order to help explain the dynamics of Jewish migration within the Roman Empire and into Europe in a manner that is more quantifiable and transparent than has been possible so far. The database includes nearly two thousand entries and includes archaeological findings, inscriptions, papyri, and literary evidence that were previously published but never brought together in one place. In this article, we describe how we have created the dataset, we discuss the data model we used to publish the dataset as findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) data, and we present the search and visualization interface that we created to make the data accessible. The article concludes with a provisional analysis of the materials. We show that the broad patterns in the spread of evidence of Jewish presence in Antiquity from our data can best be understood by contextualizing them within the larger framework of (non-Jewish) Roman history. We furthermore also document that our data suggests that Jewish migration during the time of the Roman Empire developed primarily along the coasts of the Mediterranean, while we find less evidence of Jewish presence in what used to be the German provinces of the Roman Empire.

Keywords: Antiquity, archaeology, Judaism, migration, Roman Empire

1 Background and Goals

1.1 Background

One of the challenges for the study of ancient Jewish history is the fact that while there is plenty archaeological, epigraphic, and papyrological evidence, such data have not generally been digitized in any systematical manner nor is there a single database

that makes all of the available information accessible in one place. It goes without saying that there are many advantages to presenting the relevant primary sources in the form of an interactive database. It is not just that such a database makes evidence that is typically published in specialized journals freely available to anyone with an internet connection. Nor does it just allow for newly discovered data to be added quickly and easily and thus keep the information truly up to date—something that was impossible in the past simply because one always had to work with publications that appeared in print. Perhaps the single most appealing aspect of digitizing the data and making them available via a web-based database is that one is in the position to work with larger datasets, meaning that one can actually begin to try to unravel the larger patterns and, possibly, even the inner dynamics, that shape Jewish historical migration during the period of the Roman Empire.

Because hardly any of the evidence included in our website had ever been digitized, and because none of it had ever been presented in the form of an interactive platform, we sought inspiration from similar such projects that had already materialized and that could provide us with best practices. Important projects included the PEACE Portal (Saar, 2021) and ORBIS, the Stanford Geospatial Network Model of the Roman World (Scheidel, 2013, 2014). The aim of the PEACE Portal is providing academic and general audiences with a ‘portal of epigraphy, archaeology, conservation and education of Jewish funerary culture’, with special emphasis on funerary inscriptions stretching over a period of more than two millennia and deriving, specifically, from Israel, Roman Palestine, and Germany.¹ The ORBIS project documents travel distance, time and costs in the Roman Empire and thus serves as a tool to study connectivity throughout the Roman Empire.²

In our project, the goal was to include different types of primary data, namely archaeological findings, inscriptions, papyri, and literary evidence, in an effort to see what such evidence could possibly tell us about the dynamics of Jewish mobility migration into Europe in Antiquity from the second century BCE (with our earliest evidence attesting to the late sixth century BCE), when such mobility and migration first began to take shape, until the seventh century CE, which is when the (western) Roman world came to an end, and which, interestingly enough, coincides with a very significant drop in Jewish primary data from the area of the former Roman Empire also. While creating a database of Jewish presence in the ancient world based on all the published evidence currently available, our geographical focus was on the lands encompassed by the Roman Empire.³ So far we have not included rabbinic data not just because for the geographical area we are studying such data are few and far between and require their own methodology if one is to evaluate them historically. In this area there is a separate project underway that has been designed and is being directed by Eyal Ben-Eliyahu. Known as Alma, this project is producing excellent results, which includes discussions between the Alma team and our team to integrate all of our data at a later point in time.⁴

As for the project we are presenting here, it conceptually builds on the work of Rutgers who has tried to explain the dynamics of Jewish migration in the ancient world, and who has argued that ‘if you wanted to travel the length and breadth of the Roman Empire in, say, the fourth century CE, you could probably do so by

¹ <https://peace.sites.uu.nl/epigraphy/search/>

² <https://orbis.stanford.edu/>

³ We did not include evidence on Jewish communities from the Parthian, Sasanian and Persian empires as this would require an entirely different study.

⁴ <https://experience.arcgis.com/experience/5ebdd921862447daa05118ad17b118a1/page/Home/>

travelling from one Jewish community to the next, at least for considerable stretches of your journey' (2016). Yet, many questions, for example relating to the demographic reality behind this phenomenon, remain essentially unresolved (Schwartz, 2014). Our platform aims to offer tools for addressing these and various other questions regarding Jewish mobility, migration, and integration into Roman society, making the process more quantifiable, transparent, and methodologically sound than previously possible. That said, it should finally be observed that the database we are presenting here is possible only because of the hard work of the many researchers that preceded us and that published the raw data. These include scores of archaeologists who did the actual archaeological fieldwork in many a location and the scholars who gathered evidence in the form of corpora, including, in particular, Victor Tcherikover and Alexander Fuks, Gert, David Noy, Walter Ameling, and Tal Ilan.

1.2 Process and Goals

The way our project has been shaped can be narrowed down to four distinct phases. During the first phase we realized that managing the existing data would require a database. As we had little previous experience in this area, the projects of Saar (2021), and Houten (2021), as well as their expertise, were used to help shape the project. In order to create a database that makes all the available information accessible in one place, we also had to determine its boundaries. The chronological and geographical boundaries we settled on correspond with the rise and fall of the (western) Roman Empire in both chronological and geographical terms, as this was the time and place that Jewish migration into Europe first occurred.

To flesh this out further, we defined several further goals for our project: 1) to collect all currently known primary data on Jewish presence in the Mediterranean basin and Europe during the first six centuries CE, be this evidence archaeological, inscriptional, papyrological or historical. As stated above, most of these data is currently available only in the form of published books. Once we had localized and collected all of these publications we then proceeded to 2) make the information available in the form of an interactive and searchable database that contained all of the collected evidence (more on this later). Lastly we 3) began working on an accompanying article how the website and accompanying interactive platform may help to detect mobility of Jews during the time of the Roman Empire. This article is yet to appear.

During the second phase, the project not only used the database as a place where data could be stored, but also as a point of departure that would eventually allow us to visualize the results, as already mentioned. Here the next step was to link this database to an interactive map, as the place where the results of searching through the database in a certain fashion could be visualized. This was also the phase in which the current team was formed and in which we decided to apply for a research grant from Utrecht University's *FAIR Research IT Innovation Fund*, which covered the costs of the research software developers involved in this project.⁵

The third phase included the shaping, the curating and building of our dataset, our database, and our interactive website. This phase was characterized by testing aimed at perfecting the ways in which we were incorporating the data, by reflecting on the way the data could be used, and by thinking about how to locate our project within the larger context of the Digital Humanities. This was also the period during which

⁵ <https://www.uu.nl/organisatie/it/wat-wij-doen/fair-research-it/oproep-2022-fair-it-innovatiefonds-voor-onderzoek>

meetings were held with experts from outside to inform how to move further, such as a meeting with Dr Jonathan Prag on the use of EpiDoc (see also Prag and Chartrand, 2018). Because this phase was centered around testing and perfecting our results we also ran into certain challenges. One of these was the question of which digital format to use for visualizing our data. By reaching out to colleagues in relevant fields, we were able to overcome such challenges (more details on this below).

The last phase is the current phase in which we find ourselves at this moment in time. Most of the work has been done, and we are anticipating the first results.

2 Methods

2.1 Creation of the Dataset

For the compilation of the dataset, we included data culled from various different inscriptional, archaeological and papyrological corpora, as well as other scholarly publications – essentially everything we could lay our hands on, to the extent this information was available to us in published form. The dataset offers the first large-scale integrated and digitized collection of ancient Jewish archaeological, inscriptional, papyrological and literary sources from around the Mediterranean during the time of the Roman Empire (with the exclusion of the area of Roman Palestine, which was the homeland of the Jews whence they migrated).

Currently containing 1966 data entries, our database includes records representing Jewish inscriptions, papyrological documents referring to Jewish matters, further non-Jewish textual materials that refer to Jews or Jewish communities, as well as various types of archaeological evidence that is identifiable as Jewish because of the decoration it contains, because of architectural features or because of the larger archaeological context from which such archaeological finds derive. Estimated time periods accompany each and every data-entry, as does further information regarding specific symbols, materials used, the location of the materials, and, where appropriate, a translation in English.

The types of evidence that we included in our data are very dissimilar and can differ a lot from each other. The evidence can broadly be subdivided into two groups: inscriptional and papyrological evidence deals with written text, found on either marble tablets, papyrus scrolls, or even subterranean walls. This makes it a relatively homogeneous group. The archaeological records, however, are more difficult to analyze as one group, for it not only include Jewish mosaics, but also entire synagogues or necropoleis. In order to overcome this challenge, we had to come up with a method for standardization of all the records so as to make all the different types of evidence comparable to each other. Moreover, to properly curate all these different aspects we came up with a four-pronged approach. This process was the same for all the different types of evidence that we included in our dataset.

The starting point for every data entry was its geographical information. Whenever possible, we enriched information on locations with geo-coordinates, using the Pleiades gazetteer of ancient place names where available,⁶ or by adding coordinates manually. The geographical coordinates are essential if one wants to visualize and study the diffusion of our evidence, and in return possible migration patterns.

As a next step we assessed the chronological information, and added this for each individual piece of evidence. Indicating the moment in time a particular piece of

⁶ <https://pleiades.stoa.org/>

evidence was either used or produced, it is evident that chronological indicators are a particularly useful category if one is to determine larger migratory patterns relating. Thus, a peak in the evidence might tell us something about a potential increase of the Jewish population at a given site or in a given region, which in turn might be ascribed to increased mobility. The inclusion of chronological information also proves its usefulness when contextualized against the general historical information available for a given period. For example, after the second century CE, the evidence that originates from Egypt and North Africa decreases rapidly. If one compares this to historical events from that time period, it becomes clear that there may be a causal connection with the Jewish revolts in that area in the beginning of the second century CE, when the Jewish population was decimated, to say the least (Ben Zeev, 2005; Le Bohec, 1981; Lüderitz, 1983; Tcherikover and Fuks, 1960).

Once the geographical and chronological information had been included, we also added linguistic information, particularly where it concerned inscriptional evidence. When studied comprehensively such information allows one to reflect on language usage of a population that finds itself in a Diasporic situation. What emerges from this is the importance of Greek for the Jewish communities of the Roman-period Diaspora. More than half of the Jewish inscriptions in our database turned out to have been written in Greek. Being the second most important language in the Roman empire, this was apparently also the language in which many Jewish communities communicated, amongst themselves and with one another. Such a fact is obviously a function of the integration of these Diasporic communities in the Hellenistic Greek culture that permeated the eastern half of the Roman Empire all the way down to Late Antiquity and beyond.

To determine whether the various Jewish communities were similar to one another in political, socio-economic, cultural and religious make-up, we added yet another category, using the content preserved in and provided by the primary sources themselves. This meant identifying references to jobs people had as well as religious titles and further markers such as religious symbols. These kind of cultural markers provide us with new insights in how individual Jews, groups, and even entire Jewish communities defined themselves within the Diasporic context in which they lived. Importantly the gender of the people that dedicated an inscription or were mentioned in the evidence was also included. By including this marker in our dataset as well, we wanted to try to determine what sort of cultural habits inform Jewish epigraphic practice insofar as it relates to issues of gender. Again, the results of this can be compared, in a later step, to what is known about Roman inscriptional practices in this area, once again in an effort to see whether the Jewish communities of the Roman Diaspora followed general customs or their own.

The idea to build our dataset in this way was majorly informed by projects such as the above-mentioned ORBIS project directed by Walter Scheidel, which shows the importance of being able to study evidence from a temporal and geographical perspective while keeping in mind the networks identified by Scheidel and his collaborators (Meeks, 2015; Scheidel, 2013, 2014). Scheidel's work inspired us to plot data-points on a map in the hope that various patterns might emerge that one would never be able to identify if one merely works with the data individually. The projects of Houten (Houten, 2021) and Prag (Prag and Chartrand, 2018)⁷ provided us with further inspiration on the inclusion of datasets that underlie these visualizations. These projects rely heavily on a data-driven approach, that takes as its point of departure a substantial

⁷ <https://isicily.org/>

underlying dataset. The main take-away from these projects is that if one is to look for overarching patterns, a data-driven approach based on digitized data is the only way forward.

2.2 Data Model

As we collected and curated data in the way and for the purposes described in the previous section, one of our main concerns was to create a dataset that meets the requirements of FAIR data.⁸ This implied that it was imperative that the data should be published under a free license, but also that its data format is not only open but ideally also commonly used in the field, so that the data can be reused by others and to provide interoperability with other applications. At the same time, however, it was equally important to design an editing tool where the data could be updated in an efficient and user-friendly way, and this limited our choices in data formats.

As we worked through this process, we considered three different formats. Since a large part of the primary data in our dataset concerns epigraphical data, we first considered EpiDoc, which is a widely used and well-defined open standard.⁹ EpiDoc is based on the Text Encoding Initiative format (TEI), which in itself is based on XML. Its most important strength is the detailed way in which it encodes the text of epigraphical materials with all its subtleties, such as whether parts of the text are located on the *recto* or *verso* sides, words that wrap from one line to another, abbreviations and illegible but reconstructed parts of the text. In EpiDoc, these features are encoded using XML tags and attributes, but using tools such as XSLT it is possible to convert EpiDoc documents into human-readable or even interactive formats.

For our purposes, however, EpiDoc presented us with some difficulties. While EpiDoc is strong in encoding the actual text of epigraphical materials, in our dataset the focus is not on the text itself but rather on the metadata. Even though we do record the full text and translation in our data entries where available, we are not using the EpiDoc features in encoding these texts, since the details of these texts are not our main concern. While EpiDoc allows the inclusion of metadata, it does not prescribe a standard way of doing so, and in fact we see large differences between datasets in the way they encode metadata. This means that the advantages of EpiDoc in terms of interoperability are limited for our dataset. In addition, the fact that EpiDoc is usually created by hand did not fit well with our needs to have a user-friendly and efficient editing interface. Also, the fact that EpiDoc is document-based (each inscription is represented by a separate XML file) was not a perfect match with our goal to create a database where metadata was the most important part.

As an alternative we began exploring the possibility of creating and storing the data as linked data in RDF format. Because our dataset uses parts of other datasets that are themselves available as linked open data – most prominently the Pleiades gazetteer of ancient place names (see also above) – there are obvious advantages for our dataset to be published as linked open data as well. However, the technical support of linked data is not yet at the same level as that of more traditional approaches, including relational databases. The most important consideration here was that for creating our dataset as linked open data, we would have to spend a lot of work creating an editing interface.

⁸ FAIR data is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. See the *GO FAIR* website for more information: <https://www.go-fair.org/>.

⁹ <https://epidoc.stoa.org/>

In a discussion with Dr Jonathan Prag, who as co-PI of the Fair Epigraphy project¹⁰ has done pioneering work on epigraphical data as linked open data, we discussed with him the advantages that this data format would bring to our project. We agreed that the fact that there is currently no widely adopted linked data ontology for epigraphical data greatly limits the usability of any new dataset that does not tackle this problem (see also Prag and Chartrand, 2018: 248–249). In addition, our dataset follows a relatively simple and stable structure, which means that another advantage of linked open data – flexibility in the data model – would not apply here.

Because of the difficulties that data storage in linked open data would come with and the lack of advantages for our purposes, we decided to store the data natively as a relational database using the Django framework for web applications.¹¹ This resulted in a user-friendly editing tool to update the database, which is a standard feature of Django. We added features to automatically retrieve information from external databases such as Pleiades for location data, links to which are also preserved in the database.¹² Every entry in the database carries a unique, persistent identifier and a URI, which allow external datasets to refer to our data. Whenever needed, our project team members or any potential outside collaborators can edit the data and insert new entries. The fact that our dataset is natively stored as a relational database does not close the door to linked open data: a conversion to linked open data is trivial¹³ and if at any time a standard ontology for epigraphical data gets established we will be very happy to provide a data conversion scheme.

Apart from a searchable public interface (see below), we make the dataset available for others using a JSON REST API, as well as a downloadable JSON dump, which is uploaded to Zenodo whenever significant updates are made.¹⁴

2.3 Search

To make the data accessible for researchers at large, but also to facilitate our own research, we are in the process of making it available for exploration through the web application I-Analyzer (Janssen et al., 2023). This makes it possible to perform full-text search and filter data, including, especially, inscriptions.

I-Analyzer uses Elasticsearch for full-text search. Elasticsearch is based on Apache Lucene, a NoSQL query engine. To prepare the data of the inscriptions for fast search and filtering of metadata, it needs to be indexed. I-Analyzer has formats for defining the fields which should be added to an index, and how to populate those fields from source data. It can read a wide range of formats, such as XML, CSV and HTML, but also JSON. We built in a mechanism to directly download and index the data from the JSON REST API, so that if a user of our editing tool modifies metadata, or adds new inscriptions, these changes can easily be picked up in the search interface of I-Analyzer.

I-Analyzer’s search interface consists of three tabs: the first tab can be used to filter inscriptions and explore the results; the second tab shows visualizations (see 2.4 for details), the third tab allows users to download selections of data for further offline processing.

To study the spread of the Jewish diaspora as reflected by inscriptions, we can for

¹⁰ <https://www.csad.ox.ac.uk/fair-epigraphy>

¹¹ For Django, see <https://www.djangoproject.com/>.

¹² The source code for the resulting web application can be found here: <https://github.com/CentreForDigitalHumanities/jewish-historical-migration>

¹³ For example, a conversion to JSON-LD format is as simple as adding a @CONTEXT property.

¹⁴ <https://jewishmigration.sites.uu.nl>

Figure 1: The search pane of I-Analyzer, showing filtering according to the region in which an inscription was found.

Figure 2: An inscription and its metadata, viewed in I-Analyzer.

instance filter the data according to region, as shown in Figure 1, or alternatively, by aspects including century or language of the inscriptions.

Clicking “view” on one of the inscriptions in the search results will show all the metadata of the given inscription, as well as the transcription, if present. The arrow links can be used to navigate to the detail view of the previous or next inscription in the result set, and it is possible to use permanent links to inscriptions, to be shared in publications (see Figure 2).

2.4 Visualization

I-Analyzer includes a number of visualizations to explore text and metadata in a quantitative way. Some of I-Analyzer’s visualizations, such as term frequency and neighboring words of a search term, are not applicable to this corpus, which does not focus so much on the text of an inscription as on the locations and circumstances in which inscriptions were found.

Further visualizations are possible using the categories into which we have placed

Figure 3: A histogram of the number of descriptions per region, as displayed in I-Analyzer.

the data. Thus it becomes possible to not only investigate how many inscriptions were found per region or settlement, but to visualize the results, as evidenced by the histogram visualizations included here as Figure 3.

However, because histograms do not provide one with good representations of the geographical distribution of inscriptions, we also proceeded to visualize the various locations in which the evidence contained in our database has been found on an interactive map (Figure 4). This online map uses the Vega¹⁵ visualization grammar and displays places on a neutral background map. A very simple map with only land mass as background was chosen. This is preferable over a more detailed map with the boundaries of either modern states or even a map containing the provinces of the Roman Empire as these were also subject to change over time (if the locations need to be visualized in context with geographic or cultural layers appropriate to the time period, we suggest downloading the records and loading them in a dedicated Geographic Information System). The online map is zoomable, so the location details for dense clusters can be made legible by zooming in. Clicking a location opens the document view.

3 Results

We are currently implementing the interactive map and completing the dataset compilation. For now, despite anticipating the first results, we can already see a variety of very interesting patterns emerge from the dataset, patterns that were only speculative until now. These largely confirm the provisional results produced and discussed by Dingemans (2024). They indicate various things: an increase in the number of sources throughout the centuries, followed by a rapid drop towards the end of Antiquity. But also differing levels of dispersion – *Diasporic Hubs* – throughout the Mediterranean basin which document historically significant ups-and-downs in Jewish mobility during the time of the Roman Empire.

While noting a steady increased that peaked in the fourth century, followed by a rapid decline of evidence from the fifth century CE onwards, the following aspects

¹⁵ <https://vega.github.io/vega/>

Figure 4: A map showing the geographical distribution of inscriptions, as displayed in I-Analyzer. Hovering will show in which source the inscription was documented; clicking will open the document view.

became clear: firstly, there is a significant increase in the amount of evidence during the fourth century CE which, not surprisingly but still significantly, goes hand in hand with an increase in the number of regions where Jewish evidence appears. In the first century CE, only five regions (Asia Minor, the Crimea, Egypt, Greece and Libya) are known to have contained evidence that was indicative of Jewish presence. In the fourth century this has changed significantly: now no less than twelve regions can be shown to contain Jewish evidence. Then, in the fifth century, we see a dramatic decline in Jewish evidence, which not only coincided with, but was most probably also caused by the social, political, environmental, economic, and cultural unrest that occurred during the fifth century CE (Fuks, 2017; Jones, 1973; Safrai, 1998). Not surprisingly, the number of regions where there is evidence for a Jewish presence drops dramatically from twelve in the fourth to a mere six in the sixth century. Also this drop was not just quantitative in nature. The quality of the evidence (expensive inscriptions, large buildings and so forth) also experiences a serious decline.

As for other patterns that emerge out of our database, we noticed that Asia Minor and Italy contributed very significant proportions of the evidence, making them the *Diasporic Hubs* in the Diasporic network, for nearly half of all the evidence was attributable to these two regions. That Jews moved to Rome constantly, is not difficult to explain. Rome, after all, was the *Caput Mundi* that attracted migrants from all over the Roman Empire, as indicated by historical scholarship, and, most recently, by genetic (aDNA) studies as well. Asia Minor, on the other hand, was heavily urbanized and had long been home to Jews, starting in the Hellenistic era. For Jews Asia Minor was clearly a land of opportunity. Further contributing factors here were no doubt the fact that Asia Minor was geographically near and connected to Judaea via the extensive Roman road network, as well as the sea routes from the port of Caesarea Maritima in Judaea (Hezsner, 2011).

Rome, on the other hand, was not necessarily close, housing one of the largest Diaspora communities and it inevitably kept attracting Jews from elsewhere, simply because migrants are known to travel to places where a migrant community is already in place. It is conceivable, therefore, that these two regions served as hubs: once established, they kept attracting more and more Jews that originated from the Jewish homeland and even from other places in the Jewish Diaspora during the Roman period.

The final version of the dataset will offer the user an even more complete picture than we can currently offer. In all of this we will not only provide an interface that both academic and popular public can use to inspect the data for the purposes of their own research, but we also anticipate having enough evidence ourselves to come up with a sensible reconstruction aimed at explaining the mechanisms and underlying structures of Jewish mobility and migration into ancient Europe by using the interactive map. Our publication will be part of a field that has gained popularity in recent years: Ancient migration (Bloch, 2022; Collar, 2013; Gruen, 2002; Hezsner, 2011; Horden and Purcell, 2000; Lampinen and Ferrándiz, 2022; Rutgers et al., 2019; Scheidel, 2013; Tacoma, 2016).

4 Conclusion

From the discussion presented above it follows that approaching the phenomenon of Jewish historical migration by way of an interactive platform of the kind described here offers many opportunities for future research. First of all, presenting the evidence in the way we propose here means that at any time we can easily integrate new data so that the evidence on which one bases one's conclusions is not just as comprehensive as it should be, but also always up to date. Second, because all the available data have been digitized, one can look for larger patterns and have sustained discussions on what such patterns could possibly mean (which ought to include discussion about statistical significance). Third, our project is a good point of departure for discussions about the methodology of how epigraphical (meta)data currently available in academic texts can be made more generally available according to the principles of FAIR data and software. And fourth and final, because of these principles and because our data are freely available to all, this project embraces the notion that work in this area is a collective effort where anyone interested in these materials and in the questions they raise has free access to them at any moment in time.

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Accessing the Republic. Entity Extraction from the Resolutions of the Dutch States-General

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1. Introduction

In the REPUBLIC project, we are making digitally accessible the resolutions of the States General (SG) of the Dutch Republic (1576-1796). The SG were the central ruling body of the Dutch Republic, with representatives from each province in the republic, deciding on matters of interest common to all seven provinces, such as foreign policy, defence, trade and religion. The resolutions are transcripts of the decisions made by the SG in their daily meetings. The archive consists of almost 500,000 handwritten and printed pages and around 700,000-900,000 resolutions in total. Each resolution consists of at least two parts, a proposition, introducing the issue at stake, and a decision (Thomassen, 2019a).

We have made machine-readable transcriptions and segmented the text into individual resolution using OCR, HTR and structure extraction (Koolen et al., 2020, 2023b) and made them available and full-text searchable via a public search application¹ as well as downloadable datasets on Zenodo Koolen et al. (2025). Beyond full-text search, we offer additional access points for researchers to navigate and comprehend this large and complex resource. These access points are based on several categories of named entities, including person names, institutions and geographical names and various domain- and collection-specific entity types, which are operationalised in the application both as search facets and as links in the resolution text to further information.

Named Entity Recognition (NER) on historic documents has come along in leaps and bounds in the last decade (Ehrmann et al., 2023). Improvements are partially due to the rapid increase in the availability of large historic document collections (Kaplan and Di Lenardo, 2017; Terras, 2022, 2011), the improvement of easily trainable Automatic Text Recognition (ATR) models (Colutto et al., 2019; Kahle et al., 2017; van Koert et al., 2024), sequence tagging models and NLP frameworks (Akbik et al., 2019),

¹ <https://app.goetgevonden.nl>

and the development of language-specific Large Language Models (LLM) for historic languages (Manjavacas and Fonteyn, 2021, 2022).

The domain of historic administrative governmental documents brings its own challenges for NER. Beyond the fact that historic languages can differ from modern variants in spelling, vocabulary, morphology and syntax, there are additional challenges in dealing with highly specific and formulaic terminology (Koolen et al., 2023a), many abbreviations, and long and complex nested entity references (Aguilar et al., 2016; Prada Ziegler, 2024). Aguilar et al. (2016) describes a strategy for training a NER tagger for identifying person names and locations in Medieval Latin charters, and the challenge of single entity mentions that reference a person, a location and an organisation. Prada Ziegler (2024) focuses on historic land registers, where nesting is particularly challenging problem, and presents an approach for recursively handling the multiple levels of nesting. Orasmaa et al. (2022) created a test collection of annotated named entities in a corpus of 19th century Estonian parish records, and found that NER models perform well on person names but struggle with locations. NER has also been conducted on parliamentary debates (Hyvönen et al., 2024; Puren et al., 2025) and directories (Abadie et al., 2022), where the semi-structured nature of speeches and directory listing present their own challenges and opportunities for recognising and resolving named entities.

Evaluating and curating NER output should be informed by how the output will be used. In our case, the recognised entity references serve two main purposes. First, recognised entities are highlighted in the text presented to users of the REPUBLIC search application,² which helps these users to spot these entities and quickly grasp which persons, organisations and locations are involved in a resolution. Second, the entity references are curated and offered as search facets with which users can easily select subsets of the resolutions and get an overview of the entities that occur in the resolutions that are returned as results to a search query.

In this paper we report on our approach to extracting entities from the REPUBLIC corpus, including evaluation of NER taggers for different types of entities, and our findings from curating three entity types. Based on findings by Akbik et al. (2019), we experiment with taggers that combine different types of embedding models, e.g. character embeddings, static word embeddings and BERT-based embeddings.

We address the following research questions:

- How well can we identify named entities in the resolutions?
- How can we curate entity mentions to make them useful for information access?
- What can we learn from the curation of entities about the corpus of resolutions and the operation of the States General?

Although the NER output is far from perfect, our analysis shows that it can help users in drilling down into the corpus and get insights in the relationships between (types of) entities and the issues discussed in the resolutions.

Our approach to curating the entity references is not unique, but we describe the underlying model in the hope that it offers a generalisable process that has several advantages over traditional approaches to curation. Most important is that our approach makes curation decision explicit and reusable, allowing the process to be repeated when new versions of NER output are created.

² <https://app.goetgevonden.nl>

2. The Resolutions as a Corpus

The corpus of the resolutions of the States General of the Dutch Republic consists of 278,872 scans and 537,032 pages, divided across 657 books.³ The resolutions were recorded as minutes by the greffier, who was present during the daily meetings and who was responsible for recording and archiving decisions, and providing previous resolutions to the meeting that were relevant for a matter at hand. The minutes were extended to full resolutions before being read at the start of the next meeting for approval. More information on the recording process is provided by Riemsdijk (1885); Thomassen (2019a,b), and on the digitisation and structure extraction conducted in the REPUBLIC project by Koolen et al. (2020, 2023a,b). In the project, we work with the fully extended resolutions. There are an estimated 700,000-900,000 resolutions⁴ that together contain around 130 million words. The text of the scans has been automatically transcribed using Loghi, (van Koert et al., 2024) which was trained on ground truth scans and transcriptions created with a team of volunteers. The 107 scans of printed transcriptions and 515 scans on handwritten transcriptions are available on Zenodo (Sluijter et al., 2023; van Koert, 2023). There are handwritten and printed books of resolutions and each book contains either only *ordinary* or only *secret* resolutions. Most books contain handwritten text, but for the *ordinary* resolutions of 1703-1796, we used the printed versions that were available. The secret resolutions were, for reasons of security, never printed, and cover the period 1592-1796 (see Appendix A for more details on our selection and the complex nature of the corpus). Text recognition quality is high, with a Character Error Rate (CER) below 1% for the printed resolutions and around 2-3% for the handwritten resolutions (van Koert et al., 2024).

Each resolution contains a proposition and a decision.⁵ For most propositions, the resolution mentions who introduced that proposition to the SG, and if the proposition was made via a document (letter, report, petition, bill, etc.), the date and location of sending it. The resolutions often mention organisations there are involved in the matters discussed, such as government, religious, military and naval institutions, as well as committees of SG members who were tasked to investigate the matter at hand, before coming to a final decision.

The corpus of resolutions is therefore connected to a larger archive of correspondence and decision making of the SG and is considered a key resource for studying the political history of the Dutch Republic and its interactions with the rest of the world.

3. Annotating Entities in the Resolutions

For digital access, the standard entity types of person, organisation and location are useful, but there are additional entity types that we think are valuable in the context of the resolutions and that make it easier to study aspects of the decision-making process, such as the committees that were tasked with investigating a proposed matter further, and references to earlier resolutions. We identify eight types of entities:

³ This is the set of books used in the REPUBLIC project. The full archives of the States General contains many more books, some with copies of the resolutions, resolutions in minute form or with indexes to the resolutions that were created by the greffier's office, as well as all the incoming and correspondence and reports by committees.

⁴ The exact number is unknown, as segmenting the transcribed text into individual resolutions contains errors.

⁵ Although in the early years, up to roughly 1637, this model was used inconsistently, with a substantial set of resolutions containing only a decision paragraph.

- Person (PER): a person identified by name and identifying attributions or qualifications.
- Person attributions/qualifications (ATT): the attributions or qualifications, such as title, job, legal status or relationship to the SG that is used to identify a person.
- Committees (COM): the committees of the SG that are tasked with investigation matters raised in discussing a proposition.
- Organisations (ORG): organisations including the governing bodies of regions (e.g. the court of the Kingdom of France)
- Locations (LOC): geographical locations, including as part of the names of organisations or person attributions.
- Dates (DAT): explicit date reference, absolute (e.g. 15 April 1678) or relative (the 15th of last month).
- Resolutions references (RES): explicit references to an earlier resolution.
- Other names (OTH): any other names.

Figure 1: Tagging entities using INCEpTION.

Persons are rarely mentioned just by name, but almost always with attributions or qualifications such as their job (*ambassador, captain, carpenter*), title (*duke, princess*) or legal status (*widow, minor, heir*).

A difficulty arises in tagging locations that are a part of a reference to a person or organisation, as the named location can represent both the geographical location, the political organisation or the persons in that location. The ACE coding schema introduced geopolitical entities (GPEs) (Doddington et al., 2004)), but we opted to annotate multiple types separately.

We note that person attributions differ from the rest in that they do not refer to specific entities, but to generic groups of persons with specific attributes (therefore,

are strictly speaking not named entities). We decided to include them and tag them separately, because we think they provide a valuable additional access point to the resolutions, as they allow researchers to zoom in on all resolutions dealing with certain groups of people.

We iteratively developed annotation instructions, starting from a draft set of instructions, and updating them while several project members annotated a set of resolutions and discussed any disagreements, difficult cases and uncertainties.⁶ The annotations of this development process were then discarded and a different set of resolutions was chosen for the annotation phase.

To train NER taggers, we worked with a group of 24 volunteers⁷ who annotated the resolutions in two phases. In the first phase, which ran from September until April 2023, we created a ground truth dataset of 1,631 full resolutions (370,560 word tokens) randomly sampled from the printed resolutions of 1705-1796. In the second phase, which ran from July until September 2023, 513 paragraphs (28,387 word tokens) from the handwritten resolutions of 1597-1702 were annotated.⁸ The entities were manually tagged using INCEpTION Klie et al. (2018) (see Figure 1). Although the length of the annotated paragraphs varies strongly (ranging from a single word to 6,269 words), the vast majority of annotated paragraphs range between 27 words (5th percentile) and 650 words (95th percentile). More details are available in Appendix A.1. Each resolution was annotated by three annotators. Agreement was high, with Cohen’s κ between pairs of annotators ranging between 0.7 and 0.9. Afterwards, a curator checked all annotations and resolved disagreements (mostly regarding the exact boundaries of entity references).

3.1. Nested Entities

One challenge is that entities can be nested, with e.g. a person entity containing an attribution, in turn containing an organisation, which can contain a geographical location. Prada Ziegler (2024) reports on the problem of nested entities in historical land registers of Basel, where around 60% of entity references are part of larger entity references (compared to 12% in the ACE 2005 data set⁹). Our data has many similarities with the Basel land registers, as 17,481 out of all 27,886 (63%) entity references contain a nested entity.

The fraction of entity overlap between pairs of types is shown in Table 1, indicating what fraction of entities of the type in the row overlap with the entity type in the column. Thus, of all committee references (COM), 25% contain at least one person attribution (ATT), 35% contain a location (LOC), 1% contain an organisation (ORG) and 91% contain a person name (PER). Locations are frequently part of person names (42%) person attributions (39%) and committees (35%), and the majority of person name references (69%) contain attribution information as well. Resolution references (RES) almost always contain a date (98%), but we found that only 21% of all dates are part of resolution references (in other words, most date mentions are not part of

⁶ The annotation instructions are published with the entity data (Dijkstra et al., 2025)

⁷ The REPUBLIC project worked with a large set of volunteers during the project, mostly for making and correcting ground truth transcription for the HTR and OCR step. The volunteers who signed up for the entity annotation task are a subset of this. All had developed knowledge and expertise regarding the nature of this corpus during the earlier transcription phase.

⁸ The handwritten resolutions were done in a second phase because their transcriptions were not available for the first phase. The set is smaller because we had limited time and had to prioritise other tasks with the volunteers of our project. Again, see Appendix A for more details.

⁹ <https://catalog.ldc.upenn.edu/LDC2006T06>

	ATT	COM	DAT	LOC	NAM	ORG	PER	RES
ATT	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.39	0.01	0.08	0.15	0.00
COM	0.25	0.00	0.00	0.35	0.00	0.01	0.91	0.00
DAT	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
LOC	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
NAM	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.04	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
ORG	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.32	0.00	0.01	0.08	0.00
PER	0.69	0.00	0.00	0.42	0.01	0.09	0.10	0.00
RES	0.00	0.00	0.98	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01

Table 1: Fraction of entities of one type (row) that contain at least one entity of another type (column). In bold are fractions above 0.10.

larger entity mentions).

The way we model this has consequences for information access and the ease with which research questions can be studied. Consider the following example:

Henricus Gerhardus de Beveren Esveld, Predikant in de Gereformeerde Gemeente te Schoondyke onder het Classis van Walcheren, be roepen zynde tot Predikant in de Gemeente te Enkhuisen (EN: *Henricus Gerhardus de Beveren Esveld, Pastor in the Reformed Municipality at Schoondyke, under the Classis of Walcheren, named Pastor in the Municipality of Enkhuisen*)

This names a specific person, but the reference also contains entities of other types, e.g. the locations Schoondyke and Enkhuisen and their respective municipalities and the classis of Walcheren¹⁰, which contains the location of Walcheren.

Users may be looking for this specific person, but also for any of the entities nested inside this person name. Therefore, we want to identify and give access to all entities contained in a complex reference.

The way we model this is with overlapping annotations. In XML this would correspond to the following structure (text-centric view):

```
<PER>Henricus Gerhardus de Beveren Esveld, <ATT>Predikant in de
<ORG>Gereformeerde Gemeente te <LOC>Schoondyke</LOC></ORG>
<ORG>onder het Classis van <LOC>Walcheren</LOC></ORG></ATT>,
<ATT>be roepen zynde tot Predikant in de <ORG>Gemeente te
<LOC>Enkhuisen</LOC></ORG></ATT></PER>
```

With indentation per level (data-centric view), the structure is clearer:

¹⁰ A *classis* is a supra-municipal meeting of multiple churches.

```

<PER>Henricus Gerhardus de Beveren Esveld,
  <ATT>Predikant
    <ORG>in de Gereformeerde Gemeente te
      <LOC>Schoondyke</LOC>
    </ORG>
    <ORG>onder het Classis van
      <LOC>Walcheren</LOC>
    </ORG>
  </ATT>,
  <ATT>be roepen zynde tot Predikant in de
    <ORG>Gemeente te
      <LOC>Enkhuisen</LOC>
    </ORG>
  </ATT>
</PER>

```

It is possible that an entity of a specific type contains another entity of the same type. For instance, a person name reference may contain an attribution that contains another person name. This is demonstrated in the following example:

```

Jan Barthold Wenthold, minderjaige Soon van Johan Ludolph ten Bhem Wenthold ; ... (EN:
Jan Barthold Wenthold, underage Son of Johan Ludolph ten Bhem Wenthold ; ...)

```

We consider the full phrase to be the most precise identifier for this underage son. This is tagged in INCEpTION with three entities as shown in Figure 1. We create two types of representations for training taggers. In one representation, a separate tagger is trained for each type of entity, in the other, a single tagger is trained to recognise all types of entities. Regardless of which representation we use, the flat representation required for training a sequence tagger lacks information on nesting. From (partial) overlap between entities of different types, we can reconstruct the nesting to some extent. In the above example, the person attribution partially overlaps with both the longest person name reference as the person name nested inside it. But this will not correctly identify all nesting, as in a flat structure, it is not always possible to distinguish between a nesting of two entities of the same type and a sequence of two entities of the same type. There are techniques that address these issues (Wang et al., 2022), such as the ‘second-best’ strategy by Shibuya and Hovy (2020) or the recursive strategy developed by Prada Ziegler (2024). As Table 1 shows, nesting of entities of the same type mainly occurs with person references and person attributions. In Section 5 we explain how we curate the recognised entities. Since we deconstruct composite attributions to give access to resolutions via individual terms, we do not need correct nesting information. For person references, we lack the resources to resolve the majority of them. In future work, we want to properly extract nested person references. Given the similarity to the complex person references in the Basel land registers, we consider using the recursive approach by Prada Ziegler (2024).

3.2. Entity Length

The references to entities have a high variation in length, from a single words to refer to a e.g. location, to a long phrase of dozens of words to describe a person or organisation as shown above. This variation in length is relevant for how well taggers can identify the correct boundaries. For the long person reference to *Henricus Gerhardus de Beveren*

Jan	Barthold	Wenthold	,	minderjarige	Soon	van	Johan	Ludolph	ten	Bhem	Wenthold
<i>tagged in inception</i>											
								B-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER
				B-ATT	I-ATT	I-ATT	I-ATT	I-ATT	I-ATT	I-ATT	I-ATT
B-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER
<i>per-type training</i>											
				B-ATT	I-ATT	I-ATT	I-ATT	I-ATT	I-ATT	I-ATT	I-ATT
B-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER	B-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER
<i>combined types training</i>											
B-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER	B-ATT	I-ATT	I-ATT	B-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER	I-PER

Table 2: Tagging of nested entities and the representations used for training individual taggers for single types or a single tagger for all entities

Figure 2: Distribution of the length of entities per type, in the logarithm of the number of words per entity.

Esveld above, a tagger could place the end boundary of the entity at various places in the long string, based on different levels of nesting. If the tagger leaves out the last attribution, organisation and location it has made a mistake according to the ground truth data, but not completely failed. Moreover, for curating the tagged entity references (see Section 5), the length has consequences for the possible amount of variation found in references to the same entity.

The distribution of entity lengths in the human-annotated data is shown in Figure 2, with the length of entities in number of words on a logarithmic scale. This scale is chosen because for some entity types the length ranges between a single words and dozens of words. Descriptive statistics are given in Table 3, with mean, standard deviation and 25th, 50th (median) and 75th percentiles.

There is a large difference in the length of entities across entity types. Locations are the shortest, with the majority of locations being at most 1 word, while the longest location name is 32 words. Attributions are slightly longer, with a median length of 3 words, but with high variation ($Std = 3.8$), and some very long attributions.

Person names have the highest variation, with a median of 4 words but 25% of all person names are 8 words or longer. Long person names tend to contain attributions, locations and organisations.

Long organisation entities, i.e. 20 words or more, often contain lists of organisations, e.g. a single reference to the deputies of a list of provinces (“Heeren Gedeputeerden van de Provinciën van Gelderland , van Zeeland , van Vriesland , van Overijssel en

Type	Count	Mean	Std	Min	25%	50%	75%	Max
COM	391	15.9	3.0	6	14	16	18	34
DAT	3,034	4.5	2.1	1	3	4	5	40
ATT	7,743	4.2	3.8	1	1	3	6	39
LOC	6,803	1.9	2.0	1	1	1	2	32
NAM	360	4.0	2.1	1	3	4	5	19
ORG	3,437	5.5	3.2	1	3	5	8	33
PER	5,422	6.3	5.3	1	3	4	8	74
RES	639	10.3	3.6	1	8.5	10	12	44
Total	27,829	4.5	4.2	1	1	3	6	74

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of entity lengths in the human-annotated data in number of words.

van Stad en Lande”). This is a reference to a single group, the Gentlemen deputies of five of the seven provinces.

Committees are always multi-word phrases of at least six words long and the majority are 16 words or more. Resolution references are also longer phrases with 50% of all occurrences being at least 10 words long.

4. Training and Evaluating NER Taggers

To identify and classify entities in the resolutions, we trained multiple NER taggers, one per entity type.¹¹ The reason for this is that nested entities can more easily be extracted. Each tagger identifies a specific entity type, and by computing overlap (in terms of ranges in the running text of a resolution) between entities, we can determine which entities are contained within larger entities.

The resolutions were written over a period of 220 years, in which spelling and vocabulary changed, and words had no fixed spelling (partly due to there no being no official spelling rules for Dutch until 1804). On top of that, the OCR and HTR processes introduced recognition errors, which further increased the degree of orthographic variation. Therefore, the NER taggers should be able to deal with this.

For training taggers, we split the ground truth data into sets for training, validation and testing, using a 80/10/10 split. We used the Python Flair library (Akbik et al., 2019), which allowed us to combine multiple types of embeddings, including contextual character embeddings (Akbik et al., 2018) and word-level Fasttext embeddings (Bojanowski et al., 2017), both developed from scratch based on the texts of the resolutions, and GysBERT (Manjavacas and Fonteyn, 2022), which is a BERT-based model trained on historic Dutch.

We trained NER taggers using all possible combinations of embeddings and selected the best one per entity type. In our experimental setup, we trained models with any possible combination of five different binary parameters and the three types of embeddings (*Character*, *FastText* and *GysBERT*), using as ground truth either all entity types or each of the eight entity types separately (see Appendix B for details on the training parameters and links to code).

To evaluate and compare the models, we use set-based metrics *precision*, *recall* and

¹¹ The full `REPUBLIC` code base, including all code for NER and curation and the trained NER models have been made available. See Appendix B.

Figure 3: F_1 score of best models per entity type after training only on the printed resolutions of 1705-1796 (left) and on both printed resolutions and the handwritten resolutions of 1597-1702 (right).

F_1 (the F -score that gives equal weight to precision and recall. In determining the correctness of a tagged entity, the default, strict, interpretation is that an entity is correctly tagged if the boundaries (start and end offsets) of the tagged entity exactly align with the entity in the ground truth. Especially for longer entity, it can be insightful to also include a more lenient interpretation that considers a tagged entity correct if it partially overlaps with the ground truth entity. For instance, if the ground truth entity is “the deputies of the provinces of Gelderland and of Vriesland” and the model tagged only “the deputies of the provinces of Gelderland”. Arguably, the tagged entity is still useful for users to quickly locate entities in the text (e.g. when entities are highlighted) and to select resolutions that mention the deputies of the province of Gelderland.

For model comparison, we only consider the strict interpretation. For the more detailed analysis in Section 4.2 we also consider the lenient interpretation.

As described in Section 4, we started with annotating entities in 1633 ordinary resolutions from the printed volumes of 1705-1796. Once we managed to extract decent quality paragraphs from the handwritten volumes of ordinary resolutions of 1597-1702¹² we also annotated entities in 513 handwritten paragraphs. Adding the ground truth annotations for the handwritten material made the taggers more robust, as can be seen in Figure 3, where the F_1 scores of the best models per entity type are shown when using only the ground truth of the printed resolutions (left side) and all ground truth (right side).

The evaluation results for the best performing model per entity type (in terms of F_1) are shown in Table 4. To understand the relative strengths of the different types of embeddings, we also include a comparative evaluation of models trained on a single type of embeddings. The Test column indicates which entity type the model was tested on, the Train column indicates whether the model was trained on only the annotations of the given entity type, or on the annotations of all types. In the latter case, the model is trained to tag all entity types, but we use only the tagged entities of the specific type for evaluation. The *support* column indicates the number of entities of each type in the test set.

In line with earlier work (Boros et al. (2020); Ghannay et al. (2020); Rodrigues Alves et al. (2018); Yang et al. (2018)), we find that all best models use Recurrent Neural

¹² For the secret resolutions and for the ordinary resolutions of the years 1576-1596 we had no good quality text yet at the time of ground truth creation. See Appendix A for more details.

Entity type		Embeddings	Prec.	Recall	F1	Support
Test	Train					
COM	COM	Char	1.00	0.73	0.85	41
	COM	FT	0.77	0.73	0.75	41
	COM	Gys	0.96	0.59	0.73	41
	COM	Best=Char+Gys	1.00	0.73	0.85	41
DAT	DAT	Char	0.90	0.88	0.89	249
	DAT	FT	0.87	0.86	0.87	249
	DAT	Gys	0.88	0.82	0.85	249
	DAT	Best=Char	0.90	0.88	0.89	249
ATT	ATT	Char	0.46	0.35	0.39	573
	ATT	FT	0.54	0.49	0.52	573
	ATT	Gys	0.61	0.46	0.53	573
	ATT	Best=Char+FT+Gys	0.57	0.56	0.56	573
LOC	LOC	Char	0.70	0.65	0.67	570
	LOC	FT	0.75	0.74	0.74	570
	LOC	Gys	0.79	0.60	0.68	570
	LOC	Best=FT+Gys	0.79	0.76	0.77	570
ORG	ORG	Char	0.75	0.60	0.66	283
	ORG	FT	0.80	0.71	0.75	283
	ORG	Gys	0.75	0.56	0.63	283
	ORG	Best=Char+FT+Gys	0.82	0.71	0.76	283
PER	PER	Char	0.72	0.58	0.64	405
	PER	FT	0.75	0.72	0.74	405
	PER	Gys	0.75	0.68	0.71	405
	PER	Best=Char+Gys	0.82	0.69	0.75	405
RES	RES	Char	0.81	0.62	0.70	57
	all	FT	0.83	0.67	0.74	57
	all	Gys	0.83	0.58	0.68	57
	all	Best=FT+Gys	0.82	0.70	0.76	57
OTH	All	Char	0.00	0.00	0.00	47
	All	FT	0.67	0.21	0.32	47
	All	Gys	0.30	0.21	0.25	47
	All	Best=Char+FT+Gys	0.63	0.26	0.36	47

Table 4: Evaluation results of NER taggers, trained on different types and combinations of embeddings, on the test set (*ordinary* resolutions of the periods 1597-1702 and 1705-1796).

Networks (RNNs) instead of linear layers and a Conditional Random Fields (CRF) model for the prediction layer to capture dependencies between sequences of tags (introduced by Huang et al. (2015)).¹³

The Train column indicates that most entity types are best served by training a tagger only on entities of that type. The two exceptions are resolution references (RES) and other names (OTH), which are better identified when the tagger is trained to also tag other types of entities. We speculate that for resolution references, it is beneficial to train a tagger that also learns to tag dates, because references to previous resolution always contain references to a specific date. Because the task of recognising dates seems easier (many models achieve high accuracy for tagging dates), we expect that models that separately tag the date part of resolution references, make it easier to correctly recognise the rest of the reference as a resolution reference.

For most entity types, performance in terms of F_1 is in the range of 0.75-0.90, with high precision and recall around or above 0.70, indicating that the majority of entities are identified correctly. The two exceptions are Persons attributions (ATT) and Other names (OTH). Since we did not plan to use the latter category for information access, and most other types can be identified without training on all types by a single model, the low performance causes little problems. For attributions the difficulty is partly in correctly identifying the boundaries, leading to low recall (under the lenient interpretation, performance is much higher, see Section 4.2) and partly in tagging too much, i.e. mentions of attributions that do not refer to a specific entity.

4.1. Comparing embedding types

For seven types, it is best to include the GysBERT model, which suggests that it helps to have some word- and phrase-level context to identify these types of entities. For Committees and Dates, using only a character-based embeddings model leads to better or at least equal performance compared to including word-level or contextual embeddings. We speculate that this is because they have a very standardised surface form, that merely require recognising the right character context, without interpreting deeper word-level semantics.

FastText outperforms Character embeddings for all types except committees and dates, and outperforms GysBERT for all types except attributions. FastText represents each words by sets of ngrams of length 3-6, whereas GysBERT represents words by one or a few sub-tokens. The better performance of FastText could mean that explicitly representing words by multiple levels of partially overlapping sub-tokens better captures the range of spelling variations found in long serial publications like the resolutions.

GysBERT performs better than Character embeddings for attributions, locations and persons entity types. The difference between the best combination model and the best model of the individual embedding types is relatively small.

4.2. Period-specific evaluation

Koolen et al. (2023a) found that the spelling and use of formulaic language in the resolutions changes over the 220 year period. Therefore, it is possible that the performance of taggers differs across resolutions written in different periods. Based on the stylistic periodisation introduced in (Koolen et al., 2023a), we split the test data into

¹³ We further experimented with various parameters of the PyTorch transformer models and FLAIR Stacked Embeddings, but leave out these details because of limited space.

label	Support			F_1 strict			F_1 lenient		
	1597	1705	1754	1597	1705	1754	1597	1705	1754
	1702	1753	1796	1702	1753	1796	1702	1753	1796
COM	2	17	22	1.00	0.97	0.74	1.00	0.97	0.74
DAT	27	132	90	0.88	0.87	0.88	0.96	0.97	0.94
ATT	82	225	266	0.60	0.62	0.50	0.85	0.84	0.77
LOC	74	242	254	0.85	0.81	0.75	0.93	0.88	0.89
OTH	4	9	34	0.00	0.75	0.33	0.00	0.94	0.54
ORG	30	117	136	0.73	0.76	0.70	0.81	0.83	0.85
PER	51	181	173	0.74	0.79	0.61	0.93	0.93	0.89
RES	4	23	30	0.67	0.71	0.75	0.89	0.81	0.89

Table 5: Evaluation of the NER taggers for resolutions written in different periods, with support per period (left), and the scores using strict scoring (center) and lenient scoring (right).

smaller test sets per period, so that we can compare performance of the taggers on resolutions from different periods. The available amount of ground truth per period differs strongly, with certain entity types having no or only a few positive examples for certain periods, we grouped the periods into three larger periods that each have enough positive examples to do a meaningful comparison: 1597-1702, 1705-1753, and 1754-1796.¹⁴

The strict and lenient evaluation scores per period are shown in Table 5. Columns 2-4 contain the number of positive examples per entity type and period. Particularly in the period 1597-1702 there is amount of test data is limited, meaning there is more uncertainty about the scores. Focusing on the strict scoring first (columns 5-7), the differences between 1597-1702 and 1705-1753 are small. For most entity types, occurrences are harder to recognise precisely in resolutions in the period 1754-1796. The only exceptions are dates (where there is almost no difference between the three periods) and resolution references, where performance is highest in the most recent period. With the lenient interpretation, the differences between the first two and the last period are smaller, suggesting that the difficulty in the last period is partially due to finding the correct boundaries. This is contrary to what we expected, as earlier work has established that the resolutions become increasingly formulaic, and we expect more formulaic phrasings of entities to be more easily recognisable. We have not yet been able to establish why this happens, but it serves as a warning that entity information in the latter period is less reliable.

5. Operationalising NER output

This section details the process of resolving textual references to named entities so that they can be operationalised in the search application as search facets and links in the text. A first version of the curated entity data has been published on Zenodo Dijkstra et al. (2025).

Operationalising entities found by automated processes is a problem of data linking, for which there at least two broad strands of research. We describe our approach using

¹⁴ ground truth for the years 1703 and 1704 are missing, since we do not yet have resolution texts for these years.

the term *curation* because what we describe below differs in various ways from what is commonly used in the literature on recognition (NER), detection, (NED) and linking (EL) of entities. We do more than just link entity mentions and what we do differs slightly per entity type. We also categorise entities in a bottom-up data-driven fashion. Moreover, these processes contain many manual steps, and for this combination of steps, curation is a more common term.

5.1. Approaches to Linking Entity Mentions

One strand focuses on linking individual entity mentions to external knowledge bases Guellil et al. (2024); Shen et al. (2014). Often used external knowledge bases are DBpedia, Wikidata and Wikipedia (Hachey et al., 2013; Möller et al., 2022). However, these resources have a bias in their coverage of persons, locations and organisations towards the more famous or well-researched entities (Ilievski et al., 2018). This problem is particularly relevant for early modern texts, where coverage in external knowledge bases of the persons, committees and organisations mentioned in the text is even lower (Fabo and Poibeau, 2019; Munnely and Lawless, 2018; Pontes et al., 2020). Munnely and Lawless (2018) analysed a sample of 16 Irish depositions written in 1641, and found 480 reference to 283 entities distinct entities, of which only 64 (23%) had a representation in DBpedia. There are historic knowledge bases that are more relevant for historic documents of specific periods, languages and domains, but the examples we found focus on texts and knowledge bases of more recent periods. Brando et al. (2016) used the Linked Data repository of the French National Library for linking to 19th and 20th century literary authors, while Heino et al. (2017) developed WarSampo for linking to Finnish persons and geolocations for the period 1920-1950, to deal with the many changes due to Finland ceding large areas of land to Russia at the end of the Second World War.

The other strand of research is on linking historical records (see Bailey et al. (2020) and Abramitzky et al. (2021) for overviews), where entity mentions are not linked to external resources, but to other mentions of the same entity within the dataset (internal linking). In this strand there is a strong focus on linking census records (Abramitzky et al., 2020; Bailey et al., 2020; Ruggles et al., 2018) which are typically centred on persons and locations, although it has also been explored for linking cultural heritage collections (Van Hooland and Verborgh, 2014). The record linking approaches featured in the literature share many commonalities, such as using logical criteria to rule out certain matches, using edit distance and other forms of fuzzy matching to reduce variation and using weights or probabilities to rank or filter candidate links.

Just as with *recognising* named entities in text, *linking* them is made more challenging in texts that are the result of automatic text recognition (Ehrmann, 2008; Linhares Pontes et al., 2019; Pontes et al., 2020; Stern et al., 2012; van Strien et al., 2020). Text recognition errors increase the variation in spelling, which makes it more difficult both to recognise names and to then reduce the variation to a single form.

5.2. Linking Entities in the Resolutions

The corpus of resolutions is a serial publication written in the context of daily meetings of the same governing body, so it is likely that a substantial set of entities will be mentioned in multiple resolutions. Given the low coverage of external knowledge bases for persons, committees and organisations for early modern texts (Munnely and Lawless, 2018; Pontes et al., 2020), we focus on internal linking of entities, and

Figure 4: Complementary Cumulative Distribution Function of the frequency of entity reference strings (left) and resolved or curated entities (right). Both X and Y axis are on a logarithmic scale to show straight lines typical of long-tail distributions.

only link the resolved entities to external knowledge bases for a subset of locations, persons and organisations (Section 5.5). The internal links give users of the digital publication and search application a way to navigate and select resolutions via the different types of entities.

The resolutions lack the kind of structured elements that census records have, at least at the level that we could exploit for this curation phase. For each entity mention we therefore have limited contextual information.

What we do have is frequency information on the entity mentions, and their distribution provides us with some metrics. In a natural text like the resolutions, the entity distribution is marked by their importance for the organisation that created the texts. For all entity types, important entities for the States General appear more often in the text of the resolutions and also have more orthographic variations. Here we distinguish between the frequency of distinct *reference strings* and *entity mentions*. The reference strings ‘Raad van State’ and ‘Raed van Staatte’ each occur thousands of times. They are distinct strings, but refer to the same entity. The entity mentions are the sum of the occurrences of the reference strings. The frequency distribution of the reference strings is highly skewed, with most reference strings occurring only once and relatively few occurring (tens of) thousands of times. We show the Complementary Cumulative Distribution Function (CCDF) of this distribution in Figure 4 for the reference strings (left side) and the curated entities (right side). The CCDF shows the probability that a string or entity occurs at least x times. That is, for the frequency $x = 100$, the Y axis shows the probability of a string or entity occurring at least 100 times ($X \geq 100$). The CCDF visualisation shows smooth curves that are easier to distinguish from and compare with each other at all points of the frequency range. All entity types have a distribution with a long tail.¹⁵ Although most *distinct* reference strings occur only once, they represent only a small fraction of the total number of strings, which are dominated by the tens or hundreds of reference strings that each occur (tens of) thousands of times. The distribution of person references (left side plot) falls fastest, meaning there are relatively many low-frequency references compared to e.g. the distribution of location references. The CCDF shows that a person reference string has a 0.1%

¹⁵ From a statistical modelling perspective, the tail consist of the small number of highly frequent entities, from a information extraction perspective, the tail is the opposite side of the distribution, consisting of the thousands of entities that occur only once or twice.

probability of occurring 100 times or more, while for a location reference string this is around 1%. For the curated entities (right side plot), the distribution of persons against falls fastest, having a relatively high proportion of entities that occur rarely. For the other entity types, the curves are much flatter (falling less fast) than for the reference strings. This means that they do not have a long tail of entities occurring only once or twice. The vast majority of committees, organisations, locations and attributions occur at least 10 times (at 10^1 on the X axis, their values on the Y axis are close to 10^0 or 100%). The curation process described below has thus strongly reduced variation for these entity types.

The most relevant entities from the perspective of the SG occur most frequently, therefore we consider their frequency to be an important clue for identification. The general procedure consists of finding the most frequent entities. In general we start with those entity reference strings that add up to 80-85 percent of all references of a certain type. Time permitting, this may further be extended to up to 90 percent. Then we try to reduce all variations to a standard form. Using the assumption that more frequent entities have more variations and some variations are more common than others, we choose the most frequent reference string as the standard form and map other variations to that form. These steps can be done using internal criteria. Further identification is possible by making a cross-section of persons and attributions. In the resolutions, people are often designated by a further attribution, if only for identification in the States General; 69% of person tags contain an attribution tag. Based on manual inspection, the person tags that contain no nested attribution tag are either persons mentioned earlier in a resolution, or are so well-known to the States General as to need no further qualification.

All identified entities are made available in the search application in the form of search facets and the resolved entity references are operationalised in the resolution texts as links to more information about them, and with the option to add them as search facets to narrow down the search results.

5.3. Two models of data curation

Entity type	Total references	Unique references	Unique entities
Person	1,864,673	882,081	8,108
Person att.	2,160,912	730,747	716
Location	2,187,588	201,265	2,459
Committee	139,787	55,528	103
Organisation	599,239	108,739	504
Date	834,983	217,581	43,208
Resolution ref.	185,210	13,754	?

Table 6: Total and distinct number of entity references, per entity type.

The number of entity references and the many sources of variation make a the usual method of data curation untenable. The process can be described in a schematic way as in figure 5. It is a three-step process: after applying a NER tagger to identify entity references, the text of the references is first cleaned up as far as possible in an automated way (spelling harmonisation and/or fuzzy matching reference strings that

Figure 5: A linear interpretative model of data curation.

are variants), and then passed to a domain expert, usually in the form of a spreadsheet, for manual identification.

One advantage of this *linear interpretative* method is a clear separation of competences: technical and historical know-how can be provided by different people in succession. Some of its limits, on the other hand, are immediately clear. For one, a manual pass through all references becomes impractical when the number of *distinct* references rises above a few thousand. As table 6 shows, the compound variation gives rise to much larger numbers. And while there are various ways of reducing this variation, the sequential nature of the traditional method precludes applying domain-specific knowledge to this step. The gains of doing so, meanwhile, can be significant. Take for example the five admiralties of the Republic:¹⁶ most references include a place name, and because the set of admiralty seats is limited, place names included in an admiralty organisation reference can be identified with certainty even when severely scrambled.

More generally speaking, the clean-up step benefits from the set of entities to-be-recognised being known in advance, which is not the case here. The largest drawback of this model, however, is that the manual step makes this a one-time process that cannot easily be repeated when either the input text, the NER tagger or the clean up process changes. The domain expert could ask the technical expert to add a step in the clean up process, but in the newly resulting spreadsheets, all manual work of the domain expert on the previous version needs to be redone. Since both automated text recognition and NER are rapidly-improving technologies, the need for an easily repeatable, and therefore automated, data curation step is obvious.

From these observations, we can draw two intermediate conclusions.

- One, that the integration of the two tasks of identification and resolution benefits from applying domain expertise throughout all steps of the curation process;
- Two, that any manual labour performed must be done in a way that has reusable results.

Taken together, these must lead to an *integrated process of data curation*, for which we propose a model outlined in figure 6. In this *iterative automated* model, the single

¹⁶ To wit, those of Rotterdam ('on the Meuse'), Amsterdam, West-Frisia (with its seat alternating between Hoorn and Enkhuizen), Middelburg and Frisia (first in Doccum, later in Harlingen).

Figure 6: An iterative automated model of data curation.

pipeline is replaced by a two-part process, consisting of an automated pipeline and an iterative development loop containing manual curation.

The pivotal step in this process consists not of assigning references to entities, but of *grouping* similar references in separate buckets on the basis of a growing set of logical criteria. From inspection of these groups, new or improved logical criteria can be formulated leading to finer distinctions on the next iteration. Ultimately, these criteria will grow into a separate dataset of their own, by means of which the data curation can be performed automatically. And when the reference groups have become a sufficiently fine partitions of entity references, a frequency cut-off can be declared—any non-grouped reference strings below the frequency cut-off remain unresolved—after which each group of reference strings represent a named entity.

In the last regard, the difference with the linear interpretative model of data curation is fundamental, even if the result may be very similar. Because the iterative automated process ‘zooms in’ on specific entities, it allows for the gradual discernment of boundaries between entities. These are not always clear in advance. Discerning between similar professions may be desirable when both occur frequently but unhelpful when both are rare. Changes over time may also warrant further divisions.

The iterative automated model has the advantage that identification and resolution are carried out simultaneously, allowing these finer distinctions to be made late in the curation process and only for those entities for which they would be useful. The consequence, on the other hand, is that the most common entities will be resolved with both the greatest certainty and precision, while the least-often occurring entities may not be resolved at all.

An additional advantage making the logical criteria explicit, is that it makes curation decisions transparent for criticism and improvement. At a later point in time, and outside of the scope of the REPUBLIC project, the raw NER output can easily be re-curated for a different research aim by adapting the logical criteria to suit the needs of a specific research question or project.

5.4. Methods of reducing variation

The main product of the data curation method described in the previous section is a set of logical criteria for sorting references to entities into groups of references belonging to the same entity. Remember that even though their ultimate goal is to *distinguish*

entities, we do so by ‘bundling up’ disparate strings, that is to say: by reducing variation. Consequently, the first part of the curation consists of criteria for addressing sources of variation common to all entity types: spelling and language change, scribal mistakes, and text recognition errors. Some of these sources are more-or-less regular, while others amount to noise; these sources are hard to address together. After all, strategies for addressing text recognition errors by matching terms within a certain edit distance may suffer from different spellings being too far apart, while a spelling harmonisation rule may be obstructed by a single misrecognised letter.

Month	Expression	Variants	Keywords	Variants
January	januar[ijy]+	5	2	161
February	februar[ijy]+	6	2	186
March	m[ae]+rt[eijy]*	13	9	130
April	april+(is)?	4	3	105
May	m[ae][yij]+e?	14	10	14
June	jun[ijy]+(us)?	8	6	71
July	jul[ijy]+(us)?	6	5	56
August	august([ijy]+ us)	7	2	81
September	septemb(e?r? ris)	5	3	166
October	octob(e?r? ris)	4	3	107
November	no[uv]emb(e?r? ris)	7	4	149
December	decemb(e?r? ris)	4	3	149
Total		83	52	1375

Table 7: A two-stage method for recognising month names in date strings.

One approach we found fruitful is building up a lexicon of *intentional* variants of relevant keywords, and then perform a fuzzy (edit distance-based) match against those. See table 7 for an example of a lexicon built in a semi-automatic way: for every month of the year, a regular expression is constructed covering all common variants. Matches to these expression are sorted in descending order of occurrence, and then added to the lexicon if their edit distance to earlier-selected keywords exceeds some threshold. The resulting 52 keywords are matched against the corpus again with a lower edit-distance threshold, resulting in 1375 variants that each can be mapped to one of the months. Manually-created lexicons used in other entity types include lists of abbreviations, synonyms and vocabulary specific to the entity type. A small excerpt from the lexicon used for organisation (ORG) references are the three similar words ‘Bataillon’, ‘Bataillons’ and ‘Bataille’. Since a word can only be corrected to a single keyword, the first two are present to preserve the distinction between singular and plural, while the third prevents battles from being turned into battalions. (Battles are no organisations, but some are erroneously marked as such by the NER tagger. They are discarded by a later criterium.) By fuzzy matching words in entity references to entries in the lexicon, and replacing the matching words with the matching lexicon entry, the variation in reference strings is gradually reduced. For instance, “tweede Bathillon” becomes “tweede Bataillon” (EN: second Bataillon). Organisation references are relatively long, averaging 5.5 words or 35 characters; with the steps described up to this point, their variation can be reduced by a factor of five. And thanks to the iterative automated model described above, the lexicon used for this step can be improved at any later point without disturbing subsequent steps.

The next set of criteria can be constructed by taking the largest reference groupings and picking out keywords. The purpose of these keywords may of course be selecting entities directly, but can also be grouping entities together within a certain domain. Selecting entities directly is done for personal names (PER), which form a structurally homogeneous entity type. There, the regular expression `/[uv]?a?n? *olden?b[ea]rn\w*/` identifies a certain grand pensionary of the Holland: Van Oldenbarnevelt, and all misspellings of this frequent (and therefore oft hastily-written) name. Organisations, on the other hand, are an entity type of much greater diversity, and here entity references are first sorted in separate domains (see table 8). Most domains have a distinct structure and logic of their own. Subsequent criteria may then exploit domain knowledge or characteristics of formulaic language for making refinements within those groups that would be impossible on the total set of entity references. The largest domain consists of a single organisation, the Council of State, from which only some false positives had to be removed. The example of identifying seats of admiralties has already been mentioned above. A more complex case is formed by the regiments of the States’ army, which are usually referred to by their captain. Since the military rank of these captains may change over time, so does the name of the regiment. Hence, a targeted additional set of criteria must be applied for merging references to regiments together.

Category	Total	Unique	Category	Total	Unique
Council of State	139365	3635	Countries	8524	3591
Regions	139124	29191	Offices	5207	1941
Admiralties	97359	9228	Invalid	3016	1212
Princely courts	92174	12132	Mints	2063	774
Generality	58938	11051	Representatives	2000	596
Councils	45514	13405	Internal affairs	1232	755
Other	32648	16280	Secretariats	1128	518
Local governments	27958	12878	Diplomacy	780	218
Companies	26737	9376	Parliaments	667	234
Audit institutions	25984	1006	Advocates	521	51
Military	19258	12097	Congresses	105	62
Religious	11982	7739			

Table 8: Subdomains of entity references, with total and unique number of references. The unique number is after the normalisation steps described above.

Not all criteria involve lists of keywords. Some make use of the interdependence and nesting of different entity types (See subsection 3.1). Many personal names, for instance, contain names of towns. Yet we must not conclude that one of the towns named Rijswijk occur in a resolution on a petition by a merchant named ‘Theodorus Ryswijck’! Thanks to the nested structure of the different entity types, however, we can exclude altogether all place names that occur in personal names. The identification of local governments offers an example of the interaction of *three* different entity types. Local governments are sometimes addressed as such (‘the magistrate of Amsterdam’), but more commonly by the titles of their government offices: ‘burgomasters and regents of Amsterdam’, ‘syndic and council of Geneva’, ‘high bailiff and aldermen of Ghent’, etc. etc. In the latter cases, the reference may be resolved to the proper local government whenever a person attribution (ATT) belonging to *any* local government function co-occurs with its corresponding location (LOC) within the same organisation

(ORG) reference.

In the above examples, a great strength of the iterative automated model is that it uses different sources of expertise throughout the process of data curation. Curation strategies and criteria can be tailored to (parts of) different entity types in a straightforward way, and worked on in parallel: changes made to earlier criteria do not invalidate subsequent steps. Note that while entity references are bundled together (and sometimes split again), they are not *identified* with each-other until the very last moment. This means that the context of the individual references is not lost, but remains preserved for later criteria to use.

5.5. External identification

We used HisGIS¹⁷ and Geonames¹⁸ to link location entities to geographical coordinates. Of the 2,459 location entities, 2,327 could be mapped to coordinates, representing 70% of all location references.

We are still working on further identification for organisations and persons by using external databases, some of which are available at the Huygens Institute. There is a limited number of descriptions of institutions. There are several person databases available that may be used for external identification. The most important of these are the database of officeholders¹⁹ and the overview of foreign representatives both to and from the Republic,²⁰ supplemented by more generally available overviews of European rulers and by indexes from a number of published relevant correspondences. These are a great help as both office holders and diplomats are central persons in the resolutions.

Of course, identification to these databases is somewhat more involved. Databases are not complete as they are compiled from other sources than the resolutions and based on their own criteria. Names as they appear in the databases are often spelt differently from the variations in the resolutions, and in the resolutions not all persons are designated by their full name. Some examples:

- in the 1620s Nicolaas van den Bouchorst was Lord of Noortwijk, and usually designated as Noortwijck, although in the 18th century Noortwijck was shorthand for Wigbold van der Does van Noortwijk or his son Wigbold jr.
- depending on the context, members from the prominent families like the Van Wassenaers were either simply designated as Wassenaer, or with an extension like Graaf (EN: Count) (van) Wassenaer, Van Wassenaer Twickelo, van Wassenaer Alkemade, Van Wassenaer Obdam, van Wassenaer van Duivenvoorde, Grave van Wassenaer tot Wassenaer, Van Wassenaer tot Warmond, Wassenaer van Sternburgh etc.

Fortunately, these prominent families are not very numerous because often these types of confusion can only be resolved by hand, if at all. The external databases provide dates of birth and death and dates of residence in an office that can be used, even if these are not always accurate, to merge or separate entity mentions. For prominent persons, death dates are often known, but birth dates are often missing, especially for

¹⁷ A Dutch project to map historic placenames and geographical maps to geographic coordinates, <https://hisgis.nl>.

¹⁸ <https://www.geonames.org>

¹⁹ <https://resources.huygens.knaw.nl/repertoriumambtsdragersambtenaren1428-1861/>

²⁰ <https://resources.huygens.knaw.nl/retroboeken/schutte/>

Figure 7: The number of different committees active per year.

persons in the earliest period. In those cases, we used estimated birth dates based on a combination of 1) the date they started their office, and 2) the average age of people who started office. All together, it is usually possible to use semi-automatic methods to identify the most prominent persons and also to overcome the variety in spelling. However, a manual check for the most prominent families remains necessary.

6. Insights from Curation

We can use the curated entities to analyse the corpus in various ways. First, using knowledge of the domain and corpus, experts can do temporal analyses of when and how often certain types of entities occur as a sanity check. If the results are different from what is expected, this can be a signal that there are problems in the recognition process, or that the resolutions call for revising expectations. Second, different types of entities can now easily be combined in a quantitative analysis to investigate how the resolutions relate to certain historical events. One may expect that the number of resolutions that mention military organisations and persons increases in times of war and decreases once war is over, but this need not necessarily be the case. Third, entity references can be used to investigate previous historiographic claims.

For instance, the curation of the committee entities allows us to validate the claims that the States General made more and more use of committees from around 1650 to investigate matters submitted by petitioners and to prepare decisions (Thomassen, 2019a, p.162), and that from 1672, many ad hoc committees were subsumed under a smaller number of permanent committees, each related to a fixed topic (Thomassen, 2019a, pp.122-123), (Riemsdijk, 1885, pp.268-272).

Figure 8: The fraction of resolutions that contain a reference to a committee reference per proposition type (left), and a break down of the committee mentioned in those resolutions (right).

The 97,860 committee references recognised by the COM tagger are mapped in the curation process to about 120 distinct committees. Figure 7 shows the distribution of the number of different committees active per year, and indicates a rapid increase in the number of committees starting from 1650. The number of active committees reaches its zenith of about 40 per year in 1655–1670, then decreases suddenly and stabilises to around 20 after 1672. Inspection of the number of resolutions that were passed on to each committee reveals that from the beginning of the 18th century, the vast majority of resolutions were handled by less than a dozen committees. This analysis corroborates the earlier findings and provides evidence that the output of the recognition and curation steps makes sense.

We can also combine the referenced committees with the *proposition type* of a resolution, which is the manner in which a proposition is presented to the States General. The proposition types were recognised in the resolution segmentation step, based on formulaic ways to introduce a new resolution, where each formula specifies the way in which a proposition is introduced (Koolen and Hoekstra, 2022; Koolen et al., 2020).²¹ The five most common proposition types are *missives*, *petitions*, *reports*, *memos* and *oral presentations*.

The fraction of resolutions that contain a committee reference per proposition type is shown in Figure 8 on the left. Around 20% of resolutions based on missives, reports, memos and oral presentations make reference to a committee, but over 93% of all resolutions based on reports do. The high percentage of the latter is what we would expect, as reports are submitted by committees in response to an earlier resolution, where a committee was tasked to investigate and report back. These resolutions state which committee submitted the report. The fact that not all resolutions based on reports contain a recognised committee reference is most likely due to references missed by the tagger. In this case, the analysis suggests that the recognition and curation of committees leads to results that conform to expectations.

The right side of Figure 8 shows a breakdown of the committees that are referenced in those resolutions. Resolutions based on missives are more likely to reference the committees of Naval Affairs and Foreign Affairs (missives tend to be sent by Dutch diplomats abroad, or foreign diplomats in the Republic), while resolutions based on

²¹ Together with the name and attribution of the person introducing the proposition, and the date and location of sending the document, all of which are mentioned at the beginning of each resolutions, these details form a stable referent to the submitted document that is also in the archive of the States General, and in that sense are a named entity reference.

petitions are more likely to reference the committee of Financial Affairs. One common group of petitioners are widows and orphaned children who ask the States General for financial support. In these cases, the person requesting support is mentioned in the resolution with an associated attribution, e.g. *widow* or *orphaned child*, which are tagged by the ATT tagger and (in the curation step) both categorised under *Legal Status and Relations*. This analysis is again not surprising, but increases our confidence in the quality of the curation process, and it shows the value of combining entities of different types and curation entity references into groups. By offering proposition types, committees and person attributions as search facets, users can easily select and drill down into subsets of the resolutions related to e.g. petitions mentioning family relations that involve the committee of Financial Affairs.

7. Conclusions

This paper describes the approach taken in the REPUBLIC project to operationalise named entities for information access in the corpus of resolutions of the States General of the Dutch Republic.

Our approach is informed by the purposes of highlighting entities in the text for easy document triage and utilisation as search facets for providing structured ways of making selections and drilling down into specific subsets of the resolutions. The entity types we chose are a mix of common types like persons, locations and organisations, and domain- and corpus-specific entity types such as committees, resolution references and person attributions.

Our first research question was:

- How well can we identify named entities in the resolutions?

We described how we have developed a large set of ground truth annotations for eight types of entities and performed a detailed analysis of these annotations. We found that there are strong differences between types in both the lengths of entity references and in the nature of nesting. References to committees and earlier resolutions tend to be long phrases, and many references to persons, attributions and organisations exhibit a high variance in length. The latter is related to nesting, as persons and their attributions, as well as organisations, often contain nested entities of different types. This has consequences for information access, as we need to make a choice about the level of nesting we use for creating search facets.

We compared several types of embeddings for historic Dutch text on their relative strengths for training NER taggers for different types of entities and found that Character embeddings, FastText embedding and the BERT-based contextual embeddings model GysBERT each have different strengths and weaknesses, and can be effectively combined to improve NER performance. We note that for all entity types, the best individual embedding type is close in performance to the best combination of embedding types, and that FastText embeddings outperform GysBERT on most entity types. We assume this is mostly due to the fact that the FastText embeddings were trained using the resolutions. Although we included fine-tuning of the original embedding weights as one of the options, allowing GysBERT to be fine-tuned to the NER training data, it may have been beneficial to first adapt GysBERT to the domain of resolutions by training on the full text of all resolutions.

Our second research question was:

- How can we curate entity mentions and make them useful for information access?

Next we described our approach to curating entity references, making them useful for information access. For this purpose, we have developed an integrated model of identifying and resolving entities, that makes curation decisions explicit, auditable, repeatable and reusable. Furthermore, it allows the incorporation of domain expertise in the entire curation process. This is particularly useful for large historic corpora for which few external resources of entity information exist and for which full manual curation is infeasible.

Our third research question was:

- What can we learn from the curation of entities about the corpus of resolutions and the operation of the States General?

To address this, we conducted some basic analysis of the curated committee references in relation to the resolutions they appear in. We found corroborating evidence of earlier claims as well as insights in how the SG used committees for handling the different types of documents and requests that were submitted to the SG, and on which the resolutions are based.

In future work, we want to conduct more detailed quality analysis on the output of the curation process, and on the influence of the individual curation steps. We also plan on doing more temporal analysis of how the references to types of entities change over time, both individually and in combination, in order to gain further insights in the workings of the SG, and in the extent the SG standardised their administrative and decision making processes.

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A. Resolution Corpus

The corpus of resolutions is complex in nature because it contains both *ordinary* and *secret* resolutions, and for certain periods, there are multiple versions of extended handwritten resolutions. Furthermore, from 1672 printed versions of the resolutions were made and distributed to the individual states. However, until 1705, the printed versions did not contain all ordinary resolutions.

In the `REPUBLIC` project we made a selection of resolution books that covers all ordinary and secret resolutions for the entire period. For the ordinary resolutions, we use the handwritten versions for the period 1576-1702 and the printed versions of the *ordinary* resolutions of 1703-1796 (that is, the complete set of resolutions from 1705-1796, and incomplete for 1703-1704 because we did not have handwritten versions of those years). From 1592, the SG started a separate series of books for secret resolutions, which were never printed.

Table 9: The selection of resolutions used in the `REPUBLIC` project

Resolution type	Period	Format	Complete	Available for NER training
Ordinary	1576-1702	handwritten	yes	yes
	1703-1704	printed	no	no
	1705-1796	printed	yes	yes
Secret	1592-1796	handwritten	yes	no

The segmentation of the transcriptions into individual resolutions started with the printed resolutions. Because the handwritten resolutions were more challenging to segment, we had only managed to segment the ordinary resolutions of 1597-1702 by the time we had to start the NER ground truth annotation and training. Therefore, NER training data only covers the *ordinary* resolutions, and only of the periods 1597-1702 (handwritten) and 1705-1796 (printed). To clarify the selection of resolutions used in the `REPUBLIC` project and their availability for NER, a structured overview is given in Table 9.

A.1. Document length

The 18th century printed resolutions and 17th century handwritten paragraphs that were annotated and used for training range considerably in length. The mean length is X words and the standard deviation is Y .

Some descriptive statistics, including various percentiles, are presented in Table 10.

The length of resolutions has a bi-modal distribution, that is, there are two peaks in the distribution. One peak is around 40-50 words, and consists of highly formulaic resolutions in which a missive from a diplomat or ambassador has been received that requires no decision. The other peak is around 250 words. The resolutions around this peak are the ones with a decision. In a sense then, the distribution of the length of

resolutions is a mixture of two distinct distributions of the two types of resolutions, those with a decision and those without.

B. Code and data

The entity data is published on Zenodo: Dijkstra et al. (2025).

The `REPUBLIC` code base is available on GitHub. There are specific entry points to the code for NER and curation:

- Main: <https://github.com/huygensing/republic-project>
- NER: <https://github.com/huygensing/republic-project/tree/main/nlp/>
- Curation: <https://github.com/huygensing/republic-project/tree/main/enrichment>

The trained NER models are available on Huggingface:

- Persons: <https://huggingface.co/marijnkoolen/republic-ner-persons-2023>
- Person attributions: https://huggingface.co/marijnkoolen/republic-ner-person_attributions-2023
- Locations: <https://huggingface.co/marijnkoolen/republic-ner-locations-2023>
- Organisations: <https://huggingface.co/marijnkoolen/republic-ner-organisations-2023>
- Committees: <https://huggingface.co/marijnkoolen/republic-ner-committees-2023>
- Dates: <https://huggingface.co/marijnkoolen/republic-ner-dates-2023>

Handwritten	Paragraphs		
	Printed	All	
Count	514	1631	2145
Mean	97.9	227.2	196.2
Std	99.9	382.0	341.1
Min	1.0	24.0	1.0
1%	2.0	26.0	17.4
5%	20.0	28.0	27.2
25%	44.0	47.0	46.0
50%	73.0	127.0	107.0
75%	120.0	254.5	209.0
95%	233.4	752.5	650.0
99%	435.6	1677.3	1392.2
Max	1199.0	6269.0	6269.0

Table 10: Caption

Model	fine-tune	reprojection	use context	use RNN	use CRF
Persons	yes	yes	no	yes	yes
Person attributions	yes	yes	no	yes	yes
Locations	no	yes	no	yes	yes
Organisations	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Committees	yes	yes	no	yes	yes
Dates	no	yes	no	yes	yes
Resolution references	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Other names	no	no	no	yes	yes

Table 11: Configuration of the Flair training parameters used for the eight NER models.

- Resolution references: https://huggingface.co/marijnkoelen/republic-ner-resolution_references-2023

B.1. Training parameters

We used the following training parameters. All models were trained for 10 epochs using a mini-batch size of 8 and a learning rate $\lambda = 0.05$.

The Flair library offers a range of parameters for configuring the training layers. The parameters can be on (yes) or off (no):

- *fine tuning*: fine tune the weights of the different types of embeddings (yes) or freeze them (no) during training.
- *reprojection*: reproject the embeddings to a linear layer before connecting to the output (yes) or not (no).
- *using context*: train the input with the document context (yes) or not (no).
- *use CRF*: use a CRF for output layer (yes, the units in the output layer are connected to each other and thus inform each other’s predictions), or a linear layer (no).
- *using RNN*: use an RNN-type (yes, default is LSTM) instead of a linear layer (no).

STUDIUM.AI: Datafying and Connecting the ‘Webs of Knowledge’ around the Premodern University of Leuven (1425-1797)

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This paper presents the design and implementation of STUDIUM.AI, a research infrastructure serving as a central hub for studying the academic ecosystem of the early modern University of Leuven (1425–1797). We begin by introducing the project’s core datasets—which document scholars, students, and books associated with the university—and outline the relational database architecture that interconnects them. A critical focus is our standardization pipeline for historical names and places, a preliminary step enabling robust data interlinking. Next, we address research data management challenges in this large-scale initiative, detailing our use of KU Leuven’s MANGO platform for storing active research data while adhering to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Finally, we demonstrate best practices for linking to external authority files, exemplified by our integration with the World Historical Gazetteer.

Keywords: Early Modern University of Leuven, Data interlinking, Name standardization, Research Data Management, FAIR Data, World Historical Gazetteer

1 Introduction

Founded almost 600 years ago, the early modern University of Leuven (1425-1797) turned into a thriving hub of students, professors, scholars, printers and publishers. These left us a vast array of traces and sources, be it their names noted down in the matriculation registers, the many extant student notebooks, or the impressive local production of handpress textbooks and treatises. Even if many of these historical sources perished in the fires of the first and second world war, in 2013 the UNESCO Memory of the World program recognized the remaining *Archives of the University of Leuven (1425-1797)* as *University Heritage of Global Significance*.¹ In the last decade, libraries and archives in Leuven, Louvain-la-Neuve and Brussels have digitized a

¹ <https://nieuws.kuleuven.be/en/content/2013/unesco-adds-university-archives-heritage-register>. Accessed 6 Oct. 2024.

significant portion of the surviving sources to valorize this exceptional intellectual and cultural heritage. At the same time, digitization sparked the creation of new metadata and search interfaces, whereas different research groups at KU Leuven started collecting prosopographical and book historical data from a DH-perspective.

By approaching the intellectual heritage and historical infrastructure of education of the early modern University of Leuven from different perspectives, the datasets bring about a new picture, yet one that can only be harvested across multiple platforms. This fragmentation of the data, both at the moment of its creation and through its digitized surrogates, prevents users from connecting information relating to the same actors and objects across the different datasets. For example, the famous humanist Erasmus of Rotterdam (?-1536) pops up in no less than 5 datasets, as he matriculated in 1518 and authored multiple treatises as well as textbooks. The Research Infrastructure STUDIUM.AI aims to bridge this gap by interconnecting this large array of materials, thus enabling joint searches across different platforms, and by enriching these data through linking and standardising information. footnote <https://studium-ai.org>. Accessed Oct. 6 2024. The Research infrastructure revolves around two main initiatives: on the one hand, the interlinking of several databases (on which this paper is based), and, on the other hand, the enrichment of the current resources by training an HTR-model aimed at transcribing the content in already digitized notebooks of students of the University in the premodern era (which will not be discussed here). Our paper discusses three main research questions relevant to the set-up of interlinking research infrastructures, namely:

- RQ1: Given the variety of the digitized sources and the objects of the databases concerned, what approach can be taken to interlink the data and valorize their thematic unity?
- RQ2: What workflow ensures the best transparency, reusability, and synchronicity of the data within this kind of interlinking infrastructure?
- RQ3: How can such a diverse infrastructure integrate permanent identifiers from external resources?

The paper is structured as follows: first, we outline the digital resources in the field of premodern university studies and the existing research and materials in the specific case of the early modern University (Section 2); second, we describe the ten datasets that we have currently integrated into the research infrastructure (Section 3). We then outline our current approach to interlinking the data (RQ1) (Section 4) and to ensure a stable workflow between the different partners in the project (RQ2) (Section 5). Finally, we illustrate the process and the advantages of integrating permanent identifiers to enrich our information (Section 6).

2 Literature Review

‘Datafying’ prosopographies of premodern universities is certainly not new. Inspired by the approach of serial sources pioneered by the French ‘School of the Annales’, statistical accounts of aspects of university life and recruitment were trending in the 1960s and 1970s, such as Jacques Verger’s work on the French universities, based on the *Suppliques* held by the Vatican Archives Verger (1970). As early as 1980, the digitization (entering the information in a database) of A. B. Emden’s *Biographical Registers* of

Oxford and Cambridge was carried out by the Oxford University Computing Service, a resource which was used in turn for writing new histories of the University (Aston, 1980).

Most recently, this digital prosopographical work has witnessed a resurgence using newer methods in the field of Digital Humanities. Premodern universities have been at the centre of several research projects.² For example, the *RAG-Repertorium Academicum Germanicum* (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft 2011-9) set the tone to detect geospatial clusters in the late medieval population of c. 62,000 students in the medieval Holy Roman Empire (Gubler, Kaspar, 2022; Schwinges, 2020), including Louvain up to 1527 (and some cases up to 1550). The data are stored in a relational database that is browseable online following different facets, and dynamic visualization guides the user in data exploration. The database is currently developed using NodeGoat, which is also used to produce the visualizations. Secondly, the *SP-Studium Parisiense* prosopographical database aims at gathering information for ca 40,000 people belonging to the schools and universities of Paris between the 12th and 16th centuries (Genet et al., 2016).³ Another database in development is the *Universitas Magistrorum*, which seeks to record various attributes of the professors at the University of Prague between 1458 and 1622 (Synovcová Borovičková and Škudrnová, 2021). At the European level, the project *RETE-Repertorium Eruditorum Totius Europae* under the direction of David de la Croix gathers information about scholars active in European universities between 1200 and 1800. RETE aims to describe the evolution of the learned society of Europe in multiple respects, for instance by analyzing the network of universities resulting from the movements of scholars from one institution to another; or by devising a measure of the Human Capital Index based on the publication output of historical scholars.⁴ Similar projects, aiming at reconstructing the networks around historical universities, have been developing recently (Brizzi and Frijhoff, 2018). Such projects share specific goals and challenges, and the European Network Atelier Héloïse was set up to bridge the different “national” projects in the broader framework of the European Digital Academic History.⁵

Most of these initiatives could thrive through wider initiatives relating to the digitization of cultural heritage to make it more accessible. Projects in this vein have attracted large-scale funding in recent years, such as *Europeana*⁶ and the *Towards a National Collection* project in the UK.⁷ These kinds of projects have employed the use of metadata, and now, increasingly, the linking of records and entities through the use of linked open data to make records interoperable and searchable across different archives and repositories. For early modern history, many of these projects working on interlinking records have focused on correspondence data because of its relatively easily interoperable metadata (i.e. sender, recipient, dates and places of sending and receipt). The COST action project *Reassembling the Republic of Letters 1500 – 1800* and its associated volume Hotson and Wallnig (2019a) summarised many of the challenges and opportunities in modelling and linking correspondence data from different projects and corpora, a task also taken up by the *SKILLNET* project (Van Miert, 2022),

² A list can be found here: <https://heloise.hypotheses.org/base-de-donnees>. Accessed 6 Oct. 2024.

³ <http://studium.univ-paris1.fr/>.

⁴ The RETE database can be browsed here: <https://shiny-lidam.sipr.ucl.ac.be/scholars/>. Accessed 6 Oct. 2024.

⁵ <https://heloise.hypotheses.org/>. Accessed 6 Oct. 2024.

⁶ <https://www.nationalcollection.org.uk/>. Accessed 1 Oct. 2024.

⁷ <https://www.europeana.eu/en>. Accessed 1 Oct. 2024.

the LettersSampo project at the University of Helsinki, and *Early Modern Letters Online* (Hotson and Wallnig, 2019b).⁸ This has been paired along with wider thinking about the value of research infrastructure and its relation to cultural heritage, particularly as manifested in libraries (Waters, 2023).

When narrowing the focus on the University of Leuven in the premodern era, compiling data on the academic community and book productions has been the focus of a broad array of scholarly initiatives for decades. Already in the beginning of the twentieth century, Louvain archivists and historians teamed up to edit the matriculation registers (Reusens et al., 1903-1990) as well as other source documents of the first four centuries of the university's existence.⁹

Recently, as we describe in more detail in Section 3, several projects have carried out systematic digitizations of (re)sources about the Old University. Projects can be grouped into two categories: the first one focused on the digitization of the sources, whether handwritten notes of Louvain students (as in the portal site of *Magister Dixit*¹⁰), thesis sheets they had published for defense (as in the digitized curated collection of the KU Leuven libraries¹¹), the published work of Louvain professors and scholars (as in the portal site of *Lovaniensia*¹²), or the digitization of the matriculation registers (and the additional compilation of an Excel list of names registered in these sources). The second type of dataset is related to research projects with a specific focus on data collection about research questions, such as the printed textbook production in Leuven, as in *Manuale Lovaniense* (Cammaerts, 2024)¹³, the student notes on the topic of logic as in *LLLogeia* (see for instance Geudens et al. (2020)), the persons and books at the Collegium Trilingue, as in *DaLet*¹⁴, or the *Aristotelian Diagrams*¹⁵, as in *Leonardi's* subsection on Louvain (see Demey (2024)). Besides the data creation, the project also prompted the beginning and completion of several PhD theses and research projects investigating the teaching activity at the early modern University (see for example the research projects on *Logic* by Geudens and Masolini (2016), the Louvain Trilingue within the *DaLet*-team, Feys et al. (2025) forthcoming, and the 'higher' Faculties of Canon Law, Civil Law and Theology in *@Aulam*, Soen et al. (Forthcoming)).

The novelty of the STUDIUM.AI infrastructure is twofold: on the one hand, we aim at matching databases and metadatasets of the two groups, to allow the users to jointly navigate across prosopographical information, and the information/digitized version of the documents which testify to the scholarly and student activity of the community around the premodern university. This part of the workflow is discussed in the rest of the paper. On the other hand, by exploiting HTR and NLP techniques (which are not discussed in this paper), we want to enrich the above resources in a semi-automated manner, by linking the information of the databases to the people and places mentioned in the documents.

⁸ Early Modern Letters Online. <http://emlo.bodleian.ox.ac.uk/home>. Accessed 7 Oct. 2024; LettersSampo. <https://lettersampo.demo.seco.cs.aalto.fi/en>. Accessed 5 Oct. 2024.

⁹ Especially the editions of the matriculation registers.

¹⁰ <https://www.kuleuven.be/lectio/research/MagisterDixit>. Accessed 6 Oct. 2024.

¹¹ https://kuleuven.limo.libis.be/discovery/collectionDiscovery?vid=32KUL_KUL:KULeuven&collectionId=81531994440001488.

¹² <https://www.lovaniensia.be>. Accessed 6 Oct. 2024.

¹³ <https://www.odis.be/hercules/search2.php?histid=1003367>, URL generated on 7 Oct. 2024.

¹⁴ <https://www.dalet.be/>. Accessed 6 Oct. 2024.

¹⁵ <https://leonardi.logicalgeometry.org>. Accessed 6 Oct. 2024.

3 Data

More recently, both GLAM institutions (such as KU Leuven Libraries and the State Archives) and academic research groups have invested significant resources in the digitization of sources and prosopographical information. The State Archives, through the impressive dedication of volunteers, digitized the university's matriculation records, where any person related to university (mostly students, but also professors and publishers) were registered, and also populated an Excel-list on the basis of the twentieth-century edition of Reusens, Wils and Schillings. A second, cleaned and enriched version (cross-checked again with the sources), was published as a joint effort between the State Archives, the interdisciplinary KU Leuven Research Institute LECTIO and an intern of the KU Leuven Advanced Master of Digital Humanities, Lydia Janssen (Janis et al., 2020). Within the KU Leuven, Magister Dixit, a joint project of KU Leuven Libraries and the Research Center LECTIO (now a KU Leuven Research Institute) has resulted in the—still ongoing—digitization of more than 500 manuscripts containing student notes of the early modern University, together with the creation of a metadata catalogue currently available on Zenodo (KU Leuven Libraries, 2024). Moreover, a few data-creation groups, used the platform ODIS – a digital spinoff of KADOC, Documentation and Research Centre on Religion, Culture and Society – to set up relational databases encoding information on academic prints in the Low Countries of the Early Modern Period, and on the actors (authors, publishers, printers and engravers) who contributed to the books. More precisely, they are *Manuale Lovaniense*,¹⁶ and *Scholars@OldLouvain*.¹⁷ KU Leuven Libraries has focused on printed materials, too. The *Collectio Academica Antiqua* (CAA) is a “reconstructed” collection, whose goal is to gather all printed books authored by members of the premodern University. The metadata, in the form of MARC21 XML, has been released as open data. The CAA currently offers the basis for a large-scale digitization project *Lovaniensia* whose volumes were recently OCRed via a partnership with Google Books.¹⁸ The ‘Theses from the Old University of Leuven’ collection is a set of 3,157 broadsheet academic dissertations, written by students of the Old University, kept and digitized at KU Leuven.¹⁹ At the intersection of manuscripts and prints, the DaLeT database records the students’ manually written notes on the side of printed books used at the *Collegium Trilingue*, an academic center founded in 1517 in Leuven where Ancient Greek, Latin and Hebrew were taught, with a curriculum inspired by Erasmus’ humanistic perspective (cf. (Papy, 2018)).²⁰ Finally, the *Leonardi.DB* linked data store preserves all Aristotelian diagrams published across time: this also includes diagrams preserved in students’ notes of the Old University.²¹ Table 1 offers a schematic overview of the materials available. Note that a ‘record’ in each case counts a different object: those from catalogues count individual collection items, such as a book or thesis broadside. Databases from datasets, such as the matriculation records count rows, either persons or others.

¹⁶ <https://www.odis.be/hercules/search2.php?histid=1003367>, URL generated on 7 Oct. 2024, see Cammaerts 2024.

¹⁷ The list is currently in final preparation by An Smets and Violet Soen, and will be deposited on KU Leuven RDR as well as made available through the project’s website: <https://www.kuleuven.be/lectio/research/aulam>.

¹⁸ <https://lovaniensia.be>. Accessed 6 October 2024.

¹⁹ https://kuleuven.limo.libis.be/discovery/collectionDiscovery?vid=32KUL_KUL:KULeuven&collectionId=81531994440001488&sortItemsBy=date_a.

²⁰ A partial export of the database can be found at: <https://zenodo.org/records/8305741>.

²¹ ‘Leonardi.DB’. <https://leonardi.logicalgeometry.org/>. Accessed 3 October 2024.

Table 1: Databases linked by the STUDIUM.AI infrastructure.

Database	Types of records	# records	Format
Matriculation books Louvain (MBL)	Matriculation records	143303	Excel spreadsheet
Manuale Lovaniense	Printed books	509	Relational DB/JSON exports
Scholars@OldLouvain	People	300	Relational DB/JSON exports
Magister Dixit	Manuscripts	599	MARC XML
Collectio Academica Antiqua	Printed books	2056	MARC XML
Lovaniensia	Printed books	2057	Dublin core Omeka export
Thesis sheets	Printed texts	3157	MARC XML
DaLeT	People + students notes	795	Filemaker relational DB
Leonardi.DB	Aristotelian diagrams	>6000	Linked Data
Lllogeia	Manuscripts	87	Filemaker relational DB

These data are each time gathered from particular source sets, which are historical (like in the case of the matriculation books) or artificial (like the CAA curated at the KU Leuven libraries' Special Collections divisions). This comes with some disadvantages: for the matriculation books, two books have been lost in the time, leaving lacunae for the years between 1569 and 1616 (a third volume was lost in the first World War, but as it had already been turned into a printed edition by Schilling and others, the information has survived). The thesis sheets are inevitably 'ephemeral' print which was meant as an invitation, and were often recycled afterwards as scrap paper, etc. The survival rate is very uncomplete and often depends on capricious finds in the archives (Soen and Fantoli, Forthcoming). Concerning the data contained in the 'artificial' CAA, recent research has shown that by the sheer amount of rare books collected, quantitative information deducted from the metadata corresponds significantly with information from 'gold-standard'-catalogues, like the Universal Short Title Catalogue (Scebba and Fantoli, Forthcoming). DaLeT, Leonardi.DB, LLlogeia and Manuale Lovaniense, however, are datasets made by researchers with the aim of exhaustivity, and as such, they are themselves gold-standard, as being entered and surveyed by experts in the field. The interlinking of a series of datasets (and getting them out of 'their silo') each times generates new persons, new names or name variants, as detailed below in 4.2. This not only creates larger data pools, but also helps to correct some of the earlier biases in scholarship and source records, such an almost exclusive focus on the propedeutic Faculty of Arts, which has now been flattened out in comparison with the 'higher' Faculties of Canon Law, Civil Law and Medicine (Soen and Ryan, Forthcoming).

4 Interlinking the datasets

The pivotal information that bridges all the datasets, both prosopographical and book historical, is the learned community revolving around the Old University of Leuven, i.e. the people. Book historical resources contain detailed information about the books' contributors, who were often employed at the University of Leuven. Furthermore, the Magister Dixit dataset lists the students taking the notes and the professors giving the classes, who are also recorded in the matriculation books and in the relational datasets such as DaLeT and Scholars@OldLouvain. Hence, in order to partially automate the matching across datasets, we identified a common core of prosopographical information (names, place of birth, place of death, and dates related to biographical and professional events) that we could extrapolate from the different datasets in order to match the attestations of individuals. The relational database hosting the 'common core' has been modelled from scratch and revolves around the distinction between the level of attestations of people in the source, and records of people connecting the different attestations, as described in detail in Broux (2024a).

As expected based on the different provenance and focus of the datasets, the information about people was recorded in very different ways. Some of the databases were developed by researchers (Manuale Lovaniense, Scholars@OldLouvain, DaLeT), who generally agreed on a set of (loose) standardization guidelines (standardization with the Latin name of the scholars/students, structured encoding of dates etc.). Others, such as the library metadata, were set up by expert librarians in endeavours spanning several years. In addition, priority was given to a faithful representation of the information printed in the books, which resulted in a low degree of standardization. To give only one example, the Abbot of Tongerlo from 1608–1629, who appears in the CAA metadata as a dedicatee, is listed as both 'Adriaan Stalpaerts' and 'Hadrianus Stalpaert' there.

We decided to start the standardization process from the matriculation records (MBL henceforth, for Matriculation Books Leuven), which reflect exactly what was transcribed in the critical edition of Reusens, Schillings et al. (1903), without any standardization procedure for the first and last names of students and professors. This choice was based on the observations that the MBL are by far the largest dataset available with over 143,000 entries spanning the four centuries of the Old University, and that they represent a valuable source of variants of given names and last names. In addition, it is highly unlikely that duplicate entries will be found for the same person since every university member was registered only once (and re-matriculation remained the exception to the rule). This means that there is an approximate 1:1 correspondence between records and individuals; in the bibliographical datasets, on the contrary, people may appear multiple times.

4.1 Standardizing names for matching people

This section provides a general overview of the process of standardizing names of persons, which is described in full in Broux (2024b). In the Excel file of the MBL, the student(s) were described with the fields 'Voornaam' (given name), 'Naam' (family name), 'Herkomst' (origin), and 'Bisdome' (diocese). The first step to ensure a proper standardization of names and the identification of individuals of the MBL consisted of categorizing the parts of the string identifying the full name of a matriculated person into several descriptors such as: first name, middle name, last name, patronym, function and origin. For instance, for the name 'Carolus Josephus Gummarus Bosmans

Lyranus’, the elements are classified as first name (Carolus), middle names (Josephus, Gummarus), last name (Bosmans), origin (Lyranus, from the Brabant city of Lier). In some cases, ambiguity is registered when a component of the name could be interpreted in a double sense, for instance, both as a patronym or a last name. In the enrollment by ‘Franciscus Jacobi Balduini Avesnensis’, the string ‘Balduini’ could plausibly be either the last name or the patronymic of the father Jacobus, i.e. Franciscus’ grandfather (see Broux (2024b) for an in-depth discussion of these cases of ambiguity). For the standardization and interlinking process, we kept given names and last names as separate categories for two reasons, even though several names can be used as both. On the one hand, from the onomastic perspective (since the infrastructure aims at grouping together variants of the same name under a same ID, i.e. at lemmatizing the attestations of names), the lack of distinction between first names and last would generate noise for the cases in which a first name and a last name have the same form. For example, all the variants of the last name ‘Frans’ (e.g. Franssen(s), Frandsen, Fransing) would be integrated as variants of the first name ‘Frans’, which does not correspond to the historical reality behind the data. On the other hand, since the identification of duplicate individuals in the datasets relies on the matching of the full name, this distinction avoids the conflation of, for instance, an individual named Frans Jacobs and one named Jacobus Frans (see Broux (2024b)). Hence, the next paragraphs detail the two paths taken for the standardization of first names and family names (the standardization of place names identifying the origin is discussed in detail in Section 6).

4.1.1 Standardizing family names

The MBL dataset contains 72,701 unique variants for family names and patronyms, for a total of 146,618 attestations. Their standardization relied mostly on the third edition of the dictionary of family names for Belgium and the North of France, prepared by Frans Debrabandere (*Woordenboek van de familienamen in België en Noord-Frankrijk*, hereafter referred to as WFN) that we converted into a relational database, stored within the Filemaker infrastructure.²² More precisely, we included all the variants of the family names listed by WFN, and then grouped them under the lemma proposed by WFN. Only 25% of the family names listed in the MBL (i.e. 18,274 out of the 72,701) had a precise match with one of the variants of WFN, hence we relied on a fuzzy matching approach to speed up the manual lemmatization of the remaining variants. To ensure an efficient matching, we developed a key-collision approach, or “fingerprint” approach, consisting of the simplification of the string to its essential components, both for the WFN variants and for the MBL attestations. For instance, vowels, articles, particles are removed from the string, and we clustered some interchangeable components (the details can be found in Broux (2024b)). In this way, the FileMaker interface allows team members to easily select the right WFN lemma for each MBL attestation. Once a lemma has been chosen for one MBL attestation, it is automatically assigned also to all the MBL attestations whose form is considered a variant of this

²² Debrabandere 2003. The author kindly shared a Word file of the 2014 version, available online (<https://www.cbgfamilienamen.nl/nfb/aanhangsels/wfb-voorwerk.pdf>. Accessed on 5 October 2024.). The conversion into a relational dataset was done by the STUDIUM.AI co-pi Mark Depauw. Since when we started the standardization, we were not available of the datasets for the standardization of Dutch names provided by NAMES project (<https://www.clariah.nl/projects/names-dutch-corpus-of-person-name-variants>), by Gerrit Bloothoof, and in order to avoid possible confusion coming from the implementation of two different standards, we did not use the NAMES lemmatization.

lemma by the WFN (see subsection 4.3 for a discussion of our “human in the loop” approach). As the example by Broux (2024b) illustrates, the last name Bachusius is lemmatized with the WFN last name Bachus. All the variants of this last name present in the MBL database (Bachus, Bachuijs, Bachuys, etc.) can then easily be assigned to the same lemma. To this day, 28, 869 unique variants have been processed, and they account for 66.5% of all the attestations of the MBL, while the remaining ones are each very rarely attested (once or twice) because we made the choice to first process the frequently attested ones. The standardization process resulted in the attributions of unique identifiers at the level of both variants and lemmas (resp. NamVar and Nam ID), and to every element of the original name (Descriptor ID).

4.1.2 Standardizing first names

Given names display much less variation. The 3,783 unique variants account for 170,100 attestations of given names. Because of the relatively small number of variants, we proceeded with a manual approach to the clustering, supported by the consultation of reference lists such as those found in the *Nederlandse Voornamenbank* of the Meertens Instituut,²³ the *Oxonian A Dictionary of First Names* (Hanks et al., 2006), the WFN and *Behind the Name: the Etymology and History of First Names*,²⁴ a website which collects names from various traditions and sources and has a system of manual verification for each new entry. Because each of these resources singularly only covered a small percentage of the MBL first names, and adopted different criteria in terms of grouping variants together, we did not systematically follow the lemmatization of one resource (as we did for the last names). However, the dataset downloaded from the website Behind the name, could be used to enrich our given name variants to include the gender automatically. At the end of the manual process of clustering, 2,271 distinct lemmas were identified for the given names, and received a unique identifier (as did the variants). In Figure 1, we summarize the workflow for standardizing the MBL names. Place names are discussed in Section 6.

4.2 Integrating other datasets

The benefit from of the standardisation and linking of names is widely recognized, something which is particularly important when working with digital networks, for example (Ahnert and Ahnert, 2023; Finegold et al., 2016). For the other nine datasets, a fairly uniform procedure was implemented to standardize the data, with some deviations depending on the particular data formats. There are a number of different approaches which can be taken to match. A fully automated record linkage pipeline, using software such as DeezyMatch, which uses a deep learning approach to fuzzy record linkage by generating word vectors which can be used for candidate matching and clustering, is one possible approach (Hosseini et al., 2020). Another example of an automated approach is the Entity Matching Tool developed as part of the European Holocaust Research Infrastructure consortium.²⁵ Another widely used automated approach is rules-based, for example matching various combinations of names and variants, sometimes taking into account spelling and name variations (Hill et al., 2019). This can include considering ‘edit distances’ or phonetic spelling to find fuzzy matches. However, these methods, particularly when they involve unsupervised or

²³ <https://nvb.meertens.knaw.nl/>. Accessed 6 Oct. 2024.

²⁴ <https://www.behindthename.com>. Accessed 6 Oct. 2024.

²⁵ <https://emt.ehri-project.eu>.

Figure 1: The essential steps for standardizing the MBL names.

semi-supervised clustering algorithms, are not necessarily suitable for a database meant for information retrieval, where naming incorrect matches is more detrimental than missing correct ones, in other words, precision is more important than recall.²⁶

To this end we implemented a rules-based approach without fuzzy matching, augmented with a ‘human in the loop’ workflow. Since these datasets generally start from the source record (i.e. a printed book, a thesis sheet, a bounded manuscript with student notes), the data about persons they contain is subsidiary and, in most cases, does not include a disambiguating person level, only a person-related-to-source, i.e. person attestation, level.²⁷ This did not require much additional work in most of the datasets, apart from standardizing the event date and the role the person had in relation to the event. The second step consisted of creating preliminary person records. As explained above, most of these datasets have already implemented a limited form of name standardization. This has the benefit that it is fairly straightforward to create an overarching person level for each dataset simply by grouping together those name strings with an exact match under a (temporary) unique ID (definitive IDs were only awarded upon import in the live STUDIUM.AI database). Since the standardization was not always carried out rigorously, the matching was done by using a concatenation of the name string + the date string of a person, e.g. ‘PhilippusvanDormael1611-1635’.²⁸ Only those attestations with an exact match were grouped together under a single person ID. If other attestations exist with the exact same name but a slightly deviating date (or no date at all), these were kept apart as distinct individuals to be checked during the final disambiguation round involving all datasets (as described in Subsection 4.3). The third step involved creating the Descrip-

²⁶ See for instance Shoilee et al. 2024.

²⁷ DaLet and Manuale Lovaniense are the two exceptions here. The former assigned its own Person IDs. The data of the latter is stored in ODIS, a research infrastructure used by various research projects where person disambiguation has already taken place; its person attestations are therefore linked to ODIS’ stable person IDs.

²⁸ Spaces were removed as they could potentially cause matches to be overlooked by creating meaningless variation (van Dormael is the same name as Vandormael) or by input errors such as double or trailing whitespaces.

Table 2: Number of new name variants and new names per dataset.

Database	New given name variants	New family name variants
Lovaniensia	421	1,211
CAA	332	1,049
ODIS	35	210
Magister Dixit	42	100
Thesis sheets	32	142
DaLet	106	154
LLogeia	[to be processed]	[to be processed]
Leonardi	[to be processed]	[to be processed]

Table 3: Number of new records per table in STUDIUM.AI's People section for each dataset. PS indicates unique persons, while person attestations their mentions in each database.

Dataset	PS	PSAtt	Descriptors
MBL	143,303	143,303	474,771
Lovaniensia	2,415	6,465	14,889
CAA	3,070	7,311	16,529
Manuale Lovaniense	326	1,377	2,927
Magister Dixit	620	1,605	3,793
Thesis sheets	6,538	5,305	21,296
DaLet	795	1,776	3,385
LLogeia	[to be processed]	[to be processed]	[to be processed]
Leonardi	[to be processed]	[to be processed]	[to be processed]
Total	157,067 (pre merge)	167,142	537,590

tor records. For this, the identification string listed for each person's attestation had to be broken down into distinct elements, mostly names, but sometimes also an origin or a suffix used for homonyms. As with the matriculation data, a distinction was made between first names, middle names, patronymics, and family names. The attestations of the first two categories were matched with the given name variants extracted from the matriculation records, while those of the last two categories were matched with the family name variants. In case of a match, the corresponding NamVar and Nam IDS were imported into the working file. Name variants without a match needed to be integrated into the existing setup. The Nam table, recording the lemmatized version of name variants, was sifted for a suitable candidate. If one was found, the new variant was linked to it; if not, a new standard name was created for it. This was repeated for every next dataset that was processed (see Table 2).

Once each descriptor was linked to the correct name or place ID, the dataset was ready for import. Table 3 gives an overview of the number of records in each table created from the files provided by the various participating projects.

The workflow for ingesting these datasets is described in Figure 2.

4.3 'Human in the loop' matching process

As well as this rules-based matching, the project is undertaking to match more ambiguous cases by relying on input from scholars. The human-in-the-loop approach, or semi-automated one, where automatic methods such as string matching are checked manually by experts, sometimes including 'crowd-sourcing', is a good solution where

Figure 2: General workflow for digesting datasets other than the MBL.

precision is very important. This has the advantage of producing more accurate results while at the same time greatly speeding up a fully manual approach. Ruth and Sebastian Ahnert, for example, developed a tool called ‘The Disambiguation Engine’, used for the reconciliation of person records in Tudor and Stuart correspondence. This tool grouped together identical names and displayed them alongside other metadata, allowing a user to either mark multiple similar names as the same person, or mark identical names as separate people, based on the sources themselves. A similar tool, RECON, was developed for the database Early Modern Letters Online (Hyvönen et al., 2019). These tools enable those with historical expertise to benefit from the fast and scalable methods of data analysis, and vice versa. In both RECON and the Disambiguation Engine, a relatively straightforward approach to names was taken. Names were matched primarily on simple string matches, perhaps with some basic data cleaning such as removing punctuation or spaces.

The detailed onomastic modelling carried out on the STUDIUM.AI project means a more sophisticated approach can be taken into account, by matching on name variants as well as straightforward strings. On STUDIUM.AI, this was implemented using a tool which finds potential matches by comparing combinations of name variants, and provides them within an interface which allows a user to check and merge the records together if they are deemed true matches. The tool is built into the Filemaker database. It displays all potential matches, starting with those where both a given and family name are shared (with standardisation taken into account). A user can then choose to merge records together if they conclude that the person is indeed the same. This is helpful because in many cases, the names are still not exactly the same, and we may have different sets of dates (floruit dates in one database and dates of birth and death in another, say). In other cases, we can check the original files for additional information. This is particularly useful in the case of named individuals in texts. In many cases, further information about the people can be found by consulting the original manuscript files, and we can merge these matches together. The tool was implemented at a series of data ‘edit-a-thon’ events, where interested parties and experts sat together to check and discuss the results of the automated matches.

Figure 3: Screenshot of the matching tool. On the left, a matriculation record is displayed (matriculation of Erasmus Desiderius; on the right, the potential candidates, identified through name variants' similarities) for the Lovaniensia book data.

These events resulted in approximately 6,000 person records marked and merged with existing ones. A screenshot of the interface of the matching tool is provided in Figure 3.

This de-duplication process, carried out both within and across collections, forms the basis for the connections across the STUDIUM.AI datasets. 2,148 persons are found across more than one dataset, with the most frequent being the theologian Gommarus Huygens (1631–1702), who appears in 7 of the 10 datasets. The many traces of Huygens' connection to the old University—his matriculation record, monographs, printed lecture notes and appearances as a promotor in thesis sheets—are all now interlinked.

5 Working with the KU Leuven ManGO repository for active data

Our second research question relates to best practices regarding the data, to ensure the origin and cleaning of the data happens in a transparent and reproducible way, and to respect the intellectual property and provenance of the sources and their creators. Naturally, this linking process is only feasible if the underlying data workflow supports it. Because the motivation is that STUDIUM.AI functions as a linking resource rather than as a creator of data, it was important for the workflow to support an easy method to link to the underlying data sources. At the same time, we did have to carry out processing and, in the process of this, make changes to the data, for example by standardising names. In the front end (which will be developed in the course of 2025, hence the data are not shared yet), this means having IDs to the original records so they can be consulted. To properly record our changes or augmentation to the data, this meant that we developed a workflow which would ensure that the work we carried

out on the data was reproducible from the original partner files. As a project dealing with data from different partners and in different formats and states of readiness, there are a number of key challenges:

- How do we retain as much reproducibility as possible given that manual intervention by experts was unavoidable?
- How do we correctly link back to the original data and collections provided by the partners?
- How do we ensure that the correct usage rights are communicated alongside the different records, given that the data is coming from different circumstances with different approaches to copyright?

For the data workflow and management, we have divided the process into two: first, the active research data, and second the long-term storage. By active research data, we mean the files which are currently being worked on. In this paper, we primarily describe the processes relating to the ongoing active research data phase. For the active research data, we are using a service called ManGO provided by KU Leuven.²⁹ The system is based on the open source data management software iRODS, and can be accessed from an ordinary computer through a web-based interface, or through a number of programming clients. ManGO is designed to ensure that the data we use on STUDIUM.AI is managed according to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reproducible). One key goal for FAIR data is to ensure it is ‘machine actionable’, meaning it can be easily worked on computationally without the need for manual intervention. In the context of a project like this, this might mean that at a later stage, we can easily recall and update the data used on the project with a new version without the need to re-process the data. *Findable*: Metadata for the original and processed datasets are described using the ManGO system and a standardized schema based on Dublin Core/DataCite standards³⁰, Keywords creator, publisher, geographic, and temporal coverage information are included to enhance findability. ManGO’s search function and Elasticsearch technology ensure easy retrieval of records. *Accessible*: Data is stored on centralized servers with a transparent authentication system via the ManGO platform, ensuring access to the most recent versions. Data and metadata are retrievable through the iRODS³¹ system, command line tools, and Python. *Interoperable*: Data is stored in open formats like .csv, .tsv, XML, and JSON, adhering to Dublin Core standards. Metadata and schemas are also in accessible, interoperable formats. Proprietary formats like .xlsx are converted to text-based formats (csv, tsv) for the project. *Reproducible*: Data processing is automated using scripts in Filemaker, R, or Python. Code, derived, and intermediate files are kept for reproducibility. Unique identifiers and references in Filemaker ensure FAIR data principles apply, allowing users to trace and reproduce steps with proper permissions.

A typical workflow is to import a MARC 21 XML file and convert it to a series of flat format dataframes, then extract and clean the relevant data fields. To give an example, this is the workflow used to import the data from one collection, a set of thesis sheets held by KU Leuven library.

²⁹ <https://rdm-docs.icts.kuleuven.be/mango/index.html>. Accessed 6 Oct 2024. ManGO also allows for fine-grained control over user permissions and access, meaning that both project members and partners can have access to and modify or change, if necessary, their own datasets.

³⁰ <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>. Accessed 6 Oct. 2024.

³¹ <https://irods.org/>

1. Data received by the library in MARC21 XML format. The filename is versioned and a read-only copy is uploaded to the ManGO repository.
2. To convert MARC21 into something useable by Filemaker, the XML was first processed into a series of dataframes (one for each tag) using R.
3. The relevant information on people, places, and sources was extracted from these tables.
4. The data was processed according to the Filemaker STUDIUM.AI data model, including joining the names to the existing Filemaker names variants so they could be standardized.
5. For this particular dataset, there was a piece of information not found within the semi-structured data form on the MARC21 XML. Person names had been extracted and standardized from information on the title pages, and entered in the MARC 700 field. However, the names on the title pages also included, in most cases, information on the origin of the person, and this had not been extracted alongside the rest of the name. It was information that could assist in linking records as well as historically valuable so we decided to retain it.
6. To do so, the names were extracted from the title statements using regular expressions (these origins were often found in a standardized format such as *ex Lovanii* or *Chimacensis*, or from Louvain or Chimay).
7. The result of the regex matching was a messy and incomplete list of origin places. This list of non-corrected and non-standardised place names was exported as a .csv and uploaded to a shared drive.
8. Place names checked. In some cases the regex rules gave incorrect place names, but where they were correct, they were linked to existing Filemaker place records. This was done manually by entering the correct Filemaker record IDs for places into a cloud-based spreadsheet application.
9. Updated spreadsheets were re-imported to R and used to populate the Filemaker tables before upload.
10. Final set of tables exported from R and imported into Filemaker.

Each dataset provided by partners is kept in a separate collection. The metadata schema can be updated and there is a metadata versioning system. We are using a modified version of the Dublin Core schema, including title, description, collection, a partner url, a unique identifier for the project component, as well as various standardized metadata fields such as dates and geographic location. The original datasets are kept in read-only folders so they can be accessed but not changed. Supplementary and intermediate datasets are kept in a 'work' folder, for example those necessary to do matching. Scripts used to process the raw data files are also kept here. The last sub collection contains the final files used to export the data to the Filemaker database. As far as possible, this workflow means that everything is reproducible. There are some places where this 'chain' of reproducibility has to be broken – for instance the only way to clean some of the data, for example determining and correcting place names used as part of person descriptors, is to do this manually, using a UI such as a spreadsheet. As much as possible was automated using scripts and regular expressions. However, even

with complex regex rules, the resulting dataset needed to be checked and corrected by hand by multiple people with expertise. This meant exporting a semi-processed dataset, checking manually using a shared spreadsheet, and then importing the corrected data into the final data files. Keeping these files along with the scripts to show how they were created and then used retains as much of the reproducibility as possible. However, we believe that in many cases this kind of semi-automatic workflow is the only realistic one and the aim should be to make it as easy as possible to recreate or understand which decisions were automated and which were manual.

Another key principle was that we are linking datasets together rather than providing new data. In order to preserve this principle, we needed to ensure that that our database referenced the original files sent by data partners. ManGO allowed us to have stable files with version numbers which could be referenced in an import field in the Filemaker database. Therefore, original data files provided by data partners are given unique and version names, and these names are attached to any data import to the Filemaker system. Additionally, these file identifiers can be referenced in derived data and scripts, so that it is always possible to tell exactly which version of a file the data has come from. Particularly key is having a system for doing updates over time, which a good metadata schema and versioning system allows us to do. Naturally, having good documentation (of both the original files plus any derived versions) is vital. Lastly, it was important to stick to the principle of linking rather than changing data so that we can retain the credibility of the original data sent from partners but make it easier to access for the kinds of needs of researchers and digital humanities practitioners. This means that while the data is not changed, we do augment it, for example by adding authority files to place names and giving standardized versions.

6 Integrating Authority files

As well as linking across the project's datasets through names of individual persons, we link to external resources and datasets by including different types of authority files. These 'external links' are both to the original partner datasets, where possible, and authority resources such as VIAF and geographical references in Wikidata. This brings with it the potential to make the data more interoperable in the future, as well as enhance the accuracy of the data concerned. Links are stored in a one-to-many way using a links table, which stores related URIs, authority files, and IDs. First of all, STUDIUM.AI stores a range of links and URIs from the participating datasets: e.g. the entries for 'people' in the DaLeT project, or the stable URLs for 'persons' and 'publications' used by ODIS. For printed texts cataloged by KU Leuven Libraries, the stable URLs to the KU Leuven LIMO catalogue are also included for the relevant printed texts and rare books. Whenever the MARC21 data included links to Short Title Catalogues for rare books, mostly the Universal Short-title Catalogue (USTC),³² and the Short Title Catalogue Flanders (STCV),³³ the links were extracted as to enhance interoperability. Authority files for geographical entities were handled in a slightly more complex way, which is outlined in some more detail below. The datasets contain multiple sources of geographical information (about 'places'), recording different spatial characteristics and features, related to different parts of the metadata. Most of the 160,000 names in the matriculation records contain a toponym used as part of a name descriptor, e.g. 'Jacobus Philippus Debruyen Lovaniensis', recording the place

³² <https://www.ustc.ac.uk/>. Accessed 6 Oct. 2024.

³³ <https://www.stcv.be>. Accessed 8 June 2024.

of origin (rather than of birth). In the same vein, the thesis sheets use a very similar kind of descriptor in the names of the defendants (students) and their promotors (professors). A second source of geographical data is found in bibliographic records: here, the place of publication is almost always listed on the title page or colophon of printed works, and subsequently recorded in the MARC21 metadata. Consequently, there is a complex, interesting, and interlinked spatial network surrounding these records, from the origin places of the students matriculating or graduating to the places of publication for works associated with the university. This is a valuable source of information that can be used for research in spatial history and spatial humanities, ranging from map visualisations to spatial analysis, particularly in the context of book history (Black et al., 2021; Elliott and Gillies, 2009; Lahti et al., 2019). In total there are about 33,000 unique strings used as place descriptors in the STUDIUM.AI dataset. In the first step, these were grouped together under place names in much the same manner as with family and given names. The place Leuven, for instance, is represented in the dataset as the following non-standardised strings, coming from attestations of people and sources: *Leuven*; *Liuvensis*; *Loewensis*; *Lovaiensis*; *Lovanienij*; *Lovanienis*; *Lovanieniss*; *Lovaniensis*; *Lovaniensos*; *Lovanio*; *Lovaniuensis*; *Loviensis*; *Lowaniensis*; *Lowensis*; *a Lovanio*; *civis Lovaniensis*; *de Lona* [*Lovanio*]; *de Louvanio*; *de Lovania*; *de Lovanie*; *de Lovanio*; *de Lovaniolo*; *de Lovanis*; *de lovanio*; *in Castris Lovaniensis*; *natus Lovanii*; *opidi Lovaniensis*; *oriundus Lovanio*; *prop Lovanium*; *prope Lovaniam*; *prope Lovanium*. During this phase, these 33,000 unique strings collapsed to about 9,000 place records. To geocode the dataset we used a database and resource called the World Historical Gazetteer (Grossner and Mostern, 2021). The WHG is conceived as software enabling the connection of specialist collections of place names. Using the WHG allows us to incorporate this inherent conceptual ‘fuzziness’ and represent the changing aspects of historical place names. The WHG contains an interface for geocoding. We exported a dataset containing all the various variations of the place names. The WHG checks them against a database containing geographic entities from Wikidata and Geonames, and the Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names – a total of 13 million place names. These are then manually verified using a user interface. The user interface displays all the information about the attestation, including all name variants, as well as coordinates if these had already been added to the record by the project. Alongside the information all found possible matches from the WHG index are displayed, using fuzzy matching across all the variants. Users checking the records can say whether each is a match or not, given the information at hand. Once finished, this augmented data can be downloaded and integrated within STUDIUM.AI.

So far, this process has allowed us to add 2,180 new geometries and 6,702 links (e.g Geonames, Wikidata, Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names, BNF, and Library of Congress URIs). These primarily come from (the modern borders of) Belgium (1893 unique places found so far), the Netherlands (502), France (222), Germany (144), Italy (36), Ireland (31), Spain (17), Luxembourg (15), and Turkey (15). On the one hand—if we restrict the maps to the matriculation records alone—these first visualisations confirm that Leuven recruited mainly in the Hinterland (a radius of about 150 kilometers), yet on the other hand, they now clearly show how the Revolt and the emergence of the Dutch Republic condensed the recruiting era to Belgium and a part of Northern France, in other words, that territories which were still under the Catholic Habsburg regime in the seventeenth century.

The WHG output format is called Linked Place Format – an extension of the GEOJSON format, which allows temporal scoping of place records, meaning a record can

Figure 4: A map of the currently geocoded places from the STUDIUM.AI database, projected on a current map.

associated with both a place on earth (a geometry) and a set of dates.³⁴ Our final gazetteer will be published through the WHG, and we can use the published version to generate unique place URIs which will be referred to by the project. In this way, we do not have to rely on a single digital resource but can represent the fuzziness and historicity of the place names found within the datasets. The finished dataset can be later accessioned to the WHG ‘union index’, which collects all publicly-published attestations of places under the same record, with information on the source, temporal scope, various names, and so forth.. We will be able in this way to contribute in terms of the names and variants referring to existing places, which is of onomastic and historic interest.

7 Conclusions

STUDIUM.AI started from a modest idea to integrate the wide expertise in Digital Humanities to link existing datasets together, both those generated by GLAM-institutions and those dressed by research teams or individual researchers from different disciplines. This intent to ‘break silos’ in ongoing research on the early modern history of the University of Leuven (1425-1797) evolved into a shared endeavor to build a research infrastructure across 8 teams and 4 faculties of the current KU Leuven. The research infrastructure enables collaborative research in the future by a shared back-end of linked data in a common core. In this paper, we have discussed the infrastructure under three different perspectives. First, we have shown how the task of interlinking

³⁴ See also <https://github.com/LinkedPasts/linked-places-format>. Accessed 6. Oct. 2024.

data benefits from semi-automated approaches, that, while preserving the accuracy of the identified matches, accelerate the process. Moreover, our project integrated existing reference resources (such as onomastic dictionaries) into a digital workflow. This strengthens the reliability of the final output. Second, we have discussed our efforts in terms of data-management, in order to make our infrastructure sustainable to the (inevitable) evolutions both of the source datasets and the staff involved. Finally, we described the effort of enriching the data thanks to the integration of external authority files, which paves the way to further analysis and visualizations. Along with this project to build a common core of research data, currently a new HTR model is being developed to build a full-text corpus of the handwritten student notes, which will yield, through NER and NEL, additional data.

The standardization of data (be it names of persons or places, as discussed in this paper) might be a time-consuming process, but the added value is clear. The linking of data bears the potential to visualise networks across single datasets, here 'breaking the silos' of formerly separate (meta)data creation. For example, students are now being connected to professors (through student notes or defended theses), and in turn, these can be connected to printers and publishers and so forth. The linked data also help to identify new brokers or 'bridging figures' between the academic and the book world of early modern Leuven, individuals who might otherwise not show up in the single data sets. This standardisation also brings the possibility of linking across other university datasets and even national collections, though others have discussed the conceptual problems with standardising certain categories of information, such as roles and degrees, across different datasets and traditions (Rubio Muñoz 2022). As it is, the current data enrichment by integrating geographical information helps to build out a whole new set of research questions about the worldwide spread of the networks in and especially beyond Leuven. As such, the research infrastructure can help answer questions about places, such as printed outputs and matriculation, identifying temporal-spatial clusters across datasets, looking at spatial patterns in recruitment, etc. This new interpretation of Louvain as a hub in evolving temporal-spatial clusters of the transfer of knowledge can help to reassess the historiography of the early modern university from a DH-perspective.

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The Wartime Propaganda Puzzle

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1 Abstract

This paper presents the efforts of the Media War Matching project to combine the puzzle pieces of Second World War propaganda collections, namely audio recordings of radio broadcasts, transcripts of radio broadcasts and newspapers. To give researchers a richer and broader picture of propaganda dynamics in the Nazi-occupied Netherlands, the project published digitised radio transcripts in the CLARIAH Media Suite, an online platform for humanities research, so that they could be analyzed both in isolation and in combination with other wartime media collections. In this paper, we first introduce the wartime propaganda landscape, as well as the Media War project, which combined quantitative and qualitative approaches to analyzing propaganda in pro- and anti-Nazi Dutch language media. Subsequently, we discuss the Media War Matching project, which emanated from the challenges and opportunities that the Media War research team encountered during their work. Then, we relate how we published a specific set of radio transcripts in the Media Suite so that researchers could optimally search and browse them, including the development of an algorithm to automatically date the individual pages. Next, we explain how we attempted to link the audio of radio broadcasts to the relevant transcripts, using Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR). Finally, we demonstrate how the publication of propaganda collections in the CLARIAH Media Suite, despite the limitations of the source material and the lack of success of linking, still enables the identification and comparison of quantitative patterns that can act as a starting point for further qualitative analysis of narratives. In conclusion, this paper reflects on the lessons learned and aims to inspire others to digitise, publish and link media collections.

2 Introduction

The study of historical wartime propaganda is increasingly relevant in the light of current events (Connelly et al., 2019, pp. 1-12). This is underlined by the fact that national leaders embroiled in conflicts refer to incidents from previous wars in their propaganda (Wijdeven (2022)). Understanding propaganda in the past can therefore contribute to understanding the present day.

A large number of sources of World War II propaganda in the Netherlands has survived. Yet these sources are scattered over isolated silos, residing in fragmentary collections of different media types preserved by different institutions and published on different platforms. This scattering makes it hard for propaganda researchers to find sources, let alone to see the relationships between them or discover patterns. The MediaOorlog (Media War) project, financed by the Mondriaan Fonds within the programme '75 jaar Vrijheid' (75 years of freedom), focused on making various propaganda sources available to researchers to enable them to study transnational dynamics over time. To achieve these objectives researchers within this project worked with relevant collections in the digital humanities platform CLARIAH Media Suite.

During the project, it became clear that there are significant imbalances in the availability of different types of material. In Kuitenbrouwer and Brolsma (2023) the authors argue that 'these imbalances can be explained by the historical context in which these sources were created as well as by archival policies after 1945'. For example, there are far more Nazified newspaper articles available than anti-Nazi (Kuitenbrouwer and Wijfjes (2022)), and newspaper sources are available in far larger numbers than radio recordings (Kuitenbrouwer and Brolsma (2023)). These imbalances present researchers with additional challenges, as it is hard to determine if an apparent trend is meaningful, or merely an artefact of the imbalance. The limited availability of radio recordings led the authors of Kuitenbrouwer and Brolsma (2023) to argue for this imbalance to be partially addressed by the digitisation of archives of related documents such as radio transcripts and monitoring reports, and for their publication in the CLARIAH Media Suite. Additionally this could also bring together the bulky 'radio on paper' collections and the fragmented audio which has remained from the war to reconstruct the production archives of the broadcasting organisations that have been separated over the past decades (Kuitenbrouwer (2022)).

The Media War Matching project took up this call to arms by addressing the availability, findability and usability of wartime media. More specifically, the project worked to publish the BNO (Berichtendienst Nederlandsche Omroep)¹ collection in the CLARIAH Media Suite so that it could be easily searched and browsed. This collection contains transcripts of broadcasts by the BNO radio broadcaster, a radio news service which spread Nazi propaganda. These transcripts are particularly relevant to researchers as they can provide insight into the overall broadcasting strategies and also serve as a proxy to better search and analyze surviving audio recording of radio broadcasts. In a broader goal, the project sought to combine the puzzle pieces of audio recordings of radio broadcasts, their transcripts and wartime newspapers from the same date to give researchers a richer and broader picture of wartime propaganda in the Netherlands. Finally, the project looked at how analysis of patterns over these sources could offer added value for propaganda researchers.

In this paper, we first introduce the wartime propaganda landscape. Then we delve into the Media War project, the propaganda collections involved, the approaches developed for working with them, and the challenges that gave birth to the Media War Matching project. Then we describe the publication of the BNO collection, including our efforts to date the pages and to support data and tool criticism by users of this collection. Next, we explain how we attempted to link the audio of radio broadcasts to the relevant transcripts, using Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR). After that, we demonstrate how the publication of propaganda collections in the CLARIAH

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Media Suite enables quantitative analysis. Finally, we conclude by summarizing our experiences in publishing the BNO propaganda collection, and detail both lessons learned and plans for future work.

3 Background

3.1 Multimedia wartime propaganda

During World War II, all official media in the Netherlands were under the control of the Nazis. This included the two Nazified radio stations in Hilversum, operated from March 1941 onwards by the Nederlandsche Omroep, and the existing national and regional newspapers which were brought under Nazi control after the invasion in May 1940 (Verkijk (1974), Vos (1988), Wolf and van Vree (2019)). However, there were also media available from the opposing side which challenged the Nazi propaganda narratives. Illegal newspapers were produced within the Netherlands, and the radio programmes De Brandaris and Radio Oranje were broadcast from London on the BBC transmitters to reach Dutch audiences (Sinke (2005), Sinke (2009), Winkel (1954), van den Heuvel and Mulder (1990)).

There are many imbalances in the primary sources left from the years 1940-1945 which have to be taken into consideration when analysing this propaganda battle between pro-Nazi and pro-Allied Dutch language media. The digitised war newspapers collection of the Royal Library is by far the largest propaganda archive. In the context of the Heritage of War [Erfgoed van de oorlog] project all available wartime newspapers have been digitised. The collection is available via the Delpher² portal and also in the Newspaper collection of the Media Suite.³ It consists of no fewer than 133.000 digitised newspapers segmented into 6.942.271 articles. The sheer size of this collection allows media scholars and historians to employ quantitative research methods to identify semantic patterns.

Compared to the Dutch newspaper media landscape, radio broadcasting was in various respects more dynamic due to the faster interaction that the medium offered. On both sides of the English Channel people listened intensively to the broadcasts of the adversary and produced monitoring reports that were actively used as 'ammunition' for their own propaganda. These practices continued even after the Nazi authorities confiscated wireless radio receiving sets in Occupied Netherlands in May 1943. In the last years of the war, broadcasts from London remained an important source of news about the war for the underground press. People who clandestinely listened to the BBC and Radio Oranje transcribed and reproduced the texts of these broadcasts and disseminated them in periodicals with telling titles such as *Here is the B.B.C.* (*Hier is de B.B.C.*) and *The Aether Courier* (*De Aetherkoerier*) (Kuitenbrouwer and Wijfjes, 2022, p.192).

Despite the historical importance of radio as a propaganda tool, the digitised audio archive held by The Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision (NISV) is fragmented and relatively small. It contains 2271 audio items, of which 2040 have been digitised. Of Radio Oranje broadcasts, for instance, only 223 audio fragments remain, out of an estimated total of 3500 full broadcasts. Due to the specific circumstances of the war, including censorship, a relatively large amount of paper radio sources has been

² <https://www.delpher.nl/>

³ <https://mediasuite.clariah.nl/tool/single-search?queryId=13e0c19e-0d92-4d36-9b36-db899f118ec2>

preserved compared to the period before and after. These include a large body of radio texts from the *Nederlandsche Omroep*: the complete transcripts of *Radio Oranje* and *De Brandaris*, and more than 20,000 monitoring reports (summaries and verbatim transcripts) of the broadcasts of the Hilversum stations created by the listening service of the Dutch government-in-exile. All of these analogue collections, consisting of tens of thousands of pages, are kept at the NIOD Institute for War Genocide and Holocaust Studies.

Digitizing this large 'radio on paper' archive and making it accessible to researchers together with the audio collection would offer an important extension of the available material. Reuniting these collections that have been separated and scattered over various archival institutions would also undo the artificial divisions between them. Finally, it would enable historians to conduct academic research, using both qualitative and quantitative methods, into the content of the pro-Nazi and pro-Allied propaganda and the war of words between these adversaries. This type of research, that was pioneered by the Media War project, is an important intervention in the existing scholarly literature on Dutch language media during the Second World War, which mainly examines the institutional side of wartime radio (Verkijk (1974), Sinke (2009)).

To achieve its goals the Media War research fellows made use of digital humanities techniques to study the newspaper collection in conjunction with the radio audio collection, employing both distant reading and close reading methodologies. These digitised wartime collections of *Delpher* and *NISV* are available in the online, digital humanities platform *CLARIAH Media Suite*. In addition, the fellows also consulted the paper radio archive at NIOD to fill in gaps. In the following sections we will first discuss the Media Suite, the various relevant source collections, and the challenges they posed. Subsequently, we will focus on the pilot Media War Matching project, which was created to tackle these challenges, adding a sub-collection of digitised Nazified radio transcripts to the existing collections in the Media Suite and exploring the possibilities and challenges for analysing these sources in combination with the available audio and newspapers.

3.2 The Media Suite

The Media Suite is a suite of tools developed within the *CLARIAH*⁴ project. The Media Suite brings together diverse media heritage collections, and enables researchers to search, view, bookmark and annotate items from these collections. Search results can be visualised over time, potentially revealing patterns, and these visualisations can be compared between different collections.

The Media Suite supports basic quantitative analysis with statistics and visualisations of the occurrence of search hits over time and the frequency of metadata field values. To allow more detailed analysis, the Media Suite APIs provide direct data access, so that the data can be processed by a researcher in their own software. A popular tool for this is a Jupyter Notebook⁵, an easy-to-use programming environment that combines text, code and visualisations. Direct data access is currently only available onsite at NISV for selected projects, due to copyright restrictions.

The Media Suite is already used by Dutch researchers from various humanities disciplines. At the same time, it is under active development. The Media Suite development team cooperates with users in projects to explore and develop new functionality that

⁴ <https://www.clariah.nl/>

⁵ <https://jupyter.org/>

Figure 1: Imbalance in categories within wartime newspaper collection

may be added to the Media Suite, immediately or in the future.

These characteristics make the Media Suite uniquely placed to play a key role in breaking down the barriers between propaganda collections and enabling their investigation and analysis.

3.3 The Newspaper collection

From the onset of the Media War project it was clear that the bulky newspaper collections were a rich resource but also provided various challenges for historical research on Second World War propaganda. On the basis of the existing metadata no divisions could be made between papers supporting the Nazi occupation of the Netherlands and those resisting it. Therefore, the Media War team set out to enrich the collection by categorizing the newspapers into the following categories:

- Pro-Nazi, subdivided into censored newspapers, Nazi party newspapers;
- Anti-Nazi, subdivided into illegal newspapers and newspapers which appeared in the liberated south of the Netherlands from September 1944 onwards).

The first quantitative visualisations of these categories showed significant imbalances within the wartime newspaper collections, as Figure 1) shows. The biggest discrepancy is between 'censored', which includes more than 6 million articles, and 'illegal', which contains not even 300 thousand articles. This discrepancy, however, changed over time. As the war progressed, more and more illegal papers were published. In turn, both the number and size of the censored newspapers decreased. Around September 1944 the anti-Nazi press outnumbered the pro-Nazi press. This general trend can be explained by the historical context, including the dwindling supplies of the occupying regime which was partly caused by the successful raids of the resistance to steal paper to print their own publications.

To further analyse the war of words between pro- and anti-Nazi media, the research fellows developed keyword searches to generate semantic patterns over time. The Compare tool in the Media Suite allowed them to simultaneously visualise these patterns in the categories mentioned above. To tackle the quantitative imbalances

the Media War team added a new functionality to the Compare tool to show query results relative to their own category - or in Media Suite terms, 'relative to query facet'. Despite these efforts, however, researchers occasionally encountered problems generating semantic patterns, particularly in the illegal newspaper category, which consists of a lot of newspaper titles which had relatively few articles. Considering these limitations the researchers used the visualisations not as an end product of their examination, but rather as a starting point for further qualitative analysis, as they discussed in a 'data story' about the research.⁶

3.4 The Radio audio collection

The wartime radio collection maintained by the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision is published in the Media Suite as part of the larger Sound and Vision TV and Radio collection.⁷ The category 'broadcaster' in the metadata of this collection allowed the Media War team to easily make a distinction between pro-Nazi and anti-Nazi radio items. Due to the fragmentary nature of this collection, visualisations of this material did not yield significant results. Another obstacle for employing quantitative methodologies is the poor audio quality of many of the preserved and later digitised recordings which made Audio Speech Recognition (ASR) transcriptions not sufficiently reliable. Nonetheless, the research fellows made use of selected audio fragments in their work, focusing on important 'media moments', which they identified using the visualisations of semantic patterns in the wartime newspapers.

3.5 The Radio transcript collection

Confronted with the fragmentary nature of the wartime audio sources, the Media War team became increasingly aware of the importance of the radio paper archive to gain insight into the content of both the pro-Nazi and anti-Nazi radio broadcast during the war. While these paper collections, which seem to be nearly complete, provided them with much relevant information, studying these archival sources was also very time consuming. Moreover, because of the enormous amount of radio transcripts and monitoring reports, it was only possible to study very specific, well-demarcated moments in time. Obtaining an overall picture of certain propaganda narratives throughout the war was therefore not possible. Digitizing these collections could help to provide this overall picture.

One such paper collection of interest consists of digitised radio transcripts produced by the radio news service Berichtendienst van de Nederlandsche Omroep (BNO), which made news broadcasts for the centralised and Nazi-controlled Nederlandsche Omroep. For researchers the BNO collection is particularly relevant as it allows them to study how the occupying regime and its Dutch supporters used radio news for propaganda purposes and employed certain frames to interpret events along the lines of the Nazi ideology.

The BNO was set up on 1st April 1941, less than a month after the occupying authorities ordered a concentration of Dutch broadcasting corporations into one national broadcaster. The BNO replaced the radio news service of the press agency Algemeen Nederlandsch Persbureau (ANP) that had been brought under German control immediately after the start of the occupation. It was located in The Hague and had 55

⁶ <https://mediasuitedatastories.clariah.nl/mediaoorlog/>

⁷ <https://mediasuite.clariah.nl/tool/single-search?queryId=70967a36-4b36-40a1-a51e-a056836d0d61>

employees, mostly from the Drahtlose Dienst (Wireless Service). The direction was in the hands of G. Noordhuis, a fanatic Nazi who had worked for Radio Bremen before the war. In October 1943, the BNO moved to Hilversum and the number of employees was reduced to 33 (Verkijk, 1974, pp. 637-638).

The goal of the BNO was to create propaganda in the form of news broadcasts. Aside of the approximately five daily news bulletins that were broadcast simultaneously on both Hilversum stations, the BNO also produced two daily radio talks about economy, agriculture or culture. In addition to this, the BNO was responsible for the radio items of the pundits 'De Jordaner' and 'Jan Hollander', for broadcasts to the Dutch Indies and an infamous programme aimed at Dutch seafarers that was vehemently opposed from London by Radio Oranje and De Brandaris. According to the Dutch journalist and historian Dick Verkijk, who wrote a monumental work about Radio Hilversum during the Second World War, approximately 35% of all texts spoken on the Nederlandsche Omroep were produced by BNO employees (Verkijk, 1974, p.629). The service made programmes that partially overlapped with the topics covered in the Nederlandsche Omroep broadcasts. According to Verkijk, the BNO functioned as a 'broadcaster within a broadcaster', that in fact competed with the Nederlandsche Omroep. That the BNO was successful in this competition is apparent from the fact that the service could carry on broadcasting until the end of the war, whereas the Nederlandsche Omroep was forced to cease most programmes in 1944 (Verkijk, 1974, pp. 632-634).

The BNO collection is held by the NIOD institute for War, Holocaust and Genocide studies. In the context of the Media War project a large number of BNO transcripts were digitised, according to guidelines established in *Metamorfoze*.⁸ Two parts of the BNO collection were made available for digitisation: the 'BNO reports, 1940-1945' (84 folders of mainly news transcripts) and the 'Texts of broadcasts about economy and politics' (75 folders).⁹ After digitisation, the digital scans (Figure 2) were processed by OCR (Optical Character Recognition) using Abbyy software¹⁰ to produce searchable text transcripts. The available metadata for these transcripts was rudimentary, consisting of a division into folders, with each folder assigned to a date interval, ranging from two weeks to one or more months.

The NIOD institute made the transcripts available on their website. There, researchers can browse the folders, search for words in the OCR text, and read the scanned reports. It is not, however, possible to visualise search results to discover patterns or carry out any quantitative analysis. Finding out which transcripts were recorded on which date requires browsing through the folder of transcripts to find the broadcast. This is a cumbersome task, particularly as the transcripts are not always in date order, not all pages are dated and occasionally transcripts have been put in the wrong folder.

3.6 The Media War Matching project

The main aim of the Media War Matching project was to make the digitised BNO transcripts available in the Media Suite so that they could be analyzed by researchers, both in isolation and in combination with other wartime media collections, using the digital tools that the Media Suite offers. In addition, the project aimed to investigate

⁸ <https://www.metamorfoze.nl/front>

⁹ https://www.archieven.nl/mi/298/?mivast=298&mizig=210&miadt=298&micode=103&milang=nl&mizk_alle=bno&miview=inv2

¹⁰ <https://www.abbyy.com/ocr-sdk/>

Figure 2: Example transcript from the BNO collection

and develop new methods for publishing similar 'radio on paper' collections that can be used for future projects.

4 Method and results

4.1 Publication of radio transcripts

Publishing the BNO radio transcript collection in the Media Suite required special care and new techniques, due to the lack of metadata.

4.1.1 Granularity and date/title metadata

To allow the Media Suite tools to be optimally used, a certain degree of metadata is necessary, so that the data can be split into units of a useful granularity. Of particular importance is the date field, as this metadata allows researchers to examine how the occupying authorities framed specific events and appropriated and incorporated news in their broader propaganda narratives over time. Moreover, accurate date fields are also essential for comparison. For example, the source material in the newspapers collection is separated into individual articles, which are annotated with the newspaper title and the date of publication, enabling researchers to find articles from a given newspaper on a given date, and compare trends between newspapers and over time.

For the BNO collection, as already discussed, the metadata is rudimentary. One additional piece of metadata was derived from background knowledge of the BNO. It was known that the radio programmes were broadcast under the name 'ANP' from the start of the occupation up until the BNO was officially set up in April 1941. By checking the transcripts around this date, a researcher could pinpoint the moment at which the name BNO was first used in the radio announcement, in the 8:30am broadcast on 9th April 1941. This enabled us to automatically annotate all previous broadcasts with the broadcaster 'Nazified ANP', while later broadcasts were annotated

Figure 3: Examples of different date formats in the BNO collection

with the broadcaster 'BNO'.

Ideally the transcripts would be divided up into the texts of the individual radio broadcasts, and each broadcast annotated with the broadcast title and the broadcast date. The broadcast title and broadcast date, while absent from the metadata, are printed at the start of the relevant section of the transcript in the majority of cases.

For this reason, it was opted to extract date and title information from the OCR text. The assumption was that the presence of a date and broadcast title at the top of a page would indicate the start of a new broadcast.

4.1.2 Date and title recognition by Named Entity Recognition

The OCR text from the top of each page was passed through the SPACY¹¹ named entity recogniser, with the aim of detecting the dates and titles. During this process, we discovered an error in the underlying metadata: the page text had been produced by concatenating the individual blocks of sorted text, but this sorting was incorrect, meaning that the words at the start of the page text were not necessarily the words from the top of the page. When attempting to correct this by generating a new page text from correctly sorted blocks, we discovered that short blocks of text had apparently been discarded from the metadata, meaning that the resorted text missed some words. Crucially, the date/broadcast title was often recognised as a short, isolated block, so precisely this essential information had a higher risk of being left out.

Even allowing for these losses, SPACY missed a large number of dates and titles in the text. The reason for this was not entirely clear, but looking at the missed dates, we noted the large variation in date formats used in the text (Figure 3). The date/title combinations were also usually printed in isolation, without the context that would help NER. The BNO data may also differ from the type of data on which this SPACY model is trained. Our hypothesis is that these factors are the cause of the poor NER performance in this case.

In the course of the NER tests, we discovered that our assumption that a date would signal the start of a new broadcast was incorrect. A date and/or date/title combination was also sometimes repeated partway through a broadcast.

In our tests, we used the SPACY model out of the box, so we didn't train it on the BNO data or fine-tune its parameters. This would require a large amount of work to annotate and train the model, which was out of scope for this project. Retraining could

¹¹ <https://spacy.io/>, model `nl_core_news_lg` (3.4.0)

be an option for future work.

4.1.3 Alternatives to Named Entity Recognition

Attempts to find algorithms online that were capable of detecting dates with a wide range of formats met with no success. As a result, we chose to develop our own algorithm for date detection, which we could tailor to the formats used in the BNO collection.

For the titles of the news bulletins, we faced the problem that the broadcast titles varied only minimally - Radio 1, Radio 2, Radio 3, etc. Difficulties were compounded by Roman numerals also being used: Radio I, Radio II etc. To distinguish broadcasts required accuracy of a single character, while the variable quality of the recognised text would require us to allow more character errors in order to successfully detect the word 'radio'. This paradox led us to abandon the attempt to detect program titles within this project.

4.1.4 Custom date detection

We treated short numerical dates - e.g. 10-01-41, 10.01.1941 - separately to textual dates - e.g. '10 januari 1941'. We parsed short numerical dates using existing Python functionality.¹² For textual dates, the task was more complicated, so we created various aids to help us. We constructed lists of possible date parts: days (numbers 1-31 with and without leading zeros), months (full names and abbreviations) and years (1940-1945, 40-45). As the transcripts turned out to use English and German dates in addition to Dutch, we also listed the month names and abbreviations in these languages. We developed functions tailored to matching text to days, months or years. For example, for days we conducted a strict matching (as '20' must not be allowed to match to '21'), whereas for months we used fuzzy matching¹³ to compensate for small typing or OCR errors (e.g. september). Finally, we listed date formats that occurred in the transcripts, e.g. 'day month year', 'day month'. The initial version of the algorithm used these aids in the following steps:

- Extract the start of the page text
- Split the text on spaces
- Clean up each part of the text to correct frequently occurring OCR errors. E.g. '194I' to '1941', '10' to '10'
- Try to match each part of the text to a short numerical date. If a match is found, stop
- Otherwise, match each part of the text to the lists of months and years
- For good matches: For the list of possible date formats, extract the relevant surrounding parts of the text. E.g., given the text 'Vrijdag 13 eptember 94I', we have a good match for the month 'september'. A possible date format involving the month is 'day month year'. So we extract the word before our month match and the word after, giving us the candidate text '13 eptember 94I'.

¹² <https://www.programiz.com/python-programming/datetime/strptime>

¹³ <https://pypi.org/project/fuzzywuzzy/>

Figure 4: Example of a date annotation in the Media Suite (Under 'Comment' in 'My Annotations')

- For each candidate text, we calculated the scores for matching each date part with possible days, months and years
- For each possible format, we combined the relevant scores of each date part. For example, when testing the format 'day month year' on '13 eptember 94I', we combined the scores for matching '13' with days, 'eptember' with months, and '94I' with years.
- The highest scoring candidate text was selected. If this scored higher than a given threshold, then it was selected as a match for the transcript date

Note that not all date formats used in the transcripts were complete. So correctly detecting 'jan 1941' still did not give us a full date for the transcript.

We also experimented with generating a list of all possible dates, in all possible formats, and matching this with the candidate texts via fuzzy matching. This worked less well than comparing the individual parts of the date. For example, it regarded the match of '13 september' with '15 september' as being equally good as the match '13 september' with '13 s3ptember', whereas the latter is clearly better. The large number of possible dates also led to this method being very slow.

4.1.5 Performance of custom date algorithm

To evaluate the performance of our algorithm, we displayed the results as annotations in the Media Suite (Figure 4). A researcher viewing a page of a transcript was shown an annotation with the extracted date, if present. If this date was wrong, the researcher could add their own annotation with the correct date. This was done for three complete folders of transcripts, and for the first and last 50 pages of a random selection of 2 folders per year, one from the news transcripts, and one from the economy and politics transcripts. Based on the corrected results, we could measure the algorithm performance, analyse the source of the errors, and try to improve it.

The performance of the custom date algorithm, as evaluated manually by the researcher, varied strongly per folder. The worst folder scored only 3%, whereas the best was 100%.

Manually analysing the source of the errors gave the following two main causes:

- OCR text not readable by a human 62%
- Punctuation or spaces in the date, e.g. '1/1 2/1941' 14%

Figure 5: Percentage 'bad' OCR per folder

For the next 20% of errors, there were again two main different causes. For example, bad quality OCR sometimes led to letters being split up into multiple punctuation marks. Also, the previously noted problem of short blocks of text having been discarded from the metadata led to some dates being missed. Finally, the last 4% of the errors were due to a variety of small errors or unknown reasons.

Initial impressions of the OCR quality when starting the project were positive. The availability was high: there was OCR present for 99.97% of the transcripts. When browsing through the transcripts by hand, the quality generally appeared good. The analysis of the date algorithm errors, however, showed up a subset of the transcripts that had very poor OCR. A proper analysis of the quality would require manual evaluation, or perhaps analysis using language models. As a rough approximation, we plotted the number of transcripts per folder that had OCR transcripts of 50 characters or fewer (Figure 5). We regarded such short texts as an indication of 'bad' OCR.

The results show a strong dependency on the folder, explaining why the date extraction results were also strongly dependent on the folder. For the economy and politics broadcasts, there does not seem to be a particular pattern. For the news broadcast transcripts, quality clearly deteriorates over the course of 1943, possibly linked to poor paper quality in that phase of the war.

A brief test with Tesseract OCR¹⁴ on a few example transcripts showed significantly better results. For example, the date of one transcript was OCR'd as 'SQj3d@rda< IB 1944' in the current transcript, but as 'Rad4ô) 3 aa Dondeniag 18 1et 1944' by Tesseract, and when zoomed in to just the first line: 'Radio

¹⁴ <https://github.com/tesseract-ocr/tesseract>

Figure 6: Navigation within the folder of a transcript page

3vaù Donderdag 18 Mei 1944'. This would suggest a possible gain by repeating OCR processing of the transcripts with a different algorithm. This, however, lay outside the scope and remit of the Media War Matching project.

Experiments were conducted to correct the other sources of errors, for example by extending the list of common OCR errors to be corrected during cleanup, removing punctuation, or examining longer sections of text. Each method produced improvements for some transcripts while other transcripts performed worse. The only method that produced an overall improvement on average was correcting the OCR errors. This resulted in a marginal performance increase from 54.6% to 55% on average.

This performance is far too low for reliable use of these dates in the Media Suite. However, the errors occurred mostly in dates that were only partially recognised (e.g. day and month with no year, month and year with no day). When we used the date information of the folder to determine the year for dates with only a day and a month, and otherwise discarded partial dates, then we achieved a precision of 90-100%. This is far more usable. However, this meant we had dates for 36% of the transcript pages in total. This was a trade-off for higher accuracy at the expense of coverage.

4.1.6 Final version in the Media Suite

The ideal situation was to publish the transcripts to the Media Suite as separate texts for individual broadcasts. As identifying individual broadcasts did not work, we had the choice between publishing the transcripts per folder or per page. We opted to publish the transcripts per page, as this meant researchers could quickly pinpoint relevant material instead of having to browse an entire folder, often consisting of around 600 pages. Moreover, this choice meant that plots of search results over time gave more insight into how often a word occurred in different broadcasts. However, it is also valuable for researchers to be able to easily read the context of a found page, seeing the pages before and after it in the folder. For this reason, we added a button to the viewer, to allow researchers to easily browse through the folder around their found page, and a dropdown to allow them to select other pages in the folder (Figure 6).

We had three types of date information available to annotate the pages. The first was the folder date information, which was available for every page, but was imprecise, indicating as it did a range of weeks. The second was the automatically extracted date information, which was precise to the day and also had a high accuracy, but was only available for about a third of the pages. Finally, we had the ground truth date information entered by the researcher. This was extended for the folders 310 and 397 which contain materials from the first month of the BNO's existence, and for the folders 323-330, which contain transcripts of news bulletins from September-December 1941 a period which was of particular interest to the Media War research fellows. This

Figure 7: Combining the strengths of the different dates in the Compare Tool. Yellow: Folder dates, pink: manual dates, blue: automatic dates

date information was precise to the day, highly accurate, but only available for 6% of the collection.

To get the most out of this date information, we decided to publish it all. Researchers can then switch between the dates depending on their needs. To find as much material as possible, they can use the folder date, whereas to pinpoint found pages more accurately, they can use the manual or automatic dates. The user can even utilise the Compare Tool to combine the strengths of both.

With the graph shown in Figure 7, the researcher can use the folder date line to see that there was a dip in the middle of November, with far fewer hits for 'Europa' (Europe) than in the latter half of the month. Perhaps more interesting for researchers, though incomplete, are the automatic and manual date lines, which suggest dates for further investigation, such as 9th and 26th November, perhaps caused by the publicity surrounding Hitler's speech on the 18th anniversary of the Beer Hall Putsch on the 8th of November, or the renewal of the Anti-Comintern pact on the 25th, which was presented as a milestone in the history of European unity. Obviously, given the incomplete coverage of the automatic and manual dates, this functionality must be used with care. Such hypotheses require further research into the propaganda content, for example with close reading.

In general, the characteristics of the BNO collection have a large impact on how a researcher can work with it. The poor OCR quality influences search results, as search terms are less likely to be successfully found in transcripts with poor OCR quality. Furthermore, the incomplete availability of dates influences both what can be found when searching by date, and what is visualised in the Compare tool, as only items with dates can be plotted on the Compare tool graph. To allow the researcher to work with the collection and the Media Suite tools appropriately, it is essential that they are properly informed about the limitations of both. For this reason, we documented the BNO collection, with particular emphasis on the processing that was applied to generate dates (Figure 8). The documentation was produced by a team of data engineers and propaganda researchers to ensure that it included relevant information presented in such a way that researchers could understand the implications. This

**Wartime radio news bulletins:
Berichtendienst
Nederlandsche Omroep (BNO)**

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0

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Kwesties die met oorlogsgeweld te maken hebben, wekken veel maatschappelijke belangstelling en vragen om onafhankelijk en wetenschappelijk onderzoek. Het NIOD verricht en... [read more](#)

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 Dataset
 Groups
 Activity Stream

Wartime radio news bulletins: Berichtendienst Nederlandsche Omroep (BNO)

This collection consists of transcripts made of wartime radio bulletins from the Netherlands, broadcast by the BNO (Berichtendienst Nederlandsche Omroep). The BNO operated under the aegis of the occupation regime in the Netherlands during the Second World War and actively made propaganda to promote national-socialism in its news broadcasts. The collection is provided by the NIOD (the Dutch Institute for War, Holocaust and Genocide Studies), collection 103, Nederlandsche Omroep.

The collection consists of images of the scanned transcripts. The transcripts have been processed by the NIOD using OCR (Optical Character Recognition) to make them searchable. The quality of the OCR is variable. The transcripts are stored per page, and have only very basic metadata. Each page belongs to a folder for which a year and a range of dates is known. Page dates have been automatically extracted from the transcript, and dates have been manually added for pages in certain folders. See section below for more information about dates.

This collection was imported into the Media Suite as part of the Mediaoorlog project.

What part of the collection is included in the Media Suite?

The entire BNO collection has been imported

What years does the collection cover?

The collection covers 1940-1945

Date fields

The original metadata contains no page dates, but every page belongs to a folder, for which a year and a range of dates within that year are specified.

Individual page dates have been added both manually and automatically for subsets of the collection.

Five date fields are available:

Figure 8: Documentation page for the BNO collection

documentation is included in the Media Suite and can be reached via a link in the collection (Figure 9)¹⁵.

The tools available in the Media Suite are also documented, and this information is available via icons in the tool itself and the Help section of the Media Suite.

In this way, the researcher is supported in both data and tool criticism, equipping them to work with the BNO collection in an informed manner.

¹⁵ <https://mediasuitedata.clariah.nl/dataset/wartime-radio-bulletin-transcripts>

Figure 9: Collection Selector showing the BNO collection and its documentation link

Figure 10: An example of an audio recording with an ASR transcript in the Media Suite

4.2 Matching of radio audio with transcripts and newspapers

Publishing the BNO transcript collection in the Media Suite gives unprecedented possibilities to explore the collection. But to truly start putting the propaganda puzzle together, we want to link the collections. Then a researcher could find a radio transcript discussing a given topic, listen to the audio, and look at what the newspapers were saying about that topic on the same day.

The radio transcripts can also be used to fill some of the holes in the audio collection, and vice versa. There are far more radio transcripts (to give an indication, the digitised BNO collection alone comprises 68,986 pages) than there are audio recordings (2262). At the same time, there are cases where an audio recording is present while the transcript is missing, such as the news bulletin of 8am on 25th July 1943.

In order to link transcripts to the relevant audio recording, we proposed the following steps:

- Generate speech transcripts of the audio recordings
- For each audio recording, find the transcripts within a small date range of the broadcast date of the audio (to allow some margin for errors)
- Match the words in the speech transcript with the words in the candidate transcripts
- With a sufficient number of matching words, link the transcript to the audio recording

For the first step, we used Kaldi NL¹⁶ to generate speech recognition transcripts of the audio recordings. For 27% of the collection, no transcript could be produced. For another 16%, the produced transcripts contained fewer than 50 words, which could indicate poor quality. The remaining 57% of the collection has transcripts that are longer than 50 words. All transcripts were added to the radio audio collection in the Media Suite, and can be viewed there (Figure 10).

However, a review of the transcripts quickly showed that the quality is very poor in many cases, so much so that it is often impossible to make sense of it (Figure 10).

¹⁶ https://github.com/opensource-spraakherkenning-nl/Kaldi_NL

Figure 11: An example of an audio recording with a poor quality ASR transcript

The poor performance is most likely due to the poor audio quality of the recordings. Given this poor quality, combined with the poor coverage of the date information in the BNO, it was decided to abandon attempts to link the audio with the BNO transcripts within this project.

Despite the fact that the items within the collections could not be explicitly linked, their publication together in the Media Suite still enables quantitative analysis of combined collections, as we indicated in the section on 'the radio audio collection'. To demonstrate this, we proceeded to compare semantic patterns in the BNO transcripts with the wartime newspaper collection in the Media Suite.

4.3 Quantitative analysis of combined collections

Via the visualisations provided in the Compare tool, the Media Suite supports some basic quantitative analysis of the combined collections. In the example in Figure 12, the search results for the term 'Europa' (Europe) are shown per month for the Nazi party newspapers (pink line) and the BNO transcripts (blue for folder date, yellow for the automatic page date). It can be seen that the two lines for the BNO transcript follow the same pattern, showing that despite the incompleteness of the automatic date information it is still usable to show trends. All three graphs show noticeable peaks in July 1941 and February 1943. The first peak reflects the increasing propaganda value of the 'Europe' construct for the Nazis after the start of the attack on the Soviet Union on 22nd June. The Nazis framed the fight against the 'godless Bolshevism' and the 'Asian' Soviet Russia as a common European fight or crusade to preserve the 'Christian European civilisation'. The second peak shows the urgency of 'Europe' in the propaganda offensive of the Nazis after the loss of the Battle of Stalingrad, in which Goebbels emphasised that only total war could neutralise the acute Bolshevik danger and that the fight against the Soviet Union was a matter of life and death, a struggle for the continued existence of Germany and Europe (Brolsma (2022)).

As explained in Section 3.3, the Compare Tool offers an option to provide relative graphs, compensating for the imbalance between collection sizes and therefore making it easier to obtain a meaningful comparison. Figure 13 shows the query results of the keyword term 'Europa' (Europe) relative to their own category. This graph confirms,

Figure 12: Comparing search results over time for the search term ‘Europa’. Pink: Nazi party newspapers, yellow: BNO with automatic page dates, blue: BNO with folder dates

Figure 13: Comparing search results over time for the search term ‘Europa’, relative to the category/-collection size. Pink: Nazi party newspapers, yellow: BNO with automatic page dates, blue: BNO with folder dates

and indeed foregrounds, the urgency of Europe as a propaganda concept in the context of Nazi Germany’s invasion of the Soviet Union. However, compared to Figure 12 it suggests that the peak of February 1943 was less significant, as Europe continued to be frequently used as a propaganda frame, also in the last two years of the war. These visualisations invite researchers to reflect on the continuities and discontinuities of propaganda narratives throughout the Second World War.

This sort of data visualisation is therefore useful both to identify important moments for a closer investigation of the media content, and to map out the similarities and differences between various categories of wartime media, such as between pro-/anti-Nazi media and/or between newspapers and radio broadcasts. In other words, semantic patterns in quantitative visualisations can guide researchers to interesting ‘media moments’ which merit further investigation.

The texts produced by OCR and ASR assist researchers in searching collections. However, they are also a rich resource for quantitative analysis. We wrote a Jupyter Notebook, using the Media Suite APIs, that extracted the words occurring just before or just after a given search term.¹⁷ This provides a tool for researchers to investigate in what context a word is used.

¹⁷ Stop words such as ‘de’, ‘het’, ‘van’, ‘in’, etc were excluded from this analysis

Table 1: The top ten most frequently occurring words before the word 'Europa', per (sub)collection

	1	2	3	4	5
Anti-nazi	west	oost	oorlog	rijk	geheel
Pro-nazi	nieuwe	geheel	strijdt	nieuw	west
BNO	nieuwe	geheel	oost	west	landen
Radio audio	heel	oost	west	landen	we
	6	7	8	9	10
Anti-nazi	landen	bevrijd	heel	vasteland	nieuwe
Pro-nazi	oost	landen	oorlog	midden	vasteland
BNO	oorlog	nieuw	vrijheid	vasteland	heel
Radio audio	zuid	binnen	Nederland	vanuit	rest

This notebook was used to conduct an analysis of the use of the word 'Europa' (Europe) in the anti- and pro-Nazi newspapers, the BNO collection (via OCR) and the radio audio collection (via ASR). The results are shown in Table 1

Interesting is that the most frequently occurring word in both the pro-Nazi and BNO collections is 'nieuwe' (new). The variant 'nieuw' also appears high in the ranking for these collections. These results show that the construct 'Europe' was very important for the occupying authorities to promote a national-socialist vision of the future in the nazified printed press and via Radio Hilversum. Of course, the poor - and variable - quality of the ASR and OCR means that this analysis is at best incomplete, and may also be inaccurate. For example, if a frequently occurring word is poorly recognised, then it will be counted much less often, causing it to appear to occur less frequently than it actually does. However, the fact that the results in the BNO and pro-Nazi categories are so similar seems to indicate that the quality is sufficient to discover important Nazi media frames via digital research methods, such as the frame of a 'new Europe'. The results in the ASR of the (both pro- and anti-Nazi) radio seem to consist mainly of geographical indications.

Due to the poor quality of the texts, such analyses cannot provide reliable conclusions, but can be used to discover possible interesting trends for further qualitative investigation.

5 Conclusion

During the Second World War in the Netherlands, the Berichtendienst Nederlandse Omroep (BNO) made an important contribution to the propaganda of the Nazi occupying regime through their news broadcasts. The publication of the digitised BNO transcripts in the CLARIAH Media Suite enables researchers to more effectively search through the transcripts. We did not achieve the goal of linking these transcripts to the audio recordings also stored in the Media Suite. Yet despite the absence of explicit links, the publication of collections of newspapers, radio transcripts and radio audio recordings in the same online environment means that researchers can analyse the BNO collection in conjunction with other categories of war media (categories per political-ideological signature and media type) for the first time. The availability of the OCR and ASR transcripts make it possible for them to combine qualitative analysis of the media content with various quantitative research techniques.

For both quantitative and qualitative research of the BNO transcripts, date information is essential. Making the transcripts searchable by date enables historians and media scientists not only to effectively analyse the reporting around various events - as demonstrated in the examples above - but also to make optimum use of the digital tools that the Media Suite offers. For example, they can compare semantic patterns in various media categories in the Compare Tool to identify important 'media moments' or study the use of certain frames over time. With the algorithm we developed, we succeeded in extracting dates for part of the collection.

The biggest obstacle to the automatic recognition of date information is the poor quality of the OCR. A priority in the future is therefore to improve the OCR, so that more pages can be reliably dated. This could be done by using new OCR tools, and potentially by re-scanning difficult pages. This should be discussed with the company that produced the original scans, as they may be able to suggest improvements. Alternatively, a more labour-intensive approach would be to manually annotate more pages with the date. As was demonstrated in this project, both approaches can be combined.

The large variation in date formats used in the collection also presented a challenge. An interesting option for the future could be to finetune or fully train a NER model on part of the BNO collection. This would ensure that the model is trained on dates in the formats and context such as they typically appear in the BNO collection (including the typical OCR errors) and hence can recognise them with more accuracy. This would require manual effort to identify all the variations and tag these to use as training material.

In addition to a better date recognition, improving radio ASR transcript quality could also help to make linking the radio broadcasts with the radio transcripts feasible. New speech recognition models are now available, which offer the potential for improvement. These should be tested on the radio broadcasts to see if it is possible to achieve better ASR quality.

To increase the value of the collection of wartime media in the CLARIAH Media Suite for future media-historic research into propaganda in Dutch newspapers and radio, a further expansion of this wartime media collection is desirable. This can be achieved by digitizing and publishing (parts of) the sizable radio archive of the years 1940-1945, such as the Radio Oranje transcripts and the reports of the listening service of the Dutch government in London exile. Such an addition would allow for research that will deepen our understanding of the dynamics in radio propaganda during the Second World War, and more specifically of the transnational war of words between Nazi-controlled transmissions from Hilversum and pro-Allied broadcasts from London.

In the course of the Media War Matching project, we learned a number of valuable lessons about the publication of such collections. The first was that quality starts at the source, and we would recommend that any future projects intending to publish a collection first conduct a thorough investigation of the data to identify quality issues up front. For large collections this is a challenge, as manual checking of everything is impossible, but checking samples alone can be misleading, as was the case in this project. The second lesson concerns the importance of data and tool criticism when dealing with such collections. The limitations of both data and tools must be clearly communicated with researchers to allow proper use of the collection. The third lesson is that cooperation between data engineers and historical experts is essential both to achieve this clear communication and to publish the collection (including development of tools and processing of data) in such a way that it is optimally usable by researchers.

This ongoing dialogue between experts in the various Digital Humanities disciplines brings us to our final and pivotal point. While it is important to keep in mind the ideal situation of digitised collections, each with complete metadata and linked to related collections, it is possible to achieve a great deal while falling far short of that ideal. In this particular project, we didn't put together the complete puzzle of the three propaganda collections, because of both computational challenges and the wartime circumstances that affected the production and preservation of these sources. However, what we did achieve has already proven to be of great value to researchers, showing how quantitative visualisations of media collections can serve as an entry point for further qualitative research. We would therefore encourage others to embark on the challenge of publishing such collections, to discover the limitations of the data and tools, and to use these to assist transparent and usable publication of the data, rather than letting them prevent it.

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